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En memoria de Rafael Araujo Armero (1960 - 2021)

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Land and freshwater molluscs of mainland Ecuador: an illustrated checklist

Moluscos terrestres y dulceacuícolas de Ecuador continental: un listado ilustrado

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ABSTRACT

This comprehensive checklist of non-marine molluscs from the mainland of Ecuador presents data on 331 species (of which 5 are considered as *nomen dubium*), compiled from the literature, a subset of museum databases, and some verified observations from the internet. For all taxa the original reference is given and photographs of type specimens are provided if these could be located and obtained from museums. Where these were not available the original figure(s) have been reproduced. In the introduction, a brief history of research in Ecuador (including the Galápagos archipelago) is presented. This checklist may serve as a baseline document for further research. It is not intended to be a revisionary work, although we have recognised the following new synonyms: *Neritina intermedia* (var. β) *minima* K. Miller, 1879 = *Clypeolum latissimum* (Broderip, 1833); *Aperostoma* (*Aperostoma*) *olivaceum* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942 = *Incidostoma quitense* (L. Pfeiffer, 1852); *Hemisinus pazi* Tryon, 1866 = *Hemisinus guayaquilensis* (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853); *Bulimus cuneus* L. Pfeiffer, 1854 = *Protobeliscus fairmaireanus* (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853); *Synapterpes* (*Zoniferella*) *riveti* Germain, 1907 = *Mesembrinus vesperus* Jousseaume, 1887 = *Zoniferella albopalteata* (Dunker, 1882); *Synapterpes bicingulatus* Fulton, 1908 = *Zoniferella bizonalis* (Germain, 1907); *Thaumastus thompsonoides* Oberwimmer, 1931 = *Kara thompsonii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1845). The need for further field work is illustrated by the fact that for 60 species, only imprecise localities are known, while for 168 species no modern (i.e. last 50 years) records are available. There are 179 species considered as endemics for the Ecuadorian malacofauna. For both the terrestrial and freshwater species the ecoregions where they occur are indicated where possible.

RESUMEN

Esta lista patrón exhaustiva de los moluscos no marinos de Ecuador continental aporta datos sobre 331 especies (de las cuales 5 se consideran *nomen dubium*), recopilados a partir de la literatura, de un subconjunto de bases de datos de museos y de algunas observaciones verificadas procedentes de Internet. Para todos los taxones, se proporciona

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la referencia original y, si se pueden localizar y obtener de los museos, fotografías de los ejemplares tipo. Cuando éstos no estaban disponibles, se han reproducido las figuras originales. En la introducción, se presenta una breve historia de la investigación en Ecuador (incluido el archipiélago de Galápagos). Esta lista patrón puede servir como documento de referencia para futuras investigaciones. No pretende ser un trabajo de revisión, aunque hemos reconocido los siguientes sinónimos nuevos: *Neritina intermedia* (var. β) *minima* K. Miller, 1879 = *Clypeolum latissimum* (Broderip, 1833); *Aperostoma* (*Aperostoma*) *olivaceum* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942 = *Incidostoma quitense* (L. Pfeiffer, 1852); *Hemisinus pazi* Tryon, 1866 = *Hemisinus guayaquilensis* (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853); *Bulimus cuneus* L. Pfeiffer, 1854 = *Protobeliscus fairmaireanus* (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853); *Synapterpes* (*Zoniferella*) *riveti* Germain, 1907 = *Mesembrinus vesperus* Jousseume, 1887 = *Zoniferella albobalteata* (Dunker, 1882); *Synapterpes bicingulatus* Fulton, 1908 = *Zoniferella bizonalis* (Germain, 1907); *Thaumastus thompsonoides* Oberwimmer, 1931 = *Kara thompsonii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1845). La necesidad de más trabajo de campo queda ilustrada por el hecho de que, para 60 especies, solo se conocen localidades imprecisas, mientras que para 168 especies no se dispone de registros modernos (es decir, de los últimos 50 años). Existen 179 especies consideradas endémicas de la malacofauna ecuatoriana. Tanto para las especies terrestres como para las de agua dulce, las ecorregiones donde se encuentran se indican cuando es posible.

KEY WORDS: Bivalvia, Gastropoda, distribution, ecoregions, endemics, history, synonyms, taxonomy.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Bivalvia, Gastropoda, distribución, ecorregiones, endémicos, historia, sinónimos, taxonomía.

INTRODUCTION

Recent faunistic overviews or checklists of several Neotropical countries (Belize - DOURSON *ET AL.*, 2018; Brazil - SIMONE, 2006; Colombia - LINARES & VERA, 2012; French Guiana - MASSEMIN *ET AL.*, 2009) have stimulated interest in the land and freshwater snails of these areas. However, there are still countries where the malacofauna is insufficiently known and focussed attention to study the species composition is, to a large extent, lacking. The recent visit of one of us (MTR) in 2019 to Ecuador highlighted once again the need for a guide to the land and freshwater molluscs.

Although we have been limited by the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic and were not able to study all relevant museum collections, we thought it would be helpful to present a collation of known data from the literature together, where possible, with illustrations of type specimens or original figures of species. Originally we intended to cover the whole non-marine malacofauna of the country, however

the recent review of Galápagos non-Orthalicid snails (MIQUEL & HERRERA, 2014; 2019) and the forthcoming revision of *Naesiotus* species from the archipelago (N.F. Shoobs, ANSP Philadelphia, pers. commun., July 2020), has made us limit this publication to the mainland taxa. Nevertheless we will include some general data on the history of research on the Galápagos and the number of species currently recognised.

Ecuador is a biodiverse country of which the non-marine Mollusca, despite the number of taxa described, is but poorly known. Many taxa are known from a limited number of localities, and a substantial number have not again been recorded after their initial description. There is ample room for field studies by (local) malacologists to fill in the gaps that are all too apparent. This may be even more clear when one realises that in nearly all species anatomical data is lacking, not to mention molecular studies which could solve some of the current taxonomic puzzles. Field

work could also provide interesting ecological data and, as the recent field collections mentioned above has shown, bring new species and records for the malacofauna to light. The smaller species especially seem to be understudied, particularly on the mainland.

The aim of this paper is thus to give an overview of all the non-marine molluscs of mainland Ecuador, illustrated as far as possible by their type specimens or original figures. In some cases a putatively identical specimen from a museum collection has been illustrated when neither type material nor original figures were available or deemed appropriate. Some field photographs are also added to provide information on the features of the living animal. By doing so we hope to provide a basis for subsequent research into the fascinating diversity of land and freshwater molluscs of this country. The provisional full species list occurring on the mainland of Ecuador is summarised in Table I. At the end data are added on citizen science as a potential tool, and summarising Tables specifying the number of endemics and the localities. Details on the ecoregions are given in Appendix 1 and locality coordinates in Appendix 2.

GEOGRAPHY AND ECOREGIONS

The country is divided into three main zones (Fig. 1): 1) the coastal area; 2) the Andean area with a western and an eastern chain, plus the interandine plateau; 3) the Amazonian area. Past decades have seen increased attention in the biogeographical regionalisation of ecosystems in order to facilitate conservation efforts. DINERSTEIN *ET AL.* (1995) made a first conservation assessment for Latin America and the Caribbean, and recognised 13 ecoregions for the terrestrial fauna in Ecuador: Ecuadorian dry forests, Tumbes-Piura dry forests, Western Ecuador moist forests, Napo moist forests, Northwestern Andean montane forests, Eastern Cordillera montane forests, Guayaquil flooded grasslands, Cordillera Central páramo,

Northern Andean páramo, Galápagos xeric scrub, Esmeraldas-Pacific Colombia mangroves, Gulf of Guayaquil-Tumbes mangroves, Manabí mangroves. OLSON *ET AL.* (2001) presented the same in a world-wide scheme. The ecoregions have been partly renamed or redefined since their original description (WWF, 2015) and those from the mainland are listed in Appendix 1.

The terrestrial ecoregions (Fig. 2A) have been used in conservation literature for analysis (*e.g.*, RICKETTS & IMHOFF, 2003; LOYOLA *ET AL.*, 2009; GONÇALVES-SOUZA *ET AL.*, 2020) for different groups. In this respect the mainland non-marine molluscs of Ecuador have received little or no attention (but see BREURE & BORRERO, 2008; BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016). Only species from the Galápagos have been assessed under the IUCN Red List criteria (PARENT, 2003), listing 57 species (incorrectly classified as *Bulimulus* species); of these 5 were undescribed, and 9 were assessed as Data Deficient, 15 as Vulnerable, 7 as Endangered, and 26 as Critically Endangered.

ABELL *ET AL.* (2008) presented a map for the freshwater systems (Fig. 2B), primarily based on the distribution and compositions of fish species. For Ecuador they recognise the following ecoregions: North Andean Pacific slopes-Río Atrato, Amazonas High Andes, Western Amazonas Piedmont, Amazonas Lowlands, Galapagos Islands. PERREIRA *ET AL.* (2014) made a distinction for the freshwater fauna between rivers that flow into the Pacific Ocean and those that are tributaries of the Amazon River. LASSO *ET AL.* (2016) gave a review of the conservation status of freshwater mollusc species in tropical Andean countries. They listed two *Pomacea* species for Ecuador as assessed for the Red List of IUCN.

For alternative views see JOSSE *ET AL.* (2003) for ecological systems in Latin America and the Caribbean, MORRONE (2014) for a hierarchical biogeographical classification of the Neotropical region, and MORRONE (2018) for an evolutionary biogeography of the Andean region.

Table I. Species list from mainland Ecuador with their status, respectively endemic to Ecuador, only known from imprecise localities, doubtful record (no voucher, only literature); unconfirmed record (voucher exists but not checked), introduced species, and first record for Ecuador. Key, ?: to be confirmed; x: current status; *: taxon inquirendum; †: considered extinct; ‡: first record for Ecuador.

Tabla I. Lista de especies del Ecuador continental con su estatus, respectivamente endémica de Ecuador, solo conocida de localidades imprecisas, registro dudoso (no hay ejemplar, solo literatura), registro sin confirmar (hay algún ejemplar pero no comprobado), especie introducida y primer registro para Ecuador. Clave, ?: por confirmar; x: estado actual; *: taxón inquirendum; †: considerado extinto; ‡: primera cita para para Ecuador.

Family / species	Endemic	No modern records	Imprecise locality	Doubtful (no voucher)	Unconfirmed (voucher not checked)	Introduced	New record
Helicinidae A. Férussac, 1822							
<i>Bourciera fraseri</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1859)		x					
<i>Bourciera helicinaeformis</i> L. Pfeiffer, 1852	x						
<i>Bourciera striatula</i> K. Miller, 1879	x						
<i>Bourciera viridissima</i> K. Miller, 1879	x						
<i>Bourciera</i> sp.	?		x				
<i>Helicina</i> (?) cf. <i>bourguignatiana</i> Ancey, 1892							
<i>Helicina</i> (?) <i>ecuadoriana</i> K. Miller, 1879	?	x					
<i>Helicina</i> (?) <i>laus</i> A.J. Wagner, 1905 ‡							x
<i>Helicina</i> (?) <i>rhynchostoma</i> L. Pfeiffer, 1865			x	x			
<i>Helicina</i> (?) <i>uizonata</i> F. Haas, 1966 ‡							x
Proserpinellidae H.B. Baker, 1923							
<i>Lindiella cinnanomea</i> (Sykes, 1900)	x						
<i>Archecharax cousini</i> (Jousseume, 1887)	x	x					
Neritidae Rafinesque, 1815							
<i>Clypeolum latissimum</i> (Broderip, 1833)							
Ampullariidae J.E. Gray, 1824							
<i>Asolene crassa</i> (W. Swainson, 1823)		x	x				
<i>Pomacea (Effusa) expansa</i> (K. Miller, 1879)	x	x					
<i>Pomacea (Effusa) quinindensis</i> (K. Miller, 1879)	x	x					
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) alderisoni</i> (Pain, 1946)		x					
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) bulla</i> (Reeve, 1856)				x			
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) canaliculata</i> (Lamarck, 1822)						x	
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) columellaris</i> (A.A. Gould, 1848)				x			
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) cousini</i> (Jousseume, 1887)	x	x	x				
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) cumingii</i> (King & Broderip, 1831)			x	x			
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) martinezi</i> (Hidalgo, 1866)	x	x					
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) modesta</i> (Busch, 1859)		x	x				
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) pealiana</i> (I. Lea, 1838)		x	x				
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) puntaplaya</i> (Cousin, 1887)	x	x					
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) reyrei</i> (Cousin, 1887)	x	x	x				
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) tenuissima</i> (Jousseume, 1894)	x	x	x				
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) urceus</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)							
Neocyclotidae Kobelt & Möllendorff, 1897							
<i>Daronia bicincta</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)	x	x	x				
<i>Daronia martinezi</i> (Hidalgo, 1866)	?	x					
<i>Calaperostoma bourcierii</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1854)	x	x					
<i>Calaperostoma cousini</i> (Jousseume, 1884) *	x	x					
<i>Calaperostoma</i> cf. <i>cumingii</i> (G.B. Sowerby I, 1832)					x		

Table I. Continuation.

Tabla I. Continuación.

Family / species	Endemic	No modern records	Imprecise locality	Doubtful (no voucher)	Unconfirmed (voucher not checked)	Introduced	New record
<i>Calaperostoma esmeraldense</i> (K. Miller, 1879)	x						
<i>Calaperostoma guayaquilense</i> (G.B. Sowerby II, 1850)	x	x					
<i>Calaperostoma hidalgoi</i> (Crosse, 1866) *	x	x	x				
<i>Calaperostoma nigrofasciatum</i> (K. Miller, 1879)							
<i>Calaperostoma purum</i> (Forbes, 1850)				x			
<i>Calaperostoma rosenbergi</i> (S.I. da Costa, 1898)	x	x					
<i>Incidostoma chokolatum</i> J.P.E. Morrison, 1955	x	x					
<i>Incidostoma diminutum</i> J.P.E. Morrison, 1955	x						
<i>Incidostoma dunkeri</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1857)		x					
<i>Incidostoma ecuadorensis</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)	x	x	x				
<i>Incidostoma giganteum</i> (Reeve, 1842)							
<i>Incidostoma hitomi</i> Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942	x	x	x				
<i>Incidostoma jacksoni</i> J.P.E. Morrison, 1955	x	x					
<i>Incidostoma manabense</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)	x	x					
<i>Incidostoma masvense</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)	x	x					
<i>Incidostoma pailaense</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)	x	x	x				
<i>Incidostoma pazi</i> (Crosse, 1866)	x	x					
<i>Incidostoma perezii</i> (Hidalgo, 1866)	x						
<i>Incidostoma pichinchense</i> Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942	x						
<i>Incidostoma popayanum</i> (I. Lea, 1838)					x		
<i>Incidostoma quitense</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1852)							
<i>Incidostoma salangoense</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)	x	x					
<i>Incidostoma stirlingi</i> Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942	x	x					
<i>Incidostoma subcingulatum</i> (Kobelt, 1912)	x	x	x				
<i>Lagocyclus antonii</i> (Cousin, 1887)	x	x	x				
<i>Lagocyclus crosseanus</i> (Hidalgo, 1866)	x						
<i>Lagocyclus haematomma</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1863)	x	x	x				
<i>Lagocyclus vasconesi</i> (Jousseaume, 1897)	x	x					
<i>Neocyclus granulatus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1863)	x	x	x				
Hemisinidae P. Fischer & Crosse, 1891							
<i>Hemisinus flammeus</i> (F.C. Baker, 1914)					x		
<i>Hemisinus guayaquilensis</i> (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853)							
<i>Hemisinus maculatus</i> (I. Lea, 1834)	x	x					
<i>Hemisinus simplex</i> (Tryon, 1866)	x	x	x				
Thiaridae Gill, 1871							
<i>Melanoides tuberculata</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)						x	
Cochliopidae Tryon, 1866							
<i>Andesipyrigus sketi</i> Hershler & Velkovrh, 1993							
<i>Aroapyrgus colombiensis</i> Malek & Little, 1971							
? <i>Cochliopina boetzkesi</i> (K. Miller, 1879)	x	x					
? <i>Cochliopina ecuadoriana</i> (K. Miller, 1879)	x	x					
<i>Lithococcus multicarinatus</i> (K. Miller, 1879)							
<i>Littoridina gaudichaudi</i> Souleyet, 1852 †	x	†					
<i>Pyraophorus pedrinus</i> (K. Miller, 1879)	x	x					
Lymnaeidae Rafinesque, 1815							
<i>Galba cousini</i> (Jousseaume, 1887)							

Table I. Continuation.
 Tabla I. Continuación.

Family / species	Endemic	No modern records	Imprecise locality	Doubtful (no voucher)	Unconfirmed (voucher not checked)	Introduced	New record
<i>Galba nitidella</i> (E. von Martens, 1885)	x	x					
? <i>Galba raphaelis</i> (Jousseume, 1887)	x	x					
<i>Galba schirazensis</i> (Küster, 1862)						x	
<i>Pseudosuccinea columella</i> (Say, 1817)						x	
Physidae Fitzinger, 1833							
<i>Haitia acuta</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)						x	
<i>Mayabina carolita</i> (Jousseume, 1887)							
<i>Mexinauta peruviana</i> (J.E. Gray, 1828)							
Acroloxidae Thiele, 1931							
<i>Acroloxus culicoides</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)	x	x					
Planorbidae Rafinesque, 1815							
<i>Biomphalaria cousini</i> Paraense, 1966	x						
<i>Biomphalaria equatoria</i> (Cousin, 1887)	x						
<i>Biomphalaria peregrina</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)							
<i>Biomphalaria sericea</i> (Dunker, 1848)			x				
<i>Drepanotrema anatinum</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)						x?	
<i>Drepanotrema kermatooides</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)							
<i>Drepanotrema lucidum</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1839)						x?	
<i>Drepanotrema surinamense</i> (Clessin, 1884)						x	
<i>Gyraulus hindsianus</i> (Dunker, 1848)	x						
<i>Helisoma trivolvis</i> (Say, 1818)						x	
<i>Planorbella clevei</i> Jousseume, 1887	x	x	x				
Veronicellidae J.E. Gray, 1840							
<i>Belocaulus boetzkessi</i> (K. Miller, 1879)	x	x	x				
<i>Colosius confusus</i> Gomes, Robinson, Zimmerman, Obregón & Barr, 2013							
<i>Colosius festae</i> (Colosi, 1921)	x	x					
<i>Colosius propinquus</i> (Colosi, 1921)	x	x					
<i>Colosius pulcher</i> (Colosi, 1921)							
<i>Diploselenodes occidentalis</i> (Guilding, 1825)						x	
<i>Diploselenodes olivaceus</i> (Stearns, 1871)							
<i>Sarasinula plebeia</i> (P. Fischer, 1868)						x	
<i>Sarasinula linguaeformis</i> (C.G. Semper, 1885)		x					
Achatinidae W. Swainson, 1840							
<i>Achatina (Lissachatina) fulica</i> Bowdich, 1822						x	
<i>Allopeas gracile</i> (Hutton, 1834)						x	
<i>Allopeas micra</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)							
<i>Beckianum beckianum</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)						x	
<i>Leptinaria aequatoria</i> (K. Miller, 1879)	x	x					
<i>Leptinaria eyerdami</i> F. Haas, 1951	x	x					
<i>Leptinaria funcki</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)				x			
<i>Leptinaria unilamellata</i> (d'Orbigny, 1838)							
<i>Opeas hannense</i> (Rang, 1831)						x	
<i>Opeas rarum</i> K. Miller, 1879	?	x					
<i>Protobeliscus fairmaireanus</i> (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853)							
<i>Protobeliscus haplostylus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)	x						

Table I. Continuation.
Tabla I. Continuación.

Family / species	Endemic	No modern records	Imprecise locality	Doubtful (no voucher)	Unconfirmed (voucher not checked)	Introduced	New record
<i>Protobeliscus jousseaumei</i> (Cousin, 1887)	x	x					
<i>Protobeliscus major</i> (K. Miller, 1878)	x	x					
<i>Protobeliscus pairensis</i> (Higgins, 1872)	x	x					
<i>Protobeliscus riparius</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1854)		x					
? <i>Pseudopeas viviparum</i> (K. Miller, 1878) *	x	x					
<i>Rhodea aequatoria</i> S.I. da Costa, 1899	x	x					
<i>Rhodea cousini</i> Jousseaume, 1900	x	x					
<i>Subulina octona</i> (Bruguière, 1789)						x	
<i>Synapterpes auratus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)							
<i>Synapterpes visendus</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)	?						
<i>Zoniferella albobaltea</i> (Dunker, 1882)	x	x					
<i>Zoniferella bizonalis</i> (Germain, 1907)	x						
Streptaxidae J.E. Gray, 1860							
<i>Martinella martinella</i> Jousseaume, 1887 *	x	x					
Scolodontidae H.B. Baker, 1925							
<i>Drepanostomella excisa</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1855)		x			x		
<i>Drepanostomella lyzarzaburui</i> (Jousseaume, 1887)	x	x					
<i>Guestieria locardi</i> Jousseaume, 1887	x	x					
<i>Guestieria martinida</i> Jousseaume, 1887	x	x					
<i>Guestieria powisiana</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)							
<i>Happia baezensis</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)	?	x					
<i>Happia cyclina</i> (Cousin, 1887)	x	x					
<i>Happia flora</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1852)	x	x					
? <i>Scolodonta guayaquilensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1854)	x						
<i>Systrophia entodonta</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1859)	x	x					
<i>Systrophia helicycloides</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)		x			x		
<i>Systrophia heligmoida</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)	x						
<i>Systrophia insignis</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)							
<i>Systrophia ortoni</i> (Crosse, 1871)	x						
<i>Systrophia reyrei</i> (Souverbie, 1858)	x						
<i>Systrophia stenostrepta</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1857)		x	x		x		
<i>Zilchistrophia hilaryae</i> Páll-Gergely, 2014	x						
<i>Zilchistrophia shiwararum</i> Páll-Gergely, 2014	x						
Succineidae H. Beck, 1837							
<i>Omalonyx geayi</i> Tillier, 1980							
<i>Succinea aequinoctialis</i> d'Orbigny, 1838							
<i>Succinea marianita</i> (Cousin, 1887)	x	x					
<i>Succinea martini</i> (Jousseaume, 1887)	x	x					
Strophocheilidae Pilsbry, 1902							
<i>Megalobulimus garciamoreni</i> (K. Miller, 1878)	x						
<i>Megalobulimus popelairianus</i> (Nvst, 1845)							
Orthalicidae Martens in Albers, 1860							
<i>Clathrothalicus corydon</i> (Crosse, 1869)	x	x					
<i>Clathrothalicus magnificus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)	x	x	x				

Table I. Continuation.
 Tabla I. Continuación.

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<i>Clathrothalicus phoebus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1863)	x	x	x				
<i>Corona pfeifferi</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)							
<i>Corona regalis</i> (Hupé, 1857)							
<i>Kara indentata</i> (S.I. da Costa, 1901)	x	x	x				
<i>Kara thompsonii</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1845)	x						
<i>Orthalicus bensoni</i> (Reeve, 1849)							
<i>Orthalicus bifulguratus</i> (Reeve, 1849)							
<i>Orthalicus mars</i> L. Pfeiffer, 1861		x	x				
<i>Porphyrobaphe (Oxyorthalicus) irrorata</i> (Reeve, 1849)	x						
<i>Porphyrobaphe (Oxyorthalicus) subirrorata</i> (S.I. da Costa, 1898)	x						
<i>Porphyrobaphe (Porphyrobaphe) iostoma</i> (G.B. Sowerby I, 1824)							
<i>Porphyrobaphe (Porphyrobaphe) saturnus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1860)	x	x					
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) atramentaria</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1855)		x					
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) augusti</i> (Jousseau, 1887)	x	x					
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) deburghiae</i> (Reeve, 1859)	x	x					
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) fraseri</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1858)	x						
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) kellestii</i> (Reeve, 1850)	x	x					
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) yatesi galactostoma</i> (Ancey, 1890)	x	x	x				
<i>Sultana (Sultana) sultana</i> (Dillwyn, 1817)							
Amphibulimidae P. Fischer, 1873							
<i>Plekocheilus (Aeropictus) tenuissimus</i> Weyrauch, 1967	x						
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) aristaceus</i> (Crosse, 1869)	x	x					
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) aureonitens</i> (K. Miller, 1878)	x	x					
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) cardinalis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)							
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) dolarius</i> (S.I. da Costa, 1898)		x					
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) eros</i> (Angas, 1878)	x	x					
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) floccosus</i> (Spix, 1827)							
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) jimenezi</i> (Hidalgo, 1872)	x						
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) lynciculus</i> (Deville & Hupé, 1850)							
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) nocturnus</i> Pilsbry, 1939	x						
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) oligostylus</i> Pilsbry, 1939							
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) piperitus mcgintyi</i> 'Pilsbry' H.B. Baker, 1963	x	x					
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) roseolabrum</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x	x					
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) taylorianus</i> (Reeve, 1849)	?						
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) tricolor</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x						
<i>Plekocheilus (Plekocheilus) cepeus</i> Breure & Araujo, 2015	x	x	x				
Bulimulidae Tryon, 1867							
<i>Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) aequatoria</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x	x					
<i>Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) anthisanensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x	x					
<i>Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) caliginosa</i> (Reeve, 1849)	x	x					
<i>Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) cotapaxiensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x	x					
<i>Bostryx alausiensis</i> (Cousin, 1887)	x	x					

Table I. Continuation.
Tabla I. Continuación.

Family / species	Endermic	No modern records	Imprecise locality	Doubtful (no voucher)	Unconfirmed (voucher not checked)	Introduced	New record
<i>Bostryx bilineatus</i> (G.B. Sowerby I, 1833)	x						
<i>Bostryx juana</i> (Cousin, 1887)	x						
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) aequatorianus</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x						
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) albolabiatus</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x	x					
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) ambustus</i> (Reeve, 1849)	?						
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) andai</i> Jousseaume, 1898	x	x					
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) baezensis</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)	x	x					
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) bourcierii</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x						
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) chimborasensis</i> (Reeve, 1848)	x	x					
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) chrysomelas</i> (Martens, 1867)		x	x				
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) expansus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)							
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) fallax</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)							
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) fucatus</i> (Reeve, 1849)							
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) hidalgoi</i> (S.I. da Costa, 1898)	x						
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) joubini</i> Germain, 1907	x	x	x				
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) membrielinus</i> (Crosse, 1867)							
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) nystianus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x						
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) ochrocheilus</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x	x					
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) orthostoma</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x	x	x				
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) peelii</i> (Reeve, 1859)							
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) petasites</i> (K. Miller, 1878)	x						
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) planibasis</i> Pilsbry, 1932	x	x					
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) quadrifasciatus</i> (Angas, 1878)	x						
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rabuti</i> (Jousseaume, 1898)	x	x					
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rhoadsi</i> Pilsbry, 1932	x						
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rubrovariegatus</i> (Higgins, 1868)							
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) sachsei</i> (Albers, 1854)							
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) strigatus</i> (G.B. Sowerby I, 1833)							
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) tigrinus</i> (S.I. da Costa, 1898)	x	x	x				
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) volsus</i> Fulton, 1907	x	x	x				
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) cactivorus</i> (Broderip, 1832)							
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) flavidulus</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x	x					
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) loxanus</i> (Higgins, 1872)	x	x					
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) loxensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)	x						
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) subpellucidus</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x	x	x				
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) winflei</i> Finch, 1929	x	x	x				
<i>Naesiotus florschuetzi</i> Breure, 1978	x						
<i>Naesiotus fontainii</i> (d'Orbigny, 1838)	x	x					
<i>Naesiotus quitensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)	x						
<i>Stenostylus colmeiroi</i> (Hidalgo, 1872)		x					
<i>Suniellus adriani</i> Breure, 2011	x	x					
Megaspiridae Pilsbry, 1904							
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) buckleyi</i> (Higgins, 1872)	x	x					
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) flori</i> (Jousseaume, 1897)	x						

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Tabla I. Continuación.

Family / species	Endemic	No modern records	Imprecise locality	Doubtful (no voucher)	Unconfirmed (voucher not checked)	Introduced	New record
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) hartwegi</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)		x					
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) integer</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1855)	x	x	x				
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) loxostomus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	?	x	x				
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) orcesi</i> Weyrauch, 1967	x						
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) tator</i> (Jousseume, 1887)		x	x	x			
Simpulopsidae Schileyko, 1999							
? <i>Leiostracus webberi</i> Pilsbry, 1939	x	x					
<i>Simpulopsis (Eudiopsis) citrinovitrea</i> (S. Moricand, 1836)							
Pupillidae Turton, 1831							
<i>Pupoides paretisii</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)				x			
Gastrocoptidae Pilsbry, 1918							
<i>Gastrocopta pazi</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)		x					
<i>Gastrocopta strangeana</i> (Iredale, 1937)					x		
<i>Gastrocopta wolfii</i> (K. Miller, 1879)	x	x					
Valloniidae Morse, 1864							
<i>Pupisoma (Pychopatula) dioscoricum</i> (C.B. Adams, 1845)							
<i>Pupisoma (Pupisoma?) macneilli</i> (Clapp, 1918)							
Vertiginidae Fitzinger, 1833							
<i>Sterkia (Metasterkia) bakeri</i> Pilsbry, 1921					x		
Clausiliidae J.E. Gray, 1855							
<i>Columbinia (Columbinia) cocaensis</i> (Jousseume, 1900)	x	x					
<i>Columbinia (Columbinia) perezii</i> (Jousseume, 1887)	x	x					
<i>Columbinia (Steatonenia) cousini</i> (Jousseume, 1900)	x	x	x				
<i>Columbinia (Steatonenia) reyrei</i> (Jousseume, 1887)	x	x					
<i>Cyclonena cyclostoma</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1850)				x			
<i>Incania anoecia</i> Ehrmann, 1949	x		x				
<i>Incania auriculina</i> (Jousseume, 1900)	x	x	x				
<i>Incania bourcierii</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1854)	x	x	x				
<i>Incania crosseii</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)	x	x					
<i>Neniptyx buckleyi</i> (Higgins, 1872)	x	x					
<i>Neniops archidona</i> (Jousseume, 1900)	x	x					
Limacidae Batsch, 1789							
<i>Limacus flavus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)						x	
<i>Limacus maculatus</i> (Kaleniczenko, 1851)						x	
Agriolimacidae H. Wagner, 1935							
<i>Deroceras reticulatum</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)						x	
<i>Deroceras laeve</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)						x	
<i>Deroceras invadens</i> Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011						x	
Gastrodontiidae Tryon, 1866							
<i>Zonitoides (Zonitoides) arboreus</i> (Say, 1816)						x	
Oxychilidae Hesse, 1927 (1879)							
<i>Oxychilis allianus</i> (J.S. Miller, 1822)			x	x		x	
Pristilomatidae Cockerell, 1891							
<i>Hawaiiia minuscula</i> (A. Binney, 1840)						x	

Table I. Continuation.

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Family / species	Endemic	No modern records	Imprecise locality	Doubtful (no voucher)	Unconfirmed (voucher not checked)	Introduced	New record
Euconulidae H.B. Baker, 1928							
<i>Guppya wolfii</i> (K. Miller, 1879) *	x	x					
<i>Guppya</i> sp.	?		x				
Spiraxidae H.B. Baker, 1939							
<i>Euglandina aequatoria</i> (S.I. da Costa, 1900)	x	x					
<i>Euglandina ecuadoriana</i> (K. Miller, 1878)	x	x					
<i>Euglandina saccata</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1861)	x	x					
<i>Euglandina striata</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)							
Solaropsidae H. Nordsieck, 1986							
<i>Solaropsis boetzkessi</i> (K. Miller, 1878)	x	x					
<i>Solaropsis cousini</i> Jousseume, 1887	x	x					
<i>Solaropsis gibboni</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)							
<i>Solaropsis iris</i> (K. Miller, 1878)	x	x					
<i>Solaropsis monile</i> (Broderip, 1832)							
<i>Solaropsis napensis</i> (Crosse, 1871)	x	x	x				
<i>Solaropsis quadrivittata</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)	x	x					
<i>Solaropsis selenostoma</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1854)		x					
Helicidae Rafinesque, 1815							
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)						x	
Labyrinthidae Borrero, Sei, Robinson & Rosenberg, 2017							
<i>Isomeria aequatoria</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1860)	x	x					
<i>Isomeria aequatoriana</i> (Hidalgo, 1867)	x						
<i>Isomeria alagoana</i> Jousseume, 1887	x	x					
<i>Isomeria bituberculata</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x						
<i>Isomeria bourcierii</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)							
<i>Isomeria cymatodes</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1852)	x	x					
<i>Isomeria gealei</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x	x					
<i>Isomeria globosa</i> (Broderip, 1832)							
<i>Isomeria hartwegi</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)	x	x					
<i>Isomeria jacksoni</i> Solem, 1966	x	x					
<i>Isomeria juno</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1850)		x					
<i>Isomeria kolbergi</i> (K. Miller, 1878)	x						
<i>Isomeria meyeri</i> (Kobelt, 1894)	x	x	x				
<i>Isomeria morula</i> (Hidalgo, 1870)	x	x	x				
<i>Isomeria triodonta</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)	x	x	x				
<i>Labyrinthus bifurcatus</i> (Deshayes, 1838)				x			
<i>Labyrinthus manueli</i> Higgins, 1872	x						
<i>Labyrinthus raimondii</i> (Philippi, 1867)							
Epiphragmophoridae Hoffmann, 1928							
<i>Epiphragmophora macasi</i> (Higgins, 1872)	x	x					
Mycetopodiidae J.E. Gray, 1840							
<i>Anodontites carinata</i> (Dunker, 1858)			x	x			
<i>Anodontites crispata</i> (Bruguière, 1792)							
<i>Anodontites elongata</i> (W. Swainson, 1823)		x	x				

Table I. Continuation.
Tabla I. Continuación.

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<i>Anodontites tenebricosa</i> (L. Lea, 1834)		x					
<i>Anodontites tortilis</i> (L. Lea, 1852)			x	x			
<i>Anodontites trapesialis</i> (Lamarck, 1819)							
<i>Anodontites trigona</i> (Spix, 1827)							
<i>Diplodontites cookei</i> W.B. Marshall, 1922							
<i>Lamproscapha ensiformis</i> (Spix, 1827)							
<i>Mycetopoda siliquosa</i> (Spix, 1827)		x					
<i>Mycetopodella facata</i> (Higgins, 1868)		x					
Etheriidae Deshayes 1832							
<i>Bartlettia stefanensis</i> (J. Moricand, 1856)							
Hyriidae W. Swainson, 1840							
<i>Castalia ambigua</i> Lamarck, 1819		x					
<i>Castalia crosseana</i> Hidalgo, 1865		x					
<i>Castalia ecarinata</i> Mousson, 1869			x	x			
<i>Diplodon guaranianus</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)		x	x				
<i>Diplodon hylaeus</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)			x	x			
<i>Prisodon obliquus</i> Schumacher, 1817		x					
<i>Tripodon corrugatus</i> (Lamarck, 1819)		x	x				
Cyrenidae J.E. Gray, 1840							
<i>Corbicula fluminea</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)							x
Dreissenidae J.E. Gray, 1840							
<i>Mytilopsis trautwineana</i> (Tryon, 1866)		x	x				
Sphaeriidae Deshayes, 1855							
<i>Pisidium boliviense</i> Sturany, 1900			x	x			
<i>Pisidium wolffi</i> Clessin, 1879	x	x					
<i>Sphaerium aequatortiale</i> Clessin, 1879	x	x					

HISTORY OF MALACOLOGICAL RESEARCH IN ECUADOR

The history of malacological research in the Neotropics has hardly been described in any detail (but see LINARES & VERA, 2012: 27-53 for a detailed account on Colombia). Hence we briefly summarise some relevant data for Ecuador (see also MILLER, 1878).

Historical authors and collectors: the malacofauna of the Ecuadorian mainland

The first persons to likely visit Ecuador and collect shells, among many

other things, were Alexander von Humboldt (1769-1859) and Aimé Bonpland (1773-1858) during their expedition to South America. They travelled the Andes from Colombia, Cartagena in the north to Ecuador, Guayaquil during 1801-1803 (WULF, 2016: 75-93). Their material was presented to Jean-Baptiste de Lamarck (1744-1829) and Achille Valenciennes (1794-1865), and described in the 1820s. However, one of the first dedicated shell collectors to visit the country was Hugh Cuming (1791-1865), who sailed along the west coast of South America during the years 1828-1830. During his travels in Ecuador he landed

Figure 1. Topography of mainland Ecuador. Source: Perry-Castañeda Library Map Collection, University of Texas at Austin (modified).

Figura 1. Topografía de Ecuador continental. Fuente: Colección de mapas de la biblioteca Perry-Castañeda, Universidad de Texas en Austin (modificado).

at the Bay of Guayaquil, Santa Elena, Jipijapa, Bahía de Caraquez, Atacames and Esmeraldas (DANCE, 1980: 482). He also visited the Galápagos (see below). His material was described by William Broderip (1789-1859) and George Brettingham Sowerby I (1788-1854), and later also by Lovell Reeve (1814-1865) and Louis Pfeiffer (1805-1877) (see also PETIT, 2007, 2009; NEUBERT *ET AL.*, 2020). It may be noted that Cuming's collection also contained specimens collected by many others, *e.g.*, Bourcier, Fraser, Ghiesbregt, Hartweg. The collection of Cuming was bought after his death by the National History Museum in

London and many of the type specimens have been located.

Several other expeditions were undertaken in the decades that followed Cuming's journey. The French expedition led by François de Castelnau (1810-1880) [according to BAJON (1995: 337) his likely year of birth was 1802] had the goal to explore the Amazon, to find the watershed between the Amazon and La Plata river systems, and to study waterways which would allow a connection between Trinidad and Buenos Aires (BAJON, 1995: 340). The expedition left France in April 1843 for Brazil, Paraguay, Bolivia, and Peru, and ended

Figure 2. Ecoregions of Ecuador. A. Terrestrial ecoregions (WWF, 2015). 1: Western Ecuador moist forests; 2: Ecuadorian dry forests; 3: South American Pacific mangroves; 4: Guayaquil flooded grasslands; 5: Northwestern Andean montane forests; 6: Northern Andean páramo; 7: Eastern Cordillera real montane forests; 8: Napo moist forests; 9: Tumbes-Piura dry forests; 10: Cordillera Central páramo. B. Freshwater ecoregions (FEOW, 2019). 11: North Andean Pacific Slopes-Río Atrato; 12: Amazonas High Andes; 13: Western Amazon Piedmont; 14: Amazonas Lowlands. See text in Appendix 1 for further explanation.

Figura 2. Ecorregiones de Ecuador. A. Ecorregiones terrestres (WWF, 2015). 1: Bosques húmedos del oeste de Ecuador; 2: Bosques secos ecuatorianos; 3: Manglares del Pacífico sudamericano; 4: Pastizales inundados de Guayaquil; 5: Bosques montaños andinos del noroeste; 6: Páramo andino septentrional; 7: bosques montaños reales de la Cordillera Oriental; 8: bosques húmedos de Napo; 9: Bosques secos Tumbes-Piura; 10: páramo Cordillera Central. B. Ecorregiones de agua dulce (FEOW, 2019). 11: Vertiente Norte Andino del Pacífico - Río Atrato; 12: Altos Andes del Amazonas; 13: Piemonte Amazónico occidental; 14: Tierras Bajas del Amazonas. Véase texto en el Apéndice 1 para más explicaciones.

in 1847 (PAPAVERO 1971: 149-158, map 12; BAJON, 1995: 340-343). The malacological material was examined by Louis Hupé (1819-1867) and his findings published in 1857. The material is housed in the Paris museum, type specimens have generally been located. From 1862-1866 the Spanish Comisión Científica del Pacífico explored South America, and part of the expedition travelled through Ecuador (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017). The collected shells were mainly described by Joaquin Hidalgo (1839-1923) and Hippolyte Crosse (1826-1898); the material is in the Madrid and Paris museums and has partly been recovered. James Orton (1830-1877) also visited the country (ORTON, 1871) and his molluscan material was described by

Crosse; his material is in the Harvard collection in Cambridge, Massachusetts.

Apart from these expeditions, individual travellers collected shells (usually as 'by-catch' of their main purpose) which were described by e.g. Alcide d'Orbigny (1802-1857; based on material collected by Amboise-Henry Fontaine (1795-1870), published in 1835), Edmund Higgins (collected by Clarence Buckley and published in 1872; specimens not located), Edgar Smith (1847-1916; published in 1877 without data on the collector) and Eduard von Martens (1831-1904; based on material collected by Alfred Stübel and published in 1885).

In the 1878 volume of the *Malakozologische Blätter*, the first part of a paper

on 'Die Binnenmollusken von Ecuador' was published by Konrad Miller (1844-1933). Miller was a German priest and scientist, who obtained his material partly from his fellow priest Christian Boetzkes (1840-1930) who was working in Ecuador between 1872 and 1876, and partly from the German scientist-priest Theodor Wolf who was attached to the Quito university for several years and who stayed in Ecuador from 1870 to 1891. In the 1879 issue of the *Malakozoologische Blätter*, the second part of Miller's paper appeared together with the plates. In total he described 119 taxa new to science, of which 66 were from Ecuador (BREURE, 2019b); the material has not been located.

In 1887 two papers were published, one by Félix Jousseume (1835-1921) and one by Auguste Cousin (1835-1899), that were both based on the material that Cousin had collected during his stay in Ecuador. The Jousseume collection came to the Paris museum, and part of the Cousin collection was purchased by Dautzenberg from the Parisian shell dealer Géret, and is currently housed in the Brussels museum (within the Dautzenberg collection). Material from the latter is also considered to be eligible for type status if it matches the descriptions in JOUSSEUME'S (1887a) paper, where he explicitly stated "A son départ de Paris, M. Cousin, notre collègue de la Société Zoologique de France, me remit, avec sa collection, un manuscrit contenant la liste de tous les Mollusques de l'Equateur connus jusqu'à ce jour, les observations intéressantes qu'il avait faites sur les animaux et la description d'espèces nouvelles" [On his departure from Paris, Mr. Cousin, our colleague at the French Zoological Society, has given me, together with his collection, a manuscript containing a list of all the molluscs known from Ecuador, with interesting observations he had made on the animals and descriptions of new species] (BREURE, 2020). Jousseume also published on Ecuadorian species in 1894, 1897, 1898, and 1900. At the close of the 19th century smaller contributions were made by César Ancey (1860-

1906) in 1890 and 1895, and by Solomon da Costa (1827-1907) in 1898 and 1899.

The latter author started off the 20th century with a paper published in 1900, just as his younger contemporary Ernest Sykes (1867-1954) had done. During the first decade of the 1900's, contributions by Louis Germain (1878-1942) were published in 1907, 1908, and 1910, based on material collected by Paul Rivet during a geodesic mission of the French army (SCHIAVON, 2006; LAURIÈRE, 2011). Later contributions were made by Henry Pilsbry (1862-1957) and Harald Rehder (1907-1996); their material is present in American museums. During the second half of the century the main authors that contributed to our knowledge of the Ecuadorian mainland fauna were Wolfgang Weyrauch (1907-1979); who collected first for Pilsbry and Zilch, and who only later started to publish under his own name) and José Thomé (1930-2016); the latter specialised in Veronicellid slugs. Material of the first is in the museum of Tucumán, Argentina; the latter made studies of historical collections in European and American museums, but the fate of his personal collection is unknown to us. Over the last decades a few papers and a book have been published by Modesto Correo (2008, 2010), a Cuban malacologist living in Quito (CORREO, 2008, 2010). A paper by Barna Páll-Gergely (2014), who is mainly specialised in East Asian and Eastern European species, and the first author of this study described a few new species from major museum collections (BREURE, 1978, 2011; PÁLL-GERGELY & ASAMI, 2014). This included material collected in 2000 in the regions of Nuevo Corrientes and Chuinista as part of the Eastern Ecuador expedition organized by The Shiwiari Rainforest Initiative. Material from this fieldwork is housed in the Pontificia Universidad Católica del Ecuador and the Natural History Museum, London (DIXON *ET AL.*, 2000).

Due to the spread of human influence, several historical locations may have disappeared or altered in such a way that at present suitable habitats for the species recorded have vanished. See

also Appendix 2 for the location of collecting sites used in this study.

Historical authors and collectors: the malacofauna of the Galápagos

As mentioned above, Cuming visited the Galápagos where he landed at Isla Santa Cruz, Isla San Salvador and Isla Isabela (DANCE, 1980: 482). Soon afterwards he was followed by Charles Darwin (1809-1882) who visited several islands on his trip aboard the '*Beagle*'. We do not know for sure how many shells he collected, despite the fact that he mentioned in his journal "Of land-shells I collected sixteen kinds (and two marked varieties), of which, with the exception of one *Helix* found at Tahiti, all are peculiar to this archipelago; a single fresh-water shell (*Paludina*) is common to Tahiti and Van Diemen's Land" (DARWIN, 1845 [1891]: 372). But at least one specimen is in the collection of the Natural History Museum, London, that originates from this trip (BREURE & ABLETT, 2014: 56). For many years the islands were not surveyed for the purposes of malacological collecting until the geologist Theodor Wolf visited the islands in the 1870s (WOLF, 1879) and sent his material to Miller in Stuttgart, who forwarded part of it to Theodor and Paul Reibisch in Dresden; the latter published about Wolf's material from the Galápagos in 1892. A few years earlier Ancey described several new species, without revealing who had collected his material. Around the same time the American author William Healey Dall (1845-1927) started to publish on this fauna, initially based on material collected by the geologist George Baur during one of the expeditions of the Steamer '*Albatross*' (see STEARNS, 1893, who reviewed also the previous literature). Later, the California Academy of Sciences undertook an expedition to the Galápagos in 1905-1906 (JAMES, 2010). Dall continued to publish on the fauna in the early decades of the 20th century and introduced more than 30 taxa at the species-group level. After his death it was not until 1951 that Nils Odhner (1884-1973) described a few new species, followed by Allyn G. Smith (1893-1976) in 1972, at the same time as Jean-

Jacques Van Mol (1931-2017). In 1977 Josef Vagvolgyi (1927-2000) described six new taxa from the Galápagos (ODHNER, 1951; SMITH, 1972; VAGVOLGYI, 1977). Their material is all housed in major American and European museums.

The past decades have seen an increased interest in the Galápagos fauna. For molluscs this is evidenced by the work of PARENT & CRISPIE (2006, 2009), PARENT & SMITH (2006), PARENT (2008, 2012), PARENT *ET AL.* (2008), MIQUEL & HERRERA (2014), MIQUEL & BUNGARTZ (2017), PHILIPPS *ET AL.* (2019), and the forthcoming publication by N.F. Shoobs.

The most recent list of non-marine species was published by PARENT *ET AL.* (2014). It was based on a database maintained in the Charles Darwin Foundation, Puerto Ayora, Galápagos. This list contains some obvious errors (*e.g.*, several species only known from other islands are mentioned as from Isla Santa Cruz only) and unavailable names of some *Naesiotus* species are listed. These species had been named by G. Coppois (Brussels) in his unpublished thesis in the 1980s, and the material has never been deposited in a public collection. Consequently, these names are not available according to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (Art. 10 ICZN 1999) and are not further discussed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This checklist presents the published species-group and genus-group names found in the literature, that have been applied to the non-marine mollusc fauna of mainland Ecuador, as well as unpublished records from Museum collections and online databases that could be checked by the authors. Names are arranged by family according to the classification by BOUCHET *ET AL.* (2017) for Gastropoda and BOUCHET *ET AL.* (2010) for Bivalvia. Within families, genera have been arranged in alphabetical order; the status of genera and generic placement of the species follows MOLUSCABASE (2021). Species-group names are arranged under each genus in alpha-

Figure 3. Administrative regions mainland of Ecuador. Source: Perry-Castañeda Library Map Collection, University of Texas at Austin. <<https://maps.lib.utexas.edu/maps/ecuador.html>>

Figura 3. Regiones administrativas de Ecuador continental. Fuente: Colección de mapas de la biblioteca Perry-Castañeda, Universidad de Texas en Austin. <<https://maps.lib.utexas.edu/maps/ecuador.html>>

betical order. Where type material has been located or where an original figure was given, we provide illustrations. For each family, species records from other sources are listed as doubtful (when in literature and no vouchers are mentioned: marked with an open square ('□') or as unconfirmed (mentioned in databases but not checked: marked with a black square '■'). Introduced species are indicated with a black diamond ('◆').

Records of species are divided into two categories, as far as applicable. Vouchered specimens which are in

public museums, and observations of which no voucher is known to us. These two categories have both been listed under Distribution. In the maps where the distribution of species is shown these two categories are reflected by solid and open symbols respectively. In the text, the localities are arranged according to the main administrative divisions of the country, i.e. provinces (Fig. 3). With the exception of type localities, records without precise locations have been disregarded as a complete listing of all Ecuadorian records in

museums is beyond the scope of this project.

Records for Gastropoda have been plotted on ecoregion maps when precise localities were available that could be georeferenced. Bivalvia records usually mention the river systems only and not precise localities; for the location of the river systems the reader is referred to a physiography map (Fig. 1).

Shell photos were taken with digital cameras at different institutions by their staff (see Acknowledgements), except one species which was scanned with microCT using a RX EasyTom 150 (RX Solutions, Chavanod, France; <<http://www.rxsolutions.fr>>), without filter. Reconstruction was performed using X-Act software from RX Solutions. Segmentation, visualisation, and analysis were performed using Dragonfly software (Object Research Systems Inc., Montreal, Canada).

Due to restrictions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic the accessibility of shell material, either physically or by photographs, was severely limited. The main text body was finished in November 2020 and updated in November 2021 with some recent observations on iNaturalist.

Databases used:

We consulted the following databases:

- Invert-E-base (<http://www.invertebase.org>), Musselp (<http://mussel-project.uwsp.edu/index.html>; GRAF & CUMMINGS 2020)
- GBIF (<https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.ayb9fm>; <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.4msaab>)
- iNaturalist (<https://www.inaturalist.org>); records can be retrieved with the syntax <<https://ecuador.inaturalist.org/observations/XXX>> where XXX is the observation number.

Several additional museum databases (all indicated by an asterisk (*) before their abbreviation below) were consulted. Records that we considered as in need for further verification by inspection have been omitted, and observations from iNaturalist have only been accepted if they could be confirmed by one of us.

Acronyms of repositories:

The following abbreviations are used to refer to depositories:

- *ANSP, Academy of Natural Sciences, Philadelphia PA, U.S.A.;
- CMS, Superintendencia de Controle de Endemias do Estado de São Paulo, Sao Paulo, Brazil;
- *DMNH, Delaware Museum of Natural History, Delaware DE, U.S.A.;
- EC, private collection M. Roosen, Tilburg, the Netherlands;
- *FMNH, Field Museum of Natural History, Chicago IL, U.S.A.;
- IFML, Instituto y Fundación Miguel Lillo, Tucumán, Argentina;
- *MCZ, Museum of Comparative Zoology, Cambridge MA, U.S.A.;
- MHNG, Muséum d'histoire naturelle, Geneva, Switzerland;
- MIZ, Muzeum i Instytut Zoologii, Warsaw, Poland;
- MMUE, Manchester Museum, University of Manchester, Manchester, U.K.;
- MNCN, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, Spain;
- *MNHN, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France;
- MNZW, Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa, Wellington, New Zealand;
- MRSN, Museo Regionale di Scienze Naturali, Torino, Italy;
- NHMD, Natural History Museum of Denmark, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark;
- NHM / NHMUK, Natural History Museum, London, U.K.;
- NMBE, Naturmuseum der Burgergemeinde, Bern, Switzerland;
- NHMW, Naturmuseum Wien, Vienna, Austria;
- NMW, National Museum Wales, Cardiff, U.K.;
- QCAZ, Pontificia Universidad Católica del Ecuador, Museo de Zoología, Quito, Ecuador;
- *RBINS, Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Brussels, Belgium;
- *RMNH, Naturalis Biodiversity Centre, Leiden, the Netherlands (formerly Rijksmuseum van Natuurlijke Historie);

*SMD, Senckenberg Natur-Museum, Dresden, Germany;

*SMF, Senckenberg Natur-Museum, Frankfurt am Main, Germany;

UMMZ, University of Michigan, Museum of Zoology, Ann Arbor MI, U.S.A.;

*USNM, Smithsonian Institution, Washington D.C., U.S.A.;

ZMA, Naturalis Biodiversity Centre, Leiden, the Netherlands (formerly Zoologisch Museum Amsterdam);

ZMB, Museum für Naturkunde, Humboldt Universität, Berlin, Germany;

ZMUZ, Zoologisches Museum, Universität Zurich, Switzerland.

Other abbreviations used are:

Coll., collection;

D, maximum diameter of shell;

H, height of shell;

obs., observation;

TL, type locality.

SYSTEMATIC CATALOGUE

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier, 1795

Family HELICINIDAE A. Férussac, 1822

Remarks. The Helicinidae is a pantropical family with a distribution range limited to the subtropical and tropical zones of the Neotropics, Australasia and the Pacific. The number of valid species is estimated to be in the range from 770 to 1,140 (RICHLING, 2014). A monograph of this family dates back to the early 20th century (A.J. WAGNER, 1907-1911). RICHLING (2004) has extensively studied Costa Rican and Central American helicinids and produced several studies on type material for this group (*e.g.*, RICHLING, 2005; RICHLING & GLAUBRECHT, 2008). Anatomical and molecular data are scarce.

Genus *Bourciera* L. Pfeiffer, 1852

Bourciera Pfeiffer, 1852, *Z. Malak.*, 8: 178. Type species by subsequent monotypy *Cyclostoma helicinaeformis* L. Pfeiffer, 1852.

Bourciera fraseri (L. Pfeiffer, 1859) (Figs. 4, 13)

Cyclostoma (Bourciera) fraseri Pfeiffer, 1859, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 27: 28, pl. 44 fig. 1 [as *fraseii*]. "Province of Cuenca, republic of Ecuador". Syntype NHMUK 20130063 (1).

Distribution. Azuay: Cuenca (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. GERMAIN (1907: 62) mentioned this species from Pichincha: San Tadeo; this might be a misidentification for one of the species below. This species was also reported from the eastern slopes of the Peruvian Andes (RAMÍREZ *ET AL.*, 2003).

Bourciera helicinaeformis L. Pfeiffer, 1852 (Figs. 5, 13)

Bourciera helicinaeformis Pfeiffer, 1852, *Mon. Pneumon. Viv.*: 312-313.

Cyclostoma helicinaeforme Pfeiffer, 1853, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 19: 151-152. - *Syst. Conch. Cab.*, 19 (1): 243, pl. 32 figs. 8-10 "in valle Yaraqui, reipublicae Aequatoris". Syntypes NHMUK 20130062 (3).

Distribution. Imbabura: Without specific locality (CORREOSO, 2008); Manduriacu (obs. iNaturalist 4839116, 2016); Pichincha: Yaruqui (TL); Nanegal (MARTENS, 1885a); Los Puentes (COUSIN, 1887); San Tadeo, chemin de Pachajal (GERMAIN, 1907).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Figure 4. *Bourciera fraseri* (L. Pfeiffer, 1859). Azuay: Cuenca. Syntype NHMUK 20130063 (D 10 mm). Figure 5. *Bourciera helicinaeformis* L. Pfeiffer, 1852. Pichincha: Yaruquí. Syntype NHMUK 20130062 (D 19 mm).

Figura 4. *Bourciera fraseri* (L. Pfeiffer, 1859). Azuay: Cuenca. Sintipo NHMUK 20130063 (D 10 mm). Figura 5. *Bourciera helicinaeformis* L. Pfeiffer, 1852. Pichincha: Yaruquí. Sintipo NHMUK 20130062 (D 19 mm).

Bourciera striatula K. Miller, 1879 (Figs. 6A, 13)

Bourciera striatula Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 145, pl. 5 fig. 6. "Val de Pilaton, 1200 m". Type material not located.

Distribution. Pichincha: Pilatón valley (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Bourciera viridissima K. Miller, 1879 (Figs. 6B, 13)

Bourciera viridissima Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 146, pl. 5 fig. 5. "Val de Pilaton, 1100 m".
Type material not located.

Distribution. Imbabura: Cotacachi (obs. iNaturalist 41301754, 2010; 36380240, 2019); Pichincha: Pilatón valley (TL); San Nicolas (COUSIN, 1887).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. We are of the opinion that this is a valid species..

Bourciera sp.

Distribution. Orellana: Without specified locality (obs. iNaturalist 26205252, 2020)

Remarks. These and other non-vouchered records strongly indicate the presence of an additional (undescribed) *Bourciera* species in the Amazon region.

Genus *Helicina* Lamarck, 1799

Helicina Lamarck, 1799, *Mém. Soc. Hist. Natur. Paris*, 1: 76. Type species by subsequent designation (CHILDREN, 1823: 239) *Helicina neritella* Lamarck, 1801.

Remarks. RICHLING & GLAUBRECHT (2008: 304) previously remarked: "The South American species are in need of revision, both on species level as well as for systematic arrangement. (...) Therefore the arrangement is mostly tentative and not even the assignment to *Helicina* is certain". Following these authors with their 'single-genus' solution, species are listed here as *Helicina* (?) awaiting further research.

Helicina (?) cf. *bourguignatiana* Ancey, 1892 (Fig. 7)

Helicina bourguignatiana Ancey, 1892, *J. of Conch.*, 7: 95. "Santa Cruz de la Sierra" [Bolivia]. Syn-types RBINS MT.1910 (1).

Distribution. Pastaza: Cushueme [Cushuimi] (FMNH 173031).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. This species, originally described from Bolivia, has also been recorded from Urubamba, Peru (WAGNER 1911 [1907-1911]). Given the large distance between the Ecuadorian and Peruvian localities, without localities recorded in between, the identification is tentative and needs further investigation.

Helicina (?) *ecuadoriana* K. Miller, 1879 (Figs. 8, 13)

Helicina ecuadoriana Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 146, pl. 5 fig. 4. "Val de Pilaton, circa 1000 m". Type material not located.

Distribution. Esmeraldas: Canande Reserve, obs. iNaturalist 4871736. 2016); Pichincha: Rio Pilatón valley (TL); San Miguel de los Bancos (obs. iNaturalist 62893710, 2020); Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: near Santo Domingo de los Colorados (obs. iNaturalist, 69523559, 2021).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. MARTENS (1885a) mentioned this species from Colombia, Dept. Boyacá, near Muzo, 600-800 m. Without records in the intermediate region, Martens' record needs corroboration.

Helicina (?) *laus* A.J. Wagner, 1905 (Figs. 9, 13)

Helicina ernesti laus Wagner, 1905, *Denkschr. K. Akad. Wiss.*, 78: 222, pl. 12 fig. 12. "Venezuela" [corrected to "Rio Jurua, Nebenfluss des Amazonas" (WAGNER 1910 [1907-1911]: 289-290)]. See RICHLING & GLAUBRECHT, 2008: 292-293 for discussion of ZMB and MIZ material.

Distribution. Napo: "Populat de Napo" (UF 160147).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT 0142].

Remarks. The material originated from Cousin and was later part of the Dautzenberg collection before it came in to the McGinty collection, now in UF. I. Richling (pers. commun., August 2020) confirmed their identity. The locality probably refers to Puerto Napo, for which 'Napo' is an old name. This species, now recorded for the first time in Ecuador, also occurs in Brazil and Peru.

□ *Helicina* (?) *rhynchostoma* L. Pfeiffer, 1865

Helicina rhynchostoma Pfeiffer, 1865, *Mon. Pneumon. Viv.*: 245 (ex Shuttleworth ms.). "Campanera Columbiae, 3000' supra mare". Type material not located.

Distribution. Ecuador: without specified locality (HIDALGO 1870).

Remarks. HIDALGO (1870) reports the variety "*unicolor*" from Ecuador. His material has not been located (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017) and it cannot be excluded that it concerns a misidentification of this presumably Colombian species, which was not listed by LINARES & VERA (2012). The species has also been found in Venezuela (■ UMMZ 47808).

Helicina (?) *unizonata* F. Haas, 1966 (Figs. 10, 13)

Helicina (Oxyrhombus) unizonata Haas, 1966, *Fieldiana, Zool.* 44: 231, fig. 48. "Colombia, Putumayo, Upper Río Putumayo, downstream from Puerto Asís, Nueva Granada". Holotype FMNH 114098.

Distribution. Orellana: Aguarico; Tiputini (obs. iNaturalist 25936802, 2019); Pastaza: Cushueme (FMNH 173033).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. This are the first published records of this species from Ecuador.

Comments on the family. The following species have been mentioned for this family in literature but are likely based on misidentifications:

- *Helicina moreletiana* L. Pfeiffer, 1850 (based on a record by HIGGINS, 1872); described from an unknown type locality. Also reported from Bahia, Brasil (WAGNER 1911 [1907-1911]).

- *Helicina tamsiana* L. Pfeiffer, 1850 (COUSIN, 1887: 275 mentioned it from "Inter Quito et Napo (Orton)") but we have not found any vouchers; known from Venezuela and Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012).

Figure 6. A: *Bourciera striatula* K. Miller, 1879. Pichincha: Pilatón valley. Original figure in MILLER (1879), pl. 5 fig. 6 (D 18 mm). B: *Bourciera viridissima* K. Miller, 1879. Pichincha: Pilatón valley. Original figure in MILLER (1879), pl. 5 fig. 5 a, b, c (D up to 13 mm). Figure 7. *Helicina* (?) cf. *bourguignatiana* Ancey, 1892. Pastaza: Cushueme [Cushuimi]. FMNH 173031 (D 7.4 mm). Figure 8. *Helicina* (?) *ecuadoriana* K. Miller, 1879. Pichincha: Rio Pilatón valley. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 5 fig. 4 (D 13 mm). Figure 9. *Helicina* (?) *laus* A.J. Wagner, 1905. Napo: "Populat de Napo". UF 160147 (D 11 mm).

Figura 6. A: *Bourciera striatula* K. Miller, 1879. Pichincha: Valle del Pilatón. Figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 5 fig. 6 (D 18 mm); agrandado a la derecha. B: *Bourciera viridissima* K. Miller, 1879. Pichincha: Valle del Pilatón. Figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 5 fig. 5 (D hasta 13 mm). Figura 7. *Helicina* (?) cf. *bourguignatiana* Ancey, 1892. Pastaza: Cushueme [Cushuimi]. FMNH 173031 (D 7,4 mm). Figura 8. *Helicina* (?) *ecuadoriana* K. Miller, 1879. Pichincha: Valle del río Pilatón. Figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 5 fig. 4 (D 13 mm). Figura 9. *Helicina* (?) *laus* A.J. Wagner, 1905. Napo: "Populat de Napo". UF 160147 (D 11 mm).

There are records of the genus *Alcadia* J.E. Gray, 1840 (Type species by subsequent designation (GRAY, 1847: 182) *Helicina major* J.E. Gray, 1824) reported on the <iNaturalist.com> website: Napo: Tena, urban area (obs. iNaturalist 24155002, 2019); Orellana: Francisco de Orellana; Parque Nacional Yasuní (obs. iNaturalist 38116143, 2019); Sucumbios: Reserva de producción de Fauna Cuyabeno (obs. iNaturalist 34133415, 2011), all in Napo moist forests ecoregion. [NT0142]. However the genus is not mentioned in the literature and these records need confirmation.

Family PROSERPINELLIDAE H.B. Baker, 1923

Remarks. A relatively small family of prosobranch snails related to the Helicinidae but distinguished on anatomical grounds (THOMPSON, 1980). Their distribution is limited to the Caribbean, Central America and the northern part of South America.

Genus *Linidiella* Jousseaume, 1889

Linidiella Jousseaume, 1889, *Mém. Soc. Zool. France*, 2: 256. Type species by subsequent designation (H.B. BAKER, 1923a: 84) *Proserpina swifti* Bland, 1863.

Linidiella cinnanomea (Sykes, 1900) (Figs. 11, 13)

Despoena (*Chersodespoena*) *cinnanomea* Sykes, 1900, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 4: 136, fig. "between Ayabamba and Santa Rosa". Holotype NHMUK 1900.2.2.5 (1).

Distribution. El Oro: between Ayapamba and Santa Rosa (TL); 9 km W of Pinas (UF 37413).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. There is a second place named Ayapamba in Prov. Azuay, but the UF material points to Prov. El Oro.

Genus *Archecharax* F.G. Thompson, 1980

Cyane H. Adams, 1870, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 38: 376. Not *Cyana* Felder, 1861 (Lepidoptera). *Archecharax* Thompson, 1980, *Archiv für Moll.*, 137: 20. Type species by original designation *Cyane blandiana* H. Adams, 1870.

Archecharax cousini (Jousseaume, 1887) (Figs. 12, 13)

Proserpinella cousini Jousseaume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 181, pl. 3 figs 15-16. "République de l'Équateur". Syntypes RBINS MT.43 (2).

Distribution. Pichincha: Los Puentes (BREURE, 2020).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Comments on the family. HIGGINS (1872: 687) listed the Venezuelan species *Proserpina swifti* Bland, 1863 among the shells collected by Buckley in Ecuador. We have not seen a voucher to be able to confirm this record.

Family NERITIDAE Rafinesque, 1815

Remarks. This is a large family occurring both in marine and non-marine habitats, which has recently been reviewed by EICHHORST (2016a, 2016b). Only species belonging to this family which have been reported from freshwater (or a combination of fresh- and brackish water) are listed here. See EICHHORST (2016b: 1034) for marine/brackish water species.

Figure 10. *Helicina (?) unizonata* F. Haas, 1966. Colombia, Putumayo: Upper Río Putumayo, downstream from Puerto Asís. Holotype FMNH 114098 (D 11.7 mm). Figure 11. *Linidiella cinnamomea* (Sykes, 1900). El Oro: between Ayapamba and Santa Rosa. Holotype NHMUK 1900.2.2.5 (D 15.2 mm). Figure 12. *Archecharax cousini* (Jousseau, 1887). Ecuador. Syntype RBINS MT.43 (D 10 mm).

Figura 10. *Helicina (?) unizonata* F. Haas, 1966. Colombia, Putumayo: Alto Río Putumayo, aguas abajo de Puerto Asís. Holotipo FMNH 114098 (D 11,7 mm). Figura 11. *Linidiella cinnamomea* (Sykes, 1900). El Oro: entre Ayapamba y Santa Rosa. Holotipo NHMUK 1900.2.2.5 (D 15,2 mm). Figura 12. *Archecharax cousini* (Jousseau, 1887). Ecuador. Sintipo RBINS MT.43 (D 10 mm).

Figure 13. Distribution of Helicinidae and Proserpinellidae species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 13. Distribución de las especies de Helicinidae y de Proserpinellidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Genus *Clypeolum* Récluz, 1842

Clypeolum Récluz, 1842, *Revue Zool. Soc. Cuvier.*, 5: 235. Type species by subsequent designation (PILSBRY & BEQUAERT, 1927: 162) *Neritina latissima* Broderip, 1833.

Clypeolum latissimum (Broderip, 1833) (Figs. 14, 30)

Neritina latissima Broderip in Broderip & Sowerby I, 1833, *Proc. Comm. Zool. Soc. London*, 2: 200. "Real Llejos". Syntypes NHMUK 1966645 (4), NHMUK 1971041 (3), NHMUK 1971042 (1).

Neritina intermedia (var. β) *minima* K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 171. "Rio Atacames". Type material not located. [New synonymy].

Neritina latissima var. *pilsbryi* Tryon in Tryon & Pilsbry, 1888 [1888-1889], *Man. Conch.*, (1) 10: 76, pl. 22 fig. 91. No type locality. Lectotype (BAKER, 1964: 160) ANSP 37745; paralectotype ANSP 358498 (1).

Distribution. Esmeraldas: Río Atacames (TL *minima*); Río Verde; Guayas: Guayaquil (MILLER, 1878); Manabí: Río Ayampé (Roosen, pers. obs. 2019).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific slopes - Río Atrato [301].

Remarks. EICHHORST (2016a: 313) reported the species from "West coast of the Americas from southern Mexico to Ecuador, and northern Peru".

Family AMPULLARIIDAE J.E. Gray, 1824

Remarks. This family of freshwater snails is predominantly distributed in humid (sub)tropical ecosystems in Central and South America, Africa and Asia. COWIE & THIENGO (2003) presented a catalogue of the American species, including their current taxonomic positions. Additional information on type specimens can be found in KÖHLER

Figure 14. *Clypeolum latissimum* (Broderip, 1833). A: Costa Rica, “Real Llejos”, syntype NHMUK 1966645 (D 23.5 mm); B: Manabi, río Ayampé, living specimen. (photo: M. Roosen). Figure 15. *Asolene crassa* (W. Swainson, 1823). Ecuador. Syntype of *Ampullaria solida* Busch, 1859, NHMUK 20020683 (H 38.3 mm).

Figura 14. *Clypeolum latissimum* (Broderip, 1833). A: Costa Rica, “Real Llejos”, sintipo NHMUK 1966645 (D 23,5 mm); B: Manabí, río Ayampé (foto: M. Roosen). Figura 15. *Asolene crassa* (W. Swainson, 1823). Ecuador. Sintipo de *Ampullaria solida* Busch, 1859, NHMUK 20020683 (H 38,3 mm).

& GLAUBRECHT (2006), COWIE & HÉROS (2012), COWIE *ET AL.* (2015, 2017a, b). For the biology of this group see HAYES *ET AL.* (2015), for phylogenetic data HAYES *ET AL.* (2009, 2015).

Genus *Asolene* d’Orbigny, 1838

Asolene d’Orbigny, 1838 [1834-1847], *Voy. Amér. mérid.*, 5(3): 364. Type species by subsequent designation (GRAY, 1847: 148) *Helix platae* Maton, 1811.

Asolene crassa (W. Swainson, 1823) (Fig. 15)

Ampullaria crassa Swainson, 1823 [1822-1823], *Zool. Illustr.*, 3: pl. 136 upper and lower figs. No locality given. Syntypes "possibly MMUE" (COWIE & THIENGO, 2003), not located in ROWSON ET AL. (2018).

Ampullaria solida Busch, 1859, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 27: 168. "Ecuador". Syntypes NHMUK 20020683 (2).

Distribution. Ecuador: without precise localities in literature. Pichincha: Quito (UMMZ 15639).

Remarks. The record from Quito is based on historical material and its true distribution is likely elsewhere. Further reported from Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, French Guiana, Guyana, Peru, Suriname, Venezuela (COWIE & THIENGO, 2003; LINARES & VERA, 2012).

Genus *Pomacea* Perry, 1810

Pomacea Perry, 1810 [1810-1811], *Arcana*: unnumbered plate and text [pl. 12 (COWIE & THIENGO, 2003)]. Type species by monotypy *Pomacea maculata* Perry, 1810.

Subgenus *Pomacea* (*Effusa*) Jousseaume, 1889

Effusa Jousseaume, 1889, *Mém. Soc. Zool. France*, 2: 255. Type species by subsequent designation (H.B. BAKER, 1930a: 11) *Ampullaria luteostoma* Swainson, 1823.

Pomacea (*Effusa*) *expansa* (K. Miller, 1879) (Fig. 16A, 30)

Ampullaria expansa Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 152, pl. 15 fig. 6. "Rio Santiago prope Playa de Oro, provincia Esmeraldas". Type material not located.

Distribution. Esmeraldas: Río Santiago (TL).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific slopes - Río Atrato [301].

Remarks. COWIE & THIENGO (2003) considered this a valid species, but noted that this taxon is a "junior primary homonym of *Ampullaria expansa* Nevill, 1877, which is now placed in *Pila* Röding, 1798".

Pomacea (*Effusa*) *quinindensis* (K. Miller, 1879) (Fig. 16B, 30)

Ampullaria quinindensis Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 151, pl. 15 fig. 5. "Rio Quinindé, qui influit in fluminem Esmeraldas". Type material not located.

Distribution. Esmeraldas: Río Quinindé (TL).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific slopes - Río Atrato [301].

Remarks. Considered a valid species by COWIE & THIENGO (2003).

Subgenus *Pomacea* (*Pomacea*)

Pomacea (*Pomacea*) *aldersoni* (Pain, 1946) (Fig. 17)

Pila (*Pomacea*) *aldersoni* Pain, 1946, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 26: 180, pl. 6 figs 1-2. "Ecuador, in a marsh near Santa Barbara, about 170 miles SE Quito". Holotype NHMUK 1946.6.24.25; possible paratype NMW 1955.158.02411 (1), 1981.118.00091 (1), see COWIE & THIENGO (2003: 56).

Figure 16. A: *Pomacea (Effusa) expansa* (K. Miller, 1879). Esmeraldas: Río Santiago. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 15 fig. 6 (H 32 mm). B: *Pomacea (Effusa) quinindensis* (K. Miller, 1879). Esmeraldas: Río Quinindé. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 15 fig. 5 (H up to 38 mm).
 Figura 16. A: *Pomacea (Effusa) expansa* (K. Miller, 1879). Esmeraldas: Río Santiago. Figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 15 fig. 6 (H 32 mm). B: *Pomacea (Effusa) quinindensis* (K. Miller, 1879). Esmeraldas: Río Quinindé. Figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 15 fig. 5 (H hasta 38 mm).

Distribution. Pastaza/Morona-Santiago: Santa Bárbara (TL).

Remarks. The distance and direction given by Pain leads to either the southern region of Prov. Pastaza or the northeastern region of Prov. Morona-Santiago. No locality with the name of Santa Bárbara was found in modern gazetteers. Further reported from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 95).

□ *Pomacea (Pomacea) bulla* (Reeve, 1856) (Fig. 18)

Ampullaria bulla Reeve, 1856, *Conch. Icon.*, 10: pl. 22 figs 104a-104b. No type locality given. Syn-types NHMUK 20020648 (2).

Remarks. This record is based on PAETEL (1887 [1877-1878]: 477) and indicated as “?error” by COWIE & THIENGO (2003).

❖ *Pomacea (Pomacea) canaliculata* (Lamarck, 1822) (Fig. 19)

Ampullaria canaliculata Lamarck, 1822, *Hist. Nat. Anim. sans Vert.* 6 (2): 178. “Guadeloupe”. Neotype (HAYES *ET AL.*, 2012: 737) USNM 1185844.

Distribution. Ecuador, various localities (HORGAN *ET AL.*, 2014: fig. 1).

Remarks. Introduced in 2005 (HORGAN *ET AL.*, 2014). Further reported from Lower Paraná, Uruguay and La Plata basins; see for a discussion of the native distribution and type status HAYES *ET AL.* (2012), for non-native distribution see JOSHI *ET AL.* (2017). Not mentioned as introduced in Ecuador by DARRIGRAN *ET AL.* (2020: Supplementary material 2).

17

18

Figure 17. *Pomacea (Pomacea) aldersoni* (Pain, 1946). Pastaza/Morona-Santiago: Santa Bárbara. Holotype NHMUK 1946.6.24.25 (H 61.4 mm). Figure 18. *Pomacea (Pomacea) bulla* (Reeve, 1856). Unknown locality. Syntype NHMUK 20020648 (H 21.6 mm).

Figura 17. *Pomacea (Pomacea) aldersoni* (Pain, 1946). Pastaza / Morona-Santiago: Santa Bárbara. Holotipo NHMUK 1946.6.24.25 (H 61,4 mm). Figura 18. *Pomacea (Pomacea) bulla* (Reeve, 1856). Localidad desconocida. Sintipo NHMUK 20020648 (H 21,6 mm).

Figure 19. *Pomacea (Pomacea) canaliculata* (Lamarck, 1822). Argentina, Buenos Aires: Palermo. Neotype USNM 1185844 (H 83.3 mm). Figure 20. *Pomacea (Pomacea) columellaris* (A.A. Gould, 1848). Perú: Maynas. Holotype USNM 5547 (H 62 mm).

Figura 19. *Pomacea (Pomacea) canaliculata* (Lamarck, 1822). Argentina, Buenos Aires: Palermo. Neotipo USNM 1185844 (H 83,3 mm). Figura 20. *Pomacea (Pomacea) columellaris* (A.A. Gould, 1848). Perú: Maynas. Holotipo USNM 5547 (H 62 mm).

□ *Pomacea (Pomacea) columellaris* (A.A. Gould, 1848) (Fig. 20)

Ampullaria columellaris Gould, 1848, *Proc. Boston Soc. Nat. Hist.*, 3: 74. "Province of Maynas, Peru". Holotype USNM 5547.

Remarks. COWIE & THIENGO (2003: 60) listed it with a question mark from Ecuador and gave a reference to PAIN (1960). We have seen no further records for this species. COWIE *ET AL.* (2015: 4) explained the holotype status of Gould's specimen.

Pomacea (Pomacea) cousini (Jousseau, 1887) (Fig. 21)

Ampullaria cousini Jousseau, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 185, pl. 3 fig. 3. "République de l'Équateur". Lectotype (COWIE & HÉROS, 2012: 801) MNHN-IM-2000-4483.

Distribution. Ecuador: without further precise localities.

Remarks. This species has so far not been recognised in any material after its initial description.

Figure 21. *Pomacea (Pomacea) cousini* (Jousseau, 1887). Ecuador. Lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-4483 (H 43 mm). Figure 22. *Pomacea (Pomacea) cumingii* (King & Broderip, 1831). Panamá: Saboga. Possible syntype NHMUK 20190597 (H 31.1 mm).

Figura 21. *Pomacea (Pomacea) cousini* (Jousseau, 1887). Ecuador. Lectotipo MNHN-IM-2000-4483 (H 43 mm). Figura 22. *Pomacea (Pomacea) cumingii* (King & Broderip, 1831). Panamá: Saboga. Posible sintipo NHMUK 20190597 (H 31,1 mm).

□ *Pomacea (Pomacea) cumingii* (King & Broderip, 1831) (Fig. 22)

Ampullaria cumingii King & Broderip, 1831, *Zool. J.*, 5: 344. "in Sinu Panamae". Possible syntypes NHMUK 20190597 (2).

Ampullaria quitensis Busch, 1859, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 27: 168. "Ecuador". Type material not located.

Remarks. COWIE & THIENGO (2003: 74) based the synonymy of *A. quitensis* on SOWERBY III (1909: 348).

Pomacea (Pomacea) martinezi (Hidalgo, 1866) (Figs. 23, 30)

Ampullaria martinezi Hidalgo, 1866, *J. de Conchyl.*, 14: 345, pl. 14 fig. 5. "Santa Rosa, Republicae Aequatoris". Lectotype (FISCHER-PIETTE, 1950: 68) MNHN-IM-2000-4608; paralectotypes MNCN 15.05/7524 (1), MNCN 15.05/12306 (7); MNHN-IM-2000-4609 (1), RBINS MT.1152 (1).

Figure 23. *Pomacea (Pomacea) martinezi* (Hidalgo, 1866). El Oro: Santa Rosa. Lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-4608 (H 59 mm). Figure 24. *Pomacea (Pomacea) modesta* (Busch, 1859). Ecuador. Possible syntype NHMUK 20190596 (H 26.4 mm).

Figura 23. *Pomacea (Pomacea) martinezi* (Hidalgo, 1866). El Oro: Santa Rosa. Lectotipo MNHN-IM-2000-4608 (H 59 mm). Figura 24. *Pomacea (Pomacea) modesta* (Busch, 1859). Ecuador. Posible sintipo NHMUK 20190596 (H 26,4 mm).

Distribution. El Oro: Santa Rosa (TL); MILLER, 1879: 151; SOWERBY III, 1909: 354).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. Further distributed in Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 100).

Pomacea (Pomacea) modesta (Busch, 1859) (Fig. 24)

Ampullaria modesta Busch, 1859, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 27: 168. "Ecuador". Possible syntypes NHMUK 20190596 (3).

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality.

Figure 25. *Pomacea (Pomacea) pealiana* (I. Lea, 1838). Colombia: Turbaco. Lectotype ANSP 192933 (H 34 mm). Figure 26. *Pomacea (Pomacea) puntaplaya* (Cousin, 1887). Los Ríos: Punta-
playa. Paralectotype RBINS MT.3849 (H 27.7 mm).

Figura 25. *Pomacea (Pomacea) pealiana* (I. Lea, 1838). Colombia: Turbaco. Lectotipo ANSP 192933 (H 34 mm). Figura 26. *Pomacea (Pomacea) puntaplaya* (Cousin, 1887). Los Ríos: Punta-
playa. Paralectotipo RBINS MT.3849 (H 27,7 mm).

Pomacea (Pomacea) pealiana (I. Lea, 1838) (Fig. 25)

Ampullaria pealiana Lea, 1838, *Trans. Amer. Philos. Soc.*, (n.s.) 6: 16, pl. 23 fig. 77. "Turbaco, Colombia". Lectotype (ABBOTT, 1955: 126) ANSP 192933; paralectotypes MCZ 161600.

Distribution. Ecuador: without accurate locality (PAIN, 1956: 78).

Remarks. Further distributed in Colombia, Panama, and Venezuela (COWIE & THIENGO, 2003; LINARES & VERA, 2012).

Pomacea (Pomacea) puntaplaya (Cousin, 1887) (Fig. 26)

Ampullaria puntaplaya Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 278, pl. 4 fig. 2. "Puntaplaya". Lectotype (COWIE & HÉROS, 2012: 816) MNHN-IM-2000-4622. Paralectotypes MNHN-IM-2000-4621 (3), RBINS MT.3849 (8).

27

28

Figure 27. *Pomacea (Pomacea) reyrei* (Cousin, 1887). Napo. Syntype RBINS MT.1153 (H 37.7 mm). Figure 28. *Pomacea (Pomacea) tenuissima* (Jousseume, 1894). Ecuador. Syntype RBINS MT.3850 (H 60.7 mm).

Figura 27. *Pomacea (Pomacea) reyrei* (Cousin, 1887). Napo. Sintipo RBINS MT.1153 (H 37,7 mm). Figura 28. *Pomacea (Pomacea) tenuissima* (Jousseume, 1894). Ecuador. Sintipo RBINS MT.3850 (H 60,7 mm).

Distribution. Los Ríos: “Puntaplaya” (TL).

Remarks. This locality is in the low plains SE of Babahoya.

Figure 29. *Pomacea (Pomacea) urceus* (O.F. Müller, 1774). Sucumbios: Laguna de Limoncocha, UMMZ 244901 (H 81 mm).

Figura 29. *Pomacea (Pomacea) urceus* (O.F. Müller, 1774). Sucumbios: Laguna de Limoncocha, UMMZ 244901 (H 81 mm).

Pomacea (Pomacea) reyrei (Cousin, 1887) (Fig. 27)

Ampullaria reyrei Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 279, pl. 4 fig. 7. "Napo". Syntype RBINS MT.1153 (1). Probable syntype MNHN-IM-2000-23087 (1).

Distribution. Napo: without specified locality (TL).

Remarks. As we do not know where Cousin collected his material, it is also possible that it originated in a more eastern province given the larger extent of Napo during Cousin's time.

Pomacea (Pomacea) tenuissima (Jousseau, 1894) (Fig. 28)

Ampullaria tenuissima Jousseau, 1894, *Le Naturaliste*, (2) 8: 120, fig. "Équateur". Syntypes RBINS MT.3850 (5).

Distribution. Ecuador: Only known from an unspecified locality.

Pomacea (Pomacea) urceus (O.F. Müller, 1774) (Figs. 29, 30)

Nerita urceus Müller, 1774, *Vermium terr. fluv.*, 2: 174. "in insulis Indiae". Type material not located.

Distribution. Sucumbios: Laguna de Limoncocha (UMMZ 244901-244903).

Ecoregion. Amazon Lowlands [316].

Remarks. PAIN (1960: 426) reported it from Ecuador without specific locality or voucher details. Further reported from Brazil, Colombia, French Guiana, Guyane, Trinidad, Venezuela (COWIE & THIENGO, 2003; SIMONE, 2006).

Figure 30. Distribution of *Clypeolum latissimum* (Broderip, 1833) and of Ampullariidae species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 30. Distribución de Clypeolum latissimum (Broderip, 1833) y de especies de Ampullariidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Comments on the family. In the literature the following species have been related to this family as occurring in Ecuador, which are likely misidentifications:

- HIGGINS (1872: 687) mentioned “*Paludomus cerasium* Hanley”, which probably refers to *Ampullaria cerasum* Hanley, 1854 and which was mentioned by REEVE (1856: pl. 21 fig. 99) as being from Mexico.
- *Pomacea chemnitzii* (Philippi, 1852): this species from northern Colombia, Panama and Venezuela was recorded from Ecuador by LINARES & VERA (2012: 97) without explicit vouchers.
- *Pomacea columbiensis* (Philippi, 1851), another Colombian species, was mentioned by MILLER (1879: 150); his record is also without explicit vouchers. The type material is ZMB 1343a (KÖHLER & GLAUBRECHT, 2006: 202, fig. 1G), from western Colombia.

Family NEOCYCLOTIDAE Kobelt & Möllendorff, 1897

Remarks. This large operculate family from the Neotropics has been reviewed by DE LA TORRE ET AL. (1942). See SOLEM (1960) for comments. Anatomical and molecular data are scarce and a revision of Neotropical taxa using this kind of data is already overdue. As a consequence, the classification below can only be considered as tentative.

Genus *Daronia* A. Adams, 1861

Daronia A. Adams, 1861, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, (3) 8: 244. Type species by monotypy *Cyclostrema spirula* A. Adams, 1850.

Remarks. The name *Daronia* has for a long time been used to include small, planispirally coiled, marine species. *Daronia* was established as a subgenus of *Cyclostrema* with

Cyclostrema spirula A. Adams, 1850, as type species by monotypy. The holotype was said to have been found “on the sands in one of the Philippine Islands” (label) and “in the Philippine Islands” (description). Examination (WARÉN & BOUCHET, 1988) of the holotype of *Cyclostrema* (*Daronia*) *spirula* revealed that it is a land snail belonging to the family Poteriidae (a synonym of Neocyclotidae). Furthermore, it is so similar to *Buckleyia martinezi* (Hidalgo, 1866), the type species of *Buckleyia* Higgins, 1872, that the latter is considered a junior synonym of *Daronia* (MOLLUSCABASE, 2021).

Daronia bicincta (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942) (Fig. 31)

Buckleyia bicincta Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 152, pl. 19 figs 13-15. “Ecuador”. Holotype USNM 316063.

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality (TL).

Daronia martinezi (Hidalgo, 1866) (Figs. 32, 41)

Cyclophorus martinezi Hidalgo, 1866a, *J. de Conchyl.*, 14: 273, pl. 8 fig. 5. “Baeza Reipublicae Aequatoris”. Holotype MNCN 15.05/3232.

Aperostoma (*Buckleyia*) *montezumi* Higgins, 1872, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 40: 686, pl. 56 figs 7-7a (‘Hidalgo’).

Aperostoma montezumai - Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 272 [incorrect subsequent spelling].

Distribution. Napo: Baeza (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. Higgins’ use of the name *montezumi* seems to be a slip of his pen as he ascribed the name to Hidalgo. LINARES & VERA (2012: 108) listed this species also from Colombia, Dept. Antioquia, Jericó, without citing an explicit reference or voucher. This record needs further confirmation.

Genus *Calaperostoma* Pilsbry, 1935

Calaperostoma Pilsbry, 1935, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 87: 4. Type species by original designation *Cyclostoma cumingi* G.B. Sowerby I, 1832.

Calaperostoma bourcierii (L. Pfeiffer, 1854) (Figs. 33, 41)

Cyclostoma (*Cyclophorus*) *bourcierii* Pfeiffer, 1854, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 20: 151. “prope Mindo, republicae Aequatoris”. Syntypes NHMUK 20190595 (2).

Distribution. Pichincha: Mindo (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Calaperostoma cousini (Jousseau, 1884) (Figs. 34A, 41)

Cyclophorus cousini Jousseau, 1884, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 9: 173, pl. 4 fig. 13. “environs de Pailon, province de la Esmeralda, Équateur”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Esmeraldas: El Pailón (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Figure 31. *Daronia bicincta* (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942). Ecuador. Holotype USNM 316063. (D 16.5 mm). Figure 32. *Daronia martinezi* (Hidalgo, 1866). Napo: Baeza. Holotype MNCN 15.05/3232 (D 22 mm). Figure 33. *Calaperostoma bourcierii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854). Pichincha: Mindo. Syntype NHMUK 20190595 (D 25.2 mm).

Figura 31. *Daronia bicincta* (Bartsch y J.P.E. Morrison, 1942). Ecuador. *Holotipo* USNM 316063. (D 16,5 mm). *Figura 32.* *Daronia martinezi* (Hidalgo, 1866). Napo: Baeza. *Holotipo* MNCN 15.05/3232 (D 22 mm). *Figura 33.* *Calaperostoma bourcierii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854). Pichincha: Mindo. *Sintipo* NHMUK 20190595 (D 25,2 mm).

Figure 34. A: *Calaperostoma cousini* (Jousseaume, 1884). Esmeraldas: El Pailón. Original figure in JOUSSEAUME (1884): pl. 4 fig. 13 (D 43 mm). B: *Calaperostoma esmeraldense* (K. Miller, 1879). Esmeraldas: at Rio Cachabi. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 15 fig. 3 (D 48 mm).

Figura 34. A: *Calaperostoma cousini* (Jousseaume, 1884). Esmeraldas: El Pailón. Figura original en JOUSSEAUME (1884): lám. 4 fig. 13 (D 43 mm). B: *Calaperostoma esmeraldense* (K. Miller, 1879). Esmeraldas: en Rio Cachabi. Figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 15 fig. 3 (D 48 mm).

Remarks. This taxon was mentioned in BARTSCH & MORRISON (1942), without having seen material. The only available figure is reproduced here and the species is regarded a *nomen dubium*.

Calaperostoma cf. cumingii (G.B. Sowerby I, 1832) (Figs. 35, 41)

Cyclostoma cumingii Sowerby I in Broderip & Sowerby I, 1832, *Proc. Comm. Corr. Zool. Soc. London*, 1832: 32. "America Meridionali (Island of Tumaco)". Probable syntypes NHMUK 20190593 (5).

Distribution. Pichincha: Mindo (■UF 164624); Ecuador: "Quito, Ecuador" (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. The locality 'Quito' is likely inaccurate and is a proxy for an unknown locality in Ecuador. This species was originally described from a coastal area in Colombia (BRODERIP & SOWERBY I, 1832; BARTSCH & MORRISON, 1942). The Ecuadorian material is slightly different from the type material and needs further study.

Calaperostoma esmeraldense (K. Miller, 1879) (Figs. 34B, 41)

Cyclophorus esmeraldensis Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 142, pl. 15 fig. 3. "in provincia Esmeraldas". Type material not located.

Distribution. Esmeraldas: at Rio Cachabi (TL); Mataje (CORREOSO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145], Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Calaperostoma guayaquilense (G.B. Sowerby II, 1850) (Figs. 36, 41)

Cyclostoma guayaquilense Sowerby II, 1850, *Thesaur. conch.*: 163*, pl. 31B fig. 219. "Guayaquil". Probable syntypes NHMUK 20190594 (3).

Figure 35. *Calaperostoma cumingii* (G.B. Sowerby I, 1832). Colombia: Tumaco. Probable syntype NHMUK 20190593 (D 33.5 mm). Figure 36. *Calaperostoma guayaquilense* (G.B. Sowerby II, 1850). Guayas: Guayaquil. Probable syntype NHMUK 20190594 (D 14.1 mm).

Figura 35. *Calaperostoma cumingii* (G.B. Sowerby I, 1832). Colombia: Tumaco. Sintipo probable NHMUK 20190593 (D 33,5 mm). Figura 36. *Calaperostoma guayaquilense* (G.B. Sowerby II, 1850). Guayas: Guayaquil. Sintipo probable NHMUK 20190594 (D 14,1 mm).

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (TL).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Remarks. Not known from any additional material since the original description.

Calaperostoma hidalgoi (Crosse, 1866) (Fig. 37)

Cyclophorus hidalgoi Crosse, 1866, *J. de Conchyl.*, 14: 354, pl. 14, fig. 4. "Republica Aequatoris".
Type material not located.

Figure 37. *Calaperostoma hidalgoi* (Crosse, 1866). Ecuador. Original figure in CROSSE (1866): pl. 14 fig. 4 (D 27 mm). Figure 38. *Calaperostoma nigrofasciatum* (K. Miller, 1879). Pichincha: Rio Pilaton valley. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 7 fig. 5 (D 36 mm).

Figura 37. *Calaperostoma hidalgoi* (Crosse, 1866). Ecuador. *Figura original en CROSSE (1866): lám. 14 fig. 4 (D 27 mm).* *Figura 38.* *Calaperostoma nigrofasciatum* (K. Miller, 1879). Pichincha: Valle del Rio Pilaton. *Figura original en MILLER (1879): pl. 7 fig. 5 (D 36 mm).*

Remarks. This species has not been recognised in later collected material and its precise locality remains unknown. It is considered for the time-being as a *nomen dubium*.

Calaperostoma nigrofasciatum (K. Miller, 1879) (Figs. 38, 41)

Cyclophorus nigrofasciatus Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 142, pl. 7 figs 5a-5c. "Val de Pilaton, 500-1500 m". Type material not located.

Distribution. El Oro: 9 km W of Piñas (■UF 36129); Los Ríos: between Quevedo and Quito, 500 m (BARTSCH & MORRISON, 1942: 165); Pastaza: Mera (SALVADOR ET AL., 2021); Pichincha: Rio Pilaton valley (TL); Pachajal (GERMAIN, 1907) [Pachijal]; Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Santo Domingo de los Colorados (■FMNH 70906, UF 243806).

Figure 39. *Calaperostoma purum* (Forbes, 1850). Unknown locality. Original figure in FORBES (1850): pl. 9 fig. 9 (D 48 mm). Figure 40. *Calaperostoma rosenbergi* (S.I. da Costa, 1898). Esmeraldas: Río Cachavi area. Syntype NHMUK 1907.11.21.122 (D 32 mm).

Figura 39. *Calaperostoma purum* (Forbes, 1850). Localidad desconocida. *Figura original en FORBES (1850): lám. 9 fig. 9 (D 48 mm).* *Figura 40.* *Calaperostoma rosenbergi* (S.I. da Costa, 1898). Esmeraldas: zona Río Cachavi. *Sintipo NHMUK 1907.11.21.122 (D 32 mm).*

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145], Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. This species has also been reported from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 109).

□ *Calaperostoma purum* (Forbes, 1850) (Fig. 39)

Cyclostoma purum Forbes, 1850, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 18: 56, pl. 9 fig. 9. No type locality given. Type material not located.

Remarks. BARTSCH & MORRISON (1942: 162) stated “In his [Forbes] introduction he says that the specimens he described were obtained during the surveying voyage of the ‘Herald’ and ‘Pandora’, which covered various points between the coast of Ecuador and Vancouver Island, Galapagos, and Pitcairn Islands, and the Sandwich Islands. The character of the shell would mark it as a South American species”.

Figure 41. Distribution of *Daronia* and *Calaperostoma* species (Neocyclotidae). See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 41. Distribución de las especies de *Daronia* y *Calaperostoma* (Neocyclotidae). Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Calaperostoma rosenbergi (S.I. da Costa, 1898) (Figs. 40, 41)

Cyclophorus rosenbergi da Costa, 1898, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 3: 82, pl. 6 fig. 9. "Cachabi". Syntypes NHMUK 1907.11.21.122-124.

Distribution. Esmeraldas: Rio Cachavi area (TL).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Genus *Incidostoma* Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942

Aperostoma (*Incidostoma*) Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 187. Type species by original designation *Aperostoma* (*Incidostoma*) *malleatum* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942.

Incidostoma chocolatum J.P.E. Morrison, 1955 (Figs. 42, 63)

Incidostoma chocolatum Morrison, 1955, *J. Wash. Acad. Sci.*, 45: 158, figs 10-12. "Papallagta". Holotype USNM 543527.

Distribution. Napo: Papallacta (TL); Tungurahua: Baños (USNM 618858).

Ecoregion. Northern Andean páramo [NT1006].

Incidostoma diminutum J.P.E. Morrison, 1955 (Figs. 43, 63)

Incidostoma diminutum Morrison, 1955, *J. Wash. Acad. Sci.*, 45: 159, figs 7-9. "Papallagta, Ecuador". Holotype USNM 543530.

Distribution. Napo: Papallacta (TL); Tungurahua: Baños (USNM 618857).

Ecoregion. Northern Andean páramo [NT1006].

Figure 42. *Incidostoma chocolatum* J.P.E. Morrison, 1955. Napo: Papallacta. Holotype USNM 543527 (D 23 mm). Figure 43. *Incidostoma diminutum* J.P.E. Morrison, 1955. Napo: Papallacta. Original figure in MORRISON (1955): figs 7-9 (D 19,8 mm). Figure 44. *Incidostoma dunkeri* (L. Pfeiffer, 1857). Chimborazo: Riobamba. Figure by REEVE (1864): pl. 2 fig. 9a, 9b (D 32,5 mm according to Pfeiffer).
 Figura 42. *Incidostoma chocolatum* J.P.E. Morrison, 1955. Napo: Papallacta. Holotipo USNM 543527 (D 23 mm). Figura 43. *Incidostoma diminutum* J.P.E. Morrison, 1955. Napo: Papallacta. Figura original de MORRISON (1955): figs. 7-9 (D 19,8 mm). Figura 44. *Incidostoma dunkeri* (L. Pfeiffer, 1857). Chimborazo: Riobamba. Figura de REEVE (1864): lám. 2 fig. 9a, 9b (D 32,5 mm según Pfeiffer).

Incidostoma dunkeri (L. Pfeiffer, 1857) (Figs. 44, 63)

Cyclotus dunkeri Pfeiffer, 1857, *Malak. Bl.*, 3: 256. "Nova Granada". Type material not located.

Distribution. Chimborazo: Riobamba (REEVE, 1864 [1863-1864]: pl. 2 fig. 9).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Figure 45. *Incidostoma ecuadorensis* Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942. Ecuador. Holotype USNM 307407 (D 33 m).

Figura 45. *Incidostoma ecuadorensis* Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942. Ecuador. Holotipo USNM 307407 (D 33 m).

Remarks. So far the record by Reeve is the only one for Ecuador. His shell (from “Mus. Cuming”) is figured here being not Pfeiffer’s original one which was from “Coll. Tams” and is considered lost. The dimension quoted has been taken from Pfeiffer’s paper. This species is more widely distributed in Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 113).

Incidostoma ecuadorensis (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942) (Fig. 45)

Aperostomus (*Aperostomus*) *ecuadorensis* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 248, pl. 36 figs 4-6. “Quito, Ecuador”. Holotype USNM 307407.

Distribution. Pichincha: Quito (TL).

Remarks. The description was based on historical material. The type locality has to be considered a proxy for an unspecified locality and its true distribution is as yet unknown.

Incidostoma giganteum (Reeve, 1842) (Figs. 46-48, 63)

Cyclotus giganteus Reeve, 1842, *Conch. syst.*, 2: 99, pl. 184 fig. 17 (ex J.E. Gray ex G.B. Sowerby I ms.). No type locality. Syntype NHMUK 1962719 (1); possible syntype NHMUK 1962718 (1).

Cyclotus fischeri Hidalgo, 1867, *J. de Conchyl.*, 15: 305, pl. 8 fig. 3. No type locality given. Syntypes MNCN 15.05/17560 (1), 15.05/3261 (3), MNHN-IM-2000-36380 (1).

Distribution. Pastaza: Mera (■ UF 129969); Sucumbios: Aguarico (MNCN 15.05/3262); Aguarico (obs. iNaturalist 47634861, 2018); additionally from unspecified localities (“Quito”) (MNCN 15.05/3305, 15.05/76215, 15.05/20009).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Figures 46-48. *Incidostoma giganteum* (Reeve, 1842). 46: unknown locality, syntype NHMUK 1962719 (D 51.6 mm); 47: unknown locality, syntype of *Cyclotus fischeri* Hidalgo, 1867, MNCN 15.05/17560 (D 55.5 mm); 48: Sucumbíos, Aguarico (iNaturalist 47634861).

Figuras 46-48. Incidostoma giganteum (Reeve, 1842). 46: *localidad desconocida, sintipo NHMUK 1962719 (D 51,6 mm)*; 47: *localidad desconocida, sintipo de Cyclotus fischeri Hidalgo, 1867, MNCN 15.05/17560 (D 55,5 mm)*; 48: *Sucumbios, Aguarico (iNaturalist 47634861)*.

Remarks. The classification follows BREURE & ARAUJO (2017), but we have indications that these two taxa need further study (Roosen, unpublished data). Also reported from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012) and Panama (BARTSCH & MORRISON, 1942).

Incidostoma hitomi Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942 (Fig. 49)

Incidostoma hitomi Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 194, pl. 27 figs 26-28. "Quito, Ecuador". Holotype USNM 316105 [sic, 516295].

Distribution. Pichincha: Quito (TL).

Remarks. The description was based on historical material and its true distribution is as yet unknown.

Incidostoma jacksoni J.P.E. Morrison, 1955 (Fig 55, 63)

Incidostoma jacksoni Morrison, 1955, *J. Wash. Acad. Sci.*, 45: 158, figs 13-15. "Mera, Oriente Province, Ecuador". Holotype USNM 543524.

Distribution. Pastaza: Mera (TL); Tungurahua: Agoyán (USNM 543526).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. There is also a record from "Yungilla, Rio Pastaria" [= Rio Pastaza?] (ANSP 187911), an Ecuadorian locality which we have been unable to locate.

Incidostoma manabense (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942) (Figs. 51, 63)

Aperostoma (Aperostoma) manabense Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 239, pl. 34 figs 10-12. "Between Quevedo and Calcata, Ecuador". Holotype USNM 524066.

Distribution. Los Ríos: near Quevedo (TL).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Remarks. The locality "Calcata" could not be found in Prov. Los Ríos with modern gazetteers.

Incidostoma masvense (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942) (Figs. 52, 63)

Aperostoma (Aperostoma) masvense Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 254, pl. 37 figs 1-3. "Cerro Masve, Guayas province, Ecuador". Holotype USNM 524048.

Distribution. Guayas: "Cerro Masve" (TL).

Ecoregion. Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214].

Remarks. The locality "Cerro Masve" could not be found with modern gazetteers. Likely this refers to Cerros de Másvale in Prov. Guayas. This locality is at an altitude of ca. 572 m; given this height this locality probably belongs to the ecoregion mentioned above.

Incidostoma pailaense (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942) (Fig. 53)

Aperostoma (Aperostoma) pailaense Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 231, pl. 32 figs 7-9. "Rio Paila". Holotype USNM 251171.

Figure 49. *Incidostoma hitomi* Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942. Unknown locality. Holotype USNM 516295 (D 39.2 mm). Figure 50. *Incidostoma jacksoni* J.P.E. Morrison, 1955. Pastaza: Mera. Holotype USNM 543524 (D 23 mm). Figure 51. *Incidostoma manabense* (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942). Los Ríos: near Quevedo. Holotype USNM 524066 (D 43 mm).

Figura 49. *Incidostoma hitomi* Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942. Localidad desconocida. Holotipo USNM 516295 (D 39,2 mm). Figura 50. *Incidostoma jacksoni* J.P.E. Morrison, 1955. Pastaza: Mera. Holotipo USNM 543524 (D 23 mm). Figura 51. *Incidostoma manabense* (Bartsch y J.P.E. Morrison, 1942). Los Ríos: cerca de Quevedo. Holotipo USNM 524066 (D 43 mm).

Figure 52. *Incidostoma masvense* (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942). Guayas: “Cerro Masve”. Holotype 524048 (D 30.2 mm). Figure 53. *Incidostoma pailaense* (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942). ?Chimborazo: “Rio Paila”. Holotype USNM 251171 (D 27.8 mm).
Figura 52. *Incidostoma masvense* (Bartsch y J.P.E. Morrison, 1942). Guayas: “Cerro Masve”. Holotipo 524048 (D 30,2 mm). *Figura 53.* *Incidostoma pailaense* (Bartsch y J.P.E. Morrison, 1942). ?Chimborazo: “Rio Paila”. Holotipo USNM 251171 (D 27,8 mm).

Distribution. ?Chimborazo: “Rio Paila” (TL).

Remarks. In modern gazetteers no Rio Paila is to be found, but there are different names with Paila as one of the elements, most of which are to be found in Prov. Chimborazo, others in Prov. Azuay and Pichincha. It thus remains unclear where the type locality is, but in all likelihood it is in the Central Andes.

Incidostoma pazi (Crosse, 1866) (Figs. 54, 63)

Cyclotus pazi Crosse, 1866, *J. de Conchyl.*, 14: 356, pl. 14, fig. 3. “Ambato, Reipublicae Aequatoris”.
Syntypes MNCN 15.05/21591 (25).

Figure 54. *Incidostoma pazi* (Crosse, 1866). Tungurahua: Ambato. Syntype MNCN 15.05/21591 (D 22 mm). Figure 55. *Incidostoma perezii* (Hidalgo, 1866). Napo: Baeza. Syntype MNCN 15.05/3263 (D 25 mm). Figure 56. *Incidostoma pichinchense* Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942. Ecuador: unknown locality. Holotype USNM 316109 (D 47.6 mm).

Figura 54. *Incidostoma pazi* (Crosse, 1866). Tungurahua: Ambato. Sintipo MNCN 15.05/21591 (D 22 mm). Figura 55. *Incidostoma perezii* (Hidalgo, 1866). Napo: Baeza. Sintipo MNCN 15.05/3263 (D 25 mm). Figura 56. *Incidostoma pichinchense* Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942. Ecuador: localidad desconocida. Holotipo USNM 316109 (D 47,6 mm).

Figure 57. *Incidostoma popayanum* (I. Lea, 1838). Colombia: near Popayan. Syntype USNM 104453 (D 22.6 mm).

Figura 57. *Incidostoma popayanum* (I. Lea, 1838). Colombia: cerca de Popayán. Sintipo USNM 104453 (D 22,6 mm).

Distribution. Tungurahua: Ambato (TL); Baños (MARTENS, 1885); Chimborazo: Mt. Chimborazo (BARTSCH & MORRISON, 1942).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], ? Northern Andean páramo [NT1006].

Remarks. The record by Bartsch & Morrison is based on a historical collection of which the elevation is unknown at which the material was taken.

Incidostoma perezii (Hidalgo, 1866) (Figs. 55, 64)

Cyclotus perezii Hidalgo, 1866, *J. de Conchyl.*, 14: 344, pl. 14, fig. 2. "Baeza, Reipublicae Aequatoris". Syntypes MNCN 15.05/3263 (15).

Distribution. Napo: Baeza (TL; CORREOSO, 2008); Pastaza: Mera (■ UF 485864); Tungurahua: Agoyán (■ UF 129973).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Incidostoma pichinchense Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942 (Figs. 56, 63)

Incidostoma pichinchense Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 191, pl. 25 figs 10-12. "Quito, Ecuador". Holotype USNM 316109.

Distribution. Pastaza: Mera (SALVADOR ET AL., 2021).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

■ *Incidostoma popayanum* (I. Lea, 1838) (Figs. 57, 63)

Cyclostoma popayana Lea, 1838, *Trans. Amer. Philos. Soc.*, (n.s.) 6: 94, pl. 23 fig. 76. "New Granada, near Popayan". Syntype USNM 104453.

Figures 58, 59. *Incidostoma quitense* (L. Pfeiffer, 1852). Ecuador: unknown locality. 58: syntype NHMUK 20160366 (D 35 mm); 59: holotype of *Aperostoma olivaceum* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, USNM 524084 (D 34.2 mm).

Figuras 58, 59. Incidostoma quitense (L. Pfeiffer, 1852). Ecuador: *localidad desconocida*. 58: *sintipo* NHMUK 20160366 (D 35 mm); 59: *holotipo* de *Aperostoma olivaceum* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, USNM 524084 (D 34,2 mm).

Distribution. Chimborazo: Mt. Chimborazo (REEVE, 1863 [1863-1864]: *Cyclotus* pl. 5 fig. 24); Pichincha/Napo: "inter Quito et Napo (Orton)" (MILLER, 1879: 141).

Ecoregion. ? Northern Andean páramo [NT1006].

Remarks. This is a Colombian species, which has also been reported from Venezuela (MARTENS, 1873). We have been unable to verify both Reeve's and Miller's material, for which the altitude at which the specimens were sampled is unknown.

Incidostoma quitense (L. Pfeiffer, 1852) (Figs. 58, 59, 64)

Cyclostoma (*Cyclotus*) *quitense* Pfeiffer, 1852, *Monogr. Pneumop. viv.*, 1: 17. "Quito". Syntypes NHMUK 20160366 (3).

Aperostoma (*Aperostoma*) *olivaceum* Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 251, pl. 36 figs 10-12. "Ecuador". Holotype USNM 524084. [New synonym].

Distribution. Pastaza: Mera (SALVADOR ET AL., 2021); Pichincha: Pachajal (GERMAIN, 1907); Rio El Cinto, 1300-1400 m (MARTENS, 1885a).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. The type specimen of *Aperostoma* (*Aperostoma*) *olivaceum* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942 is nearly identical with Pfeiffer's taxon, which is the reason why we consider them as synonyms. Also reported from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 118).

Incidostoma salengoense (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942) (Figs. 60, 63)

Aperostoma (*Aperostoma*) *salengoense* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 253, pl. 37 figs 18-20. "Salengo Island, Ecuador". Holotype USNM 104432 [*sic*, 104452].

Distribution. Manabí: Salango Island (TL).

Ecoregion. Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214].

Incidostoma stirlingi Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942 (Figs. 61, 63)

Incidostoma stirlingi Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 195, pl. 27 figs 20-22. "Mendez, Upper Paute River, Ecuador". Holotype USNM 516296.

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Méndez (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Incidostoma subcingulatum (Kobelt, 1912) (Fig. 62)

Neocyclotus (*giganteus* var.?) *subcingulatum* Kobelt, 1912 [1911-1914], *Syst. Conchyl.-Cab.*, (1) 19 (4): 892, pl. 133 figs 4-6. "Ecuador". Type material not located.

Distribution. Ecuador: only known from unspecified localities (RBINS INV.62358; ■USNM 98109, 126907, 366106).

Genus *Lagocyclus* Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942

Lagocyclus Bartsch & Morrison, 1942, *Bull. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 181: 154. Type species by original designation *Cyclophorus crosseanus* Hidalgo, 1866.

Lagocyclus antonii (Cousin, 1887) (Fig. 65)

Cyclophorus antonii Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 85, pl. 4 fig. 4. No type locality given. Syntypes RBINS MT.3816 (2).

Figure 60. *Incidostoma salengoense* (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942). Manabí: Salango Island. Holotype USNM 104452 (D 37.4 mm). Figure 61. *Incidostoma stirlingi* Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942. Morona-Santiago: Méndez. Holotype USNM 516296 (D 25 mm). Figure 62. *Incidostoma subcingulatum* Kobelt, 1912. Ecuador. Original figure Kobelt 1912: pl. 133 figs 4-6 (D 38 mm).
 Figura 60. *Incidostoma salengoense* (Bartsch y J.P.E. Morrison, 1942). Manabí: Isla Salango. Holotipo USNM 104452 (D 37.4 mm). Figura 61. *Incidostoma stirlingi* Bartsch y J.P.E. Morrison, 1942. Morona-Santiago: Méndez. Holotipo USNM 516296 (D 25 mm). Figura 62. *Incidostoma subcingulatum* Kobelt, 1912. Ecuador. Figura original Kobelt 1912: lám. 133 figs. 4-6 (D 38 mm).

63

64

Figure 63 Distribution of *Incidostoma* species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions. Figure 64. Distribution of *Incidostoma* and *Lagocyclus* species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 63. Distribución de especies de *Incidostoma*. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones. Figura 64. Distribución de especies de *Incidostoma* y *Lagocyclus*. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Distribution. Ecuador: no specific locality known.

Lagocyclus crosseanus (Hidalgo, 1866) (Figs. 64, 66)

Cyclophorus crosseanus Hidalgo, 1866, *J. de Conchyl.*, 15: 343, pl. 14 fig. 1. "Republica Aequatoria".
Syntypes MNCN 15.05/3217 (1), MNHN-IM-2000-35823 (2).

Figure 65. *Lagocyclus antonii* (Cousin, 1887). Ecuador: unknown locality. Syntype RBINS MT.3816 (D 21.7 mm). Figure 66. *Lagocyclusrosseanus* (Hidalgo, 1866). A, B: Ecuador, unknown locality, syntype MNCN 15.05/3217 (D 26.4 mm); C-E: Ecuador, Cushiimi, FMNH 173026 (D 21.7 mm).
 Figura 65. *Lagocyclus antonii* (Cousin, 1887). Ecuador: localidad desconocida. Sintipo RBINS MT.3816 (D 21,7 mm). Figura 66. *Lagocyclusrosseanus* (Hidalgo, 1866). A, B: Ecuador, localidad desconocida, sintipo MNCN 15.05/3217 (D 26,4 mm); C-E: Ecuador, Cushiimi, FMNH 173026 (D 21,7 mm).

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Cushiimi (FMNH 173026); Pastaza: Tiguino (■ UF 193580) [Tihuano].

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. This is the first material with precise records for this species. However, due to the bad state of preservation of all type material, it is difficult to compare other specimens in all relevant characteristics. The FMNH specimen is somewhat smaller, with a few more spiral cords on the penultimate whorl, but “the specimen’s peristome is very thin and brittle, so it might not be fully grown” (J. Gerber, pers. commun. September 2020). We tentatively regard it as this species, awaiting further material for research. Also the specimen which BARTSCH & MORRISON (1942) had at hand is smaller than Hidalgo’s type, but we were unable to consult this material and refrain from making definite conclusions.

Lagocyclus haematomma (L. Pfeiffer, 1863) (Fig. 67)

Cyclophorus haematomma Pfeiffer, 1863, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 31: 276. "Ecuador". Syntypes NHMUK 20160365 (3).

Distribution. Ecuador: not known from an accurate locality.

Lagocyclus vasconesi (Jousseume, 1897) (Figs. 64, 68)

Cyclophorus vasconesi Jousseume, 1897, *Le Naturaliste*, (2) 11: 250, fig. "La Coca". Possible syntypes RBINS MT.3829 (1), MT.3838 (1).

Distribution. Orellana: Puerto Francisco de Orellana (TL).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Genus *Neocyclotus* Crosse & P. Fischer, 1888

Neocyclotus Crosse & P. Fischer in P. Fischer & Crosse, 1888 [1880-1902], *Mission au Mexique*, 7 (2): 148. Type species by subsequent designation *Cyclostoma dysoni* L. Pfeiffer, 1851.

Remarks. BARTSCH (1942: 132) introduced *Austrocyclotus* (type species: *Cyclostoma stramineum* Reeve, 1843, by original designation) as a subgenus of *Aperostoma* Troschel, 1847 for a group of species "marked by closely placed threads crossing each other in protractive and retractive series, producing an engine-turned pattern". This subgenus is considered a junior synonym of *Neocyclotus* (MOLLUSCABASE, 2021).

Neocyclotus granulatus (L. Pfeiffer, 1863) (Fig. 69)

Cyclotis granulatus Pfeiffer, 1863, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 30: 275. "Ecuador". Syntypes NHMUK 20160364 (3).

Distribution. Ecuador: only known without accurate locality (MNCN 15.05/1506).

Remarks. The type material could not be located during our study, and there is no image of a type specimen available.

Comments on the family. In the literature the following species related to this family have been associated with Ecuador:

- *Cyclophorus delphinulus* Mousson, 1869 (*Malak. Bl.*, 16: 180) was described without type locality but collected by Wallis in "nördlichen Südamerika" [northern South America, from publication title]. For this species, of which BARTSCH & MORRISON (1942: 158) only gave a translation of the original description without seeing any material, a monotypic genus *Filocyclus* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942 was erected. According to LINARES & VERA (2012: 109) there is type material in the Zurich museum, which we have been unable to consult. So far this species has not been recognised in material collected in Ecuador.

Family HEMISINIDAE P. Fischer & Crosse, 1891

Remarks. This Neotropical family of freshwater snails has recently been reviewed by GLAUBRECHT & NEIBER (2019a). Anatomical data have been given in *e.g.*, FISCHER &

Figure 67. *Lagocyclus haematomma* (L. Pfeiffer, 1863). Ecuador: unknown locality. Syntype NHMUK 20160365 (D 20.8 mm). Figure 68. *Lagocyclus vasconesi* (Jousseau, 1897). Orellana: Puerto Francisco de Orellana. Possible syntype RBINS MT.3829 (D 15.5 mm).

Figura 67. *Lagocyclus haematomma* (L. Pfeiffer, 1863). Ecuador: *localidad desconocida*. Sintipo NHMUK 20160365 (D 20,8 mm). *Figura 68.* *Lagocyclus vasconesi* (Jousseau, 1897). Orellana: Puerto Francisco de Orellana. Posible sintipo RBINS MT.3829 (D 15,5 mm).

CROSSE (1891 [1880-1902]), THIELE (1928); phylogenetic data was presented by *e.g.* STRONG *ET AL.* (2011). Unpublished data from M. Neiber (pers. commun. August 2020) suggests that the species mentioned below show closer affinities with the type species of *Hemisinus* from Jamaica than to Argentinian *Aylacostoma*. The delimitation of these two genera needs, however, further study.

Figure 69. *Neocyclotus granulatus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1863). Ecuador: unknown locality. MNCN 15.05/21506 (D 22.2 mm). Figure 70. *Hemisinus flammeus* (F. Baker, 1914). Brazil: Rio Jamauchim. Holotype ANSP 109366 (H 23.5 mm).

Figura 69. *Neocyclotus granulatus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1863). Ecuador: localidad desconocida. MNCN 15.05/21506 (D 22.2 mm). Figura 70. *Hemisinus flammeus* (F. Baker, 1914). Brasil: Rio Jamauchim. Holotipo ANSP 109366 (H 23,5 mm).

Genus *Hemisinus* W. Swainson, 1840

Hemisinus Swainson, 1840, *Treatise malac.*: 341. Type species by monotypy *Strombus lineolatus* W. Wood, 1828.

Remarks. The following species need further research as their delimitation could not be ascertained. Some of these have been classified in *Aylacostoma*, "however, unpublished genetic data place a specimen from Colombia closer to the type species of

Figures 71, 72. *Hemisinus guayaquilensis* (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853). 71A: Guayas, near Guayaquil, original figure in PETIT DE LA SAUSSAYE (1853): pl. 5 fig. 6 (H 14-17 mm); 71B: Guayas, Estero Salado, original figure in MILLER (1879) for *Hemisinus osculati* var. *saladensis*: pl. 7 fig. 6 (H 17 mm); 72: Ecuador, unknown locality, lectotype of *Hemisinus pazi* Tryon, 1866, ANSP 26781 (H 22 mm).

Figuras 71, 72. *Hemisinus guayaquilensis* (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853). 71A: Guayas, cerca de Guayaquil, figura original en PETIT DE LA SAUSSAYE 1853: lám. 5 fig. 6 (H 14-17 mm); 71B: Guayas, Estero Salado, figura original en MILLER (1879) de *Hemisinus osculati* var. *saladensis*: lám. 7 fig. 6 (H 17 mm); 72: Ecuador, localidad desconocida, lectotipo de *Hemisinus pazi* Tryon, 1866, ANSP 26781 (H 22 mm).

Hemisinus from Jamaica than to Argentinian *Aylacostoma*, so that my suggestion would be to place all the taxa mentioned below tentatively in *Hemisinus*." (M. Neiber, pers. commun. August 2020).

■ *Hemisinus flammeus* (F.C. Baker, 1913) (Figs. 76, 81)

Hemisinus flammeus Baker, 1913, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 65: 657, pl. 25 fig. 15. "Rio Jamauchim". Holotype ANSP 109366.

Distribution. Pastaza: Puyo (■ANSP 188811).

Ecoregion. Amazonas High Andes [312].

Remarks. This is a Brazilian species (SIMONE, 2006: fig. 193). The type locality as given above, is mentioned in CLENCH & TURNER, 1962 who attributed this species incorrectly to Pilsbry, was not given in the original publication. However, it was mentioned in the same paper for the subspecies *elongatus* which was collected "at a different date and possibly at a different locality".

Hemisinus guayaquilensis (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853) (Fig 71, 72, 81)

Melania guayaquilensis Petit de la Saussaye, 1853, *J. de Conchyl.*, 4: 157, pl. 5 fig. 6. "près de Guayaquil". Type material not located.

Melania osculati A. Villa & G.B. Villa, 1854, *Giorn. Malac.*, 2 (8): 113. "Quito".

Hemisinus pazi Tryon, 1866, *Amer. J. Conch.*, 2: 300, pl. 20 fig. 6. "Quito". Lectotype (BAKER, 1964: 191) ANSP 26781; paralectotype ANSP 453510 (1), MNCN 15.05/11412 (5). [New synonym].

Hemisinus osculati var. β *saladensis* K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 164, pl. 7 figs 6a-6b. "Estero Salado". Type material not located.

Distribution. El Oro: Balsas (GLAUBRECHT & NEIBER, 2019a); Guayas: near Guayaquil (TL); Pichincha: near Quito (GERMAIN, 1907).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. The synonymy of *H. pazi* with Petit de la Saussaye's taxon is confirmed by a MNCN identification of Tryon's type material, of which a lot also appears to be present in that museum (R. Araujo pers. commun. 26 June 2020). The record from Germain is possibly a misidentification and may refer to the next species (*Hemisinus maculatus*); it has been excluded from the distribution map. Also reported from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 120; as *Aylacostoma guayaquilensis*). In the ANSP database we found a synonymy of Tryon's taxon with *Hemisinus pulcher* Reeve, 1860, a Brazilian species with a limited distribution (SIMONE, 2006), of which the type material is in NHMUK; after comparing the type material of both species we refrain from following this view.

Hemisinus maculatus (I. Lea, 1834) (Fig. 73, 81)

Melanopsis maculata Lea, 1834, *Trans. Amer. Philos. Soc.*, (n.s.) 5: 82, pl. 19 fig. 75. "Peru".

Hemisinia osculatii A. Villa & G.B. Villa, 1855, *Diario Atti Accad. Milano* 10 (2): 8. "Quito".

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality (THOMPSON, 2011: 43); recorded from Quito (■ANSP 122968) and Rio Dante (■ANSP 221409).

Remarks. The record from Quito does not necessarily indicate the true occurrence and the distribution of this species needs further research. The locality "Rio Dante" could not be located, it could be a misspelling for Río Daule [near Guayaquil].

Hemisinus simplex (Tryon, 1866) (Fig. 74)

Hemisinus simplex Tryon, 1866, *Amer. J. Conch.*, 2: 301, pl. 20 fig. 7. "Quito". Lectotype (BAKER, 1964: 191) ANSP 26782; paralectotype ANSP 453513 (1), MNCN 15.05/11416 (4).

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality (TL).

Figure 73. *Hemisinus maculatus* (I. Lea, 1834). Peru. Original figure in LEA (1834): pl. 19 fig. 75 (H 12.7 mm). Figure 74. *Hemisinus simplex* (Tryon, 1866). Ecuador: unknown locality. Lectotype ANSP 26782 (H 17 mm). Figure 75. *Melanoides tuberculata* (O.F. Müller, 1774). Manabí: Río Ayampé (photos: M. Roosen). (H ca 25 mm).

Figura 73. *Hemisinus maculatus* (I. Lea, 1834). Perú. Figura original en LEA (1834): lám. 19 fig. 75 (H 12,7 mm). Figura 74. *Hemisinus simplex* (Tryon, 1866). Ecuador: localidad desconocida. Lectotipo ANSP 26782 (H 17 mm). Figura 75. *Melanoides tuberculata* (O.F. Müller, 1774). Manabí: Río Ayampé (fotos: M. Roosen). (H ca 25 mm).

Family THIARIDAE Gill, 1871

Remarks. This family has its likely origins in South-East Asia, occurring also in Australia, some Pacific islands, sub-Saharan Africa, and has been introduced in other parts of that continent as well as in the Americas. Its occurs in lotic and lentic freshwater, with some species tolerating brackish environments (GLAUBRECHT & NEIBER, 2019b). Morphological data can be found *e.g.* in BROWN (1994) and GLAUBRECHT (1996). Phylogenetic studies have been published by LYDEARD *ET AL.* (2002), STRONG *ET AL.* (2011).

Figure 76. A, B: *Andesipyrghus sketi* Hershler & Velkovrh, 1993, Colombia, Santander, La Paz; holotype USNM 860574 (H 2 mm); C: *Aroapyrgus colombiensis* Malek & Little, 1971, Colombia, valle de Cauca, near Pichinde, holotype DMNH 41542 (H 3.1 mm). Figure 77. A: ?*Cochliopina boetzkesi* (K. Miller, 1879), Guayas, near Guayaquil, original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 8 fig. 4 (H 4.5 mm); B: ?*Cochliopina ecuadoriana* (K. Miller, 1879), Guayas, near Guayaquil, original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 8 fig. 3 (H 7 mm). Figure 78. *Lithococcus multicarinatus* (K. Miller, 1879). Esmeraldas: Rio Cayapas. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 15 fig. 4 (H 9 mm).

Figura 76. A, B: *Andesipyrghus sketi* Hershler & Velkovrh, 1993, Colombia, Santander, La Paz, holotipo USNM 860574 (H 2 mm); C: *Aroapyrgus colombiensis* Malek & Little, 1971, Colombia, valle de Cauca, cerca de Pichinde, holotipo DMNH 41542 (H 3,1 mm). Figura 77. A: ?*Cochliopina boetzkesi* (K. Miller, 1879), Guayas, cerca de Guayaquil, figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 8 fig. 4 (H 4,5 mm); B: ?*Cochliopina ecuadoriana* (K. Miller, 1879), Guayas, cerca de Guayaquil, figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 8 fig. 3 (H 7 mm). Figura 78. *Lithococcus multicarinatus* (K. Miller, 1879). Esmeraldas: Rio Cayapas. Figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 15 fig. 4 (H 9 mm).

Genus *Melanoides* Olivier, 1804

Melanoides Olivier, 1804, *Voyage empire Othoman...*, 3: 69. Type species by monotypy *Melanoides fasciata* Olivier, 1804.

❖ *Melanoides tuberculata* (O.F. Müller, 1774) (Figs. 81, 75)

Merita tuberculata Müller, 1774, *Vermium test. fluv.*, 2: 191. "In littore Coromandel". Type material not located.

Distribution. Esmeraldas: Rio Blanco (CORREOSO, 2008 [as *Aylacostoma* sp.]); Manabí: Agua Blanca; Rio Ayampé (both Roosen, pers. observ. 2019); Sucumbios: Shushufindi (CORREOSO, 2008 [as *Aylacostoma* sp.]).

Figure 79. *Littoridina gaudichaudi* Souleyet, 1852. Guayas: near Guayaquil. Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-33996 (H 5 mm). Figure 80. *Pyrgophorus pedrinus* (K. Miller, 1879). Pichincha: Río San Pedro. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 6 Figure 7 (H 6.5 mm).

Figura 79. *Littoridina gaudichaudi* Souleyet, 1852. Guayas: cerca de Guayaquil. Sintipo MNHN-IM-2000-33996 (H 5 mm). Figura 80. *Pyrgophorus pedrinus* (K. Miller, 1879). Pichincha: Río San Pedro. Figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 7 Figura 3 (H 6,5 mm).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Río Atrato [301].

Remarks. This species is widespread in the tropics and in South America also known from the neighbouring countries Brazil, Colombia, and Peru (SIMONE, 2006; RAMÍREZ *ET AL.*, 2003; LINARES & VERA, 2012).

Family COCHLIOPIDAE Tryon, 1866

Remarks. This family of aquatic gastropods from brackish and freshwater systems occurs mainly in the Neotropics with some representatives in the Mediterranean and Africa (HERSHLER & THOMPSON, 1992). These authors have reviewed the generic classifications and counted less than 300 species names. Anatomical data is presented in the same paper. Phylogenetic data are in LIU *ET AL.* (2001).

Genus *Andesipyrgus* Hershler & Velkovrh, 1993

Andesipyrgus Hershler & Velkovrh, 1993, *Proc. Biol. Soc. Wash.*, 106: 182. Type species by monotypy *Andesipyrgus sketi* Hershler & Velkovrh, 1993.

Andesipyrgus sketi Hershler & Velkovrh, 1993 (Fig. 76A-B, 81)

Andesipyrgus sketi Hershler & Velkovrh, 1993, *Proc. Biol. Soc. Wash.*, 106: 183, figs 1-5. "Colombia (Santander Department): La Paz area (6° 11' N 73° 35' W), Cueva de los Indios, ca. 6 km SW of La Paz, 1995 m". Holotype USNM 860574.

Distribution. Napo: near Archidona, Cuevas de Jumandi, 140 km SW [sic] of Quito, about 500 m (HERSHLER & VELKOVHR, 1993: 183).

Ecoregion. Amazonas High Andes [312].

Remarks. For additional localities in Colombia see HERSHLER & VELKOVHR, 1993.

Genus *Aroapyrgus* H.B. Baker, 1931

Aroapyrgus Baker, 1931, *Nautilus*, 36: 143. New name for *Aroa* H.B. Baker, 1930 not Walker, 1855. Type species by original designation *Potamopyrgus ernesti vivens* H.B. Baker, 1930.

Aroapyrgus colombiensis Malek & Little, 1971 (Fig. 76C, 81)

Aroapyrgus colombiensis Malek & Little, 1971, *Nautilus*, 85: 20, fig. 1. "Tributary of the Río Pichinde, near Pichinde, Municipio de Cali, Valle de Cauca Department, Colombia". Holotype DMNH 41542; paratypes DMNH 41543, FMNH 168647, ANSP 321818.

Distribution. Orellana: near Nuevo Rocafuerte (AMUNÁRRIZ, 1991).

Ecoregion. Amazonas Lowlands [316].

Genus *Cochliopina* J.P.E. Morrison, 1946

Cochliopina Morrison, 1946, *Smiths. Misc. Coll.*, 106 (6): 18. Type species by original designation: *Cochliopa riograndensis* Pilsbry & Ferriss, 1906.

Remarks. The following species were listed by HERSCHLER & THOMPSON (1992: 130) as possibly cochliopinids and are only tentatively arranged under this genus. Their generic assignment remains uncertain until anatomical studies on identified material can be done. THOMPSON (2011: 50) remarked about the distribution: "... south to the Río Santiago, Ecuador".

?*Cochliopina boetzkesi* (K. Miller, 1879) (Fig. 77A)

Paludestrina boetzkesi Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 155, pl. 8 figs 4a, 4A-4C. Type locality: "prope S. Domingo; flumine Guayaquil". Type material not located.

?*Cochliopina ecuadoriana* (K. Miller, 1879) (Fig. 77B)

Paludestrina ecuadoriana Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 153, pl. 8 figs 3a, 3A-3C. Type locality: "fluminae Guayaquil prope urbem; prope San Domingo in Andibus occidentalibus, circa 400 m". Type material not located.

Genus *Lithococcus* Pilsbry, 1911

Lithococcus Pilsbry, 1911, *Report Patagonia*, 3 (5): 602. Type species by original designation *Lithoglyphus multicarinatus* K. Miller, 1878.

Lithococcus multicarinatus (K. Miller, 1879) (Fig. 78, 81)

Lithoglyphus multicarinatus Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 157, pl. 15 fig. 4. "Rio Cayapas". Type material not located.

Distribution. Esmeraldas: Río Cayapas (TL); Santa María stream (MOLINERO ORTIZ & BOGAN, 2018).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Río Atrato [301].

Figure 81. Distribution of *Hemisinus* (Hemisinidae), *Melanoides* (Thiaridae) and Cochliopidae species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 81. Distribución de especies de Hemisinus (Hemisinidae), Melanoides y Cochliopidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Remarks. Due to a typo the year of publication of this taxon was erroneously mentioned as 1878 in BREURE (2019b). Also reported from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 125).

Genus *Littoridina* Souleyet, 1852

Littoridina Souleyet in Eydoux & Souleyet, 1852, *Voyage La Bonite, Zool.*, 2: 563. Type species by monotypy *Littoridina gaudichaudi* Souleyet, 1852.

Littoridina gaudichaudi Souleyet, 1852 (Figs. 79)

Littoridina gaudichaudi Souleyet in Eydoux & Souleyet, 1852, *Voyage La Bonite, Zool.*, 2: 565, pl. 31 figs 31-33. “dans la rivière de Guayaquil”. Syntypes MNHN-IM-2000-33996 (4).

Remarks. According to HERSHLER & THOMPSON (1992: 67) this species is now extinct at the only locality known (= TL).

Genus *Pyrgophorus* Ancey, 1888

Pyrgophorus Ancey, 1888, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 5: 188. Type species by subsequent designation (PILSBRY, 1911: 562) *Pyrgulopsis spinosus* Call & Pilsbry, 1886.

Pyrgophorus pedrinus (K. Miller, 1879) (Figs. 80, 81)

Hydrobia pedrina Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 165, pl. 6 figs 7a, 7A-7B. “Chillo, Rio S. Pedro”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Pichincha: Rio San Pedro (TL).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Figure 82. A-C: *Galba cousini* (Jousseaume, 1887), Pichincha, near Quito, Chanchu-Yacu, syntype RBINS MT.3847 (H 9.1 mm); D: *Galba nitidella* (Martens, 1885), Tungurahua, near Agoyán, lectotype ZMB 35593 (H 7.8 mm). Figure 83. ?*Galba raphaelis* (Jousseaume, 1887). Azuay: near Cuenca. Syntype RBINS MT.3827 (H 7 mm).

Figura 82. A-C: *Galba cousini* (Jousseaume, 1887), Pichincha, cerca de Quito, Chanchu-Yacu, sintipo RBINS MT.3847 (H 9,1 mm); D: *Galba nitidella* (Martens, 1885), Tungurahua, cerca de Agoyán, lectotipo ZMB 35593 (H 7,8 mm). Figura 83.? *Galba raphaelis* (Jousseaume, 1887). Azuay: cerca de Cuenca. Sintipo RBINS MT.3827 (H 7 mm).

Comments on the family. Apart from the records described above, CORREOSO (2008) reports two unidentified Cochliopid species from the Itambi river near San Pablo lake and from Cuicocha lake (Imbabura province).

Family LYMNAEIDAE Rafinesque, 1815

Remarks. This large and diverse family of freshwater pulmonates occurs on all the continents except Antarctica. Phylogenetic data in SAADI ET AL. (2020).

Genus *Galba* Schrank, 1803

Galba Schrank, 1803, *Fauna Boica*: 75. Type species by subsequent designation (ICZN, 1998: 123) *Buccinum truncatum* O.F. Müller, 1774.

Figure 84. *Galba schirazensis* (Küster, 1862). Iran: Chiras. Original figure in KÜSTER (1862): pl. 11 figs 28-31 (H 6.8 mm).

Figura 84. *Galba schirazensis* (Küster, 1862). Irán: Chiras. Figura original en KÜSTER (1862): lám. 11 figs. 28-31 (H 6,8 mm).

Galba cousini (Jousseume, 1887) (Figs. 82A-C, 87)

Limnaea cousini Jousseume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 182, pl. 3 fig. 8. "Chancu-Yacu, près de Chillogallo, canton de Quito". Syntypes RBINS MT.3847 (20), MNHN-IM-2000-35288 (8), MNHN-IM-2000-35289 (12).

Distribution. Pichincha: near Quito, Chancu-Yacu (TL); Lago San Pablo (PARAENSE, 2004).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. This species has also been reported from Chile (VALDOVINOS, 2006: 91), Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 126), and Venezuela (POINTIER *ET AL.*, 2004).

Galba nitidella (E. von Martens, 1885) (Figs. 82D, 87)

Limnaea nitidella Martens, 1885, *Conch. Mitth.*, 2: 178, pl. 35 figs 16-17. "Chorrera de Agoyan". Lectotype (KILIAS, 1961: 164) and 18 paralectotypes ZMB 35593.

Distribution. Tungurahua: near Agoyán (TL).

Ecoregion. Amazonas High Andes [312].

Remarks. VINARSKI (2016: 140) suggested this taxon may be identical to *Galba cousini* (Jousseume, 1887), in which case Martens' name has priority.

?*Galba raphaelis* (Jousseume, 1887) (Figs. 83, 87)

Limnaea raphaelis Jousseume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 183, pl. 3 fig. 1. "à environs 2570 mètres (...) la région sud de Cuenca (prov. d'Azuaay)". Syntypes RBINS MT.3827 (23), MT.3828 (112).

Distribution. Azuay: near Cuenca (TL).

Ecoregion. Amazonas High Andes [312].

Remarks. This species is not reported in recent overviews of freshwater snails in Ecuador (CARON *ET AL.*, 2017), and may fall into the synonymy with one of the other species mentioned for this family.

❖ *Galba schirazensis* (Küster, 1862) (Figs. 84, 87)

Limnaeus schirazensis Küster, 1862 [1862-1863], *Syst. Conch.-Cab.*, (1) 17B: 53, pl. 11 figs 28-31 (ex Von dem Busch ms.). "bei Schiras in Persien". Type material not located.

Distribution. Pichincha: Cayambe; Chillogallo (both localities BARGUES ET AL., 2011); near Machachi (CARON ET AL., 2017).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. This species has been overlooked for many years; see BARGUES ET AL. (2011) for data and way of introduction.

Comments on the family. Another introduced *Galba* species, *G. truncatula* (O.F. Müller, 1774), is mentioned by DARRIGRAN ET AL. (2020) in their Supplementary Material, without further data or reference to a voucher.

Genus *Pseudosuccinea* F.C. Baker, 1908

Pseudosuccinea Baker, 1908, *Science*, 27: 943. Type species by original designation *Lymnaea columella* Say, 1817.

❖ *Pseudosuccinea columella* (Say, 1817) (Fig. 87)

Lymnaea columella Say, 1817: 14. No type locality mentioned.

Distribution. Guayas: Nobol (PARAENSE, 2004).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. Say remarked "inhabits stagnant waters and miry places", and his paper dealt with "American Fresh Water and Land Shells". LINARES & VERA (2012: 126), who listed this species as *Lymnaea columella*, give further details of the extensive distribution of this species.

Family PHYSIDAE Fitzinger, 1833

Remarks. An overview of this family which is common "in the North Temperate to Arctic Zones and throughout the Americas" was given by TAYLOR (2003: 2). Taylor also summarised information on anatomy, phylogeny and biogeography of this family. Phylogenetic data also in SAADI ET AL. (2020).

Genus *Haitia* Clench & Aguayo, 1932

Haitia Clench & Aguayo, 1932, *Proc. New Engl. Zool. Club*, 13: 37. Type species by original designation *Physa elegans* Clench & Aguayo, 1932.

❖ *Haitia acuta* (Draparnaud, 1805) (Figs. 85, 87)

Physa acuta Draparnaud, 1805, *Tableau moll. France*: 55, pl. 3 figs 10-11. "La Garonne". Syntypes NHMW 1820/XXVI/45.

Distribution. Pichincha: near Quito, tributary of Río Pedro (PARAENSE, 2004).

Figure 85. *Haitia acuta* (Draparnaud, 1805). France: Bordeaux, NHMUK 1898.5.20.10726 (H 12 mm). Figure 86. A, B: *Mayabina carolita* (Jousseume, 1887), Pichincha, San Nicolás, syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2613 (H 9,8 mm); C, D: *Mexinauta peruviana* (J.E. Gray, 1828), Peru, Lima, syntype NHMUK 1950.5.24.3 (H 23,8 mm).

Figura 85. *Haitia acuta* (Draparnaud, 1805). *Francia:* Burdeos, NHMUK 1898.5.20.10726 (H 12 mm). *Figura 86.* A, B: *Mayabina carolita* (Jousseume, 1887), Pichincha, San Nicolás, sintipo MNHN-IM-2000-2613 (H 9,8 mm); C, D: *Mexinauta peruviana* (J.E. Gray, 1828), Perú, Lima, sintipo NHMUK 1950.5.24.3 (H 23,8 mm).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. TAYLOR (2003: 137) listed this species as native to northeastern U.S.A. and adjacent Canada; "further range to the west and south is so poorly known as to be speculative". DARRIGRAN *ET AL.* (2020: Supplementary Material 4) have pointed out

that this species shows all the characteristics of an invasive species; it presents uncertainties in the species delimitation, and material from South America has been classified as *Physa cubensis* L. Pfeiffer, 1839, which is currently considered a synonym.

Genus *Mayabina* D.W. Taylor, 2003

Mayabina Taylor, 2003, *Rev. Biol. Trop.*, 51, Suppl. 1: 88. Type species by original designation *Physa cisternina* Morelet, 1851.

Mayabina carolita (Jousseau, 1887) (Figs. 86A-B, 87)

Aplecta carolita Jousseau, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 184, pl. 3 fig. 5. "San-Nicolas, canton de Megia". Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2613 (1).

Aplecta martinidella Jousseau, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: pl. 3 fig. 5; Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 262. "San Nicolas, canton de Megia". Syntypes MNHN-IM-2000-2628 (14).

Distribution. El Oro: Santa Rosa; Guayas: Chanduy (TAYLOR, 2003); Pichincha: San Nicolas (TL).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. TAYLOR (2003: 95) gave as distribution "Ecuador to northernmost Chile".

Genus *Mexinauta* D.W. Taylor, 2003

Mexinauta Taylor, 2003, *Rev. Biol. Trop.*, 51, Suppl. 1: 74. Type species by original designation *Physa nitens* Philippi, 1841.

Mexinauta peruviana (J.E. Gray, 1828) (Figs. 86C-D, 87)

?*Physa peruviana* Gray, 1828, *Spicil. Zool.*, 1: 5, pl. 6 fig. 10. [Peru] "Swamps between Lima and Callao". Syntypes NHMUK 1950.5.24.3-6 (4).

Aplecta gualbertoi Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 261, pl. 4 fig. 3. "Mapasingue". Syntypes MNHN-IM-2000-2631 (12).

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (TAYLOR 2003); Mapasingue (COUSIN, 1887).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. According to TAYLOR (2003: 76) this species is distributed from Ecuador to central Peru.

Family ACROLOXIDAE Thiele, 1931

Remarks. This is a species-poor family of freshwater limpets occurring worldwide. Recent literature deals mainly with species from Russia, East Asia and Europe. Anatomical and phylogenetic data is scarce, but see SOLDATENKO & PETROV (2019), SAADI ET AL. (2020).

Genus *Acroloxus* H. Beck, 1838

Ancylus (Acroloxus) Beck, 1838 [1837-1838], *Index moll.*: 124. Type species by subsequent designation (HERRMANNSEN, 1846 [1846-1847]: 15) *Patella lacustris* Linnaeus, 1758.

Figure 87. Distribution of Lymnaeidae and Physidae species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 87. Distribución de especies de Lymnaeidae y Physidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Acroloxus culicoides (d'Orbigny, 1835) (Figs. 88, 99)

Ancylus culicoides d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 23. "provincia Guayaquilensi (republica Colombiana)". Syntypes NHMUK 1854.12.4.280 (2).

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (TL).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. GRAY (1854) remarked that this sinistral species was "belonging to the genus *Veletia* [*sic*, *Velletia* Gray in Turton, 1840 = *Acroloxus* H. Beck, 1838]".

Family PLANORBIDAE Rafinesque, 1815

Remarks. A large family of worldwide freshwater snails with several dozen species in the Neotropics (PARAENSE, 2003, 2005; SIMONE, 2006; LINARES & VERA, 2012). Fossil records have been studied by CABRERA & MARTÍNEZ (2016, 2018), SALVADOR *ET AL.* (2018). Anatomical data in PARAENSE (2004). Phylogenetic data in JØRGENSEN *ET AL.* (2004), ALBRECHT *ET AL.* (2007), SAADI *ET AL.* (2020).

Genus *Biomphalaria* Preston, 1910

Biomphalaria Preston, 1910, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, (8) 6: 535. Type species by original designation *Biomphalaria smithii* Preston, 1910.

Biomphalaria cousini Paraense, 1966 (Figs. 89, 99)

Biomphalaria cousini Paraense, 1966, *Rev. Brasil. Biol.*, 26: 119, figs 2, 4, 6. "Santa Domingo de los Colorados, Province of Pichincha, in a brook flowing into the river Pobe". Type material not located.

Distribution. Esmeraldas: Rio Quininde (UF 139051, 139081); Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: affluent Rio Pobe, Santo Domingo de los Colorados (PARAENSE, 2004).
Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Biomphalaria equatoria (Cousin, 1887) (Figs. 90, 99)

Planorbis equatorius Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 263, pl. 4 fig. 8. "Équateur". Syntypes RBINS MT.3841 (10), MT.3832 (10), MT.3833 (5), MT.3834 (14).

Distribution. Guayas: Mapasingue-Macare; between Guayaquil and Pascuales; Pascuales; Nobol; Santa Lucia; Isla Puná, Carmelo [Carmela] (PARAENSE, 2004).
Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Biomphalaria peregrina (d'Orbigny, 1835) (Fig. 91, 99)

Planorbis peregrina d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 26. "Patagonia, Montevideo (republica Uruguayensi orientali); Pampas; provincia Corrientes (republica Argentina); provincia Rio-Grande (republica Boliviana) et provincia Guayaquilensi (republica Colombiana)". Syntypes NHMUK 1854.12.4.267-273 (55).

Planorbis canonicus Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 264, pl. 4 fig. 11. "le lac Saint-Paolo, près Quito". Syntypes RBINS MT.3852 (20).

Distribution. Pichincha: San Pablo lake (TL *canonicus*).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. Also reported from Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Peru, Puerto Rico (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 130).

Biomphalaria sericea (Dunker, 1848) (Fig. 92)

Planorbis sericeus Dunker, 1848, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 16: 42. "Patria ignota". Syntypes NHMUK 1969154 (3).

Distribution. Los Ríos: without specified locality (BARBOSA ET AL., 1963; PARAENSE, 2004).
Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Genus *Drepanotrema* Crosse & P. Fischer, 1880

Drepanotrema Crosse & P. Fischer in P. Fischer & Crosse, 1880 [1880-1902], *Mission au Mexique*, 7 (2): 59. Type species by subsequent designation (DALL, 1905: 86) *Planorbis yzabalensis* Crosse & P. Fischer, 1879.

❖? *Drepanotrema anatinum* (d'Orbigny, 1835) (Figs. 93, 99)

Planorbis anatinus d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 28. "ripis Parana (republica Argentina)". Syntypes NHM 1854.12.4.278 (1).

Distribution. Guayas: Santa Lucia (PARAENSE, 2004).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. A widely distributed species in South America, the native range of which is unclear.

Figure 88. *Acroloxus culicoides* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Guayas: Guayaquil. Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.280 (L 6,5 mm). Figure 89. *Biomphalaria cousini* Paraense, 1966. Esmeraldas: Río Quinindé, UF 139051 (D 7,4 mm). Figure 90. *Biomphalaria equatoria* (Cousin, 1887). Ecuador. Syntype RBINS MT. 3831 (D 22,3 mm).

Figura 88. *Acroloxus culicoides* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Guayas: Guayaquil. Sintipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.280 (L 6,5 mm). Figura 89. *Biomphalaria cousini* Paraense, 1966. Esmeraldas: Río Quinindé, UF 139051 (D 7,4 mm). Figura 90. *Biomphalaria equatoria* (Cousin, 1887). Ecuador. Sintipo RBINS MT. 3831 (D 22,3 mm).

Drepanotrema kermatoides (d'Orbigny, 1835) (Figs. 94, 99)

Planorbis kermatoides d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 27. "provincia Limacensi (republica Peruviana)". Syntypes NHMUK 1854.12.4.276 (10).

Distribution. Guayas: Nobol (PARAENSE, 2004).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Río Atrato [301].

Figure 91. *Biomphalaria peregrina* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Unknown locality. Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.267 (D 12.5 mm). Figure 92. *Biomphalaria sericea* (Dunker, 1848). Unknown locality. Syntype NHMUK 1969154 (D 15 mm).

Figura 91. *Biomphalaria peregrina* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Localidad desconocida. Sintipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.267 (D 12,5 mm). Figura 92. *Biomphalaria sericea* (Dunker, 1848). Localidad desconocida. Sintipo NHMUK 1969154 (D 15 mm).

❖? *Drepanotrema lucidum* (L. Pfeiffer, 1839) (Fig. 99)

Planorbis lucidus Pfeiffer, 1839, *Archiv Naturges.*, 5: 354. "[Cuba]". Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: Lomas de Sargentillo, between Guayaquil and Pascuales (PARAENSE, 2004).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. This species is widely distributed in the Neotropics, and it might be introduced.

❖ *Drepanotrema surinamense* (Clessin, 1884) (Figs. 95, 99)

Planorbis surinamensis Clessin 1884 in Küster et al. 1841-1886, *Syst. Conch.-Cab.*, (1) 17a: 126, pl. 17 fig. 11 (ex Dunker ms.). "Jamaica und Surinam (Gegend von Paramaribo)". Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: Nobol (PARAENSE, 2004).

Figure 93. *Drepanotrema anatinum* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Argentina: Parana. Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.278 (D 2.8 mm). Figure 94. *Drepanotrema kermatoides* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Peru: Lima. Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.276 (D 11.2 mm).

Figura 93. *Drepanotrema anatinum* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Argentina: Paraná. Sintipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.278 (D 2,8 mm). Figura 94. *Drepanotrema kermatoides* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Perú: Lima. Sintipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.276 (D 11,2 mm).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. Although Paraense did not mention it, this seems to be an introduced species.

Genus *Gyraulus* Charpentier, 1837

Gyraulus Charpentier, 1837, *Mém. Soc. Helv. Sci. Nat.*, 1: 21. Type species by subsequent designation (DALL, 1870: 351) *Planorbis albus* O.F. Müller, 1774.

Gyraulus hindsianus (Dunker, 1848) (Figs. 96, 99)

Planorbis hindsianus Dunker, 1848, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 16: 41. "in insulâ Puna in sinu ad Guayaquil". Syntypes NHMUK 1969148 (15).

Planorbis (*Gyraulus*) *boetzkesi* K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 148, pl. 7 figs 4a-4c. Type material not located.

Figure 95. *Drepanotrema surinamense* (Clessin, 1884). Suriname: near Paramaribo. Original figure in CLESSIN (1884): pl. 17 fig. 11 (D 6.5 mm). Figure 96. *Gyraulus hindsianus* (Dunker, 1848). Guayas: Isla Puna. Syntype NHMUK 1969148 (D 3.3 mm).

Figura 95. *Drepanotrema surinamense* (Clessin, 1884). Surinam: cerca de Paramaribo. Figura original en CLESSIN (1884): lám. 17 fig. 11 (D 6,5 mm). Figura 96. *Gyraulus hindsianus* (Dunker, 1848). Guayas: Isla Puna. Sintipo NHMUK 1969148 (D 3,3 mm).

Distribution. Guayas: Isla Puna (TL); Pichincha: Lago San Pablo, Hacienda San Roque; Quito, Cumbayá; Río San Pedro (PARAENSE, 2004).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. Paraense did not mention this species from Dunker's type locality in Guayas.

Genus *Helisoma* W. Swainson, 1840

Planorbis (*Helisoma*) Swainson, 1840, *Treatise malac.*: 337. Type species by monotypy *Planorbis bicarinatus* G.B. Sowerby I, 1822.

Figure 97. *Helisoma trivolvis* (Say, 1818). U.S.A.: Columbia River, NHMUK 20200308 (D 22.7 mm).
Figure 98. *Planorbella clevei* (Jousseau, 1887). Ecuador. Syntype RBINS MT. 3841 (D 18.2 mm).
Figura 97. *Helisoma trivolvis* (Say, 1818). EE.UU.: Río Columbia, NHMUK 20200308 (D 22,7 mm).
Figura 98. *Planorbella clevei* (Jousseau, 1887). Ecuador. Sintipo RBINS MT. 3841 (D 18,2 mm).

❖ *Helisoma trivolvis* (Say, 1818) (Figs. 97, 99)

Planorbis trivolvis Say in Nicholson, 1818, *Amer. ed. British encycl.*, 4: [11], pl. 2 fig. 2. "French Creek, near Lake Erie".

Distribution. Guayas: between Guayaquil and Pascuales (PARAENSE, 2004).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Remarks. Although Paraense did not mention it, this seems to be an introduced species.

Comments on the genus. A second introduced *Helisoma* species, *H. duryi* (Wetherby, 1879), is mentioned by DARRIGRAN *ET AL.* (2020) in their Supplementary Material, without further data or reference to a voucher.

Genus *Planorbella* Haldeman, 1843

Planorbis (*Planorbella*) Haldeman, 1843, *Monogr. freshw. univalve Moll.*: 14. Type species by subsequent monotypy *Planorbis campanulatus* Say, 1821.

Planorbella clevei (Jousseume, 1887) (Fig. 98)

Planorbis clevei Jousseume in Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 263, pl. 4 fig. 9. "Équateur". Syntypes RBINS MT.3841 (1), MT.3842 (3), MT.3843 (7), MT.3844 (9).

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality (TL).

Remarks. The generic placement of this taxon is provisional.

Family VERONICELLIDAE J.E. Gray, 1840

Remarks. Slugs of this family are notoriously difficult to identify on the basis of the external morphology alone. Anatomical studies are mainly available for Brazilian species. A molecular study of representatives of this family is pending (D. Robinson, pers. comm.).

Genus *Belocaulus* Hoffmann, 1925

Belocaulus Hoffmann, 1925, *Jen. Z. Naturw.*, 61: 245. Type species by subsequent designation (H.B. BAKER, 1925: 16) *Vaginula angustipes* Heynemann, 1885.

Belocaulus boetzkessi (K. Miller, 1879) (Fig. 100)

Veronicella boetzkessi Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 134, pl. 10 figs 4a-4c. "In Andibus occidentalibus, 2500 m". Type material not located.

Veronicella complanata K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 133, pl. 10 figs 2a-2c. "In Andibus occidentalibus, 2500 m". Type material not located.

Distribution. Ecuador: western Cordillera (TL).

Remarks. Described on the basis of two specimens, respectively found to be a single specimen. The type locality is too imprecise to allocate to a province. HOFFMANN (1925: 212) synonymised the two Miller taxa and united them with two species described later by Simroth from Colombia (*Vaginula varians* Simroth, 1913 and *V. rufescens* Simroth, 1913, both from Antioquia). The former is considered by THOMÉ (1993) as a separate *Sarasinula* species, the latter as *Potamojanuarius rufescens* (Simroth, 1913); see GLAUBRECHT, 2010: 327; LINARES & VERA, 2012: 137, 139.

Genus *Colosius* Thomé, 1975

Colosius Thomé, 1975, *Iheringia, Zool.*, 48: 13. Type species by original designation *Vaginula lugubris* Colosi, 1921.

Colosius confusus Gomes, Robinson, Zimmerman, Obregón & Barr, 2013 (Figs. 101, 107)

Colosius confusus Gomes et al., 2013, *Malacologia*, 56: 7, figs 2-7, 12. "Ecuador, Tungurahua, Baños de Agua Santa, 2,000 m". Holotype ANSP A22109; paratypes ANSP, CMS, FMNH, MRSN, QCAZ.

Figure 99. Distribution of *Acroloxus* and Planorbidae species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 99. Distribución de especies de *Acroloxus* y Planorbidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Distribution. Bolivar: San Miguel; Chimborazo: Alausi; Cotopaxi: Otonga; 1 mi NE Mount Cotopaxi (UF 255555); Imbabura: Caranqui; Embabura; Napo: Baeza; Cosanga; Cuyuja; El Chaco; Papallacta; Pichincha: Pululahua; Tungurahua: Baños (TL); Patate (all from GOMES ET AL., 2013 unless mentioned otherwise).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145], Northern Andean páramo [NT1006].

Remarks. Also reported from Colombia and Peru (GOMES ET AL., 2013).

Colosius festae (Colosi, 1921) (Fig. 107)

Vaginula festae Colosi, 1921, *Atti Soc. Ital. Sci Nat.*, 60: 156. "Ecuador (Pun)".

Distribution. Carchi: El Pun (TL).

Ecoregion. Northern Andean páramo [NT1006].

Remarks. This species was tentatively considered as a *Belocaulus* species by HOFFMANN (1925: 247); THOMÉ (1975a) placed the species in the current genus.

Colosius propinquus (Colosi, 1921) (Fig. 107)

Vaginula propinqua Colosi, 1921, *Atti Soc. Ital. Sci Nat.*, 60: 157. "Ecuador (Pun)".

Distribution. Carchi: El Pun (TL).

Ecoregion. Northern Andean páramo [NT1006].

Remarks. Also reported from Puerto Rico (THOMÉ ET AL., 1997); these authors keep this species separate from the following, although HOFFMANN (1925: 202) indicated that Colosi was already uncertain about the distinction between the two.

Figure 100. *Belocaulus boetzkesi* (K. Miller, 1879). Ecuador: western Cordillera. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 10 fig. 4 (L 63 mm). Figure 101. *Colosius confusus* Gomes, Robinson, Zimmerman, Obregón & Barr, 2013. External colour variation. A: dorsal view of a specimen from Volcán Pululahua, Pichincha; B: ventral view of the specimen shown in A; C: dorsal view of specimen from cantón Quijos, Napo. Abbreviations, ca: bands without or with less spots often present on each side of the lighter line of the notum, that together form sometimes a lozenge-shaped area; ki: keel; yl: lighter line located longitudinally and centrally on the notum; ys: yellow spots commonly found on the notum. Figure adapted from GOMES ET AL. (2013).

Figura 100. *Belocaulus boetzkesi* (K. Miller, 1879). Ecuador: Cordillera occidental. Figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 10 fig. 4 (L 63 mm). Figura 101. *Colosius confusus* Gomes, Robinson, Zimmerman, Obregón & Barr, 2013. Variación de color externa. A: vista dorsal de un espécimen del Volcán Pululahua, Pichincha; B: vista ventral del espécimen mostrado en A; C: vista dorsal de un ejemplar del cantón Quijos, Napo. Abreviaturas, ca: bandas sin o con menos manchas a menudo presentes a cada lado de la línea más clara del notum, que juntas forman a veces un área en forma de rombo; ki: quilla; yl: línea más clara ubicada longitudinal y centralmente en el notum; ys: manchas amarillas que se encuentran comúnmente en el notum. Figura adaptada de GOMES ET AL. (2013).

Colosius pulcher (Colosi, 1921) (Figs. 102, 107)

Vaginula pulchra Colosi, 1921, *Atti Soc. Ital. Sci Nat.*, 60: 157. "Ecuador (Cañar, Cuenca, Gualaceo, Papallacta, Quito)". Lectotype (THOMÉ, 1970: 23) MRSN 503.

Vaginula lugubris Colosi, 1921, *Atti Soc. Ital. Sci Nat.*, 60: 157. "Ecuador (Quito, Huaco, El Troje)".

Distribution. Azuay: Cuenca; Gualaceo; Cañar: Cañar; Carchi: San Gabriel; Chimborazo: Penipe-Puela; Cotopaxi: Boliche; Iliniza Sur; Latacumba; Pastocalle; Pujili; Imbabura: San Pablo; Lita (all Carchi, Chimborazo, Cotapaxi and Imbabura records from GOMES ET AL., 2013); Napo: Archidona (GOMES ET AL., 2013); Cosanga (WIKTOR & STAWARCZYK, 2011); Papallacta; Pichincha: Aloag (GOMES ET AL., 2013); El Troje; Pasachoa; Pululahua (both GOMES ET AL., 2013); Quito; Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Santo Domingo de los Colorados (GOMES ET AL., 2013); Sucumbios: Oyacachi (GOMES ET AL., 2013) (all COLOSI, 1921 except mentioned otherwise).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178], Northern Andean páramo [NT1006].

Figure 102. *Colosius pulcher* (Colosi, 1921). External colour variation in adult specimens. A, dorsal view of a specimen from Pasochoa, Pichincha; B, dorsal view of a specimen from the same locality; C, dorsal view of a specimen from the same locality; D, ventral view of the specimen shown in A; E, ventral view of the specimen shown in B; F, ventral view of a specimen from Pasochoa, Pichincha; G, ventral view of a specimen from the same locality; H, dorsal view of a specimen from the same locality; I, dorsal view of the specimen shown in F. Abbreviations, bs: black spots distributed on the entire notum; fp: female genital pore; fo: foot; yl: lighter line located longitudinally and centrally on the notum; ys: yellow spots that are distributed irregularly on the notum. Figure adapted from GOMES ET AL. 2013. Figure 103. *Diploselenodes occidentalis* (Guilding, 1825). Guayas: unspecified locality. A, dorsal view. B, ventral view (photos: S. Gomes).

Figura 102. *Colosius pulcher* (Colosi, 1921). Variación de color externo en ejemplares adultos. A, vista dorsal de un ejemplar de Pasochoa, Pichincha; B, vista dorsal de un ejemplar de la misma localidad; C, vista dorsal de un ejemplar de la misma localidad; D, vista ventral del espécimen mostrado en A; E, vista ventral del espécimen mostrado en B; F, vista ventral de un espécimen de Pasochoa, Pichincha; G, vista ventral de un espécimen de la misma localidad; H, vista dorsal de un ejemplar de la misma localidad; I, vista dorsal del espécimen mostrado en F. Abreviaturas, bs: manchas negras distribuidas en todo el notum; fp: poro genital femenino; fo: pie; yl: línea más clara ubicada longitudinal y centralmente en el notum; ys: manchas amarillas que se distribuyen irregularmente en el notum. Figura reproducida de GOMES ET AL. (2013). Figura 103. *Diploselenodes occidentalis* (Guilding, 1825). Guayas: localidad no especificada. A, vista dorsal. B, vista ventral (fotos: S. Gomes).

Remarks. The locality El Troje (a Hacienda) is here assigned to Prov. Pichincha, but similar named Haciendas are located in Prov. Chimborazo and Imbabura. The record from Cosango was based on a juvenile specimen identified by Wiktor on the basis of HOFFMANN (1925) as *Belocaulus* sp. Based on the locality this is likely *Belocaulus pulcher* (Colosi, 1921), now classified as a *Colosius* species. Also mentioned from Colombia, Peru and Bolivia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 140), but note that GOMES ET AL. (2013: 16-20) excluded several literature references and listed only specimens from Ecuador.

Genus *Diploselenodes* Thomé, 1975

Diploselenodes Thomé, 1975, *Iheringia*, Zool. 48: 13. Type species by original designation *Vaginulus bielenbergi* Semper, 1885.

❖ *Diploselenodes occidentalis* (Guilding, 1825) (Fig. 103)

Onchidium occidentale Guilding, 1825, *Trans. Linn. Soc. London*, 14: 323, pl. 9 figs 9-12. "Insulae St. Vincentii".

Distribution. Guayas: from unspecified locality (S. Gomes, pers. commun. 31 October 2020). **Remarks.** Widespread in the Antilles: Barbados, Dominica, Guadeloupe, Martinique, St. Vincent (TL), St. Thomas, Trinidad (HOFFMANN, 1925). Also reported from the Bahamas, Colombia, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Guyana, Panama, U.S.A.: Hawaii, and Venezuela (THOMÉ ET AL., 1997).

Diploselenodes olivaceus (Stearns, 1871) (Figs. 104, 107)

Veronicella olivacea Stearns, 1871, *Conch. Memo.*, 8: 1. "Nicaragua". Lectotype (THOMÉ & LOPES-PITONI, 1976: 710) USNM 39160.

Veronicella arcuata K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 130, pl. 9 figs 2a-2c. "In plano Ibarrensi, 2500 m". Type material not located.

Veronicella teres K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 131, pl. 10 figs 1a-1c. "In plano Ibarrensi".

Veronicella atopunctata K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 132, pl. 9 figs 3a-3d. "Ibarra". Type material not located.

Veronicella andensis K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 134, pl. 8 figs 5a-5c. "Andibus occidentalis, 2500 m". Type material not located.

Veronicella cephalophora K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 135, pl. 9 figs 1a-1c. "In Andibus occidentalibus". Type material not located.

Veronicella quadricularis K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 137, pl. 10 figs 3a-3c. "In Andibus occidentalibus, 2500 m". Type material not located.

Veronicella aequatoriensis Germain, 1908, *Bull. Mus. Nat. Hist. Nat.*, 14: 63. "Alausi". Type material not located.

Veronicella riveti Germain, 1908, *Bull. Mus. Nat. Hist. Nat.*, 14: 63; Germain, 1910, *Mission Serv. Géogr.*, 9, Zool., 3: C.4, pl. 1 figs 1, 4-7. "La Galia, Yaguachi". Type material not located.

Veronicella alausiensis Germain, 1910, *Mission Serv. Géogr.*, 9, Zool., 3: C.8, pl. 1 figs 2-3 [See Remarks].

Vaginula esilicaulis Colosi, 1921, *Atti Soc. Ital. Sci Nat.*, 60: 160. "Ecuador (Balzar, Vinces)". Type material not located.

Distribution. Chimborazo: Alausí (TL *aequatoriensis*); Guayas: Balzar (*esilicaulis*); Yaguachi Nuevo (TL *riveti*); Imbabura: near Ibarra (TL *arcuata*, *atopunctata*, *teres*); Los Ríos: Vinces (*esilicaulis*).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145], Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178], Guayaquil flooded grasslands [NT0905].

Figure 104. *Diploselenodes olivaceus* (Stearns, 1871). Imbabura: Ibarra. Original figure of *Veronicella arcuata* in MILLER (1879): pl. 9 fig. 2. Figure 105. *Sarasinula plebeia* (P. Fischer, 1868). Guayas: Guayaquil, dorsal view (photos: S. Gomes). Figure 106. *Sarasinula linguaeformis* (Semper, 1885). Guayas: Guayaquil. Original figure in Semper (1885): pl. 25 fig. 4 (L 90 mm).
 Figura 104. *Diploselenodes olivaceus* (Stearns, 1871). Imbabura: Ibarra. Figura original de *Veronicella arcuata* en MILLER (1879): lám. 9 fig. 2. Figura 105. *Sarasinula plebeia* (P. Fischer, 1868). Guayas: Guayaquil, vista dorsal (fotos: S. Gomes). Figura 106. *Sarasinula linguaeformis* (Semper, 1885). Guayas: Guayaquil. Figura original en Semper (1885): lám. 25 fig. 4 (L 90 mm).

Remarks. Miller described his species mostly on the basis of one or two specimens and did not dissect them. GERMAIN (1910) introduced *Veronicella alausiensis* as a replacement name for *Veronicella aequatoriensis* Germain, 1908, not *Vaginula aequatorialis* Simroth, 1896. However, given the differences in the specific epithet this was an unnecessary action. According to GLAUBRECHT (2010: 322) *Vaginula aequatorialis* was described by SIMROTH (1896: 18) from [Uganda] "Oagénya", thus not a Neotropical species, and is a junior synonym of *Meisenheimeria stuhlmanni* (Simroth, 1895). Colosi mentioned localities in two different provinces for his *Vaginula esilicaulis*; we refrain from making a restriction. HOFFMANN (1925: 148-152) listed in total 13 species which he considered as synonyms of Stearns' species, which has thus the nucleus of its distribution in northwestern South America and southern Central America.

Genus *Sarasinula* Grimpe & Hoffmann, 1924

Sarasinula Grimpe & Hoffmann, 1924, *Zool. Anz.*, 58: 177. Type species by original designation *Vaginulus plebeius* P. Fischer, 1868.

Figure 107. Distribution of Veronicellidae species, and Ecuadorian distribution of *Achatina* (*Lissachatina*) *fulica* (*Achatinidae*) according to records in GBIF (2020). See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions. *Figura 107. Distribución de especies de Veronicellidae, y distribución de Achatina* (*Lissachatina*) *fulica* (*Achatinidae*) *en Ecuador según registros en GBIF (2020). Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecoregiones.*

❖ *Sarasinula plebeia* (P. Fischer, 1868) (Figs. 105, 107)

Veginulus plebeius Fischer, 1868, *J. de Conchyl.*, 16: 145. “in Nova Celedonia”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (S. Gomes, pers. commun. 31 October 2020).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Remarks. This species was mentioned by CORREOSO (2008: 98) as “prodría vivir en Ecuador” [could live in Ecuador], but citing at the same time a locality “entre Calcali y Yunguilla” [near Quito]. GOMES (2015) also mentioned Ecuador as the locality, without giving further details. The figure of a specimen herein from Guayaquil is proof of this record. Gomes also mentioned the original area as southern South America, east of the Andes.

Sarasinula linguaeformis (C.G. Semper, 1885) (Figs. 106, 107)

Vaginula linguaeformis Semper 1885 [1870-1894], *Reisen Arch. Philipp.*, 2 (3): 307, pl. 25 fig. 4; pl. 27 fig. 3. “Guayaquil”. Type material not located.

Veronicella marianita Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 190, pl. 4 fig. 14. “Gualacco y Azogues, prov. del Azuay”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Azuay: between Gualaceo and Azogues (TL *marianita*); Guayas: Guayaquil (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Remarks. Synonymy based on HOFFMANN (1925: 193-194). Also reported from Brazil, Guyana, Paraguay, Peru (THOMÉ, 1975b; THOMÉ ET AL., 1997; GOMES, 2007).

Figure 108. *Achatina (Lissachatina) fulica* Bowdich, 1822. El Oro: Pasage. iNaturalist 103285984.
Figura 108. *Achatina (Lissachatina) fulica* Bowdich, 1822. El Oro: Pasage. iNaturalist 103285984.

Family ACHATINIDAE W. Swainson, 1840

Remarks. This family, originally of African origin, is represented in the Neotropics mainly by Subulininae which were regarded until recently as a separate family (SCHILEYKO, 1999b); all species except the first one below belong to this group. The Subulininae subfamily is distributed circumglobally in tropical and subtropical zones. The relationships within the Achatinidae were clarified by FONTANILLA *ET AL.* (2017). Further molecular data on the pest species *Achatina fulica* in FONTANILLA (2010). Data on Neotropical Subulininae is dispersed in the literature, often on specific aspects; *e.g.* MEDEIROS *ET AL.* (2015), D'ÁVILA *ET AL.* (2018), MIQUEL & JAIME (2018). Revisionary work may be found in PILSBRY (1906-1907), and recently in GREGO *ET AL.* (2007); a faunal revision of Belize is in DOURSON *ET AL.* (2018).

Note that Subulininae species are notoriously difficult to identify, partly because these species do not exhibit characteristics of an adult stage and also because anatomical and molecular data are still largely lacking.

Genus *Achatina* Lamarck, 1799

Achatina Lamarck, 1799, *Mém. Soc. Hist. Nat. Paris*, 1: 75. Type species by monotypy *Bulla achatina* Lamarck, 1799.

Subgenus *Achatina (Lissachatina)* Bequaert, 1950

Achatina (Lissachatina) Bequaert, 1950, *Bull. Mus. Comp. Zool.*, 150: 49. Type by original designation *Achatina fulica* Bowdich, 1822.

❖ *Achatina (Lissachatina) fulica* Bowdich, 1822 (Figs. 108, 107)

Achatina fulica Bowdich, 1822, *Elem. conch.*, 1: pl. 13 fig. 1. Type locality not given. Type material lost (RAHEEM *ET AL.*, 2014: 115).

Distribution. El Oro: Pasage (obs. iNaturalist 103285984, 2021). Guayas: Guayaquil; Pastaza: Puyo; Pichincha: Mindo; Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Santo Domingo de los Colorados (BARRERO *ET AL.*, 2009; GOLDYN *ET AL.*, 2017).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Napo moist forests [NT0142], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145], Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178], Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214], Tumbes-Piura dry forests [NT0232].

Remarks. Also reported from the Galápagos, Santa Cruz Island (MIQUEL & HERRERA, 2014). See GOLDYN *ET AL.* (2016, 2017) for further notes on the Ecuadorian distribution of this species. Undoubtedly there will be other occurrences in mainland Ecuador which have not been reported in literature (yet). In GBIF 227 occurrences were recorded from Ecuador (Fig. 117; data available on 25 June 2020). This species is rapidly becoming a worldwide pest.

Genus *Allopeas* H.B. Baker, 1935

Allopeas Baker, 1935, *Nautilus*, 48: 84. Type species by original designation *Bulimus gracilis* Hutton, 1834.

❖ *Allopeas gracile* (Hutton, 1834) (Figs. 109A-B, 118)

Bulimus gracilis Hutton, 1834, *J. Asiatic Soc. Bengal*, 3 (26): 84. "Mirzapur, Uttar Pradesh State, India". Lectotype (RAHEEM *ET AL.*, 2014: 118) NHMUK 1856.9.15.68/1, paralectotypes NHMUK 1856.9.15.68/2-11 (10).

Opeas acutius K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 124, pl. 13 fig. 3. "circa Guayaquil". Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: between Guayaquil and Manta, Pedro Carbo (■ANSP 180304).

Ecoregion. Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214].

Remarks. Also reported from the Galápagos; San Cristóbal (ANSP), Floreana and Santa Cruz Islands (anthropogenic areas; MIQUEL & HERRERA, 2014).

Allopeas micra (d'Orbigny, 1835) (Figs. 109C-E, 118)

Helix micra d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 9. "versant oriental des Andes boliviennes....aussi aux environs de Rio de Janeiro". Syntypes NHMUK 1854.12.4.87 (9), MNHN-IM-2000-4683.

Bulimus cuencanus L. Pfeiffer, 1859, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 27: 26. "Cuenca". Syntypes NHMUK 1986186 (2).

Opeas dresseli K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 123, pl. 14 fig. 1. "circa Guayaquil". Type material not located.

Distribution. Azuay: Cuenca (PFEIFFER, 1859); Guayas: Guayaquil (MILLER, 1879); between Guayaquil and Manta, Pedro Carbo (■ANSP 180305, MCZ 139892).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Remarks. Also reported from the Galápagos: Floreana and San Cristóbal Islands (MIQUEL & HERRERA, 2014). Widely distributed in Central and South America.

Genus *Beckianum* H.B. Baker, 1961

Beckianum Baker, 1961, *Nautilus*, 75: 84. Type species by original designation *Bulimus beckianus* L. Pfeiffer, 1846.

Figure 109. A, B: *Allopeas gracile* (Hutton, 1834), India, Mirzapur, lectotype NHMUK 1856.9.15.68/1 (H 13 mm); C-E: *Allopeas micra* (d'Orbigny, 1835), Bolivia, eastern Andean slopes, syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.87 (H 6 mm). Figure 110. A: *Beckianum beckianum* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846), Morona Santiago, 6 km SSE Sucua, UF 139066 (H 6.4 mm); B, C: *Leptinaria eyerdami* F. Haas, 1951, Tungurahua, Baños, holotype FMNH 30844 (H 6.4 mm).

Figura 109. A, B: *Allopeas gracile* (Hutton, 1834), India, Mirzapur, lectotipo NHMUK 1856.9.15.68/1 (H 13 mm); C-E: *Allopeas micra* (d'Orbigny, 1835), Bolivia, vertientes andinas orientales, sintipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.87 (H 6 mm). Figura 110. A: *Beckianum beckianum* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846), Morona Santiago, 6 km SSE Sucua, UF 139066 (H 6,4 mm); B, C: *Leptinaria eyerdami* F. Haas, 1951, Tungurahua, Baños, holotipo FMNH 30844 (H 6,4 mm).

❖ *Beckianum beckianum* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846) (Figs. 110A, 118)

Bulimus beckianus Pfeiffer, 1846, *Symb. Helic.*, 3: 82. "insula Opara?". Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: Bucay (■ANSP 148443), Pedro Carbo, between Guayaquil and Manta (■ANSP 180305); Morona-Santiago: 2 km W Patuca (UF 139061); 6 km SSE Sucua (UF 139066); Pastaza: Puyo (UF 40454).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214], Guayaquil flooded grasslands [NT0905].

Remarks. Note that “insula Opara” is the Polynesian island today known as Rapa, one of the most isolated places in the world and possibly an error in the location of the original material.

Genus *Leptinaria* H. Beck, 1837

Leptinaria Beck, 1837 [1837-1838], *Index moll.*: 79. Type species by subsequent designation (HERRMANNSEN, 1847 [1846-1847]: 583) *Helix unilamellata* d’Orbigny, 1835.

Leptinaria aequatoria (K. Miller, 1879) (Figs. 111, 118)

Spiraxis aequatoria Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 127, pl. 13 figs 6-6b. “Circa Guayaquil”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (TL).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Remarks. It cannot be excluded that this taxon may prove to be a synonym of one of the other *Leptinaria* species mentioned here.

Leptinaria eyerdami F. Haas, 1951 (Figs. 110B-C, 118)

Leptinaria (*Lamellaxis*) *eyerdami* Haas, 1951, *Feldiana*, Zool. 31: 542, fig. 124. “Baños, Tunguaragua, Ecuador”. Holotype FMNH 30844; paratypes ANSP 187914 (4), FMNH 30845 (5).

Distribution. Tungurahua: Baños (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. This species has not been reported since its description and may be a possible endemic.

□ *Leptinaria funcki* (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)

Achatina funcki Pfeiffer, 1848, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 15: 232. “Merida in Venezuela”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (HIDALGO, 1872).

Remarks. BREURE & ARAUJO (2017) were unable to locate the voucher for Hidalgo’s record. It might be a misidentification.

Leptinaria unilamellata (d’Orbigny, 1838) (Figs. 112, 118)

Helix unilamellata d’Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 9. “provincia Santa Cruz de la Sierra (republica Boliviana)” [*nomen nudum*].

Achatina lamellata Potiez & Michaud, 1835, *Galerie moll.*: pl. 11 figs 7-8 [figure only, no name].

Bulimus unilamellatus d’Orbigny, [30 March] 1838 [1834-1847], *Voyage Amér. mérid.*, 5 (3): 257. “république de Bolivia, (...) à vingt lieux de Santa-Cruz de la Sierra”. Syntypes NHMUK 1854.12.4.84 (6).

Achatina lamellata Potiez & Michaud, [< 27 October] 1838, *Galerie moll.*: 128; plate explanation: 12. “?”. Type material not located.

Figure 111. *Leptinaria aequatoria* (K. Miller, 1879). Guayas: Guayaquil. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 13 figs 6-6b (H 14 mm). Figure 112. *Leptinaria unilamellata* (d'Orbigny, 1838). Bolivia: near Santa Cruz de la Sierra. Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.84 (H 15.5 mm). Figure 113. A: *Opeas hannense* (Rang, 1831), Guayas, near Guayaquil, original figure of *Opeas aciculaeforme* in MILLER (1879): pl. 13 fig. 4 aBA (H 7 mm); B: *Opeas rarum* (K. Miller, 1879), Guayas: near Guayaquil, original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 14 fig. 2 aAB (H 8 mm).
 Figura 111. *Leptinaria aequatoria* (K. Miller, 1879). Guayas: Guayaquil. Figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 13 figs. 6-6b (H 14 mm). Figura 112. *Leptinaria unilamellata* (d'Orbigny, 1838). Bolivia: cerca de Santa Cruz de la Sierra. Sintipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.84 (H 15,5 mm). Figura 113. A: *Opeas hannense* (Rang, 1831), Guayas, cerca de Guayaquil, figura original de *Opeas aciculaeforme* en MILLER (1879): lám. 13 fig. 4 aBA (H 7 mm); B: *Opeas rarum* (K. Miller, 1879), Guayas, cerca de Guayaquil, figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 14 fig. 2 aAB, (H 8 mm).

Achatina concentrica Reeve, 1849 [1848-1850], *Conch. Icon.*, 5: pl. 19 fig. 106 “Bolivia”. Type material not located.

Leptinaria valenzuela Jousseume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 170, pl. 3 fig. 4. “La Coca, prov. d’Orienté”. Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-4667 (11), RBINS MT.3846 (60); MCZ 102952 (2).

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Milagro (■MCZ 139880); Morona-Santiago: 2 km W Patuca (■UF 139042); Orellana: San Francisco de Orellana (TL *valenzuela*); Sucumbios: Cuyabeno Nature Reserve, near the Cuyabeno lodge (Roosen, pers. obs. 2019).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178], Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. THOMPSON (2011) recognised both *Leptinaria l. lamellata* and *L. l. concentrica*, but their distributions overlapped. The Peruvian *L. anomala* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846) is clearly closely related. Jousseume’s taxon was mentioned as a junior subjective synonym of *Leptinaria lamellata concentrica* (Reeve, 1849) by THOMPSON (2011: 164). Also known from other countries in Central America and the West Indies, Brazil, Bolivia, Peru, and some islands in Polynesia (see CHRISTENSEN ET AL., 2018). BREURE ET AL. (2020) solved the nomenclatural issue on the publication date of the work of Potiez & Michaud, and the synonymy of both taxa from these authors and d’Orbigny (see also HORSACK ET AL., 2020).

Genus *Opeas* Albers, 1850

Opeas Albers, 1850, *Die Heliceen*: 175. Type species by subsequent designation: *Helix goodalli* J.S. Miller, 1822.

❖ *Opeas hannense* (Rang, 1831) (Figs. 113A, 118)

Helix goodalli J.S. Miller, 1822, *Ann. Philos.* (n.s.) 3: 381. Not *Helix goodalli* A. Férussac, 1821.

Helix (*Cochlicella*) *hannensis* Rang, 1831, *Ann. Sci. Nat.*, 24: 41, pl. 3 fig. 8. “Hann sur la presqu’île du Cap-Verd”. Type material not located.

Bulimus pumilus L. Pfeiffer, 1840, *Archiv Naturges.*, 6: 252. “Cuba”. Type material not located.

Opeas aciculaeforme K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 125, pl. 13 fig. 4. “circa Guayaquil”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (MILLER, 1879).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Remarks. First mentioned [as *Opeas goodalli* (J.S. Miller, 1822)] for Ecuador without any localities by PILSBRY (1906 [1906-1907]: 201), who considered *Opeas aciculaeforme* K. Miller, 1879 a synonym. ODHNER (1951) recorded the first occurrence on the Galápagos; now known from Isabela and Santa Cruz Islands (MIQUEL & HERRERA, 2014). The species is considered to be of eastern Asian origin (ROBINSON, 1999) and is thus introduced, likely in the 19th century or earlier.

Opeas rarum K. Miller, 1879 (Figs. 113B, 118)

Opeas rarum Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 125, pl. 14 fig. 2. “Circa Guayaquil”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: near Guayaquil (TL).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Remarks. STREBEL & PFEFFER (1882) reported this species from Guatemala and eastern Mexico. DALL (1926) mentioned it from Mexico, Nayarit, Isla María Magdalena. We

consider it doubtful if these records are correct for this Ecuadorian taxon. The relation of *Opeas rarum* and *O. hannense* deserves more attention.

Genus *Protobeliscus* Pilsbry, 1906

Obeliscus (Protobeliscus) Pilsbry, 1906 [1906-1907], *Man. Conch.* (2) 18: 251. Type species by original designation *Bulimus cuneus* L. Pfeiffer, 1852.

Protobeliscus fairmaireanus (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853) (Figs. 114, 125)

Bulimus fairmaireanus Petit de la Saussaye, 1853, *J. de Conchyl.*, 4: 250, pl. 8 fig. 7. "Guayaquil". Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-4704.

Bulimus cuneus L. Pfeiffer, 1854, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 20: 154. "in ripis fluvii Mira, reipublicae Aequatoris". Syntypes NHMUK 1985073 (3). [New synonymy].

Obeliscus cuneus var. *minor* K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 195; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 6 fig. 3b. "Val de Pilaton". Type material not located.

Distribution. Azuay: Cuenca (■MCZ 139878); Antisana (■MCZ 139957); Cuenca-Paute road, between Puente Descanso and Paute (■MCZ 102301, 125323); Bolivar: San José de Chimbo (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017, cf. CALATAYUD, 1994); Carchi: valley Río Mira (PFEIFFER, 1854b); Guayas: Guayaquil (TL); Napo: Baeza (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Pichincha: Los Puentes (COUSIN, 1887); Pilatón valley (MILLER, 1878); Nanegal (GERMAIN, 1907; ■MCZ 102301); Guarumos (SALVADOR *ET AL.*, 2020); 15 km N Quito (■MCZ 139882); Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Santo Domingo de los Colorados (GERMAIN, 1907).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. The historical locality "Guayaquil" is likely a proxy for a sampled locality elsewhere and should not be taken literally. The locality "Horongo", mentioned for this species by GERMAIN (1907), is linked to Nanegal. This species is also recorded from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 212).

Protobeliscus haplostylus (L. Pfeiffer, 1846) (Figs. 115A-C, 125)

Bulimus haplostylus Pfeiffer, 1846, *Symb. Helic.*, 3: 84. "Loxa reipublicae Aequatoris". Probable syntype NHMUK 1987021 (1).

Distribution. Azuay: Cuenca (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); El Catamajia [Catamayo], near Loja (TL); Pichincha: Los Puentes (COUSIN, 1887); Tungurahua: Baños (■MCZ 113919); Rio Pastaza, Yunquille (■MCZ 132197).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Protobeliscus jousseaumei (Cousin, 1887) (Figs. 115D-F, 125)

Obeliscus jousseaumei Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 238, pl. 4 fig. 1. "à la descente d'Azagues, venant de Molobog (...) à une altitude d'environ 2,400 mètr.". Syntypes RBINS MT.3845 (28), MNHN IM 2000-4647 (4).

Distribution. Cañar: between Azogues and Molobog (TL); Pichincha: near Pululuhua (RBINS, ex Cousin).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Figure 114. *Protobeliscus fairmaireanus* (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853). Guayas: Guayaquil. A, B: syntype MNHN-IM-2000-4707 (H 65 mm); C-E: Ecuador, banks of the Río Mira, syntype of *Bulimus cuneus* L. Pfeiffer, 1854) NHMUK 1985073 (H 65.3 mm). Figure 115. A-C: *Protobeliscus haplostylus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846), Azuay, Loja, probable syntype NHMUK 1987021 (H 38.2 mm); D-F: *Protobeliscus jousseaumei* (Cousin, 1887), Cañar, between Azogues and Molobog, syntype RBINS MT.3845 (H 28.3 mm).

Figura 114. *Protobeliscus fairmaireanus* (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853). Guayas: Guayaquil. A, B: sintipo MNHN-IM-2000-4707 (H 65 mm); C-E: Ecuador, riberas del Río Mira, sintipo de *Bulimus cuneus* L. Pfeiffer, 1854) NHMUK 1985073 (H 65,3 mm). Figura 115. A-C: *Protobeliscus haplostylus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846), Azuay, Loja, posible sintipo NHMUK 1987021 (H 38,2 mm); D-F: *Protobeliscus jousseaumei* (Cousin, 1887), Cañar, entre Azogues y Molobog, sintipo RBINS MT.3845 (H 28,3 mm).

Protobeliscus major (K. Miller, 1878) (Figs. 116A, 125)

Stenogyra (*Obeliscus*) *cuneus* var. *major* Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 196; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 6 fig. 3a. "Val de Pilaton".

Distribution. Pichincha: Río Pilatón valley (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Figure 116. A: *Protobeliscus major* (K. Miller, 1878), Pichincha, Río Pilatón valley, original figure in Miller (1879): pl. 6 fig. 3a (H 86 mm); B: *?Pseudopeas viviparum* (K. Miller, 1878), Pichincha, Río Pilatón valley, original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 6 fig. 4 (H 6 mm). Figure 117. A-C: *Protobeliscus pairensis* (Higgins, 1872), Guayas, Paila? syntype NHMUK 1880.12..3.2 (H 47 mm); D-F: *Protobeliscus riparius* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854), Ecuador, banks of the Río Mira, syntype NHMUK 1987018 (H 55 mm).

Figura 116. A: *Protobeliscus major* (K. Miller, 1878), Pichincha, valle del río Pilatón, figura original en Miller (1879): lám. 6 fig. 3a (H 86 mm); B: *?Pseudopeas viviparum* (K. Miller, 1878), Pichincha, valle del río Pilatón, figura original en MILLER (1879): lám. 6 fig. 4 (H 6 mm). Figura 117. A-C: *Protobeliscus pairensis* (Higgins, 1872), Guayas, ¿Paila? sintipo NHMUK 1880.12..3.2 (H 47 mm); D-F: *Protobeliscus riparius* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854), Ecuador, orillas del río Mira, sintipo NHMUK 1987018 (H 55 mm).

Protobeliscus pairensis (Higgins, 1872) (Fig. 117A-C)

Rumina (*Stenogyra*) *pairensis* Higgins, 1872, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 40: 685, pl. 56 fig. 1. "Paira".
Syntype NHMUK 1880.12.3.2 (1).

Distribution. Guayas: Paila?

Remarks. Localities with the name 'Paira' could not be found with modern gazetteers. The name could be a misspelling for Paila, which is in Prov. Guayas.

Figure 118. Distribution of Achatinidae (Subulininae) species.
 Figura 118. Distribución de especies de Achatinidae (Subulininae).

Protobeliscus riparius (L. Pfeiffer, 1854) (Figs. 117D-F, 125)

Bulimus riparius Pfeiffer, 1854, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 20: 155. “cum praecedente [in ripis fluvii Mira, reipublicae Aequatoris]”. Syntypes NHMUK 1987018 (3).

Distribution. Carchi: valley Río Mira (PFEIFFER, 1854a).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Remarks. This taxon has sometimes been considered as a subspecies of *Bulimus cuneus* L. Pfeiffer, 1854, described from the same locality. It is herein tentatively treated as a separate species, but needs more research to ascertain this status. Also recorded from Colombia and Peru (LINARES & VERA, 2012; RAMÍREZ ET AL., 2003); especially the latter needs further confirmation.

Genus *Pseudopeas* Putzeys, 1899

Pseudopeas Putzeys, 1899, *Ann. Soc. R. Malac. Belgique*, 34: lviii. Type species by subsequent designation (PILSBRY, 1906 [1906-1907]: 114) *Pseudopeas pulchellum* Putzeys, 1899.

Remarks. PILSBRY (1906 [1906-1907]) mentioned that the apical sculpture consists of very fine spiral lines when seen under a microscope. This genus was described for species from Africa and the single South American species is an enigmatic member in Pilsbry’s classification. See remarks below.

?*Pseudopeas viviparum* (K. Miller, 1878) (Fig. 116B)

Opeas viviparum Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 197; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 6 fig. 4. “Val de Pilaton”. Type material not located.

Figure 119. A-C: *Rhodea aequatoria* da Costa, 1899, Imbabura, Paramba, lectotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.144 (H 21.8 mm); D-F: *Rhodea cousini* Jousseume 1900, Pichincha, Guallabamba [Guayllabamba], holotype MNHN-IM-2000-4636 (H 40.4 mm).

Figura 119. A-C: *Rhodea aequatoria* da Costa, 1899, Imbabura, Paramba, lectotipo NHMUK 1907.11.21.144 (H 21,8 mm); D-F: *Rhodea cousini* Jousseume 1900, Pichincha, Guallabamba [Guayllabamba], holotipo MNHN-IM-2000-4636 (H 40,4 mm).

Distribution. Pichincha: Pilatón valley (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. PILSBRY (1906 [1906-1907]: 216) classified this species within this genus on account of Miller's description of viviparity. The shape of the shell resembles some *Bulimulid* species; if the protoconch sculpture consists of fine spiral striae it could belong to the genus *Bostryx* Troschel, 1847; however, viviparity is not known in that group. Unfortunately, as long as Miller's type material is not found, this is a *nomen dubium*.

Genus *Rhodea* H. Adams & A. Adams, 1855

Rhodea Adams & Adams, 1855, *The genera of Recent Mollusca*: 135. Type species by original designation *Achatina californica* L. Pfeiffer, 1846.

Rhodea aequatoria S.I. da Costa, 1899 (Figs. 119A-C, 125)

Rhodea aequatoria S.I. da Costa, 1899, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 3: 304, figs 3-4. "Paramba". Lectotype (GREGO *ET AL.*, 2007: 22) NHMUK 1907.11.21.144 (1); paralectotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.145 (1).

? *Rhodea equatorensis* Jousseume, 1900, *Bull. Soc. Philom. Paris*, (9) 2: 37, pl. 1 fig. 17 [sic, 16]. "Los Puentes". Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-4637.

Distribution. Imbabura: Paramba (TL); Pichincha: Los Puentes (JOUSSEUME, 1900).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. GREGO *ET AL.* (2007) have revised this genus and considered Jousseume's type not fully-grown; because its type locality is in the same region, they considered it as a junior synonym of da Costa's taxon.

Figure 120. *Subulina octona* (Bruguière, 1789). Sucumbios: Nueva Loja. iNaturalist 69032240.
Figura 120. *Subulina octona* (Bruguière, 1789). Sucumbios: Nueva Loja. iNaturalist 69032240.

Rhodea cousini Jousseau, 1900 (Figs. 119D-F, 125)

Rhodea cousini Jousseau, 1900, *Bull. Soc. Philom. Paris*, (9) 2: 36, pl. 1 fig. 15. "Guallabamba y entre pacto [Pacto] y Pachijal, Equateur". Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-4636.

Distribution. Imbabura: El Chontal nature reserve, near Chontal river (CORREOSO, 2010); Pichincha: Guallabamba [Guayllabamba] (TL); near Pachijal (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Genus *Subulina* H. Beck, 1837

Achatina (*Subulina*) Beck, 1837 [1837-1838], *Index moll.*: 76. Type species by subsequent designation *Bulimus octonus* Bruguière, 1789.

❖ *Subulina octona* (Bruguière, 1789) (Figs. 120, 125)

Bulimus octonus Bruguière, 1789 [1789-1792], *Encycl. method.*, 1: 325. "les îles Antilles".

Subulina guayaquilensis K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 126, pl. 13 fig. 5. "Guayaquil".

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (MILLER, 1879); Durán, off Guayaquil (■ANSP 148466); Pedro Carbo, between Guayaquil and Manta (■ANSP 180310); Pastaza: Montalvo (■ANSP 306769); near Andoas, Montoloo (■MCZ 226459); Sucumbios: Cuyabeno Nature Reserve, near Cuyabeno lodge (Roosen, pers. obs. 2019); Nueva Loja (obs. iNaturalist 69032240, 2021).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142], Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178], Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214],

Remarks. The first record of this species for the Galápagos was given by ODHNER (1951), who mentioned "some specimens introduced with cultivated plants" for San Cristóbal Island. Now known from San Cristóbal and Santa Cruz Island (agricultural areas; MIQUEL & HERRERA, 2014). Also in many other countries in the Neotropics and elsewhere. See also ROBINSON (1999) and BIELER & SLAPCINSKY (2000) for discussion on the origin of this species.

Figure 121. A-C: *Synapterpes auratus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846), unknown locality, syntype NHMUK 1987019 (H 26.7 mm); D-F: *Synapterpes visendus* (Hidalgo, 1869), Napo, Baeza, lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-28157 (H 32 mm). Figure 122. *Zoniferella albobalearata* (Dunker, 1882). Colombia: near Pasto. A: original figure in DUNKER (1882): pl. 11 figs 7-8 (H 13 mm); B-D: Pichincha, Los Puentes, syntype of *Mesembrinus vesperus* Jousseau, 1887, MNHN-IM-2000-28158 (H 18.4 mm).

Figura 121. A-C: *Synapterpes auratus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846), *localidad desconocida, sintipo* NHMUK 1987019 (H 26,7 mm); D-F: *Synapterpes visendus* (Hidalgo, 1869), *Napo, Baeza, lectotipo* MNHN-IM-2000-28157 (H 32 mm). *Figura 122.* *Zoniferella albobalearata* (Dunker, 1882). *Colombia: cerca de Pasto.* A: *figura original en DUNKER* (1882): lám. 11 figs. 7-8 (H 13 mm); B-D: *Pichincha, Los Puentes, sintipo de Mesembrinus vesperus* Jousseau, 1887, MNHN-IM-2000-28158 (H 18,4 mm).

Genus *Synapterpes* Pilsbry, 1896

Synapterpes Pilsbry, 1896, *Nautilus*, 10: 46. Type species by original designation *Bulimus hanleyi* Pfeiffer, 1846.

Synapterpes auratus (L. Pfeiffer, 1846) (Figs. 121A-C, 125)

Bulimus auratus Pfeiffer, 1846, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 14: 32. "Locality unknown". Syntypes NHMUK 1987019 (3).

Distribution. Napo: Baeza (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Pichincha: Los Puentes near Guala (COUSIN, 1887); km 52 Quito-Nanegalito (obs. iNaturalist 9244832, 2017).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Also reported from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 217).

Synapterpes visendus (Hidalgo, 1869) (Figs. 121D-F, 125)

Bulimus visendus Hidalgo, 1869, *J. de Conchyl.*, 17: 50, pl. 5 fig. 8. "Baeza, Reipublicae Aequatoris".
Lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-28157 (BREURE, 1975: 1153); paralectotypes MNCN 15.05/3163 (2),
15.05/3208 (4), 15.05/3207 (1), 15.05/76230 (1).

Distribution. Napo: Baeza (TL); Pichincha: Los Puentes (COUSIN, 1887); near San Miguel de los Bancos (obs. iNaturalist 59311912, 2020).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Careful field collections could show that this and the previous species are but colour forms.

Genus *Zoniferella* Pilsbry, 1906

Zoniferella Pilsbry, 1906 [1906-1907], *Man. Conch.*, (2) 18: 233. Type species by original designation: *Bulimus albobalteatus* Dunker, 1882.

Zoniferella albobalteata (Dunker, 1882) (Figs. 122, 125)

Bulimus albobalteatus Dunker, 1882, *Jahrb. deutsch. Malak. Ges.*, 9: 378, pl. 11 figs 7-8. "prope Pasto Columbiae". Type material not located.

Mesembrinus vesperus Jousseume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 168, pl. 3 fig. 2. "Los Puentes, près Quito". Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-28158. [New synonymy].

Synapterpes (*Zoniferella*) *riveti* Germain, 1907, *Bull. Mus. Nat. Hist. Nat.*, 13: 60, fig. "Cerro de San Tadeo, chemin de Pachajal". Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-4672. [New synonymy].

Distribution. Ecuador: without precise locality (NHM); Pichincha: Los Puentes (TL *vesperus*); near Pachijal (TL *riveti*); Tungurahua: Rio Pastaza, Yunquille (■MCZ 142217).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. The differences between Dunker's species and the two taxa of Jousseume and Germain are so slight, that we fail to see why they should be kept separate.

Zoniferella bizonalis (Germain, 1907) (Figs. 123, 124, 125)

Synapterpes (*Zoniferella*) *riveti* var. *bizonalis* Germain, 1907, *Bull. Mus. Nat. Hist. Nat.*, 13: 61. "Cerro de San Tadeo, chemin de Pachajal". Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-4671 (2).

Synapterpes bicingulatus Fulton, 1908, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 8: 84, fig. 3. "Ecuador". Syntype NHMUK 1908.7.6.89 (1). [New synonymy].

Distribution. Pichincha: near Pachajal [Pachijal] (TL); San Miguel de los Bancos (obs. iNaturalist, 38589146, 2020).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Tentatively separated from the former species because of its different body whorl coloration. Further study is needed to confirm its identity as a separate species.

Comments on the family. In the literature the following species related to this family has been mentioned for Ecuador:

Figures 123, 124. *Zoniferella bizonalis* (Germain, 1907). 123: Pichincha, near Pachajal [Pachijal]; A, B: syntype MNHN-IM-2000-4671 (H 21.1 mm); C-E: syntype of *Synapterpes bicingulatus* Fulton, 1908, NHMUK 1908.7.6.89 (H 20.1 mm); 124: Pichincha, Nanegalito, living specimen (photo: Adrián González Guillén).

Figuras 123, 124. Zoniferella bizonalis (Germain, 1907). 123: Pichincha, cerca de Pachajal [Pachijal]; A, B: sintipo MNHN-IM-2000-4671 (H 21,1 mm); C-E: sintipo de *Synapterpes bicingulatus* Fulton, 1908, NHMUK 1908.7.6.89 (H 20,1 mm); 124: Pichincha, Nanegalito, ejemplares vivos (foto: Adrián González Guillén).

- *Opeas guatemalensis* Strebel, 1882 (in STREBEL & PFEFFER, 1882. *Beitr. Kenntn. mexik. Land-Süssw.-Conchyl.*, 5: 105, pl. 7 fig. 2a) was described from Guatemala and was mentioned from Ecuador by LINARES & VERA (2012: 218; as *Leptopeas guatemalense*) without clear reference or voucher.

Family STREPTAXIDAE J.E. Gray, 1860

Remarks. A large family distributed in tropical and subtropical areas in Africa, Asia and the Neotropics. For an overview of genera, distribution and phylogenetic data, see SUTCHARIT *ET AL.*, (2010). For literature on Neotropical taxa, see SIMONE (2006, 2013), BARBOSA *ET AL.* (2008).

Genus *Martinella* Jousseume, 1887

Martinella Jousseume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 173. Type species by monotypy *Martinella martinella* Jousseume, 1887.

Figure 125. Distribution of Achatinidae (Subulininae) species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 125. Distribución de especies de Achatinidae (Subulininae). Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecoregiones.

Martinella martinella Jousseaume, 1887 (Figs. 126, 136)

Martinella martinella Jousseaume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 173, pl. 3 fig. 14. "San-Nicolas, canton de Mégia". Type material not located.

Distribution. Pichincha: San Nicolas (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. This species, which has not been recollected after its description, was originally found at a now densely populated area. Possibly it has become extinct. It is considered as a *nomen dubium*.

Family SCOLODONTIDAE H.B. Baker, 1925

Remarks. The systematic position of this family has been redefined by HAUSDORF (2006). Recent phylogenetic research on this family can be found in SAADI & WADE (2019); further molecular research will undoubtedly lead to changes in classification in this relatively understudied group. For literature on South American taxa see CUEZZO & MIRANDA (2009), MIQUEL & RODRIGUEZ (2015), MIQUEL & BUNGARTZ (2017), WENDEBOURG & HAUSDORF (2019), SALVADOR & CAVALLARI (2020).

Genus *Drepanostomella* Bourguignat, 1890

Drepanostomella Bourguignat, 1890, *Moll. d'Afr. équat.*: 42. Type species by monotypy *Helix ammoniformis* d'Orbigny, 1835.

Figure 126. *Martinella martinella* Jousseume, 1887. Pichincha: San Nicolás. Original figure in JOUSSEAUME (1887): pl. 3 fig. 14 (D 3.5 mm). Figure 127. *Drepanostomella excisa* (L. Pfeiffer, 1855). Colombia: Santa Ana. Syntype NHMUK 20130191 (D 3.9 mm).

Figura 126. *Martinella martinella* Jousseume, 1887. Pichincha: San Nicolás. Figura original en JOUSSEAUME (1887): lám. 3 fig. 14 (D 3,5 mm). Figura 127. *Drepanostomella excisa* (L. Pfeiffer, 1855). Colombia: Santa Ana. Sintipo NHMUK 20130191 (D 3,9 mm).

■ *Drepanostomella excisa* (L. Pfeiffer, 1855) (Figs. 127, 136)

Helix excisa Pfeiffer, 1855, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 22: 54. "Santa Ana, New Granada". Syntypes NHMUK 20130191 (4).

Distribution. Chimborazo: Huigra (■ ANSP 322270).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Although the ANSP museum specimen is identified as *Drepanostomella excisa* in RAMÍREZ (1993), the catalogue entry of the ANSP reads *Drepanostomella* sp. without a specific identification, and its locality reads "Huigra". Current locality adapted from another *Drepanostomella* collected in the same year by S.N. Rhoads. This species, described from Dept. Antioquia, Colombia, is not mentioned by LINARES & VERA (2012).

Drepanostomella lyzarzaburui (Jousseume, 1887) (Figs. 128, 136)

Ammonoceras lyzarzaburui Jousseume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 174, pl. 3 fig. 17. "San-Nicolas, canton de Mégia". Syntypes MNHN-IM-2000-25754 (2), 25755 (4), RBINS MT.3836 (3).

Distribution. Pichincha: San Nicolas (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Genus *Guestieria* Crosse, 1872

Guestieria Crosse, 1872, *J. de Conchyl.*, 20: 199. Type species by monotypy *Helix powisiana* L. Pfeiffer, 1848.

Guestieria locardi Jousseume, 1887 (Figs. 129, 136)

Guestieria locardi Jousseume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 175, pl. 3 fig. 13. "Los Puantès, canton de Quito". Syntypes MNHN-IM-2000-25757 (9), RBINS MT.3835 (3).

Distribution. Ecuador: Mapoto, near Rio Pastaza (REIBISCH, 1896), Napo: Baeza (■UF 37410), Pichincha: Los Puentes (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. The locality 'Mapoto' could not be located using modern gazetteers. It cannot be excluded that material from the eastern side of the Andes will shown to be a distinct species.

Guestieria martinida Jousseume, 1887 (Figs. 130, 136)

Guestieria martinida Jousseume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 176, pl. 3 fig. 19. "San-Nicolas, canton de Mégia, province de Pichincha". Syntypes RBINS MT.3830 (12), MNHN-IM-2000-25756 (1).

Distribution. Pichincha: San Nicolas (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Guestieria powisiana (L. Pfeiffer, 1848) (Figs. 131, 136)

Helix powisiana Pfeiffer, 1848, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 2: 34. Nom nov. for *Helix involuta* Pfeiffer, 1845 not Thomae, 1845. "The mountains of Quendeu, New Granada" [now Quindío, a province of Colombia]. Type material not located.

Distribution. Azuay: Lago Zurucuchu, 11 miles west of Cuenca (FMNH 106267); Guayas: Guayaquil (PFEIFFER, 1853b).

Ecoregion. Northern Andean páramo [NT1006].

Remarks. The historical locality "Guayaquil" is likely a proxy for a sampled locality elsewhere and the record by Pfeiffer should be considered as an inaccurate locality. More wide-spread in Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 229).

Genus *Happia* Bourguignat, 1890

Happia Bourguignat, 1890, *Moll. d'Afr. équat.*: 39. Nom. nov. for *Ammonoceras* Pfeiffer, 1855 not Lamarck, 1822. Type species by typification of replaced name *Helix ammonoceras* L. Pfeiffer, 1854.

Figure 128. *Drepanostomella lyzarzaburui* (Jousseau, 1887). Pichincha: San Nicolás. Syntipo RBINS MT.3836 (D 2.4 mm). Figure 129. *Guestieria locardi* Jousseau, 1887. Pichincha: Los Puentes. Syntipo RBINS MT.3835 (D 8.4 mm). Figure 130. *Guestieria martinida* Jousseau, 1887. Pichincha: San Nicolás. Syntipo RBINS MT.3830 (D 2.3 mm). Figure 131. *Guestieria powisiana* (L. Pfeiffer, 1848). Azuay: 11 miles W Cuenca. FMNH 106267 (D 8 mm).

Figura 128. *Drepanostomella lyzarzaburui* (Jousseau, 1887). Pichincha: San Nicolás. Sintipo RBINS MT.3836 (D 2,4 mm). Figura 129. *Guestieria locardi* Jousseau, 1887. Pichincha: Los Puentes. Sintipo RBINS MT.3835 (D 8,4 mm). Figura 130. *Guestieria martinida* Jousseau, 1887. Pichincha: San Nicolás. Sintipo RBINS MT.3830 (D 2,3 mm). Figura 131. *Guestieria powisiana* (L. Pfeiffer, 1848). Azuay: 11 millas al O de Cuenca. FMNH 106267 (D 8 mm).

Figure 132. *Happia baezensis* (Hidalgo, 1869). Napo: Beaza. Syntype MNCN 15.05/3304 (D 16.9 mm). Figure 133. *Happia cyclina* (Cousin, 1887). Cotopaxi: Pucayacu. Syntype RBINS MT.3839 (D 17.2 mm).

Figura 132. *Happia baezensis* (Hidalgo, 1869). Napo: Beaza. Sintipo MNCN 15.05/3304 (D 16.9 mm).

Figura 133. *Happia cyclina* (Cousin, 1887). Cotopaxi: Pucayacu. Sintipo RBINS MT.3839 (D 17.2 mm).

Happia baezensis (Hidalgo, 1869) (Figs. 132, 136)

Helix baezensis Hidalgo, 1869, *J. de Conchyl.*, 17: 411. "Baeza". Syntypes MNCN 15.05/3304 (2), MNCN 15.05/3177 (1).

Distribution. Napo: Beaza (TL); Pichincha: Los Puentes (COUSIN, 1887).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. This taxon has been synonymised in the literature with *Happia cuzcana* (Philippi, 1869), a species from southern Peru. This needs additional research and for the time being we keep Hidalgo's taxon as a valid species.

Happia cyclina (Cousin, 1887) (Figs. 133, 136)

Ammonoceras cyclina Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 245, pl. 4 fig. 6. Not given. Syntypes RBINS MT.3839 (2).

Figure 134. *Hattia flora* (L. Pfeiffer, 1852). Colombia: unknown Andean locality. Syntype NHMUK 20190598 (D 31.4 mm). Figure 135. *Scolodonta guayaquilensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854). Guayas: Babahoya. Syntype NHMUK 20190599 (D 10.5 mm).

Figura 134. *Hattia flora* (L. Pfeiffer, 1852). Colombia: *localidad andina desconocida*. Sintipo NHMUK 20190598 (D 31,4 mm). *Figura 135.* *Scolodonta guayaquilensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854). Guayas: Babahoya. Sintipo NHMUK 20190599 (D 10,5 mm).

Distribution. Cotopaxi: Pucayacu (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Cousin remarked “Cette espèce, dont je n’ai pu me procurer que la coquille de trois individus, présente une taille intermédiaire entre l’*A. cuzcana* et l’*A. flora*” [This species, of which I was only able to obtain the shells of three individuals, has an intermediate size between *A. cuzcana* and *A. flora*]. A lot with two specimens was found in the Dautzenberg collection, with a label reading “Hac. Puca Yacu près Quevedo”.

Hattia flora (L. Pfeiffer, 1852) (Figs. 134, 136)

Helix flora Pfeiffer in Reeve, 1852 [1852-1854], *Conch. Icon.*, 7: pl. 96 fig. 534. “Andes of Colombia”. Syntypes NHMUK 20190598 (3).

Figure 136. Distribution of Streptaxidae and Scolodontidae species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 136. Distribución de especies de Streptaxidae y Scolodontidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Distribution. Pastaza: Puyo (■ ANSP 170726, MCZ 160604); Mera (■ ANSP 306779, MCZ 145287); Pichincha: Los Puentes near Gualea (COUSIN, 1887); Nanegal (MARTENS, 1885a); Cerro de San Tadeo, Pachijal (GERMAIN, 1910).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. The allocation by LINARES & VERA (2012: 230) of this species seems solely based on the name of Colombia in the original publication, without taking into account that this does not necessarily imply the current country. They did not mention any specific localities for Colombia and based on current data the species is considered an Ecuadorian endemic.

Genus *Scolodonta* Doering, 1875

Streptaxis (*Scolodonta*) Doering, 1875, *Bol. Acad. Cienc. Cordoba*, 1: 438. Type species by monotypy *Streptaxis semperi* Doering, 1875.

? *Scolodonta guayaquilensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854) (Figs. 135, 136)

Helix guayaquilensis Pfeiffer, 1854, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 20: 152. "ad Babahoya, Guayaquil". Syntypes NHM 20190599 (3).

Distribution. Guayas: Babahoya (TL); Pichincha: Los Puentes (■ ANSP 67315) Tungurahua: Baños (■ FMNH 107869)

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. The generic placement of this species needs confirmation.

Figure 137. *Systrophia entodonta* (L. Pfeiffer, 1859). Azuay: Cuenca. Possible syntype NHMUK 20190603 (D 5.7 mm). Figure 138. *Systrophia helicycloides* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Bolivia. Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.1.104 (D 14.6 mm).

Figura 137. *Systrophia entodonta* (L. Pfeiffer, 1859). Azuay: Cuenca. Posible sintipo NHMUK 20190603 (D 5,7 mm). Figura 138. *Systrophia helicycloides* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Bolivia. Sintipo NHMUK 1854.12.1.104 (D 14,6 mm).

Genus *Systrophia* L. Pfeiffer, 1855

Systrophia Pfeiffer, 1855, *Malak. Bl.*, 2: 136. Type species by subsequent designation (H.B. BAKER, 1925: 14) *Helix systrophia* Albers, 1854.

Remarks. See the recent paper by SALVADOR & CAVALLARI (2020) who elucidated the status of some of the Ecuadorian taxa of this genus mentioned in literature.

Systrophia entodonta (L. Pfeiffer, 1859) (Figs. 137, 147)

Helix entodonta Pfeiffer, 1859, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 27: 24, pl. 43 fig. 2. "Cuenca, republic of Ecuador". Possible syntypes NHMUK 20190603 (2).

Distribution. Azuay: Cuenca (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

■ *Systrophia helicycloides* (d'Orbigny, 1835) (Figs. 138, 147)

Helix helicycloides d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 6. "republica Boliviana". Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.104.

Distribution. Azuay: Cuenca (■ FMNH 30516)

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. Further confirmation is required for this Bolivian species. This species has also been reported from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 228).

Systrophia heligmoida (d'Orbigny, 1835) (Figs. 139, 147)

Helix heligmoida d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 2. [Ecuador] "provincia Guayaquilensi (republica Colombiana)". Syntypes NHMUK 1854.12.4.106 (3).

Distribution. Chimborazo: Bucay (■ ANSP 148451); six miles below Huigra (■ ANSP 148475); Guayas: Guayaquil (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Pedro Carbo, between Guayaquil and Manta (■ ANSP 180261); Los Ríos: Balzar (■ UF 36136, UF 36143).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. The historical locality "Guayaquil" is likely a proxy for a sampled locality elsewhere and should be considered as inaccurate. The current classification of this species follows the recent paper by SALVADOR & CAVALLARI (2020).

Systrophia insignis (d'Orbigny, 1835) (Figs. 140, 147)

Helix insignis d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 5. "provincia Guayaquilensi (republica Colombiana)". Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.73 (1).

Distribution. Guayas: near Guayaquil (TL), Tungurahua: Baños (■ ANSP 187920, FMNH 30842, FMNH 126907).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. The historical locality "Guayaquil" is likely a proxy for a sampled locality elsewhere and should be treated as inaccurate. RAMÍREZ (1993) considered the ANSP lot as an unidentified *Wayampia* [= *Scolodonta*] species. We consider this lot only tentatively as this species, as specimens from the eastern side of the Andes may prove to be a distinct species. LINARES & VERA (2012: 228) reported this taxon from Colombia, but also listed Chile as occurrence; this needs further confirmation as this species has not been recognised from Peru.

Systrophia ortonii (Crosse, 1871) (Figs. 141, 147)

Helix ortonii Crosse, 1871, *J. de Conchyl.*, 19: 227. "Republica Aequatoris: in via e Quito ad Napo". Syntypes MNHN-IM-2000-34559 (1), MCZ 156670 (1); possible syntypes RBINS MT.3840 (2).

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Ashuara (■ FMNH 174885, 223546); Cusuimi (■ FMNH 173034); Pastaza: Rio Cotapino, Pacayacu (■ ANSP 268126); Sucumbios: Cuyabeno national park, deep jungle, close to the border with Peru (EC00006).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Figure 139. *Systrophia heligmoida* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Guayas: near Guayaquil. Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.106 (D 12,5 mm). Figure 140. *Systrophia insignis* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Guayas: near Guayaquil. Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.73 (D 8,5 mm). Figure 141. *Systrophia ortonii* (Crosse, 1871). Ecuador: on the way from Quito to Napo. Possible syntype RBINS MT.3840 (D 13,3 mm).

Figura 139. *Systrophia heligmoida* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Guayas: cerca de Guayaquil. Sintipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.106 (D 12,5 mm). Figura 140. *Systrophia insignis* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Guayas: cerca de Guayaquil. Sintipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.73 (D 8,5 mm). Figura 141. *Systrophia ortonii* (Crosse, 1871). Ecuador: camino de Quito a Napo. Posible sintipo RBINS MT.3840 (D 13,3 mm).

Remarks. Although the ANSP record is unconfirmed, it is on the way from Quito to Napo and thus would confirm with the data given by Crosse, who based himself on material collected by Orton.

Systrophia reyrei (Souverbie, 1858) (Fig. 142, 147)

Helix reyrei Souverbie, 1858, *J. de Conchyl.*, 7: 65; pl. 8 fig. 8. [Ecuador] "Guayaquil (Columbia)". Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (TL); Pedro Carbo, between Guayaquil and Manta (■ANSP 180299).

Ecoregion. Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214].

Remarks. The present classification of this species follows SALVADOR & CAVALLARI (2020); this species was classified as *Polygyratia* in BREURE & ARAUJO (2017).

■*Systrophia stenostrepta* (L. Pfeiffer, 1857) (Fig. 143)

Helix stenostrepta Pfeiffer, 1857, *Malak. Bl.*, 3: 260. "Tarapoto in Andibus Peruanis". Type material not located.

Distribution. Ecuador: no specific locality (■ANSP 1451, FMNH 30526, FMNH 30527, FMNH 7247).

Remarks. This Peruvian species could be expected at a locality east of the Andes.

Genus *Zilchistrophia* Weyrauch, 1960

Zilchistrophia Weyrauch, 1960, *Archiv für Moll.*, 89: 26. Type species by original designation: *Zilchistrophia tridentata* Weyrauch, 1960.

Zilchistrophia hilaryae Páll-Gergely, 2014 (Figs. 144, 147)

Zilchistrophia hilaryae Páll-Gergely in Páll-Gergely & Asami, 2014, *ZooKeys*, 453: 3, figs 1B-C, E, 2A-H, 3A-B, 4B, D, F, 5A-D. "Ecuador, Pastaza Province, Chuintsa, transect 7 (samples 360-369)". Holotype NHMUK 20020375/1. Many paratypes in NHM.

Distribution. Pastaza: Chuintas (TL).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Zilchistrophia shiwiarorum Páll-Gergely, 2014 (Figs. 145, 147)

Zilchistrophia shiwiarorum Páll-Gergely in Páll-Gergely & Asami, 2014, *ZooKeys*, 453: 7, figs 1D, F, 2I-M, 3C-D, 4A, C, E. "Ecuador, Pastaza Province, near Nuevo Corrientes, transect 5 (sample 141)". Holotype NHMUK 20020382. Many paratypes in NHM.

Distribution. Pastaza: near Nuevo Corrientes (TL).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Comments on the family. The following Scolodontidae have not yet been reported from the country or whose records are likely misidentifications:

Figure 142. *Systrophia reyrei* (Souverbie, 1858) “Ecuador”, Coll. Azpeitia, MNCN 15.05/76235 (D 5.3 mm), reproduced from BREURE & ARAUJO (2017). Figure 143. *Systrophia stenostrepta* (L. Pfeiffer, 1857). Ecuador. ANSP 1415 (D 9.8 mm). Figure 144. *Zilchistrophia hilaryae* Páll-Gergely, 2014. Pastaza: Chuintas. Holotype NHMUK 20020375/1 (D 5 mm).

Figura 142. *Systrophia reyrei* (Souverbie, 1858) “Ecuador”, Coll. Azpeitia, MNCN 15.05/76235 (D 5,3 mm), reproducido de BREURE & ARAUJO (2017). Figura 143. *Systrophia stenostrepta* (L. Pfeiffer, 1857). Ecuador. ANSP 1415 (D 9,8 mm). Figura 144. *Zilchistrophia hilaryae* Páll-Gergely, 2014. Pastaza: Chuintas. Holotipo NHMUK 20020375/1 (D 5 mm).

- ■ *Systrophia orbicula* (d’Orbigny, 1835) was described as *Helix orbicula* d’Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 6, from “republica Boliviana”. There is one lot from Imbabura: Paramba (■FMNH 157836) which is likely a misidentification.

- *Systrophia cereonitens* Haas (1951, *Fieldiana*, Zool. 31: 533, fig. 117) was described from Peru, Dept. Cajamarca, San Ignacio, which is close to the Ecuadorian border. The holotype is FMNH 30924 (Fig. 146).

Family SUCCINEIDAE H. Beck, 1837

Remarks. This circumglobally family has many described species, most of which are anatomically unknown (SCHILEYKO, 2007); we refrain from using the subgenera used

Figure 145. *Zilchistrophia shiwiarorum* Páll-Gergely, 2014. Pastaza: near Nuevo Corrientes. Holotype NHMUK 20020382 (D up to 3.9 mm). Figure 146. *Systrophia cereonitens* Haas, 1951. Perú: San Ignacio. Holotype FMNH 30924 (D 14.5 mm).

Figura 145. *Zilchistrophia shiwiarorum* Páll-Gergely, 2014. Pastaza: cerca de Nuevo Corrientes. Holotipo NHMUK 20020382 (D hasta 3,9 mm). Figura 146. *Systrophia cereonitens* Haas, 1951. Perú: San Ignacio. Holotipo FMNH 30924 (D 14,5 mm).

by this author. Phylogenetic research on this group has been published by e.g. DUTRA-CLARKE ET AL. (2001), RUNDELL ET AL. (2004). Recent literature on South American species comprise GARCIA ET AL. (2012), ARRUDA ET AL. (2016), VIDIGAL ET AL. (2018). Note that species may be difficult to recognise on the basis of external morphology alone, and the classification of species given below will likely be altered after a revision has been done using anatomical and molecular data.

Genus *Omalonyx* d'Orbigny, 1838

Helix (*Succinea*) division *Omalonyx* d'Orbigny, 1838 [1834-1847], *Voyage Amér. mérid.*, 5 (3): 229. Type species by subsequent designation (PFEIFFER, 1848b: 549) *Helix unguis* d'Orbigny, 1836.

Omalonyx geayi Tillier, 1980 (Figs. 148, 151)

Omalonyx geayi Tillier, 1980, *Mém. Mus. Nat. Hist. Nat., Zool.*, (n.s.) 118: 87, figs 69-71, pl. 5 fig. 6. "Kaw". Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-35820; paratypes MNHN-IM-2000-35821 (10), -35822 (2).

Distribution. Sucumbios: Limoncocha (ARRUDA ET AL., 2016).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Figure 147. Distribution map of Scolodontidae species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 147. Mapa de distribución de especies de Scolodontidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Remarks. This species from French Guiana has also been recorded from Bolivia, Brazil, Suriname and Trinidad. For a picture of a living specimen, see MASSEMIN *ET AL.* (2009): 397.

Genus *Succinea* Draparnaud, 1801

Succinea Draparnaud, 1801, *Tableau moll. France*: 32. Type species by subsequent designation (FLEMING, 1822: 574) *Helix putris* Linnaeus, 1758.

Succinea aequinoctialis d'Orbigny, 1838 (Figs. 149, 151)

Succinea aequinoctialis d'Orbigny, 1838 [1834-1847], *Voyage Amér. mérid.*, 5 (3): 231. "les lieux humides des environs de Guayaquil, république de l'Équateur" Syntypes NHMUK 1854.12.4.46 (6).

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (COUSIN, 1887); Duran, off Guayaquil (■ANSP 148468); near Santa Elena, Ballenita (■ANSP 195209); near Palmar (■UF 139055, 139091); near Progeso (■UF 139103, 139109); near Zapotal (■UF 139107); Manabí: Jipijapa (■UF 139037).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178], Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214].

Remarks. Also recorded from Colombia and Peru (LINARES & VERA, 2012; RAMÍREZ *ET AL.*, 2003).

Succinea marianita (Cousin, 1887) (Figs. 150A-C, 151)

Neritostoma marianita Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 236, pl. 4 figs 5-5bis. "San-Nicolas". Syntypes RBINS MT.3837 (15).

Distribution. Pichincha: San Nicolas (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Cousin wrote “se trouve comme la précédente à San-Nicolas” [occurs with the preceding [*Neritostoma martini*] at San Nicolas].

Succinea martini (Jousseau, 1887) (Fig. 150D, 151)

Neritostoma martini Jousseau, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 169, pl. 3 fig. 12. “Saint-Nicolas, canton de Mégia”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Pichincha: San Nicolas (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. COUSIN (1887: 236) mentioned the same locality as “San-Nicolas, canton de Ubégia”; this might be a reading error from the manuscript and could not be found in modern gazetteers. The only name ‘San Nicolas’ associated with Cantón de Mejía is a hacienda of that name located in Sangolquí.

Family STROPHOCHEILIDAE Pilsbry, 1902

Remarks. This South American family has its main distribution in Brazil and adjacent countries. It is herein considered to include *Megalobulimus*, a genus which was placed in a separate family by some authors (e.g., SCHILEYKO, 1999b). A revision of the Strophocheilidae (s.l.) was published by BEQUAERT (1948). Fossil records for this family see MIQUEL & MANCENIDO (1999), SALVADOR ET AL. (2018). Anatomical and phylogenetic data in JARAMILLO ET AL. (2014).

Genus *Megalobulimus* K. Miller, 1878

Bulimus (*Megalobulimus*) Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 172. Type species by monotypy *Bulimus* (*Borus*) *garciamoreni* Miller, 1878.

Megalobulimus garciamoreni (K. Miller, 1878) (Figs. 152, 151)

Bulimus (*Borus*) *garciamoreni* Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 172, pl. 1 fig. 1. No type locality given [Ecuador from title of paper] and type material not located.

Distribution. Esmeraldas: Without specific locality (MILLER, 1879); Los Ríos: Pisagua (MILLER, 1878); Pichincha: Nanegal (GERMAIN, 1907); valley Río Pilaton (TL); Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Santo Domingo de los Colorados (GERMAIN, 1907).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145], Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Remarks. In all specimens we have seen (Roosen, unpublished data), the height of the spire is exceeded by the height of the aperture. In *Megalobulimus popelairianus* this is the other way around. *M. garciamoreni* can be separated from the Peruvian *M. thammianus* (von Martens, 1877) by the same criteria. Moreover, the Andes clearly separates *M. garciamoreni* populations from the Amazonian *M. popelairianus*. The two species were nevertheless synonymized by MIQUEL & MANCENIDO (1999).

Figure 148. *Omalonyx geayi* Tillier, 1980. French Guyane: Kaw. Paratype MNHN-IM-2000-35822 (L 13.4 mm). Figure 149. *Succinea aequinoctialis* d'Orbigny, 1838. Guayas: near Guayaquil. Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.46 (H 18.8 mm). Figure 150. A-C: *Succinea marianita* (Cousin, 1887), Pichincha, San Nicolas, syntype RBINS MT.3837 (H 6.6 mm); D: *Succinea martini* (Jousseaume, 1887), Pichincha, San Nicolas, original figure in JOUSSEAUME (1887): pl. 3 fig. 12; (H 14 mm).

Figura 148. *Omalonyx geayi* Tillier, 1980. Guayana francesa: Kaw. Paratipo MNHN-IM-2000-35822 (L 13,4 mm). Figura 149. *Succinea aequinoctialis* d'Orbigny, 1838. Guayas: cerca de Guayaquil. Sintipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.46 (H 18,8 mm). Figura 150. A-C: *Succinea marianita* (Cousin, 1887), Pichincha, San Nicolás, sintipo RBINS MT.3837 (H 6,6 mm); D: *Succinea martini* (Jousseaume, 1887), Pichincha, San Nicolás, figura original en JOUSSEAUME (1887): lám. 3 fig. 12 (H 14 mm).

Figure 151. Distribution map of Succineidae and Strophocheilidae species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 151. Mapa de distribución de especies de Succineidae y Strophocheilidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecoregiones

Megalobulimus popelairianus (Nyst, 1845) (Figs. 153, 154, 151)

Bulimus popelairianus Nyst, 1845, *Bull. Acad. R. Sci. Belgique*, 12 (2): 151, pl. 3 fig. 5. "South America". Syntype RBINS MT.2890 (1).

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Ashuara (■FMNH 187290); Cusuimi (■FMNH 173053, 187294); Napo: without accurate locality (COUSIN, 1887); La Selva Jungle Lodge, Rio Napo (■ANSP 3911732); Rio Jatunyacu (■MCZ 64953); Pastaza: Nuevo Corrientes (NHMUK 20200350, 20200351); Puyo (GOLDBERG, 1985); Sucumbios: near Turin (■ANSP 361467).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. See above. Also reported from Colombia and Peru (RAMÍREZ *ET AL.*, 2003; LINARES & VERA, 2012).

Comments on the family. In literature the following species related to this family have also been mentioned as occurring in Ecuador:

- *Bulimus valenciennesii* L. Pfeiffer, 1842 (*Symb. Helic.*, 2: 52). This Brazilian species was mentioned from Ecuador by LINARES & VERA (2012: 236) without further evidence.

Family ORTHALICIDAE Martens in Albers, 1860

Remarks. The classification of this and the following four families—belonging to the superfamily Orthalicoidea—have been revised on the basis of molecular research (BREURE & ROMERO, 2012). The Orthalicidae are strictly Neotropical, occurring in southern Florida, the Caribbean, Central America, and in South America south to

Figure 152. *Megalobulimus garciamoreni* (K. Miller, 1878). Ecuador. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 4 Figure 1. Figures 153, 154. *Megalobulimus popelairianus* (Nyst, 1845). 153: South America, unknown locality; syntype RBINS MT.2850 (H 130 mm); the specimen was scanned by Dr C. d'Udekem d'Acoz using the CT facility (DISSCO-FED project) of the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences; 154: unknown locality, living specimen (photo: Adrián González Guillén).

Figura 152. Megalobulimus garciamoreni (K. Miller, 1878). Ecuador. *Figura original en MILLER* (1879): lám. 4 *Figura 1. Figuras 153, 154. Megalobulimus popelairianus* (Nyst, 1845). 153: América del Sur, localidad desconocida; sintipo RBINS MT.2850 (H 130 mm); el espécimen fue escaneado por el Dr. C. d'Udekem d'Acoz utilizando la instalación CT (proyecto DISSCO-FED) del Real Instituto Belga de Ciencias Naturales; 154: localidad desconocida, ejemplar vivo (foto: Adrián González Guillén).

Bolivia. Revisionary work has been done by PILSBRY (1899) and STREBEL (1909). Anatomical studies were presented by *e.g.* BREURE (1978), BREURE & COPPOIS (1978), BREURE & ESKENS (1981), BREURE & SCHOUTEN (1985). Recent studies on type material were NEUBERT & JANSSEN (2004), BREURE (2013a, 2016a) and BREURE & ABLETT (2015). Note that in southern Colombia species of *Hemibulimus* occur (see PILSBRY 1909 [1908-1910: 114-117]); one of the species previously regarded as a *Hemibulimus*, Pfeiffer's *Achatina magnifica*, is now placed in *Clathrorthalicus* Strebel, 1909.

Figure 155. *Clathrorthalicus corydon* (Crosse, 1869). Ecuador: unknown locality. Syntypes MNCN 15.05/8077 (A, B: H 42.1 mm), MNCN 15.05/21868 (C, D: H 38.2 mm). Figure 156. A, B: *Clathrorthalicus magnificus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1848), Ecuador, unknown locality, syntype NHMUK 20100508 (H 46.6 mm); C-E: *Clathrorthalicus phoebus* (Pfeiffer, 1863), Ecuador, unknown locality, lectotype NHMUK 1975143 (H 30.5 mm).

Figura 155. *Clathrorthalicus corydon* (Crosse, 1869). Ecuador: localidad desconocida. Sintipos MNCN 15.05/8077 (A, B: H 42,1 mm), MNCN 15.05/21868 (C, D: H 38,2 mm). Figura 156. A, B: *Clathrorthalicus magnificus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1848), Ecuador, localidad desconocida, sintipo NHMUK 20100508 (H 46,6 mm); C-E: *Clathrorthalicus phoebus* (Pfeiffer, 1863), Ecuador, localidad desconocida, lectotipo NHMUK 1975143 (H 30,5 mm).

Genus *Clathrorthalicus* Strebel, 1909

Orthalicus (*Clathrorthalicus*) Strebel, 1909, *Jahrb. Hamb. Wiss. Anst.*, 26, Beiheft, 2: 150. Type species by original designation *Orthalicus wallisi* Strebel, 1909.

Remarks. Species of this genus probably live high up in trees, in the canopy layer.

Clathrorthalicus corydon (Crosse, 1869) (Figs. 155, 163)

Bulimus corydon Crosse, 1869, *J. de Conchyl.*, 17: 185; Crosse, 1870, *J. de Conchyl.*, 18: 104, pl. 6 fig. 6. "Quito". Syntypes MNCN 15.05/8077 (1), MNCN 15.05/13683 (1), MNCN 15.05/21868 (1).

Figure 157. *Corona pfeifferi* (Hidalgo, 1869). Pastaza: Canelos. Syntype MNCN 15.05/3280 (H 56.3 mm). Figure 158. *Corona regalis* (Hupé, 1857). Brazil. A-B, Original figure in HUPÉ (1857): pl. 10 fig. 3 (H 70 mm). C, ZMA.MOLL 386331 (H 73.1 mm).
 Figura 157. *Corona pfeifferi* (Hidalgo, 1869). Pastaza: Canelos. Sintipo MNCN 15.05/3280 (H 56,3 mm). Figura 158. *Corona regalis* (Hupé, 1857). Brasil. A-B, figura original en HUPÉ (1857): lám. 10 fig. 3 (H 70 mm). C, ZMA.MOLL 386331 (H 73,1 mm).

Distribution. Pichincha: Mindo (BARRERO & BREURE, 2011).
Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Clathrothalicus magnificus (L. Pfeiffer, 1848) (Fig. 156A-B)

Achatina magnifica Pfeiffer, 1848, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 15: 232. "Quito, Ecuador". Syntypes NHMUK 20100508 (2).

Distribution. Ecuador: without precise locality.

Remarks. BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2016) found the type material to be subadults and suggested it strongly resembles specimens of the previous taxon. See also the remarks by BREURE & ABLETT (2015: 39) on this species.

Clathrorthalicus phoebus (L. Pfeiffer, 1863) (Fig. 156C-E)

Bulimus phoebus Pfeiffer, 1863, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 30: 274. "Ecuador". Lectotype NHMUK 1975143 (BREURE, 1979: 30).

Distribution. Ecuador: without precise locality.

Genus *Corona* Albers, 1850

Achatina (*Corona*) Albers, 1850, *Die Heliceen*: 193. Type species by subsequent designation (HERRMANNSEN, 1852: 36) *Helix* (*Cochlitoma*) *regina* A. Férussac, 1821.

Remarks. See for a general note on the distribution of *Corona* species BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2016: 48).

Corona pfeifferi (Hidalgo, 1869) (Figs. 157, 163)

Orthalicus pfeifferi Hidalgo, 1869, *J. de Conchyl.*, 17: 412; Hidalgo, 1870: 65, pl. 6 fig. 8. "Canelos, reipublicae Aequatoris". Syntype MNCN 15.05/3280 (1).

Corona pfeifferi cincta Strebel, 1909, *Jahrb. Hamb. Wiss. Anst.*, 26, Beiheft, 2: 135, pl. 21 fig. 337, pl. 22 figs 356-357.

Distribution. Napo: Tena (RBINS); Tiputini (RBINS); Pastaza: Canelos (TL); Tungurahua: Topo (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008; SALVADOR ET AL., 2021); Sucumbios: Puerto Montúfar (obs. iNaturalist, 21114224, 2019).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. Also recorded from Peru (BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2010).

Corona regalis (Hupé, 1857) (Figs. 158, 163)

Bulimus regalis Hupé, 1857, *Anim. Expéd. Amérique du Sud*, 8: 34, pl. 10 fig. 3. "le Brésil". Type material not located.

Bulimus loroisianus Hupé, 1857, *Anim. Expéd. Amérique du Sud*, 8: 35, pl. 2 fig. 4. No type locality. Type not located.

Distribution. Tungurahua: Baños (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. Also recorded from Brazil, Colombia, and Peru (RAMÍREZ ET AL., 2003; SIMONE, 2006; LINARES & VERA, 2012).

Figure 159. A, B: *Kara indentata* (S.I. da Costa, 1901), Ecuador, lectotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.115 (H 44 mm); C, D: *Kara thompsonii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1845), Ecuador, unknown locality, lectotype NHMUK 1975464 (H 71 mm). Figure 160. *Kara thompsonii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1845). A: Azuay, Cuenca, lectotype of var. *lutea* Cousin, 1887 RBINS MT.2358 (H 77.6 mm); B: Azuay, Cuenca, lectotype of var. *nigricans* Cousin, 1887 RBINS MT.2363 (H 62.8 mm); C: Azuay, Azogues, ca 2400 m, lectotype of var. *zebra* Cousin, 1887 RBINS MT.2375 (H 46.4 mm).

Figura 159. A, B: *Kara indentata* (S.I. da Costa, 1901), Ecuador, lectotipo NHMUK 1907.11.21.115 (H 44 mm); C, D: *Kara thompsonii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1845), Ecuador, localidad desconocida, lectotipo NHMUK 1975464 (H 71 mm). Figura 160. *Kara thompsonii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1845). A: Azuay, Cuenca, lectotipo de la var. *lutea* Cousin, 1887 RBINS MT.2358 (H 77,6 mm); B: Azuay, Cuenca, lectotipo de la var. *nigricans* Cousin, 1887 RBINS MT.2363 (H 62,8 mm); C: Azuay, Azogues, aprox. 2400 m, lectotipo de la var. *zebra* Cousin, 1887 RBINS MT.2375 (H 46,4 mm).

Genus *Kara* Strebel, 1910

Thaumastus (*Kara*) Strebel, 1910, *Abh. Naturw. Ver. Hamburg*, 19 (3): 16. Type species by monotypy *Bulinus thompsonii* L. Pfeiffer, 1845.

Kara indentata (S.I. da Costa, 1901) (Fig. 159A-B)

Strophocheilus (*Dryptus*) *indentatus* da Costa, 1901, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 4: 239, pl. 24 fig. 8. "Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 44) NHMUK 1907.11.21.115; paralectotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.116 (1).

Distribution. Ecuador: without precise locality.

Kara thompsonii (L. Pfeiffer, 1845) (Figs. 159C-D, 160, 163)

Bulimus thompsonii Pfeiffer, 1845, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 13: 74. "Quito". Lectotype NHMUK 1975464 (BREURE, 1978: 34).

Orphnus thompsoni var. *lutea* Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 212. "Cuenca". Possible syntypes RBINS MT.3818 (3).

Orphnus thompsoni var. *nigricans* Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 212. "Cuenca". Lectotype RBINS MT.2363 (BREURE 2011: 36); paralectotypes RBINS MT.2364 (3).

Orphnus thompsoni var. *olivaceus* Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 212. "Cuenca". Lectotype RBINS MT.2366 (BREURE 2011: 36); paralectotypes RBINS MT.2367 (3).

Orphnus thompsoni var. *zebra* Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 212. "près Azagues [Azogues], sur la pente, à environs 2400 m alt." Lectotype RBINS MT.2375 (BREURE 2011: 42); paralectotypes RBINS MT.2376 (9).

Thaumastus thompsonoides Oberwimmer, 1931, *Senckenbergiana*, 13: 194, figs 3, 6. "Loja, Ecuador". Holotype SMF 5144. [New synonymy].

Distribution. Azuay: Cuenca; Azogues (COUSIN, 1887); Cuenca-Paute (■MCZ 124918); *ibid*, Loja (OBERWIMMER, 1931); San Francisco; Sigsig (obs. iNaturalist 100606762, 2021); El Oro: Zaruma (both BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. Re-examination of the available material of this species brings us to believe that Oberwimmer's taxon is merely a colour variation.

Genus *Orthalicus* H. Beck, 1837

Orthalicus Beck, 1837 [1837-1838], *Index moll.*: 59. Type species by subsequent designation *Buccinum zebra* O.F. Müller, 1774.

Orthalicus bensoni (Reeve, 1849) (Figs. 161A-B, 163)

Bulimus bensoni Reeve, 1849 [1848-1850], *Conch. Icon.*, 5: pl. 78 fig. 571. "Banks of the Amazon". Syntype NHMUK 1975582 (1).

Orthalicus isabellinus Martens, 1873, *Festschr. Ges. naturf. Ges. Berlin*: 190, pl. 1 fig. 8. Syntypes ZMB 8876 (2).

Distribution. Pastaza: Sarayacu (PILSBRY, 1899: 148); Río Napo (BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. Also recorded from Brazil, Colombia, French Guiana, Peru, and Suriname (MARTENS, 1873; ALTENA, 1975; SIMONE, 2006; MASSEMIN ET AL., 2009; LINARES & VERA, 2012). See also BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2016: 55-56).

Figure 161. A, B: *Orthalicus bensoni* (Reeve, 1849), “Banks of the Amazon”, syntype NHMUK 1975582 (H 66.6 mm); C, D: *Orthalicus bifulguratus* (Reeve, 1849), Colombia, unknown Andean locality, lectotype NHMUK 20140082; (H 56.9 mm). Figure 162. *Orthalicus mars* Pfeiffer, 1861. Ecuador. Syntypes NHMUK 20100504 (H 76.6 mm).

Figura 161. A, B: Orthalicus bensoni (Reeve, 1849), “Bancos del Amazonas”, sintipo NHMUK 1975582 (H 66,6 mm); C, D: *Orthalicus bifulguratus* (Reeve, 1849), Colombia, localidad andina desconocida, lectotipo NHMUK 1975583 (H 56,9 mm). *Figura 162. Orthalicus mars* Pfeiffer, 1861. Ecuador. Sintipos NHMUK 20100504 (H 76,6 mm).

Orthalicus bifulguratus (Reeve, 1849) (Figs. 161C-D, 163)

Bulimus bifulguratus Reeve, 1849 [1848-1850], *Conch. Icon.*, 5: pl. 82 fig. 606. “Andes of Columbia”.

Lectotype (BREURE & SCHOUTEN, 1985: 29) NHMUK 1975583.

Zebra fulgur K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 186; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 6 figs 1a-b.

Distribution. El Oro: 10.2 km W Pinas; Pichincha: Milpe; San Nicolás; Valley Rio Cristal (obs. iNaturalist 19476235, 2019); Tungurahua: near Ambato; Topo (all BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016 except mentioned otherwise).

Figure 163. Distribution of Orthalicidae species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.
 Figura 163. Distribución de especies de Orthalicidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecoregiones.

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Also reported from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012).

Orthalicus mars L. Pfeiffer, 1861 (Fig. 162)

Orthalicus mars Pfeiffer, 1861, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 29: 25, pl. 2 fig. 8. "In republica Aequatoris".
 Syntypes NHMUK 20100504 (3).

Distribution. Ecuador: without precise locality.

Remarks. Also known from Brazil (SIMONE, 2006).

Genus *Porphyrobaphe* Shuttleworth, 1856

Porphyrobaphe Shuttleworth, 1856, *Noticiae malac.*, 1: 70. Type species by subsequent designation (Martens in ALBERS & MARTENS, 1860: 227) *Bulimus iostoma* G.B. Sowerby I, 1824.

Subgenus *Porphyrobaphe* (*Oxyorthalicus*) Strebel, 1909

Porphyrobaphe (*Oxyorthalicus*) Strebel, 1909, *Jahrb. Hamb. Wiss. Anst.*, 26 Beiheft, 2: 117. Type species by original designation *Bulimus irroratus* Reeve, 1849.

Porphyrobaphe (*Oxyorthalicus*) *irrorata* (Reeve, 1849) (Figs. 164A-B, 172)

Bulimus irroratus Reeve, 1849 [1848-1850], *Conch. Icon.*, 5: pl. 62 fig. 427. "Brazil? New Granada?".
 Syntypes NHMUK 1975248 (3).

Dryptus irroratus var. β *elongata* K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 179; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 2 fig. 2a.

Figure 164. A, B: *Porphyrobaphe (Oxyorthalicus) irrorata* (Reeve, 1849), “Brazil? New Granada?”, syntype NHMUK 1975248 (H 77 mm); C-E: *Porphyrobaphe (Oxyorthalicus) subirrorata* (S.I. da Costa, 1898), Imbabura, Paramba, lectotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.114 (H 62,6 mm). Figure 165. *Porphyrobaphe (Porphyrobaphe) iostoma* (G.B. Sowerby I, 1824). A: Manabí, Isla La Plata, ZMA.MOLL 386512 (H 66,8 mm); B: Manabí, Salango, living specimen (photo: Adrián González Guillén).
 Figura 164. A, B: *Porphyrobaphe (Oxyorthalicus) irrorata* (Reeve, 1849), “¿Brasil? ¿Nueva Granada?”, sintipo NHMUK 1975248 (H 77 mm); C-E: *Porphyrobaphe (Oxyorthalicus) subirrorata* (S.I. da Costa, 1898), Imbabura, Paramba, lectotipo NHMUK 1907.11.21.114 (H 62,6 mm). Figura 165. *Porphyrobaphe (Porphyrobaphe) iostoma* (G.B. Sowerby I, 1824). A: Manabí, Isla La Plata, ZMA.MOLL 386512 (H 66,8 mm); B: Manabí, Salango, ejemplar vivo (foto: Adrián González Guillén).

Dryptus irroratus var. γ *minor* K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 180; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 2 fig. 2b.

Distribution. Napo: “Oriente”; Pastaza: Puyo; Mera; Pichincha: 71.7 km SW Quito, road to Santo Domingo; Mindo; near Nanegal; Gualea; Río Cinto; Río Pilaton valley; Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Santo Domingo de los Colorados; Tungurahua: Topo (all BREURE & BORRERO, 2008; see also SALVADOR ET AL., 2021).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Porphyrobaphe (Oxyorthalicus) subirrorata (S.I. da Costa, 1898) (Figs. 164C-E, 172)

Strophocheilus (Eurytus) subirroratus da Costa, 1898, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 3: 83, fig. II. “Paramba, Ecuador”. Lectotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.114 (BREURE & SCHOUTEN, 1985: 54); paralectotype ANSP 220422 (1).

Distribution. Imbabura: Paramba (TL); Pastaza: Mera (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Subgenus *Porphyrobaphe* (*Porphyrobaphe*)

Porphyrobaphe (Porphyrobaphe) iostoma (G.B. Sowerby I, 1824) (Figs. 165, 172)

Bulimus iostoma Sowerby I, 1824, *Zool. J.*, 1: 58, pl. 5 fig. 1. No type locality given. Type material not located.

Bulimus phasianella Valenciennes in Humboldt & Bonpland, 1827 [1813-1832], *Recueil d'observ. zool.*, 2: 244; Valenciennes in Humboldt & Bonpland, 1832 [1813-1832], *Recueil d'observ. zool.*, 2: pl. 55 fig. 4a-4b. “Nouvelle-Espagne”.

Bulimus grevillei L. Pfeiffer, 1875 [1870-1876], *Novit. conch.*, 4: 143, pl. 133 figs 4-5 (ex Sowerby ms.). “Quito”. Type material not located.

Distribution. El Oro: near Machala; Chacras; Santa Rosa; Esmeraldas: various localities (all BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016; ■UF 139140); Guayas: Chongón; Puna (Strebel 1909); 5 km N Santa Elena (BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016); various localities (■UF 139104, 139116, 139117, 139141, 139144); Manabí: Jama (BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016); ibid, Machalilla (STREBEL 1909; CORREOSO, 2008); between Manta and Bahía de Caraquez (COLTRO & COLTRO, 2000a); Bahía de Caraquez; Salango; Jipijapa (all COLTRO & COLTRO, 2000b); Isla La Plata (ZMA 386512); Punta Blanca (COLTRO & COLTRO, 2000c); various localities (■UF 139103, 139104, 139135, 139136, 139143); Agua Blanca (Roosen, pers. obs. 2019).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178], Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214], Tumbes-Piura dry forests [NT0232], South American Pacific mangroves [NT1405].

Remarks. This is one of the emblematic species for the Guayas region (CORNEJO, 2015: 68). Also reported from Colombia and Peru (LINARES & VERA, 2012; BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016).

Porphyrobaphe (Porphyrobaphe) saturnus (L. Pfeiffer, 1860) (Figs. 166, 172)

Bulimus saturanus Pfeiffer, 1860, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 28: 136 [*lapsus calami*, see BREURE & ABLETT 2015: 49].

Figure 166. *Porphyrobaphe* (*Porphyrobaphe*) *saturnus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1860). Chimborazo: Pallatanga. Syntype NHMUK 20140080 (H 74.1 mm). Figure 167. *Sultana* (*Metorthalicus*) *atramentaria* (L. Pfeiffer, 1855). A: Colombia, unknown Andean locality, syntype of *Orthalicus iodes* Shuttleworth, 1856, NMBE 19045 (H 67.8 mm); B, C: unspecified locality, syntype of *Bulimus boussingaultii* Hupé, 1857, MNHN-IM-2000-28025 (H 65.3 mm).

Figura 166. *Porphyrobaphe* (*Porphyrobaphe*) *saturnus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1860). Chimborazo: Pallatanga. Sintipo NHMUK 20140080 (H 74,1 mm). *Figura 167.* *Sultana* (*Metorthalicus*) *atramentaria* (L. Pfeiffer, 1855). A: Colombia, localidad andina desconocida, sintipo de *Orthalicus iodes* Shuttleworth, 1856, NMBE 19045 (H 67,8 mm); B, C: localidad no especificada, sintipo de *Bulimus boussingaultii* Hupé, 1856, MNHN-IM-2000-28025 (H 65,3 mm).

Bulimus saturnus Pfeiffer, 1860, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 28: pl. 51 fig. 6. "Pallatanga, Republic of Ecuador". Syntypes NHMUK 20140080 (3).

Distribution. Chimborazo: Pallatanga (TL); Loja: Malacatus (STREBEL, 1909).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Genus *Sultana* Shuttleworth, 1856

Sultana Shuttleworth, 1856, *Noticiae malac.*, 1: 58. Type species by tautonymy *Helix sultana* Dillwyn, 1817.

Subgenus *Sultana* (*Metorthalicus*) Pilsbry, 1899

Orthalicus (*Metorthalicus*) Pilsbry, 1899, *Man. Conch.*, (2) 12: 187. Type species by original designation *Bulimus yatesi* L. Pfeiffer, 1855.

Sultana (*Metorthalicus*) *atramentaria* (L. Pfeiffer, 1855) (Figs. 167, 172)

Bulimus atramentaria Pfeiffer, 1855, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 22: 116. "New Grenada". Type material not located.

Orthalicus iodes Shuttleworth, 1856, *Noticiae malac.*, 1: 68, pl. 4 fig. 8 "in Andibus Columbiae"; Neubert & Gosteli, 2003, *Contr. Nat. Hist.*, 1: 30, pl. 6 fig. 2. Syntype NMBE 19045.

Bulimus boussingaultii Hupé, 1857, *Anim. Expéd. Amérique du Sud*, 8: 37, pl. 9 fig. 2. Not given (see remarks). Syntypes MNHN-IM-2000-28024 (2), -28025 (1).

Distribution. Pastaza: Canelos (MARTENS, 1885: 156).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. Also reported from Colombia and Peru (LINARES & VERA, 2012; BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016). Hupé based his taxon on a figure in REEVE (1848 [1848-1850]: pl. 27 fig. 168b), the specimen of which was collected at "Chopo, Province of Pamplona, New Grenada" [= Pamplonita, Dept. Norte de Santander, Colombia]. This specimen was not located in NHM. Hupé's figure is, however, based on one of the syntypes (herein Figure 180 B-C) in the Paris museum. The two lots were collected respectively by Boussingault in 1849 at Socorro [Dept. Santander, Colombia] (28024) and by Ghiesbregt at an unspecified place (28025).

Sultana (*Metorthalicus*) *augusti* (Jousseau, 1887) (Figs. 168, 172)

Porphyrobaphe augusti Jousseau, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 165, pl. 3 fig. 10. "l'Équateur". Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-28014.

Distribution. Azuay: Quebrada Machai (PILSBRY, 1899: 195); Pastaza: Mera; Puyo; Pichincha: Mirador (RBINS); Tungurahua: Topo (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. The locality 'Mirador', tentatively located in Prov. El Oro by BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2016), is now allocated to Prov. Pinchincha.

Sultana (*Metorthalicus*) *deburghiae* (Reeve, 1859) (Figs. 169, 172)

Bulimus deburghiae Reeve, 1859, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 27: 123. "Peruvian side of the Amazon". Lectotype (BREURE & SCHOUTEN, 1985: 27) NHMUK 19601622 (1).

Bulimus gloriosus L. Pfeiffer, 1862, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 29: 387, pl. 37 fig. 4. "Republic of Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE & SCHOUTEN, 1985: 27) NHMUK 1975243 (1).

Orthalicus (*Porphyrobaphe*) *gloriosus* var. β *elongatus* K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 185; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 5 fig. 1. "Nanegal".

Figure 168. *Sultana (Metorthalicus) augusti* (Jousseaume, 1887). Ecuador. Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-28014 (H 68.4 mm). Figure 169. *Sultana (Metorthalicus) deburghiae* (Reeve, 1859). A, B: Peru, near the Amazon, lectotype NHMUK 19601622 (H 64.7 mm); C, D: Ecuador, lectotype of *Bulimus gloriosus* L. Pfeiffer, 1862, NHMUK 1975243 (H 75.4 mm). Figure 170. *Sultana (Metorthalicus) fraseri* (L. Pfeiffer, 1858). Azuay: near Cuenca. Lectotype NHMUK 1975246 (H 88.9 mm).

Figura 168. *Sultana (Metorthalicus) augusti* (Jousseaume, 1887). Ecuador. Holotipo MNHN-IM-2000-28014 (H 68,4 mm). Figura 169. A, B: *Sultana (Metorthalicus) deburghiae* (Reeve, 1859), Perú, cerca del Amazonas, lectotipo NHMUK 19601622 (H 64,7 mm); C, D: Ecuador, lectotipo de *Bulimus gloriosus* L. Pfeiffer, 1862, NHMUK 1975243 (H 75,4 mm). Figura 170. *Sultana (Metorthalicus) fraseri* (L. Pfeiffer, 1858). Azuay: cerca de Cuenca. Lectotipo NHMUK 1975246 (H 88,9 mm).

Distribution. Napo: 6.5 km SSE Baeza; Nachiyacu; Pastaza: Cerros de Abitagua; Mera; Porvenir; Pichincha: Mirador; Nanegal; Tungurahua: Topo; Baños; Río Negro (all BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Figure 171. A, B: *Sultana (Metorthalicus) kellettii* (Reeve, 1850), Ecuador? lectotype NHMUK 1975241 (H 61.2 mm); C: *Sultana (Metorthalicus) yatesi galactostoma* (Ancey, 1890), Ecuador, syntype NMW 1955.158.24079 (H 67.5 mm); D: *Sultana (Sultana) sultana* (Dillwyn, 1817), Perú, Tarapoto, syntype of *Orthalicus trullisatus* Shuttleworth, 1856, NMBE 18962 (H 87.4 mm).
 .Figura 171. A, B: *Sultana (Metorthalicus) kellettii* (Reeve, 1850), ¿Ecuador? lectotipo NHMUK 1975241 (H 61,2 mm); C: *Sultana (Metorthalicus) yatesi galactostoma* (Ancey, 1890), Ecuador, sintipo NMW 1955.158.24079 (H 67,5 mm); D: *Sultana (Sultana) sultana* (Dillwyn, 1817), Perú, Tarapoto, sintipo de *Orthalicus trullisatus* Shuttleworth, 1856, NMBE 18962 (H 87,4 mm).

Sultana (Metorthalicus) fraseri (L. Pfeiffer, 1858) (Figs. 170, 172)

Bulimus fraseri Pfeiffer, 1858, *Malak. Bl.*, 5: 239. "in provincia Cuenca reipublicae Aequatoris".
 Lectotype (BREURE & SCHOUTEN, 1985: 28) NHMUK 1975246 (1).
Orthalicus fraseri brevispira Pilsbry, 1899, *Man. Conch.*, (2) 12: 194, pl. 46 figs 34-35. Holotype ANSP 78573.

Distribution. Azuay: near Cuenca (TL); Loja: (STREBEL, 1909: 154, as forma *brevispira*; no specific locality mentioned); Malacatos (USNM 316083); Morona-Santiago: Gualaquiza (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Sultana (Metorthalicus) kellettii (Reeve, 1850) (Figs. 171A-B, 172)

Bulimus kellettii Reeve, 1850 [1848-1850], *Conch. Icon.*, 5: pl. 89 fig. 661. "Ecuador?". Lectotype (BREURE & SCHOUTEN, 1985: 28) NHMUK 1975241.
Bulimus yatesi 'Shuttleworth' Hupé, 1857, *Anim. Expéd. Amérique du Sud*, 8: 31, pl. 8 figs 1-1a.
Bulimus fungairinoi Hidalgo, 1867, *J. de Conchyl.*, 15: 72, pl. 4 fig. 4. Syntypes MNCN 15.05/3159 (2).

Distribution. Azuay: Cuenca; Nabón (STREBEL, 1909: 160); Loja: Malacatos (STREBEL, 1909: 159); Pastaza: Mera; Cerros de Abitagua; Tungurahua: Río Negro (all BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Sultana (Metorthalicus) yatesi galactostoma (Ancey, 1890) (Fig. 171C)

Porphyrobaphe galactostoma Ancey, 1890, *Bull. Soc. Malac. France*, 7: 153. "Republica Aequatoris".
 Syntype NMW 1955.158.24079 (1).

Figure 172. Distribution of Orthalicidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.
 Figura 172. Distribución de Orthalicidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecoregiones.

Distribution. Ecuador: without precise locality.

Remarks. The record by ANCEY (1903: 89) of this species from Peru is probably a mistake; no voucher could be located.

Subgenus *Sultana* (*Sultana*)

Sultana (*Sultana*) *sultana* (Dillwyn, 1817) (Figs. 171D, 172)

Helix sultana Dillwyn, 1817, *A descriptive catalogue*, 2: 920. "New Zealand" [sic]. Based on Chemnitz vol. 11, p. 281, pl. 210 fig. 2070-2071 "ex museo Spengleriano". Type material lost in NHMD.

Orthalicus trullisatus Shuttleworth, 1856, *Notic. malac.*, 1: 58, pl. 5 fig. 1. "ab oriente Andium prope Tarapoto". Syntypes NMBE 18962 (2).

Orthalicus sultana angustior Preston, 1914, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, (8) 13: 524. "Eastern Peru". Type material not located.

Distribution. Los Ríos: Palenque Science Center (UF 181509); Manabí: Jama (obs. iNaturalist 40539468, 2012); Morona-Santiago: 59 km SSE Patuca (UF 139123); Cusuimi (■FMNH 173044); Ashuara (■FMNH 174887); Napo: Nachiyacu (ANSP 170700); Orellana: Francisco de Orellana (obs. iNaturalist 41668292, 2007); Loreto (ANSP 195216); Tiputini (RBINS); Pastaza: Puyo; Sucumbios: Lago Agrio; Providencia (obs. iNaturalist 100037692, 2021); Shushufindi (obs. iNaturalist 39785771, 2019; 98327100, 2021); Tungurahua: Topo (ANSP 306772); Zamora-Chinchepe: Yantzaza (obs. iNaturalist 34014028, 2019).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Napo moist forests [NT0142], Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178], Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214].

Remarks. Also reported from Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, French Guiana, Peru, and Suriname (ALTENA, 1975; SIMONE, 2006; MASSEMIN *ET AL.*, 2009; LINARES & VERA, 2012; BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016).

Figure 173. *Sultana (Metorthalicus) elizabethae* Ahuir & Torres, 2019. Peru: near Huancabamba. Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-35011 (H 69.5 mm).

Figura 173. *Sultana (Metorthalicus) elizabethae* Ahuir & Torres, 2019. Perú: cerca de Huancabamba. Holotipo MNHN-IM-2000-35011 (H 69,5 mm).

Comments on the genus. The following species has not yet been reported from the country:
- *Sultana (Trachyorthalicus) elizabethae* Ahuir & Torres, 2019, *Malac. Mostra Mond.*, 104: 3, figs. "Peru, near Huancabamba, Piura". Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-35011 (Fig. 173). This Peruvian species has not yet been found in Ecuador, but the type locality is so close to the border that it may be expected in Prov. Zamora-Chinchepe or Loja. Although the authors placed this taxon in a different subgenus, we retain here the opinion of BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2016: 72) that the protoconch sculpture does not warrant a distinction between the two subgenera and the correct name for this taxon should be *Sultana (Metorthalicus) elizabethae* Ahuir & Torres, 2019.

Comments on the family. The following species from this family are no longer considered as belonging to the Ecuadorian malacofauna:

- *Bulimus maracaibensis* Pfeiffer, 1856 (*Malak. Bl.*, 3: 186) was listed by BREURE & BORRERO (2008). This was based on an unconfirmed record by MARTENS (1893 [1890-1901]) and is well outside the range of this species as explained by BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2016: 84).

- *Orthalicus obductus* Shuttleworth, 1856 (*Noticiae malac.*, 1: 61, pl. 3 figs 1-3) was described from northern Colombia. The Ecuadorian record is likely a misidentification (BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016: 84).

Family AMPHIBULIMIDAE P. Fischer, 1873

Remarks. This family is restricted to the Caribbean and the northern part of South America, although some species occur as south as Bolivia (BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016). Revisionary work has been done by PILSBRY (1895-1896), BORRERO & BREURE (2011) for Colombian species, and BREURE (2013b, 2019a) for Pantepui taxa. Anatomical data is

Figure 174. *Plekocheilus (Aeropictus) tenuissimus* Weyrauch, 1967. A: Pichincha, Tandayapa, holotype IFML 17031 (H 27.8 mm); B: Carchi, near El Laurel, living specimen (photo: Adrián González Guillén). Figure 175. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) aristaceus* (Crosse, 1869). Ecuador: unknown locality. Lectotype MNCN 15.05/7180 (H 48.3 mm).

Figura 174. *Plekocheilus (Aeropictus) tenuissimus* Weyrauch, 1967. A: Pichincha, Tandayapa, holotipo IFML 17031 (H 27,8 mm); B: Carchi, cerca de El Laurel, ejemplar vivo (foto: Adrián González Guillén). Figura 175. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) aristaceus* (Crosse, 1869). Ecuador: localidad desconocida. Lectotipo MNCN 15.05/7180 (H 48,3 mm).

given by BREURE (1978, 2009, 2013b). Recent studies on type material can be found in NEUBERT & JANSSEN (2004), KÖHLER (2007), BREURE (2013a, 2016a) and BREURE & ABLETT (2015). We follow COWIE *ET AL.* (2004) for the authorship of J.A. Wagner (1827). The report by WILLIAMS (2002) about predation by a bird of an “arboreal *Plekocheilus* sp.” is erroneous; firstly because these species are not truly arboreal, and secondly because his figure clearly shows that the shell picked up by the bird is a *Drymaeus* species.

Figure 176. A: *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) cardinalis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853), Ecuador, unknown locality, syntype ZMB 112721 (H 46 mm); B, C: *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) doliarius* (S.I. da Costa, 1898), Imbabura, Hacienda Paramba, lectotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.110 (H 58 mm). Figure 177. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) eros* (Angas, 1878). Ecuador: unknown locality. Lectotype NHMUK 1879.1.21.2 (H 35.5 mm).

Figura 176. A: *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) cardinalis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853), Ecuador, localidad desconocida, sintipo ZMB 112721 (H 46 mm); B, C: *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) doliarius* (S.I. da Costa, 1898), Imbabura, Hacienda Paramba, lectotipo NHMUK 1907.11.21.110 (H 58 mm). Figura 177. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) eros* (Angas, 1878). Ecuador: localidad desconocida. Lectotipo NHMUK 1879.1.21.2 (H 35,5 mm).

Genus *Plekocheilus* Guilding, 1828

Plekocheilus Guilding, 1828, *Zool. J.*, 3: 532. Type species by monotypy *Caprella undulata* Guilding, 1824.

Subgenus *Plekocheilus (Aeropictus)* Weyrauch, 1967

Plekocheilus (Aeropictus) Weyrauch, 1967, *Acta Zool. Lilloana*, 21: 465. Type species by original designation *Bulimus veranyi* L. Pfeiffer, 1848.

Plekocheilus (Aeropictus) tenuissimus Weyrauch, 1967 (Figs. 174, 178)

Plekocheilus (Orcesiellus) tenuissimus Weyrauch, 1967, *Acta Zool. Lilloana*, 21: 469, figs 23, 50. "Ecuador, Tandayapa, en la vertiente oriental del cerro Pichincha, aproximadamente 2500 m". Holotype IFML 17031 (ex WW 3364).

Figure 178. Distribution of Amphibulimidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 178. Distribución de Amphibulimidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecoregiones.

Distribution. Carchi: El Laurel (BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016); Pichincha: Tandayapa (TL).
Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145], North Andean páramo [NT1006].

Subgenus *Plekocheilus* (*Eurytus*) Albers, 1850

Plekocheilus (*Eurytus*) Albers, 1850, *Die Heliceen*: 169. Type species by subsequent designation
Helix pentadina d'Orbigny, 1835.

Remarks. A key to species from (among others) Ecuador was given by BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2016: 15).

Plekocheilus (*Eurytus*) *aristaceus* (Crosse, 1869) (Figs. 175, 178)

Bulimus aristaceus Crosse, 1869, *J. de Conchyl.*, 17: 185. "Quito, republica Aequatoris". Lectotype
 (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2015: 88) MNCN 15.05/7180.

Distribution. Chimborazo: Bucay; Cotopaxi: Páramo de Sighos; Pichincha: Río Pilaton valley (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).
Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Plekocheilus (*Eurytus*) *aureonitens* (K. Miller, 1878) (Fig. 178)

Eurytus aureonitens Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 181; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 6 fig. 2.
 "Valli Pilatonensi". Type material not located.

Distribution. Pichincha: Río Pilaton valley (TL).
Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2016: 14, fig. 9A) suggested this taxon might possibly be a junior subjective synonym of *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) taylorianus* (Reeve, 1849).

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) cardinalis (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) (Figs. 176A, 178)

Bulimus cardinalis Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 316. "Quito". Syntype ZMB 112721 (1).

Distribution. Napo: Nachiyacu; Topo; Pastaza: Mera; Puyo; Pichincha: Milpe; Mindo; Nanagal (all BREURE & BORRERO, 2008; BORRERO & BREURE, 2011); "Paramo de Pichincha" [*sic?*, Pichincha] (GERMAIN, 1907).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. The locality given by GERMAIN (1907) probably refers to Mount Pichincha near Quito. This species has also been recorded from southern Colombia (BORRERO & BREURE, 2011: 44).

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) doliarius (S.I. da Costa, 1898) (Figs. 176B-C, 178)

Strophocheilus (Eurytus) doliarius da Costa, 1898, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 3: 84, fig. 1. "Paramba Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 30) NHMUK 1907.11.21.110; paralectotype SMF 9513 (1).

Distribution. Imbabura: Hacienda Paramba (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Previously this locality was assigned to Prov. Carchi by BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2016). Also occurring in Colombia (BORRERO & BREURE, 2011: 45).

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) eros (Angas, 1878) (Figs. 177, 178)

Bulimus (Eurytus) eros Angas, 1878, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 46: 312, pl. 18 figs 6-7. "Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE & ABLETT, 2011: 21) NHMUK 1879.1.21.2.

Distribution. Loja: ?Chaguarpamba (BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) floccosus (Spix, 1827) (Figs. 179, 190)

Achatina floccosa Spix in J.A. Wagner, 1827, *Test. fluvi. Brasil*: 10, pl. 9 figs 3-4. "sylvis Provinciarum septemtrionalium Brasiliae". Syntype ZSM 20020116 (1).

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Ashuara (■FMNH 187606); Napo: 120 km SE Quito (Weyrauch 1967b); Nachiyacu (■ANSP 170178); Tena (■MCZ 64954); Tungurahua: Topo (SALVADOR ET AL., 2021).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. Also recorded from Brazil and Peru (RAMÍREZ ET AL., 2003; SIMONE, 2006).

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) jimenezi (Hidalgo, 1872) (Figs. 180, 190)

Bulimus gibbonius I. Lea 1838: Hidalgo, 1870, *J. de Conchyl.*, 18: 54. Not *Bulimus gibbonius* Lea, 1838.

Figure 179. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) floccosus* (Spix, 1827). Brazil: southern forests. Syntype ZSM 20020116 (H 60 mm). Figure 180. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) jimenezi* (Hidalgo, 1872). Napo: San José de Suno. Syntypes MNCN 15.05/1066 (H 69 mm).
 Figura 179. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) floccosus* (Spix, 1827). Brasil: bosques del sur. Sintipo ZSM 20020116 (H 60 mm). Figura 180. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) jimenezi* (Hidalgo, 1872). Napo: San José de Suno. Sintipos MNCN 15.05/1066 (H 69 mm).

Bulimus jimenezi Hidalgo, 1872, *Moluscos Viaje al Pacífico*, 1: 93, pl. 5 figs 2-3. "San José". Syntypes MNCN 15.05/1066 (2), 15.05/3158 (2).

Distribution. Napo: Nachiyacu; Sarayacu (both WEYRAUCH, 1967b); Rio Quijos; Orellana: San José de Suno; Pastaza: Puyo; Mera (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008; BORRERO & BREURE, 2011).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) lynciculus (Deville & Hupé, 1850) (Figs. 181, 190)

Bulimus lynciculus Deville & Hupé, 1850, *Rev. Magas. Zool.*, (2) 2: 640, pl. 15 fig. 1. "Mission de Sarayacu, sur les bords de la rivière de l'Ucuyali, Pérou". Type material not located.
Plekocheilus (Eurytus) jacksoni Pilsbry, 1939, *Notulae Nat.*, 19: 1, fig. 2. Holotype ANSP 170694.

Figure 181. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) lynciculus* (Deville & Hupé, 1850). Peru: Sarayacu. Holotype of *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) jacksoni* Pilsbry, 1939, ANSP 170694 (H 45.4 mm).

Figura 181. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) lynciculus* (Deville & Hupé, 1850). Perú: Sarayacu. Holotipo de *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) jacksoni* Pilsbry, 1939, ANSP 170694 (H 45,4 mm).

Distribution. Napo: Nachiyacu; Orellana: Loreto (WEYRAUCH, 1967b); Tungurahua: Rio Pastaza watershed (BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016); Topo (■ ANSP 306771).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. Also reported from Colombia and Peru (TL, RAMÍREZ ET AL., 2003; LINARES & VERA, 2012).

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) nocturnus Pilsbry, 1939 (Figs. 182, 190)

Plekocheilus nocturnus Pilsbry, 1939, *Notulae Nat.*, 19: 3, fig. 5. "Ecuador, Puyo". Lectotype (BAKER, 1963: 229) ANSP 170695.

Distribution. Imbabura: Ibarra; Pastaza: Mera; Puyo (BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016); Tungurahua: Topo (SALVADOR ET AL., 2021).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) oligostylus Pilsbry, 1939 (Figs. 183, 190)

Plekocheilus oligostylus Pilsbry, 1939, *Notulae Nat.*, 19: 3, fig. 6. "Colombia [sic, Ecuador, Nachiyacu (CLENCH & TURNER, 1962: 109)]". Lectotype (BAKER, 1963: 229) ANSP 170696.

Distribution. Napo: Nachiyacu (TL); Rio Quijos valley; Pastaza: Puyo; Sarayacu; Mera (all BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Figure 182. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) nocturnus* Pilsbry, 1939. Pastaza: Puyo. Lectotype ANSP 170695 (H 51 mm). Figure 183. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) oligostylus* Pilsbry, 1939. Napo: Nachiyacu. Lectotype ANSP 170696 (H 71 mm).

Figura 182. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) nocturnus* Pilsbry, 1939. Pastaza: Puyo. Lectotipo ANSP 170695 (H 51 mm). *Figura 183.* *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) oligostylus* Pilsbry, 1939. Napo: Nachiyacu. Lectotipo ANSP 170696 (H 71 mm).

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) piperitus mcgintyi 'Pilsbry' H.B. Baker, 1963 (Figs. 184, 190)

Plekocheilus mcgintyi Pilsbry, 1944, *Nautilus*, 57: pl. 9 fig. 6 [Nomen nudum].

Plekocheilus mcgintyi 'Pilsbry' H.B. Baker, 1963, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 115: 229. "Rio Napo, northeastern boundary of Ecuador". Possible syntype ANSP 227455 (1).

Distribution. Napo: Rio Jatunyacu [= Rio Napo] valley (TL).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. The nominate taxon occurs in northern Peru.

Figure 184. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) piperitus mcgintyi* 'Pilsbry' H.B. Baker, 1963. Napo: Rio Jatunyacu [= Rio Napo] valley. Possible syntype ANSP 227455 (H 56.8 mm). Figure 185. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) roseolabrum* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Loja: Malacatos. Lectotype NHMUK 1975135 (H 42 mm).
Figura 184. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) piperitus mcgintyi* "Pilsbry" H.B. Baker, 1963. Napo: Valle del Río Jatunyacu [= Río Napo]. Posible sintipo ANSP 227455 (H 56,8 mm). *Figura 185.* *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) roseolabrum* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Loja: Malacatos. Lectotipo NHMUK 1975135 (H 42 mm).

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) roseolabrum (E.A. Smith, 1877) (Figs. 185, 190)

Bulimus roseolabrum Smith, 1877, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 45: 362, pl. 39 fig. 8. "Malacatos, South Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE, 1978: 16) NHMUK 1975135; paralectotype NHMUK 1877.3.28.2 (1).

Distribution. Loja: Malacatos (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Figures 186, 187. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) taylorianus* (Reeve, 1849). 186: Ecuador, near Quito, lectotype NHMUK 1874.12.11.271 (H 58.5 mm); 187: living specimen, Imbabura, Chontal Alto, photography courtesy of Adrián González Guillén.

Figuras 186, 187. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) taylorianus* (Reeve, 1849). 186: Ecuador, cerca de Quito, lectotipo NHMUK 1874.12.11.271 (H 58,5 mm); 187: ejemplar vivo, Imbabura, Chontal Alto, fotografía cortesía de Adrian González Guillén.

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) taylorianus (Reeve, 1849) (Figs. 186, 187, 190)

Bulimus taylorianus Reeve, 1849 [1848-1850], *Conch. Icon.*, 5: pl. 81 fig. 602. "Environs of Quito".
Lectotype (BREURE, 1978: 16) NHMUK 1874.12.11.271.

Eurytus taylorioides minor K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 181, pl. 4 fig. 1; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 7 fig. 1. Type material not located.

Distribution. Chimborazo: Mt. Chimborazo; Cotopaxi: Sigchos; Imbabura: Ibarra; Napo: Nachiyacu; Pastaza: Mera; Puyo; Pichincha: Mindo (■ UMMZ 238571); Nanegal; Pacto; Pintag; Gualea; Tungurahua: Topo (all others BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. BORRERO & BREURE (2011: 43) suggested that this Ecuadorian species may extend into northern Peru. So far it has not been recorded from that country.

Plekocheilus (Eurytus) tricolor (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) (Figs. 188, 190)

Bulimus tricolor Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 325. "Gualea, Neu Granada". Type material not located.

Bulimus semipictus Hidalgo, 1869, *J. de Conchyl.*, 17: 188. "Baeza, reipublicae Aequatoris". Lectotype (BREURE, 1975: 1139) MNHN-IM-2000-28113; paralectotypes MNCN 15.05/3161 (6).

Distribution. Bolivar: N of Bucay; Cotopaxi: Sigchos; Imbabura: Ibarra; Los Ríos: Cerro Samana; Napo: Baeza (TL *semipictus*); Pichincha: Gualea (TL); Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Santo Domingo de los Colorados; Tungurahua: Topo (all BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Figure 188. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) tricolor* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Pichincha: Guala. Lectotype of *Bulimus semipictus* Hidalgo, 1869, MNHN-IM-2000-28113 (H 37.7 mm). Figure 189. *Plekocheilus (Plekocheilus) cecepeus* Breure & Araujo, 2015. Ecuador: unknown locality. Holotype MNCN 15.05/60013P (H 44.8 mm).

Figura 188. *Plekocheilus (Eurytus) tricolor* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Pichincha: Guala. Lectotipo de *Bulimus semipictus* Hidalgo, 1869, MNHN-IM-2000-28113 (H 37,7 mm). Figura 189. *Plekocheilus (Plekocheilus) cecepeus* Breure & Araujo, 2015. Ecuador: localidad desconocida. Holotipo MNCN 15.05/60013P (H 44.8 mm).

Subgenus *Plekocheilus* (*Plekocheilus*)

Plekocheilus (Plekocheilus) cecepeus Breure & Araujo, 2015 (Fig. 189)

Plekocheilus (Plekocheilus) cecepeus Breure & Araujo, 2015, *ZooKeys*, 516: 89, fig. 2. "Ecuador, Quito". Holotype MNCN 15.05/60013P; paratypes 15.05/7477P (3).

Distribution. Ecuador: without accurate locality.

Figure 190. Distribution of Amphibulimidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.
 Figura 190. Distribución de Amphibulimidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Family BULIMULIDAE Tryon, 1867

Remarks. This is a large family (25 genera) occurring throughout the Neotropics. Revision of the family at species level was done by PILSBRY (1897-1898); on the generic level by BREURE (1979), while SCHILEYKO (1999a) made the latest re-classification. Anatomical data is given by BREURE (1978), BREURE & ESKENS (1981); phylogenetical data is summarised in BREURE & ROMERO (2012); further data can be found in PARENT & CRESPI (2006), BREURE (2016b). A first paper on the *Naesiotus nux* genome was published by HUNTER ET AL. (2016). Recent studies on type material can be found in NEUBERT & JANSSEN (2004), KÖHLER (2007), BREURE (2011, 2012, 2013a, 2016a) and BREURE & ABLETT (2014).

Genus *Bocourtia* Rochebrune, 1882

Bocourtia Rochebrune, 1882, *Bull. Soc. Philom. Paris*, (7) 6: 117. Type species by subsequent designation (HUBENDICK, 1951: 114) *Bocourtia lymnaeiformis* Rochebrune, 1882.

Subgenus *Bocourtia* (*Kuschelenia*) Hylton Scott, 1951

Kuschelenia Hylton Scott, 1951, *Acta Zool. Lilloana*, 12: 539. Type species by monotypy *Kuschelenia simulans* Hylton Scott, 1951.

Bocourtia (*Kuschelenia*) *aequatoria* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) (Figs. 191, 197)

Bulimus aequatorius Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 420. "reipublicae Aequatoris, monte Schinchulagua". Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 85) NHMUK 1975377.

Distribution. Chimborazo: Cerro Chanchalahua (TL); Cotopaxi: Mulalo near Latacunga (MARTENS, 1885a).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Figure 191. *Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) aequatoria* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Chimborazo: Cerro Chanchalagua. Lectotype NHMUK 1975377 (H 37.8 mm). Figure 192. *Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) anthisanensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Napo: Cerro Antisana. Lectotype NHMUK 1975372 (H 40.2 mm).
Figura 191. *Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) aequatoria* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Chimborazo: Cerro Chanchalagua. Lectotipo NHMUK 1975377 (H 37,8 mm). *Figura 192.* *Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) anthisanensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Napo: Cerro Antisana. Lectotipo NHMUK 1975372 (H 40,2 mm).

Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) anthisanensis (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) (Fig 192, 197)

Bulimus anthisanensis Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 406. "monte Anthisana (44000' [sic]) reipublicae Aequatoris". Lectotype (BREURE, 1978: 170) NHMUK 1975372.

Distribution. Napo: Cerro Antisana (TL).

Figure 193. *Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) caliginosa* (Reeve, 1849). Unknown locality. Lectotype NHMUK 20100518 (H 35.4 mm). Figure 194. *Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) cotopaxiensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Cotopaxi/Pichincha: Cerro Cotopaxi. Lectotype NHMUK 1975370 (H 33.9 mm).

Figura 193. *Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) caliginosa* (Reeve, 1849). *Localidad desconocida.* *Lectotipo NHMUK 20100518 (H 35,4 mm).* *Figura 194.* *Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) cotopaxiensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). *Cotopaxi / Pichincha: Cerro Cotopaxi.* *Lectotipo NHMUK 1975370 (H 33,9 mm).*

Ecoregion. North Andean páramo [NT1006].

Remarks. MARTENS (1885a) mentioned this species from Cerro Altar near Riobamba, together with the next species, and *Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) cotopaxiensis* (Pfeiffer, 1853) from Cerro Antisana. His data needs verification.

Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) caliginosa (Reeve, 1849) (Figs. 193, 197)

Bulimus caliginosus Reeve, 1849 [1848-1850], *Conch. Icon.*, 5: pl. 82 fig. 609. “—?”. Lectotype (BREURE & ABLETT, 2014: 37) NHMUK 20100518.

Distribution. Chimborazo: without specified locality (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Cerro Altar near Riobamba (MARTENS, 1885a); Pichincha: “Cratère de Pichencha [*sic*, Pichincha]” (GERMAIN, 1907).

Ecoregion. North Andean páramo [NT1006].

Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) cotopaxiensis (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) (Figs. 194, 197)

Bulimus cotopaxiensis Pfeiffer, 1853. *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 419. “reipublicae Aequatoris, montem Cotopaxi”. Lectotype (BREURE, 1978: 175) NHMUK 1975370.

Distribution. Cotopaxi/Pichincha: Cerro Cotopaxi (TL); Pichincha: Mt. Pasochoa (obs. iNaturalist 25067790, 2019).

Ecoregion. North Andean páramo [NT1006], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Genus *Bostryx* Troschel, 1847

Bulimus (Bostryx) Troschel, 1847, *Z. Malak.*, 4: 49. Type species by monotypy *Bulimus (Bostryx) solutus* Troschel, 1847.

Bostryx alausiensis (Cousin, 1887) (Fig 195A-B, 197)

Thaumastus alausiensis Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 228, pl. 4 fig. 13. “sur le versant du mont Hacu, entre Achapallas et la rivière Sula, sur le territoire Alaúsi, province de Chimborazo”. Lectotype (BREURE, 1975: 1141) MNHN-IM-2000-20820; paralectotypes RBINS MT.2333 (1), MT.2334 (12).

Distribution. Chimborazo: Achupallas (TL).

Ecoregion. North Andean páramo [NT1006].

Bostryx bilineatus (G.B. Sowerby I, 1833) (Figs. 196, 197)

Bulimus bilineatus Sowerby I, 1833, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 1: 37. [Ecuador] “ad Sanctam Elena et in Columbiá”. Syntypes ZMB 10261 (4).

Bulimus fontainei d’Orbigny; Hidalgo, 1872, *Moluscos Viaje al Pacífico*, 1: 126.

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Isla de Puna (RMNH 114207); Colonche (■MCZ 145194); 9 km S Manglaralto (■UF 139114); 4 km N Monteverde (■UF 139077, 139115); environs of Palmar (■UF 139056, 139078, 139090); environs of Progreso (■UF 139040, 139047, 139079, 139110); 3 km E Zapotal (■UF 139106); Santa Elena (TL); Manabí: Agua Blanca (Roosen, pers. obs. 2019); 1 km S Ayampe (■UF 139048); 11 km WSW Jipijapa (■UF 139038); Manta (■MCZ 125318); Las Cruces (■MCZ 113835).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178], Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214], Guayaquil flooded grassland [NT0905].

Figure 195. A, B: *Bostryx alausiensis* (Cousin, 1887), Chimborazo, Achupallas, lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-20820 (H 24.5 mm); C-E: *Bostryx juana* (Cousin, 1887), Azuay, Gualaceo, lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-21318 (H 23.5 mm). Figure 196. *Bostryx bilineatus* (G.B. Sowerby I, 1833). A: Guayas, Santa Elena, syntype ZMB 10261 (H 14.1 mm); B, C: Manabí, Agua Blanca, M. Roosen leg. (H 14.5 mm); D: Manabí, Salango, living specimen (photo: Adrián González Guillén).
 Figura 195. A, B: *Bostryx alausiensis* (Cousin, 1887), Chimborazo, Achupallas, lectotipo MNHN-IM-2000-20820 (H 24,5 mm); C-E: *Bostryx juana* (Cousin, 1887), Azuay, Gualaceo, lectotipo MNHN-IM-2000-21318 (H 23,5 mm). Figura 196. *Bostryx bilineatus* (G.B. Sowerby I, 1833). A: Guayas, Santa Elena, sintipo ZMB 10261 (H 14,1 mm); B, C: Manabí, Agua Blanca, M. Roosen leg. (H 14,5 mm); D: Manabí, Salango, ejemplar vivo (foto: Adrián González Guillén).

Remarks. BREURE & ARAUJO (2017) have argued that d'Orbigny's taxon, which is from Bolivia and belongs to the genus *Naesiotus* (BREURE & ABLETT, 2014: 78), is similar in shape and size to Sowerby's taxon and may be easily confused. LINARES & VERA (2012: 180) listed this species also from Colombia, but with reference only to 19th century collections which do not reflect the current limits of that country. Given the distribution above this is understood as an Ecuadorian endemic species.

Bostryx juana (Cousin, 1887) (Figs. 195C-E, 197)

Thaumastus juana Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 228, pl. 4 fig. 10. "Gualacco, province de Cuença". Lectotype (BREURE, 1975: 1141) MNHN-IM-2000-21318; paralectotypes MNHN-IM-2000-21319 (6), RBINS MT.2357 (7).

Distribution. Azuay: Gualaceo (TL); between Santa Ana and San Bartolomé (RMNH 114400).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Figure 197. Distribution of Bulimulidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.
 Figura 197. Distribución de Bulimulidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Genus *Drymaeus* Albers, 1850

Drymaeus Albers, 1850, *Die Heliceen*: 155. Type species by subsequent designation *Helix hygrohyla* d'Orbigny, 1835.

Remarks. The species from adjacent Colombia have recently been revised by BREURE & BORRERO (2019), and a key to subgenera was given. Please note that the colour pattern in *Drymaeus* species may be variable, so the figures presented may not conclusively show the whole variation within a certain species.

Subgenus *Drymaeus* (*Drymaeus*)

Drymaeus (*Drymaeus*) *aequatorianus* (E.A. Smith, 1877) (Figs. 198, 212)

Bulimus (*Drymaeus*) *aequatorianus* Smith, 1877, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 45: 363, pl. 30 fig. 7. "Ecuador".

Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 106) NHMUK 1975137; paralectotypes NHMUK 1975138 (3).

Drymaeus aequatorianus var. *elata* Germain, 1907, *Bull. Mus. Nat. Hist. Nat.*, 13: 57. "Cerro de San Tadeo, chemin de Pachajal". Type material not located.

Distribution. Carchi: 1.5 hour walk W Chical; San Nicolas (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008); Pichincha: San Tadeo (GERMAIN, 1907); Tandayapa (WILLIAMS, 2002: fig. 1); Mindo, Mindo Cloudforest reserve, Yellow House trails (Roosen, pers. observ.).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. LINARES & VERA (2012: 180) listed this species, misspelled as *aequatorianus*, from southern Colombia, but see the comments in BREURE & BORRERO (2019: 5-6).

Drymaeus (*Drymaeus*) *albolabiatu*s (E.A. Smith, 1877) (Figs. 199, 212)

Bulimus (*Drymaeus*) *albolabiatu*s Smith, 1877, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 45: 363, pl. 39 fig. 4. "Malacatos, South Ecuador". Holotype NHMUK 1877.3.28.3.

Figure 198. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) aequatorianus* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Ecuador: unknown locality. Lectotype NHMUK 1975137 (H 26.6 mm). Figure 199. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) albolabiatus* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Loja: Malacatos. Holotype NHMUK 1877.3.28.3 (H 34 mm).

Figura 198. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) aequatorianus* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Ecuador: localidad desconocida. Lectotipo NHMUK 1975137 (H 26,6 mm). Figura 199. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) albolabiatus* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Loja: Malacatos. Holotipo NHMUK 1877.3.28.3 (H 34 mm).

Distribution. Loja: Malacatos (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. May prove to be a synonym of *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) orthostoma* (E.A. Smith 1877); see BREURE & BORRERO (2008: 22).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) ambustus (Reeve, 1849) (Figs. 200, 212)

Bulimus ambustus Reeve, 1849 [1848-1850], *Conch. Icon.*, 5: pl. 74 fig. 535. “—?”. Lectotype (BREURE & ESKENS, 1981: 5) NHMUK 1975441.

Bulimus loxensis var. β *minor* L. Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 422 [nomen nudum].

Bulimus chamaeleon L. Pfeiffer, 1854 [in Küster & Pfeiffer 1840-1865], *Syst. Conch.-Cab.* (1) 13 (1): 105, pl. 33 figs 17-18. “Quito”. Syntypes NHMUK 1975448 (3).

Distribution. Napo: Baeza; Pichincha: Alchipichi; Nanegal; Casitagua (GERMAIN, 1907); “Quito” (SALVADOR ET AL., 2021); Tungurahua: Ambato; Mocha (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017 unless mentioned otherwise); Tacunga (ORTON, 1871).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Probably erroneously also mentioned from Peru (see BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) andai Jousseume, 1898 (Figs. 201, 212)

Drymaeus andai Jousseume, 1898, *Le Naturaliste*, (2) 12: 14. “Tena, Équateur”. Lectotype (BREURE, 1975: 1149) MNHN-IM-2000-23113.

Distribution. Napo: Tena (TL); Nachiyacu (ANSP 170711).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. The single ANSP specimen, identified as *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) inaequalis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1857) and which was listed as such by BREURE & BORRERO (2008), appears to be a misidentification for this species. *Drymaeus inaequalis*, for which no type material has been located, is listed from Peru by RAMÍREZ ET AL. (2003).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) baezensis (Hidalgo, 1869) (Figs. 202, 212)

Bulimus baezensis Hidalgo, 1869, *J. de Conchyl.*, 17: 189. “Baeza, reipublitaie Aequatoris”. Lectotype (BREURE, 1975: 1149) MNHN-IM-2000-23112; paralectotypes MNCN 15.05/3154 (3), 15.05/3155 (2), 15.05/3205 (5), 15.05/3206 (7).

Distribution. Napo: Baeza (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. The record by GERMAIN (1907: 57) of this species from Pichincha, near Calacali needs further confirmation.

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) bourcierii (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) (Figs. 203, 212)

Bulimus bourcierii Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 314. “Pichincha reipublicae Aequatoris”. Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 107) NHMUK 1975446; paralectotypes NHMUK 1975447 (2).

Figure 200. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) ambustus* (Reeve, 1849). Unknown locality. Lectotype NHMUK 1975441 (H 29 mm). Figure 201. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) andai* Jousseaume, 1898. Napo: Tena. Lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-23113 (H 43.2 mm).
Figura 200. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) ambustus* (Reeve, 1849). *Localidad desconocida.* Lectotipo NHMUK 1975441 (H 29 mm). *Figura 201.* *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) andai* Jousseaume, 1898. Napo: Tena. Lectotipo MNHN-IM-2000-23113 (H 43,2 mm).

Distribution. Pichincha: without specific locality; Tungurahua: Chaupi (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).
Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Figure 202. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) baezensis* (Hidalgo, 1869). Napo: Baeza. Lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-23112 (H 30.5 mm). Figure 203. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) bourcierii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Pichincha: unknown locality. Lectotype NHMUK 1975446 (H 23.9 mm).
Figura 202. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) baezensis* (*Hidalgo, 1869*). *Napo: Baeza. Lectotipo MNHN-IM-2000-23112 (H 30,5 mm).* *Figura 203.* *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) bourcierii* (*L. Pfeiffer, 1853*). *Pichincha: localidad desconocida. Lectotipo NHMUK 1975446 (H 23,9 mm).*

Figure 204. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) chimborasensis* (Reeve, 1848). Chimborazo. Syntype NHMUK 1975460 (H 39.7 mm). Figure 205. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) chrysomelas* (Martens, 1867). Peru: Chanchamayo.. Lectotype ZMB 11835 (H 46.5 mm).
 Figura 204. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) chimborasensis* (Reeve, 1848). Chimborazo. Sintipo NHMUK 1975460 (H 39,7 mm). Figura 205. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) chrysomelas* (Martens, 1867). Peru: Chanchamayo. Localidad desconocida. Lectotipo ZMB 11835 (H 46,5 mm).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) chimborasensis (Reeve, 1848) (Figs. 204, 212)

Bulinus chimborasensis Reeve, 1848 [1848-1850], *Conch. Icon.*, 5: pl. 44 fig. 275. "Chimborazo, Columbia [sic, Ecuador], New Granada". Syntypes NHMUK 1975460 (3).

Distribution. Chimborazo [probably on the slopes of Cerro Chimborazo, which could also be in Prov. Bolívar or Tungurahua].

Ecoregion. North Andean páramo [NT1006].

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) chrysomelas (Martens, 1867) (Fig. 205)

Bulinulus (Thaumastus) chrysomelas Martens, 1867, *Malak. Bl.*, 14: 145. ["oberes Amazonenstrom-gebiets"]. Lectotype (KÖHLER, 2007: 144) ZMB 11835a.

Distribution. Napo: without precise locality (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017).

Remarks. Also reported from Peru (KÖHLER, 2007).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) expansus (L. Pfeiffer, 1848) (Figs. 206, 212)

Bulinus expansus Pfeiffer, 1848, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 2: 60. [Peru] "Huallaga". Type material not located.

Mesembrinus (Mormus) expansus orcesi Weyrauch, 1958, *Archiv für. Moll.*, 87: 130, pl. 7 fig. 15. "Ecuador, Montalvo, Rio Bobonaza, Zufluss des Rio Pastaza, 314 m, 270 km SE Quito". Holotype SMF 156292.

Figure 206. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) expansus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1848). Peru: Huallaga. Holotype of (*Mesembrinus (Mormus) expansus orcesi* Weyrauch, 1958, SMF 156292 (H 41 mm). Figure 207. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) fallax* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Tungurahua: unknown locality. Lectotype NHMUK 1969142 (H 22.4 mm).

Figura 206. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) expansus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1848). Perú: Huallaga. Holotipo de *Mesembrinus (Mormus) expansus orcesi* Weyrauch, 1958, SMF 156292 (H 41 mm). Figura 207. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) fallax* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Tungurahua: localidad desconocida. Lectotipo NHMUK 1969142 (H 22,4 mm).

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Cusuimi (■FMNH 173050); Orellana: Loreto; Pastaza: Montalvo (TL *orcesi*); *ibid.*, Sarayacu (all WEYRAUCH, 1958); Canelos (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Tungurahua: Topo (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. Also reported from Brazil, Colombia, and Peru (RAMÍREZ ET AL., 2003; SIMONE, 2006; LINARES & VERA, 2012; BREURE & BORRERO, 2019). This species seems to be widespread and several subspecies have been described from its distribution range. A critical revision, using morphological, anatomical and molecular data, is much needed. Until then this species is classified as a variable species (*sensu lato*).

Figure 208. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) fucatus* (Reeve, 1849). Unknown locality. Lectotype NHMUK 1874.12.11.224 (H 23.5 mm). Figure 209. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) hidalgoi* (S.I. da Costa, 1898). Ecuador. Holotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.28 (H 39 mm).

Figura 208. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) fucatus* (Reeve, 1849). Localidad desconocida. Lectotipo NHMUK 1874.12.11.224 (H 23,5 mm). Figura 209. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) hidalgoi* (S.I. da Costa, 1898). Ecuador. Holotipo NHMUK 1907.11.21.28 (H 39 mm).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) fallax (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) (Figs. 207, 214A, 212)

Bulimus fallax Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 375. "Tunguragua reipublicae Aequatoris".

Lectotype (BREURE & ABLETT, 2014: 72) NHMUK 1969142.

Hamadryas fallax var. *major* Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 219. "le long du chemin d'Aloag à Chones, canton de Mégia". Syntype RBINS MT.3815 (1).

Distribution. Pastaza: Puyo; Pichincha: Quito; *ibid*, near Aloag; Nono [formerly Mitad del Mundo]; Alaspungo (GERMAIN, 1907) [Alaspungu]; near Nanegal; Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Santo Domingo de los Colorados (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008, unless mentioned otherwise); Tungurahua: without precise locality (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) fucatus (Reeve, 1849) (Figs. 208, 212)

Bulimus fucatus Reeve, 1849 [1848-1850], *Conch. Icon.*, 5: pl. 83 fig. 615. No type locality given.

Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 109) NHMUK 1874.12.11.224.

Distribution. Pichincha: Nanegal (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Also reported from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 187); see comments in BREURE & BORRERO (2019: 17).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) hidalgoi (S.I. da Costa, 1898) (Figs. 209, 212)

Bulimulus (Drymaeus) hidalgoi da Costa, 1898, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 3: 81, pl. 6 fig. 2.

"Ecuador". Holotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.28.

Distribution. Napo: Nachiyacu; Pastaza: Mera (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) joubini Germain, 1907 (Fig. 210)

Drymaeus (Antidrymaeus) joubini Germain, 1907, *Bull. Mus. Nat. Hist. Nat.*, 13: 59, fig. 2. "République de l'Équateur". Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-23014.

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality (TL).

Remarks. This is a sinistral species of which neither a precise locality nor anatomical data are known. It has not been re-found after the original description. A paper on the status of *Drymaeus (Antidrymaeus)* species is in preparation, but as this group is defined by anatomical and molecular data it is unsure if Germain's taxon belongs to it; therefore it is tentatively placed in the nominate subgenus.

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) membielinus (Crosse, 1867) (Figs. 211, 212)

Bulimus membielinus Crosse, 1867, *J. de Conchyl.*, 15: 445. "in Republica Aequatoris". Syntypes

MNCN 15.05/7355 (1), MNCN 15.05/20344 (1).

Figure 210. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) joubini* Germain, 1907. Ecuador. Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-23014 (H 26.5 mm). Figure 211. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) membrielinus* (Crosse, 1867). Ecuador. Syntype MNCN 15.05/7355 (H 38.6 mm).

Figura 210. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) joubini* Germain, 1907. Ecuador. Holotipo MNHN-IM-2000-23014 (H 26,5 mm). *Figura 211.* *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) membrielinus* (Crosse, 1867). Ecuador. Sintipo MNCN 15.05/7355 (H 38,6 mm).

Distribution. Napo (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Orellana: Loreto (WEYRAUCH, 1958).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. Also listed from Peru (RAMÍREZ *ET AL.*, 2003).

Figure 212. Distribution of Bulimulidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.
 Figura 212. Distribución de Bulimulidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) nystianus (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) (Figs. 213, 214B, 226)

Bulimus nystianus Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 374. “in valle Pomasqui reipublicae Aequatoris”. Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 112) NHMUK 1975573.

Thaumastus (?) *nystianus* var. *lutea* Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: map 220.

Thaumastus (?) *nystianus* var. *nigricans* Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 221.

Distribution. Napo: Cerro Antisana; Pichincha: Pomasqui (TL); Machachi (all BREURE & BORRERO, 2008; BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Tumbaco (PILSBRY, 1898 [1897-1898]: 263).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) ochrocheilus (E.A. Smith, 1877) (Figs. 215, 226)

Bulimus (Drymaeus) ochrocheilus Smith, 1877, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 45: 364, pl. 39 fig. 5. “Malacatos, South Ecuador”. Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 112) NHMUK 1877.3.28.4.

Distribution. Loja: Malacatos (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) orthostoma (E.A. Smith, 1877) (Figs. 216, 226)

Bulimus (Drymaeus) orthostoma Smith, 1877, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 45: 364, pl. 39 fig. 5. “Ecuador?”. Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 112) NHMUK 1975132; paralectotypes NHMUK 1975133 (2).

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality.

Remarks. May prove to be a synonym of *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) albolabiatus* (E.A. Smith, 1877); see BREURE & BORRERO (2008: 22). Records of this species in GBIF could

Figure 213. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) nystianus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Pichincha: Pomasqui. Lectotype NHMUK 1975573 (H 31.9 mm). Figure 214. Living specimens. A: *Drymaeus (D.) fallax* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853), Imbabura, Apuela; B: *Drymaeus (D.) nystianus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853), Imbabura, Buenos Aires (photos: Adrián González Guillén).

Figura 213. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) nystianus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Pichincha: Pomasqui. Lectotipo NHMUK 1975573 (H 31,9 mm). Figura 214. Fotografías de especímenes vivos. A: *Drymaeus (D.) fallax* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853), Imbabura, Apuela; B: *Drymaeus (D.) nystianus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853), Imbabura, Buenos Aires (fotos: Adrián González Guillén).

not be verified, but seem at least partly to be misidentifications; which are the reasons why we have been reluctant to include them without prior verification. This species is also listed from Peru by RAMÍREZ *ET AL.* (2003).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) peelii (Reeve, 1859) (Figs. 217, 226)

Bulimus peelii Reeve, 1859, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 27: 123. "Peruvian side of Amazonas". Type material not located.

Drymaeus fordii Pilsbry, 1898 [1897-1898], *Man. Conch.*, (2) 11: 205, pl. 38 figs 1-3. Locality unknown. Lectotype (BAKER, 1963: 227) ANSP 72368.

Figure 215. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) ochrocheilus* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Loja: Malacatos. Lectotype NHMUK 1877.3.28.4 (H 37.1 mm). Figure 216. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) orthostoma* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Ecuador. Lectotype NHMUK 1975312 (H 36.5 mm).

Figura 215. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) ochrocheilus* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Loja: Malacatos. Lectotipo NHMUK 1877.3.28.4 (H 37,1 mm). Figura 216. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) orthostoma* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Ecuador. Lectotipo NHMUK 1975312 (H 36,5 mm).

Figure 217. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) peelii* (Reeve, 1859). Unknown locality. Lectotype of *Drymaeus fordii* Pilsbry, 1898, ANSP 72368 (H 42.5 mm). Figure 218. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) petasites* (K. Miller, 1878). Pichincha: Nanegal. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 7 fig. 2 (H 36 mm).
 Figura 217. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) peelii* (Reeve, 1859). Localidad desconocida. Lectotipo de *Drymaeus fordii* Pilsbry, 1898, ANSP 72368 (H 42,5 mm). Figura 218. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) petasites* (K. Miller, 1878). Pichincha: Nanegal. Figura original en MILLER (1879): pl. 7 fig. 2 (H 36 mm).

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Miasal; Orellana: Loreto (both according to WEYRAUCH, 1958); Pastaza, Canelos (MARTENS, 1885a: 160).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. Also listed from Peru (RAMÍREZ *ET AL.*, 2003).

Figure 219. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) planibasis* Pilsbry, 1932. Chimborazo: Chunchi. Holotype ANSP 148436 (H 34.8 mm).

Figura 219. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) planibasis* Pilsbry, 1932. Chimborazo: Chunchi. Holotipo ANSP 148436 (H 34,8 mm).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) petasites (K. Miller, 1878) (Figs. 218, 226)

Otostomus (Drymaeus) petasites Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 189; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 4 (sic, 7) figs 2a-b. "cum praecedente [Nanegal, Sebondo; in valli Pilatonensi, 1000 m (P. Boetzkes)]; Nanegal" [restricted to Nanegal (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008: 22)]. Type material not located.

Distribution. Los Ríos: 35 mi E of Quevedo; Pichincha: Nanegal; valley of Río Pilatón; Los Puentes (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008); Mindo (CORREOSO, 2008); Tulipe (Roosen pers. obs. 2019).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) planibasis Pilsbry, 1932 (Figs. 219, 226)

Drymaeus planibasis Pilsbry, 1932, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 84: 395, pl. 28 fig. 18. "Ecuador, above Chunchi, Pagma Forest". Holotype ANSP 148436.

Distribution. Chimborazo: Chunchi (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) quadrifasciatus (Angas, 1878) (Figs. 220, 226)

Bulimus (Otostomus) quadrifasciatus Angas, 1878, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 46: 312, pl. 18 figs 2-3. "Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 113) NHMUK 1879.1.21.3.

Bulimus (Otostomus) napo Angas, 1878, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 46: 312, pl. 18 figs 4-5. "Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 111) NHMUK 1879.1.21.4.

Figure 220. *Drymaeus* (*Drymaeus*) *quadrifasciatus* (Angas, 1878). Ecuador. A-C: lectotype NHMUK 1879.1.21.3 (H 28.9 mm); D-F: lectotype of *Bulimus* (*Otostomus*) *napo* Angas, 1878 NHMUK 1879.1.21.4 (H 31.1 mm).

Figura 220. *Drymaeus* (*Drymaeus*) *quadrifasciatus* (Angas, 1878). Ecuador. A-C: lectotipo NHMUK 1879.1.21.3 (H 28,9 mm); D-F: lectotipo de *Bulimus* (*Otostomus*) *napo* Angas, 1878, NHMUK 1879.1.21.4 (H 31,1 mm).

Distribution. Napo: Cuyuja (GERMAIN, 1907); Pichincha: Nanegal (WEYRAUCH, 1958); Tungurahua: Cerro Tungurahua near Baños (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. GERMAIN (1907) mentioned another locality, "Guila", which could not be located in gazetteers.

Figure 221. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rabuti* (Jousseau, 1898). Napo: Tena. Lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-21314 (H 25.7 mm). Figure 222. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rhoadsi* Pilsbry, 1932. Pichincha: Río Pachijal valley. Holotype ANSP 148440 (H 38.3 mm).

Figura 221. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rabuti* (Jousseau, 1898). Napo: Tena. Lectotipo MNHN-IM-2000-21314 (H 25,7 mm). Figura 222. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rhoadsi* Pilsbry, 1932. Pichincha: Valle del río Pachijal. Holotipo ANSP 148440 (H 38,3 mm).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rabuti (Jousseau, 1898) (Figs. 221, 226)

Hamadryas rabuti Jousseau, 1898, *Le Naturaliste*, (2) 12: 14. "Tena, Équateur". Lectotype (BREURE, 1975: 1152) MNHN-IM-2000-21314.

Distribution. Napo: Tena (TL).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rhoadsi Pilsbry, 1932 (Figs. 222, 226)

Drymaeus rhoadsi Pilsbry, 1932, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 84: 394, pl. 28 fig. 5. "Ecuador, Pachijal". Holotype ANSP 148440.

Figure 223. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rubrovariegatus* (Higgins, 1868). Peru: Huamachuco. Syntype NHMUK 1868.4.3.1 (H 32.8 mm). Figure 224. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) sachsei* (Albers, 1854). Peru: Río Marañón. A: lectotype ZMB 10290a (H 30 mm); B: paralectotype MHNG-MOLL-63524 (H 31.9 mm). Figure 225. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) strigatus* (G.B. Sowerby I, 1833). Peru: Huallaga. Syntype NHMUK 20090168 (H 24.9 mm).

Figura 223. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rubrovariegatus* (Higgins, 1868). Perú: Huamachuco. Sintipo NHMUK 1868.4.3.1 (H 32,8 mm). Figura 224. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) sachsei* (Albers, 1854). Perú: Río Marañón. A: lectotipo ZMB 10290a (H 30 mm); B: paralectotipo MHNG-MOLL-63524 (H 31,9 mm). Figura 225. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) strigatus* (G.B. Sowerby I, 1833). Perú: Huallaga. Sintipo NHMUK 20090168 (H 24,9 mm).

Distribution. Pichincha: Río Pachijal valley (TL); Mindo (WEYRAUCH, 1967b).
Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rubrovariegatus (Higgins, 1868) (Figs. 223, 226)

Bulinus (Ostostomus) rubrovariegatus Higgins 1868, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 36: 178, pl. 12 figs 2-2a. "Huamachuco, Peru". Syntypes NHMUK 1868.4.3.1 (3).

Distribution. El Oro: 6 km N Zaruma on road to Malvas (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).
Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].
Remarks. Also listed from Peru (RAMÍREZ *ET AL.*, 2003).

Figure 226. Distribution of Bulimulidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.
 Figura 226. Distribución de Bulimulidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) sachsei (Albers, 1854) (Figs. 224, 226)

Bulimus sachsei Albers, 1854, *Malak. Bl.*, 1: 30. "Columbia australi [sic, Peru] ad fluvium Maranhon". Lectotype (KÖHLER, 2007: 148) ZMB 10290a.

Ostotomus (Mormus) catamayensis K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 120, pl. 12 fig. 4. "Catamayo (prov. Loja) 2000-3000'". Type material not located.

Distribution. Chimborazo: Huigra; Loja: Catamayo; Loja (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Also listed from Peru (RAMÍREZ ET AL., 2003).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) strigatus (G.B. Sowerby I, 1833) (Figs. 225, 226)

Bulinus strigatus Sowerby I, 1833 [in Sowerby I & II, 1832-1841], *Conch. Illustr.*: figs 95-96. "[Peru] Huallaga". Syntypes NHMUK 20090168 (3).

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Cushuimi (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. Also listed from Peru (RAMÍREZ ET AL., 2003).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) tigrinus (S.I. da Costa, 1898) (Fig. 227)

Bulimulus (Drymaeus) tigrinus da Costa, 1898, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 3: 82, pl. 6 fig. 6. "Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 115) NHMUK 1907.11.21.55; paralectotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.56 (1).

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality.

Figure 227. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) tigrinus* (S.I. da Costa, 1898). Ecuador. Lectotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.55 (H 20.8 mm). Figure 228. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) volsus* Fulton, 1907. Ecuador. Lectotype NHMUK 1907.5.3.162 (H 30.3 mm).

Figura 227. *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) tigrinus* (S.I. da Costa, 1898). Ecuador. Lectotipo NHMUK 1907.11.21.55 (H 20,8 mm). *Figura 228.* *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) volsus* Fulton, 1907. Ecuador. Lectotipo NHMUK 1907.5.3.162 (H 30,3 mm).

Remarks. PILSBRY (1898 [1897-1898]: 231) suggested that this taxon may be a junior synonym of *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) strigatus* (G.B. Sowerby, 1833).

Drymaeus (Drymaeus) volsus Fulton, 1907 (Fig. 228)

Drymaeus volsus Fulton, 1907, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, (7) 19: 153, pl. 10 fig. 2. "Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 115) NHMUK 1907.5.3.162.

Figure 229. *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) cactivorus* (Broderip, 1832). Loja: unknown locality. Original figure of *Ostostomus (Mormus) occidentalis* in MILLER (1879): pl. 13 fig. 2 (H 23 mm).

Figura 229. *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) cactivorus* (Broderip, 1832). Loja: localidad desconocida. Figura original de *Ostostomus (Mormus) occidentalis* en MILLER (1879): pl. 13 fig. 2 (H 23 mm).

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality.

Remarks. This species was also mentioned for eastern Colombia by BREURE & BORRERO (2019: 27).

Subgenus *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus)* Albers, 1850

Mesembrinus Albers, 1850, *Die Heliceen*: 157. Type species by subsequent designation (Martens in ALBERS & MARTENS, 1860: 214) *Helix virgulata* A. Férussac, 1821.

Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) cactivorus (Broderip, 1832) (Figs. 229, 240)

Bulinus cactivorus Broderip in Broderip & Sowerby I, 1832, *Proc. Comm. Corr. Zool. Soc. London*, 2: 31. "ad montem Chris". Type material not located.

Ostostomus (Mormus) occidentalis K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 121, pl. 13 fig. 2. "in campis provinciae Loja, qui Peruvianae provinciae Tumbes adjacent, 100 m; Guayaquil". Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: 3 km E Zapotal; 11 km W Progreso (Gomés Rendón) (both BREURE & BORRERO, 2008); Loja: without specific locality (MILLER, 1879); Manabí: Agua Blanca (Roosen, pers. obs. 2019).

Ecoregion. Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214], Guayaquil flooded grasses [NT0905].

Remarks. Also listed from Peru (RAMÍREZ ET AL., 2003).

Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) flavidulus (E.A. Smith, 1877) (Figs. 230, 240)

Bulinus (Liostracus) flavidulus Smith, 1877, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 45: 364, pl. 39 fig. 3. "Zaruma, South Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 119) NHMUK 1975134; paralectotypes NHMUK 1877.3.28.5 (2).

Distribution. El Oro: Zaruma (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Figure 230. *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) flavidulus* (E.A. Smith, 1877). El Oro: Zaruma. Paralectotype NHMUK 1877.3.28.5 (H 22 mm). Figure 231. *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) loxanus* (Higgins, 1872). Loja: unknown locality. Lectotype NHMUK 1975552 (H 26.5 mm).

Figura 230. *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) flavidulus* (E.A. Smith, 1877). El Oro: Zaruma. Paralectotipo NHMUK 1877.3.28.5 (H 22 mm). *Figura 231.* *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) loxanus* (Higgins, 1872). Loja: localidad desconocida. Lectotipo NHMUK 1975552 (H 26,5 mm).

Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) loxanus (Higgins, 1872) (Figs. 231, 240)

Ostostomus loxanus Higgins, 1872, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 40: 685, pl. 56 figs 2-2a. "Loxa". Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 121) NHMUK 1975552 (1).

Distribution. Loja: without specific locality (TL).

Remarks. This species was listed from Colombia by LINARES & VERA (2012: 196), but BREURE & BORRERO (2019: 46) regarded this as very doubtful and have excluded it from that malacofauna. Therefore this species is now considered an Ecuadorian endemic.

Figure 232. *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) loxensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846). Loja: Catamayo. Lectotype NHMUK 1975553 (H 34.7 mm).

Figura 232. *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) loxensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846). Loja: Catamayo. Lectotipo NHMUK 1975553 (H 34,7 mm).

Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) loxensis (L. Pfeiffer, 1846) (Figs. 232, 240)

Bulimus loxensis Pfeiffer, 1846, *Symb. Helic.*, 3: 85. "El Catamaja prope Loxa reipublicae Aequatoris". Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 119) NHMUK 1975553; paralectotypes NHMUK 1975554 (2).

Distribution. Loja: Catamayo (TL); road to Gonzanama (RMNH 114404).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) subpellucidus (E.A. Smith, 1877) (Fig. 233)

Bulimulus (Liostracus) subpellucidus Smith, 1877, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 45: 364, pl. 39 fig. 2. "Ecuador". Syntype NHMUK 1872.5.22.19 (1).

Distribution. Ecuador: without precise locality (TL).

Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) wintlei Finch, 1929 (Fig. 234)

Drymaeus wintlei Finch, 1929, *J. of Conch.*, 18: 275, figs. "Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE, 1979: 125) NHMUK 1929.6.11.1.

Distribution. Ecuador: without precise locality (TL).

Comments on the genus. In the literature the following species related to this genus have been mentioned as occurring in Ecuador:

- *Bulimus lautus* Gould (1856, *Proc. Boston Soc. Nat. Hist.*, 6: 12) was described "From the mountains of Equador, near Quito", and compared to *B. semiclausus*, *B. knorri*, *B.*

Figure 233. *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) subpellucidus* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Ecuador. Syntype NHMUK 1872.5.22.19 (H 20 mm). Figure 234. *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) wintlei* Finch, 1929. Ecuador. Lectotype NHMUK 1929.6.11.1 (H 21.7 mm).

Figura 233. *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) subpellucidus* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Ecuador. Sintipo NHMUK 1872.5.22.19 (H 20 mm). Figura 234. *Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) wintlei* Finch, 1929. Ecuador. Lectotipo NHMUK 1929.6.11.1 (H 21,7 mm).

murrinus and *B. fabrefactus*, which are all *Drymaeus* species with an angulated aperture. This unfigured species was placed by all later authors in the synonymy of *Bulimus fallax* Pfeiffer, 1853; JOHNSON (1964: 99) was unable to locate Gould's type material. Since Gould stated that the collector, Joseph P. Couthouy, found the material "near Chimborazo" where *Drymaeus fallax* does not occur, we consider Gould's taxon as a *nomen inquirendum*.

- *Bulimus elegantissimus* Mousson (1873, *Malak. Bl.*, 21: 11) was described from “Nördlichem Süd-Amerika” and was reported by BREURE & BORRERO (2008) from southern Ecuador based on material in FMNH (173042, 173043). We have now seen this material and this is a putative new species. Mousson’s taxon was considered as a junior subjective synonym of the Colombian *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) felix* (L. Pfeiffer, 1862) by BREURE & BORRERO (2019).

The following species from this genus is no longer considered as belonging to the Ecuadorian malacofauna:

- *Bulimus inaequalis* Pfeiffer (1857, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 24: 330) was described from “Banks of the Maranhon” and was listed as *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) inaequalis* (Pfeiffer, 1857) by BREURE & BORRERO (2008). This was based on an unconfirmed record in ANSP which, after consultation and re-identification, is now listed under *D. (D.) andai* Jousseume above.

Genus *Naesiotus* Albers, 1850

Naesiotus Albers, 1850, *Die Heliceen*: 162. Type species by subsequent designation (Martens in ALBERS & MARTENS, 1860: 220) *Bulinus nux* Broderip, 1832.

Remarks. The type species of *Naesiotus* occurs on the Galápagos, where a radiation of this genus is present (Shoobs, forthcoming). The relation between the island and the mainland species classified as *Naesiotus* needs further research.

Naesiotus florschuetzi Breure, 1978 (Figs. 235, 240)

Naesiotus florschuetzi Breure, 1978, *Zool. Verh. Leiden*, 164: 160, pl. 2 fig. 2. “Ecuador, Prov. El Oro, 31 miles N Santa Rosa”. Holotype UF 22772.

Distribution. El Oro: 31 miles N Santa Rosa (TL); Guayas: 4 km N Palmar (UF 139089). **Ecoregion.** Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214], Tumbes-Piura dry forests [NT0232].

Remarks. The material was originally collected by K. Campbell who did not provide field notes (J. Slapcinsky, pers. commun. 17 August 2020); therefore the precise type locality and habitat of the species remains unknown. If we assume he followed the road towards Guayaquil, the type locality would be in the region of Pagua, Prov. El Oro.

Naesiotus fontainii (d’Orbigny, 1838) (Figs. 236, 240)

Bulimus fontainii d’Orbigny, 1838 [1834-1847], *Voyage Amér. mérid.*, 5 (3): 273. “environs de Guayaquil”. Lectotype (BREURE & ABLETT, 2014: 78) NHMUK 1854.12.4.165.

Distribution. Guayas: near Guayaquil (TL).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Naesiotus quitensis (L. Pfeiffer, 1848) (Figs. 237, 240)

Bulimus quitensis Pfeiffer, 1848, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 2: 230. [Ecuador] “Quito”. Lectotype (BREURE & COPPOIS, 1978: 181) NHMUK 1975230.

Bulimus irregularis L. Pfeiffer, 1848, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 2: 231. “Quito, Ecuador”. Syntype NHMUK 20100564 (1).

Figure 235. *Naesiotus florschuetzi* Breure, 1978. El Oro: 31 miles N Santa Rosa. Holotype UF 22772 (H 22.5 mm). Figure 236. *Naesiotus fontainii* (d'Orbigny, 1838). Guayas: near Guayaquil. Lectotype NHMUK 1854.12.4.165 (H 13.2 mm).

Figura 235. *Naesiotus florschuetzi* Breure, 1978. El Oro: 31 millas al N de Santa Rosa. Holotipo UF 22772 (H 22,5 mm). Figura 236. *Naesiotus fontainii* (d'Orbigny, 1838). Guayas: cerca de Guayaquil. Lectotipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.165 (H 13,2 mm).

Bulinus caliginosus Reeve, 1849 [1848-1850], *Conch. Icon.*, 5: pl. 82 fig. 609. No locality given. Lectotype (BREURE & ABLETT, 2014: 37) NHMUK 20100518/1, paralectotypes NHMUK 20100518/2-3 (3).

Bulinus catlowiae L. Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 427. "prope Quito". Lectotype 1975414 (BREURE & COPPOIS, 1978: 182); paralectotype ZMB 1566 (1).

Naesiotus quitensis jacksoni Rehder, 1940, *Nautilus*, 53: 116, pl. 13 figs 1, 5. "Guaillabamba, Prov. del Pichincha, some 22 miles northeast of Quito on the western slope of the eastern Andes". Holotype USNM 473969.

Naesiotus quitensis orinus Rehder, 1940, *Nautilus*, 53: 116, pl. 13 figs 6, 10. "foothills of Chimborazo, near Riobamba, Prov. del Chimborazo, approximately 12,000 feet". Holotype USNM 473971.
Naesiotus quitensis vermiculatus Rehder, 1940, *Nautilus*, 53: 117, pl. 13 figs 17, 19. "Agoyan on the Río Pastaza, near Baños Tungurahua, in the Provincia del Tungurahua". Holotype MCZ 64957.
Naesiotus quitensis ambatensis Rehder, 1940, *Nautilus*, 53: 117, pl. 13 figs 12, 14. "Ambato, Prov. del Tungurahua". Holotype USNM 473973.
Naesiotus quitensis antisana Rehder, 1942, *Nautilus*, 55: 103. "Ecuador, Prov. Pichincha, slopes of Mt. Antisana". Holotype USNM 516940.

Distribution. Carchi: 35 km N Ibarra on the road to El Angel, 1700 m; Chimborazo: Riobamba; S of Cajabamba; Cerro de Altar (PILSBRY 1897 [1897-1898]: 33); Imbabura: Cerro Imbabura; Chota; 9.4 km N Ibarra; Otavalo (PILSBRY 1896 [1895-1896]: 159); Pillaro (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); ?"Salinas Ibarre, 1659 m, coll. Stübel" (PILSBRY 1897 [1897-1898]: 34); Napo: slopes of Mt. Antisana; Pastaza: Cerros de Abitagua; *ibid.*, ?Río Pastaza, 3.2 km above Falls Agougou; *ibid.*, ?banks of Río Pastaza [both localities not located in modern gazetteers]; Pichincha: "Quito"; Parque Metropolitano de Quito (CORREOSO, 2008); 14.5 km NW Quito; slopes Cerro Pichincha; Pomasqui; 13.9 km W Pifo; Cayambe; Tumbaco; Guailabamba (both PILSBRY 1897 [1897-1898]: 34); 1 km W Mitad del Mundo [Nono], 2400 m; 22.6 km NNE Quito at the road to Cayambe, 2200 m; Chimba, 3 km E Olmedo; Cumbayá, 9.6 km NE Quito; above Chillogallo (PILSBRY 1897 [1897-1898]: 33); Tungurahua: 8 km N San Antonio; Ambato (PILSBRY 1897 [1897-1898]: 35); Cerro Cachigani near Ambato; Puñapi; Baños; Río Agoyán falls (BREURE & BORRERO, 2008, unless mentioned otherwise).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145], North Andean páramo [NT1006].

Remarks. The different subspecies introduced by Rehder need further study as they cover only part of the extensive distribution of this quite variable species, both in shape and colour, on the interandine plateau; *cf.* also the data provided by PARODIZ (1979). See GUTIÉRREZ & GUAINILLA (2018) for the economic use of this species.

Genus *Stenostylus* Pilsbry, 1898

Drymaeus (*Stenostylus*) Pilsbry, 1898 [1897-1898], *Man. Conch.*, (2) 11: 184. Type species by subsequent designation (PILSBRY 1898 [1897-1898]: 313) *Bulimus nigrolimbatus* Pfeiffer, 1854.

Stenostylus colmeiroi (Hidalgo, 1872) (Figs. 238, 240)

Bulimus colmeiroi Hidalgo, 1872, *Moluscos Viaje al Pacífico*, 1: 122. "Baeza, República del Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE, 1975: 1153) MNHN 20822; paralectotype MNCN 15.05/3301 (1).

Distribution. Napo: Baeza (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. Also listed from Colombia (see BREURE & BORRERO, 2019: 4).

Genus *Suniellus* Breure, 1978

Scutalus (*Suniellus*) Breure, 1978, *Zool. Verh. Leiden*, 164: 188. Type species by original designation *Suniellus chillu* Breure, 1978.

Remarks. This is a genus occurring at high altitudes in the Andes, of which currently only one species is known from Ecuador. Other species occur in Peru and Bolivia.

Figure 237. *Naesiotus quitensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1848). A-C: Ecuador, unknown locality, lectotype NHMUK 1975230 (H 26.5 mm); D: Pichincha, near Quito, lectotype of *Bulimus carlowiae* Pfeiffer, 1853, NHMUK 1975414 (H 25.1 mm); E: Pichincha, Guallabamba, holotype of *Naesiotus quitensis jacksoni* Rehder, 1940, USNM 473969 (H 28.9 mm); F: Chimborazo, near Riobamba, holotype of *Naesiotus quitensis orinus* Rehder, 1940, USNM 473971 (H 26.4 mm); G: Tungurahua, Ambato, holotype of *Naesiotus quitensis ambatensis* Rehder, 1940, USNM 473973 (H 20.7 mm); H: Pichincha, Cerro Antisana, holotype of *Naesiotus quitensis antisana* Rehder, 1942, USNM 516940 (H 27.1 mm).

Figura 237. *Naesiotus quitensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1848). A-C: Ecuador, localidad desconocida, lectotipo NHMUK 1975230 (H 26,5 mm); D: Pichincha, cerca de Quito, lectotipo de *Bulimus carlowiae* Pfeiffer, 1853, NHMUK 1975414 (H 25,1 mm); E: Pichincha, Guallabamba, holotipo de *Naesiotus quitensis jacksoni* Rehder, 1940, USNM 473969 (H 28,9 mm); F: Chimborazo, cerca de Riobamba, holotipo de *Naesiotus quitensis orinus* Rehder, 1940, USNM 473971 (H 26,4 mm); G: Tungurahua, Ambato, holotipo de *Naesiotus quitensis ambatensis* Rehder, 1940, USNM 473973 (H 20,7 mm); H: Pichincha, Cerro Antisana, holotipo de *Naesiotus quitensis antisana* Rehder, 1942, USNM 516940 (H 27,1 mm).

Suniellus adriani Breure, 2011 (Fig. 239)

Suniellus adriani Breure, 2011, *ZooKeys*, 101: 45, figs 17C-E. "Ecuador, Pichincha, 'San Diego Cuchu'". Holotype RBINS MT.2378.

Figure 238. *Stenostylus colmeiroi* (Hidalgo, 1872). Napo: Baeza. Lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-20822 (H 17 mm). Figure 239. *Suniellus adriani* Breure, 2011. Pichincha: unknown locality. Holotype RBINS MT.2378 (H 32.5 mm).

Figura 238. *Stenostylus colmeiroi* (Hidalgo, 1872). Napo: Baeza. Lectotipo MNHN-IM-2000-20822 (H 17 mm). Figura 239. *Suniellus adriani* Breure, 2011. Pichincha: localidad desconocida. Holotipo RBINS MT.2378 (H 32,5 mm).

Distribution. Pichincha: unknown locality (TL).

Remarks. It remains unclear to what (presumably local) place 'San Diego Cuchu' refers. Without doubt this is at a high elevation within the North Andean páramo [NT1006] ecoregion.

Family MEGASPIRIDAE Pilsbry, 1904

Remarks. This family, consisting of only a few genera, has its distributional focus in Brazil and the Andean regions of Bolivia, Ecuador and Peru (see remarks in BREURE &

Figure 240. Distribution of Bulimulidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.
 Figura 240. Distribución de Bulimulidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecoregiones.

MOGOLLÓN, 2016: 25). Revision at the species level in PILSBRY (1895-1896, 1903-1904). Anatomical data is presented in PILSBRY (1901-1902), ZILCH (1953) and BREURE (1978). Phylogenetic data in BREURE & ROMERO (2012). Recent studies on type material can be found in NEUBERT & JANSSEN (2004), KÖHLER (2007), BREURE (2011, 2013a) and BREURE & ABLETT (2015).

Genus *Thaumastus* E. von Martens, 1860

Bulimulus (*Thaumastus*) Martens in Albers & Martens, 1860, *Die Heliceen*, 2nd ed.: 215. Type species by original designation *Bulinus hartwegi* L. Pfeiffer in PHILIPPI, 1846.

Subgenus *Thaumastus* (*Thaumastus*)

Thaumastus (*Thaumastus*) *buckleyi* (Higgins, 1872) (Figs. 241A-B, 249)

Orthalicus (*Porphyrobaphe*) *buckleyi* Higgins, 1872, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 40: 685, pl. 56 fig. 3. "San Lucas". Syntypes NHMUK 1872.5.22.6 (2).

Distribution. Loja: San Lucas (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Thaumastus (*Thaumastus*) *flori* (Jousseume, 1897) (Figs. 241C-D, 249)

Dryptus flori Jousseume, 1897, *Le Naturaliste*, (2) 11: 265. "Machala Équateur". Lectotype (BREURE, 1975: 1139) MNHN-IM-2000-22474; paralectotypes MNHN-IM-2000-22475 (2).

Distribution. El Oro: Machala (TL); Pichincha: Nanegal (WEYRAUCH, 1967b: 472).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Figure 241. A, B: *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) buckleyi* (Higgins, 1872), Loja, San Lucas, syntype NHMUK 1872.5.22.6 (H 93 mm); C, D: *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) flori* (Jousseume, 1897), El Oro, Machala, lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-22474 (H 86 mm). Figure 242. *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) hartwegi* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846). Loja: near Catamayo. Syntype NHMUK 1975126 (H 57 mm).
 Figura 241. A, B: *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) buckleyi* (Higgins, 1872), Loja, San Lucas, sintipo NHMUK 1872.5.22.6 (H 93 mm); C, D: *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) flori* (Jousseume, 1897), El Oro, Machala, lectotipo MNHN-IM-2000-22474 (H 86 mm). Figura 242. *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) hartwegi* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846). Loja: cerca de Catamayo. Sintipo NHMUK 1975126 (H 57 mm).

Thaumastus (Thaumastus) hartwegi (L. Pfeiffer, 1846) (Figs. 242, 249)

Bulimus hartwegi Pfeiffer in Philippi 1846 [1845-1847], *Abb. Besch. Conch.*, 2: 111, pl. 4 fig. 1. "respublica [sic] Aequatoris, ubi ad 'El Catamajia' prope Loxa". Syntypes NHMUK 1975126 (1).
Zebra loxensis K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 119, pl. 12 fig. 2. "in provincia Loja in valli Catamayo 1500-2000' s.m.". Type material not located.
Plekocheilus (Eurytus) conspicuus Pilsbry, 1932, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 84: 390, pl. 27 figs 4. "near divide near Huasimal, Cascadero, Bella Vista trail, Dept. of Tumbes, Peru, at about 4000 feet". Holotype ANSP 141959.

Figure 243. *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) integer* (L. Pfeiffer, 1855). Ecuador. Lectotype NHMUK 1975244 (H 81.5 mm). Figure 244. *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) loxostomus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Ecuador. Syntype NHMUK 1975125 (H 71.3 mm).

Figura 243. *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) integer* (L. Pfeiffer, 1855). Ecuador. Lectotipo NHMUK 1975244 (H 81,5 mm). *Figura 244.* *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) loxostomus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Ecuador. Sintipo NHMUK 1975125 (H 71,3 mm).

Distribution. Loja: near Catamayo (TL, also of *loxensis*); Cuenca; Loja; Malacatos (all STREBEL, 1910).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. Also reported from Peru (PILSBRY, 1932; BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2010).

Thaumastus (Thaumastus) integer (L. Pfeiffer, 1855) (Fig. 243)

Bulimus integer Pfeiffer, 1855, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 22: 114. "Quito, Ecuador". Lectotype (BREURE, 1978: 31) NHMUK 1975244; paralectotype NHMUK 1975245 (1).

Figure 245. *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) orcesi* Weyrauch, 1967. Pichincha: Nanegal. Holotype IFML 17030 (H 49.4 mm).

Figura 245. *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) orcesi* Weyrauch, 1967. Pichincha: Nanegal. Holotipo IFML 17030 (H 49,4 mm).

Pachytholus pseudoiostomus Strebel, 1909, *Jahrb. Hamb. Wiss. Anst.*, 26, Beiheft, 2: 139, pl. 21 fig. 338, pl. 26 figs 397-398. "Chile [sic]". Type material not located.

Distribution. Ecuador: without precise locality.

Thaumastus (Thaumastus) loxostomus (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) (Fig. 244)

Bulimus loxostomus Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 379. "in Andibus Novae Granadae". Syntype NHMUK 1975125 (1).

Distribution. Ecuador: without precise locality.

Remarks. This species has not been recollected since its original publication. BREURE & BORRERO (2008) assumed this species to be distributed in southern Ecuador, while LINARES & VERA (2012: 206) attributed it to the Colombian malacofauna without further evidence.

Thaumastus (Thaumastus) orcesi Weyrauch, 1967 (Figs. 245, 249)

Thaumastus (Thaumastus) orcesi Weyrauch, 1967, *Acta Zool. Lilloana*, 21: 473, fig. 2. "Ecuador, cuenca del río Esmeraldas, 35 km al noroeste de Quito, region de Nanegal, 1500 m". Holotype IFML 17030 (ex WW 3165).

Distribution. Pichincha: Nanegal (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Figure 246. *Thaumastus* (*Thaumastus*) *tatutor* (Jousseume, 1887). ?Ecuador. Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-28122 (H 99 mm).

Figura 246. *Thaumastus* (*Thaumastus*) *tatutor* (Jousseume, 1887). ?Ecuador. Holotipo MNHN-IM-2000-28122 (H 99 mm).

□ *Thaumastus* (*Thaumastus*) *tatutor* (Jousseume, 1887) (Fig. 246)

Tatutor tatutor Jousseume, 1887, *Le Naturaliste*, (2) 1: 6, fig. 1. "Nouvelle Grenade". Holotype MNHN-IM-2000-28122.

Distribution. ?Ecuador: without precise locality.

Remarks. This species has not been recollected since its description. Given the political-administrative boundaries of the former 'Nouvelle Grenade', it may be expected to occur in Colombia, Ecuador or Venezuela.

Family SIMPULOPSIDAE Schileyko, 1999

Remarks. A family with currently three genera, distributed mainly in Brazil, but one species shows a disjunct distribution in Argentina, Colombia, Ecuador, and Paraguay; a few species of uncertain status have been reported from Central America. Revised at the species level in PILSBRY (1897-1898, 1899). Anatomical data is presented in PILSBRY (1901-1902), BREURE (1978), MURATOV & GARGOMINY (2011), SIMONE & SALVADOR (2016). Phylogenetic data in BREURE & ROMERO (2012). Recent studies on type material can be found in NEUBERT & JANSSEN (2004), KÖHLER (2007), BREURE (2011, 2016a) and BREURE & ABLETT (2015).

Genus *Leiostracus* Albers, 1850

Leiostracus Albers, 1850, *Die Heliceen*: 156. Type species by subsequent designation (Martens in ALBERS & MARTENS, 1860: 213) *Bulimus vittatus* Spix in Wagner, 1827.

Figure 247. ?*Leiostracus webberi* Pilsbry, 1939. Tungurahua: near Baños. Holotype ANSP 174057 (H 22 mm). Figure 248. *Simpulopsis (Eudioptus) citrinovitrea* (S. Moricand, 1836). Brazil: near Bahia. Lectotype MHNG-MOLL-64617 (H 16 mm).

Figura 247. ?*Leiostracus webberi* Pilsbry, 1939. Tungurahua: cerca de Baños. Holotipo ANSP 174057 (H 22 mm). *Figura 248.* *Simpulopsis (Eudioptus) citrinovitrea* (S. Moricand, 1836). Brasil: cerca de Bahía. Lectotipo MHNG-MOLL-64617 (H 16 mm).

Remarks. The genus *Leiostracus* is generally considered to be limited to eastern Brazil (SIMONE, 2006: 121-124 lists it from the states of Bahia, Esperito Santa, Minas Gerais, Rio de Janeiro, Pernambuco, and Sao Paulo), occurring with one species in French Guiana (MASSEMIN ET AL., 2009: 406). The record of the following species, based on one subadult specimen and never been recollected since its original description, needs to be viewed with much suspicion. PILSBRY (1939b) even erected a new subgenus for it, considered a separate genus by SCHILEYKO (1999a) and MOLLUSCABASE (2021). For such an act we fail to see any evidence.

? *Leiostracus webberi* Pilsbry, 1939 (Figs. 247, 249)

Leiostracus (Grptostracus) webberi Pilsbry, 1939, *Nautilus*, 53: 28, pl. 7 fig. 3. "in the foothills of the Andes not far from the town of Banos, Ecuador". Holotype ANSP 174057.

Distribution. Tungurahua: near Baños (TL).

Figure 249. Distribution of Megaspiridae and Simpulopsidae species. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 249. Distribución de especies de Megaspiridae y Simpulopsidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Remarks. This species was described on the basis of material received third-hand from an unknown collector. Pilsbry remarked “It is quite possible that the single specimen is not quite mature, and that the lip becomes expanded when full grown”. It has not been recollected since its description and the locality may be erroneous.

Genus *Simpulopsis* H. Beck, 1837

Simpulopsis Beck, 1837 [1837-1838], *Index moll.*: 100. Type species by subsequent designation (GRAY, 1847: 171) *Helix* (*Cochlohydra*) *sulculosa* A. Férussac, 1821.

Subgenus *Simpulopsis* (*Eudioptus*) E. von Martens, 1860

Bulimulus (*Eudioptus*) Martens in Albers & Martens, 1860, *Die Heliceen*, 2nd ed.: 223. Type species by original designation *Helix* (*Cochlogena*) *pseudosuccinea* S. Moricand, 1836.

Simpulopsis (*Eudioptus*) *citrinovitrea* (S. Moricand, 1836) (Figs. 248, 249)

Helix (*Cochlogena*) *citrinovitrea* Moricand, 1836, *Mém. Soc. Phys. Hist. Nat. Genève*, 7 (2): 436, pl. 2 fig. 19. “[Brazil] aux environs de Bahia”. Lectotype (BREURE, 2016: 67) MHNG-MOLL-64617.

Bulimus fulguratus K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 187; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 6 fig. 6. Type material not located.

Bulimulus (*Paracochlea*) *willineri* Hylton Scott, 1967, *Comm. Soc. Malac. Uruguay*, 2 (13): 90. “San Estinaslao, Paraguay”.

Distribution. Pichincha: 59 km W Machachi (BREURE, 1978: 235).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Also reported from Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, and Paraguay (HYLTON SCOTT, 1967; BREURE, 1978; SIMONE, 2006; CUEZZO *ET AL.*, 2013).

Family PUPILLIDAE Turton, 1831

Remarks. Through time the demarcation of this circumglobally family has shifted. The most recent generic classification is by SCHILEYKO (1998a), who remarked “classification of the family requires a thorough revision based on anatomical investigation”; herein we follow MOLLUSCABASE (2021). Taxa at the species level have been revised by PILSBRY (1920-1921). Phylogenetic data has been reported for several species (groups); for a general paper see NEKOLA ET AL. (2015). Research on South American pupillids is relatively scarce; see e.g., STUARDO & VARGAS-ALMONACID (2000), ARAYA ET AL. (2017).

Genus *Pupoides* L. Pfeiffer, 1854

Bulimus (Pupoides) Pfeiffer, 1854, *Malak. Bl.*, 1: 192. Type species by monotypy *Bulimus nitidens* L. Pfeiffer, 1839.

□ *Pupoides paredesii* (d’Orbigny, 1835) (Fig. 250)

Helix paredesii d’Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 21. “provincia Pazensi (republica Boliviana); provincia Limacensi (republica Peruviana)”. Syntypes NHMUK 1854.12.4.236-237 (11).

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (HIDALGO, 1870).

Remarks. BREURE & ARAUJO (2017) could not locate the voucher for the record of Hidalgo. The historical locality “Guayaquil” is likely a proxy for a sampled locality elsewhere and should be treated with some suspicion.

Family GASTROCOPTIDAE Pilsbry, 1918

Remarks. This worldwide family is currently classified on the basis of features connected with the structure of the aperture (SCHILEYKO, 1998b). A revision of species known at that time was given by PILSBRY (1916-1918). Recent studies of South American species include e.g. MIQUEL & HERRERA (2014), MIQUEL & BRITO (2019). For fossil records see SALVADOR ET AL. (2018).

Genus *Gastrocopta* Wollaston, 1878

Gastrocopta Wollaston, 1878, *Testacea Atlantica*: 515. Type species by subsequent designation (PILSBRY, 1916 [1916-1918]: 7) *Pupa acarus* Benson, 1856.

Gastrocopta pazi (Hidalgo, 1869) (Figs. 251A, 256)

Pupa pazi Hidalgo, 1869, *J. de Conchyl.*, 17: 412. “Amancaez, republica Peruvian; Guayaquil, republica Aequatoris; Panama (Paz)”. Syntypes MNCN 15.05/3284 (13), MNCN 15.05/3285 (7), MNCN 15.05/3286 (1), MNCN 15.05/3281 (46).

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017).

Ecoregion. Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178].

Remarks. PILSBRY (1927 [1927-1935]: 65) stated “it appears that *G. wolfii* and perhaps other forms of the *servilis* group have been confused with the true *G. pazi*”. See also remarks below. Also listed from Peru (RAMÍREZ ET AL., 2003).

Figure 250. *Pupoides paredesii* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Bolivia: near La Paz, or Peru: near Lima. Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.236 (H 3.8 mm). Figure 251. A: *Gastrocopta pazi* (Hidalgo, 1869), Guayas, Guayaquil (?), syntype MNCN 15.05/3284 (H 5.3 mm); B-D: *Gastrocopta strangeana* (Iredale, 1937), Australia, Garden Island near Sydney, syntype NHMUK 1989085 (H 3 mm).
 Figura 250. *Pupoides paredesii* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Bolivia: cerca de La Paz, o Perú: cerca de Lima. Sintipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.236 (H 3,8 mm). Figura 251. A: *Gastrocopta pazi* (Hidalgo, 1869), Guayas, Guayaquil (?), sintipo MNCN 15.05/3284 (H 5,3 mm); B-D: *Gastrocopta strangeana* (Iredale, 1937), Australia, Garden Island cerca de Sydney, sintipo NHMUK 1989085 (H 3 mm).

■ *Gastrocopta strangeana* (Iredale, 1937) (Figs. 251B-D, 256)

Pupa strangei L. Pfeiffer, 1854, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 20: 69. "Gordon Island, Port Jackson" [i.e. Garden Island, Sydney, Australia]. Syntypes NHMUK 1989085 (2). Not *Pupa strangei* Benson, 1853.

Australbinula strangeana Iredale, 1937. *The Australian Zoologist*, 8(4): 301 (replacement name).

Distribution. Guayas: Pedro Carbo Quebrada, between Guayaquil and Manta (■ANSP 180259).

Ecoregion. Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214].

Remarks. The report of this species, described originally from Australia, may indicate either an introduction or a possible misidentification.

Gastrocopta wolfii (K. Miller, 1879) (Figs. 252, 256)

Pupa (Leucochila) wolfii Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 127. "Guayaquil". Syntype SMF 1844 (1).

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (TL); Duram (■ANSP 45169).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. The historical locality "Guayaquil" is likely a proxy for a sampled locality elsewhere and needs further confirmation. The difference in size between the type material of this species and *Gastrocopta pazi* (Hidalgo, 1869) places Pilsbry's remark in a different light. However, these microsnailed pupae are largely understudied in this area and additional research may further our knowledge on status and distribution of this group.

Family VALLONIIDAE Morse, 1864

Remarks. This world-wide distributed family has been revised at species level by PILSBRY (1927-1935) and most recently at the generic level by SCHILEYKO (1998a). The American species of *Pupisoma* have been revised by HAUSDORF (2007).

Genus *Pupisoma* Stoliczka, 1873

Pupisoma Stoliczka, 1873, *J. Asiatic Soc. Bengal*, 42 (2): 32. Type species by original designation *Pupa lignicola* Stoliczka, 1871.

Subgenus *Pupisoma (Ptychopatula)* Pilsbry, 1889

Pupisoma (Ptychopatula) Pilsbry, 1889, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 41: 191. Type species by subsequent designation (PILSBRY, 1889 [1889-1890]: 62) *Helix caeca* Guppy 1868.

Pupisoma (Ptychopatula) dioscoricum (C.B. Adams, 1845) (Figs. 253, 256)

Helix dioscoricola Adams, 1845, *Proc. Boston Soc. Nat. Hist.*, 2: 16. "Jamaica". Syntypes MCZ 135518 (3), MHNG-MOLL 38728 (4).

Pupisoma americanum Möllendorff, 1899, *Nachr. Deutsch. Malak. Ges.*, 31: 91 [partim]. "Cuenca, Ecuador". Lectotype (HAAS, 1937: 10) SMF 10697.

Distribution. Azuay: Cuenca (TL *americanum*, SMF 10697, 10698, 356923).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. Also reported from Galápagos: Fernandina, San Cristóbal and Santa Cruz Islands (MIQUEL & HERRERA, 2014), United States of America (Florida and Texas) to south Brazil and north Argentina. Some of this distribution could be anthropogenic (HAUSDORF, 2007). The same author has shown that the Ecuadorian type material of Möllendorff comprised of two species and that paralectotypes of *P. americanum* belong to the present species.

Subgenus *Pupisoma (Pupisoma)*

Pupisoma (Pupisoma?) macneilli (Clapp, 1918) (Figs. 254, 256)

Thysanophora macneilli Clapp, 1918, *Nautilus*, 31: 74, pl. 8 fig. 1. "U.S.A., Alabama, Magazine Point 8 miles N Mobile". Syntypes ANSP 128335.

Figure 252. *Gastrocopta wolfii* (K. Miller, 1879). Guayas: Guayaquil. Syntype SMF 1844 (H 2.3 mm). Figure 253. *Puposoma (Ptychopatula) dioscoricolum* (C.B. Adams, 1845). Jamaica. Syntypes MCZ 135518 (D 1.4 mm).

Figura 252. *Gastrocopta wolfii* (K. Miller, 1879). Guayas: Guayaquil. Syntype SMF 1844 (H 2,3 mm). *Figura 253.* *Puposoma (Ptychopatula) dioscoricolum* (C.B. Adams, 1845). Jamaica. Syntypes MCZ 135518 (D 1,4 mm).

Puposoma americana Möllendorff, 1899, *Nachr. Deutsch. Malak. Ges.*, 31: 91 [partim]. "Cuenca, Ecuador". Paralectotypes SMF 10698 [partim].

Distribution. Azuay: Cuenca (TL *americana*); Morona Santiago: 2 km W Patuca (HAUSDORF, 2007).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. Originally described from southern United States and also reported from Argentina, Belize, Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Guatemala, Honduras, Jamaica, Mexico, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Suriname, Trinidad and Tobago, and Venezuela (HAUSDORF, 2007). The same author has shown that the Ecuadorian type material of Möllendorff comprised of two species.

Comments on the family. In the literature the following species related to this family has been mentioned as occurring in Ecuador:

- *Puposoma comicolense* H.B. Baker, 1828 (*Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 79: 224, pl. 15 figs 4-7) was described from Mexico and mentioned from Ecuador by LINARES & VERA (2012: 144). According to HAUSDORF (2007: 1491) this relates to the record of a synonym from the Galápagos islands, *Puposoma galapagorum* Pilsbry, 1934.

Figure 254. *Pupisoma* (*Pupisoma*?) *macneilli* (Clapp, 1918). U.S.A.: 8 miles N Mobile. Original figure in CLAPP (1918): pl. 8 fig. 1 (H 1.5 mm). Figure 255. *Sterkia* (*Metasterkia*) *bakeri* Pilsbry, 1921. Mexico, Vera Cruz: Hacienda de Cuatotolapan. A, Original figure in PILSBRY (1921): pl. 24 figs 1-3 (H 1.9 mm). B, Lectotype ANSP 141375 (H 1.9 mm).

Figura 254. *Pupisoma* (*Pupisoma*?) *macneilli* (*Clapp*, 1918). *EE.UU.*: 8 millas N Mobile. *Figura original en CLAPP* (1918): pl. 8 fig. 1 (H 1,5 mm). *Figura 255.* *Sterkia* (*Metasterkia*) *bakeri* *Pilsbry*, 1921. *México*, Vera Cruz: Hacienda de Cuatotolapan. A, *Figura original en PILSBRY* (1921): pl. 24 figs. 1-3 (H 1,9 mm). B, *Lectotipo ANSP 141375* (H 1,9 mm).

Figure 256. Distribution of Gastrocoptidae, Pupillidae, Vertiginidae and Clausiliidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 256. Distribución de Gastrocoptidae, Pupillidae, Vertiginidae y Clausiliidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Family VERTIGINIDAE Fitzinger, 1833

Remarks. This large family occurs on all continents, except Antarctica. PILSBRY (1918-1920, 1920-1921) has monographed all known taxa at that time; SCHILEYKO (1998b) has reviewed the generic systematics. Phylogenetic data have been compiled by NEKOLA & COLES (2016). For recent South American references on this group see HAUSDORF (2008).

Genus *Sterkia* Pilsbry, 1898

Sterkia Pilsbry, 1898, *Nautilus*, 11: 119. Type species by subsequent designation (PILSBRY, 1920: 49) *Pupa calamitosa* Pilsbry, 1889.

Subgenus *Sterkia* (*Metasterkia*) Pilsbry, 1920

Sterkia (*Metasterkia*) Pilsbry, 1920 [1920-1921], *Man. Conch.*, (2) 26: 50. Type species by original designation *Sterkia antillensis* Pilsbry, 1920.

■ *Sterkia* (*Metasterkia*) *bakeri* Pilsbry, 1921 (Figs. 255, 256)

Sterkia (*Metasterkia*) *bakeri* Pilsbry, 1921 [1920-1921], *Man. Conch.*, (2) 26: 236, pl. 24 figs 1-3. "Hacienda de Cuatutolapan, between Rio San Juan and Arroyo Hueyapan, Acayucan, State of Vera Cruz, Mexico".

Distribution. Azuay: Pedro Carbo, between Guayaquil and Manta (■ ANSP 180308)
Ecoregion. Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214].

Family CLAUDILIIDAE J.E. Gray, 1855

Remarks. This family is widespread with three main centres of diversity (western Europe, East Asia, and the Neotropics) and ca. 1300 species (NORDSIECK, 2007; UIT DE WEERD & GITTENBERGER, 2013). The generic classification has been summarised by SCHILEYKO (2000a). Phylogenetic information in UIT DE WEERD & GITTENBERGER (2013). Recent papers on Neotropical species are e.g. NORDSIECK (2005, 2010), NEUBERT & NORDSIECK (2005), GREGO & SZEKERES (2008), THOMPSON (2008). For fossil records see SALVADOR ET AL. (2018).

Genus *Columbinia* Poliński, 1924

Nenia (*Columbinia*) Poliński, 1924, *Bull. Acad. Polon. Sci.*, B (1924): 743. Type species by subsequent designation (PILSBRY, 1926: 9) *Nenia columbiana* Poliński, 1924.

Subgenus *Columbinia* (*Columbinia*)

Columbinia (*Columbinia*) *cocaensis* (Jousseau, 1900) (Figs. 257A-B, 256)

Nenia cocaensis Jousseau, 1900, *Bull. Soc. Philom. Paris*, (9) 2: 16, pl. 1 fig. 7. "Liputini, La Coca (Equateur)". Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2453 (1).

Distribution. Orellana: Puerto Francisco de Orellana (TL).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. Liputini could not be found with modern gazetteers; La Coca is an old name for Puerto Francisco de Orellana. Also mentioned from southern Colombia by LINARES & VERA (2012: 147), but without voucher.

Columbinia (*Columbinia*) *perezi* (Jousseau, 1887) (Figs. 257C-D, 256)

Nenia perezi Jousseau, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 170, pl. 3 fig. 11. [Ecuador] "entre Aloag et Rio Toachi (...) canton de Megia, province de Pichincha". Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2656 (4), 2657 (1). *Nenia femurina* Jousseau, 1900, *Bull. Soc. Philom. Paris*, (9) 2: 21, pl. 1 fig. 6. "Equateur (...) le long du chemin de Aloag au Rio Roachi [*sic*, Toachi]". Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2469 (1). *Clausilia* (*Nenia*) *deyrollei* Ancey, 1895, *Le Naturaliste* (2) 9: 25. "Équateur". Type material not located.

Distribution. Pichincha: between Alóag and the Río Toachi [near Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas] (TL); San Nicolas (■MCZ 113898); "Quito" (■MCZ 137012).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Subgenus *Columbinia* (*Steatonenia*) Pilsbry, 1926

Steatonenia Pilsbry, 1926, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 78: 9. Type species by original designation *Nenia cocki* Pilsbry, 1919.

Columbinia (*Steatonenia*) *cousini* (Jousseau, 1900) (Fig. 258A-B)

Nenia cousini Jousseau, 1900, *Bull. Soc. Philom. Paris*, (9) 2: 32, pl. 1 fig. 12. "Equateur (...) à trois cents kilomètres de Quito". Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2459 (1).

Figure 257. A, B: *Columbinia (Columbinia) cocaensis* (Jousseaume, 1900), Orellana, Puerto Francisco de Orellana, syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2453 (H 17,4 mm); C, D: *Columbinia (Columbinia) perezi* (Jousseaume, 1887), Pichincha, between Alóag and the Río Toachi, syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2656 (H 22,5 mm). Figure 258. A, B: *Columbinia (Steatonia) cousini* (Jousseaume, 1900), Ecuador, unknown locality, syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2459 (H 22,6 mm); C, D: *Columbinia (Steatonia) reyrei* (Jousseaume, 1887), Azuay, between Yunguilla Guarco and Huasihuaco, syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2671 (H 22,5 mm).

Figura 257. A, B: *Columbinia (Columbinia) cocaensis* (Jousseaume, 1900), Orellana, Puerto Francisco de Orellana, syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2453 (H 17,4 mm); C, D: *Columbinia (Columbinia) perezi* (Jousseaume, 1887), Pichincha, entre Alóag y el Río Toachi, syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2656 (H 22,5 mm). Figura 258. A, B: *Columbinia (Steatonia) cousini* (Jousseaume, 1900), Ecuador, localidad desconocida, syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2459 (H 22,6 mm); C, D: *Columbinia (Steatonia) reyrei* (Jousseaume, 1887), Azuay, entre Yunguilla Guarco y Huasihuaco, syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2671 (H 22,5 mm).

Distribution. Ecuador: Unspecified locality.

Remarks. Since in the original description only the distance but not the direction was given in relation to Quito, we are unable to establish the region where this taxon occurs in Ecuador.

Columbinia (Steatonia) reyrei (Jousseume, 1887) (Figs. 258C-D, 256)

Nenia reyrei Jousseume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 172, pl. 3 fig. 9. [Ecuador] “entre Yunguilla-Guaicu et Huasi-Guaicu, sur la route de Cuenca à Guayaquil, à une altitude de 2,900 mètres environ.”. Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2671 (1).

Distribution. Azuay: between Yunguilla Guarco and Huasihuaico (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Genus *Cyclonenia* H. Nordsieck, 1999

Cyclonenia Nordsieck, 1999, *Bacteria*, 63: 172. Type species by original designation *Clausilia cyclostoma* L. Pfeiffer, 1850.

Cyclonenia cyclostoma (L. Pfeiffer, 1850) (Fig. 259A-C)

Clausilia cyclostoma Pfeiffer, 1850, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 17: 135. “in Archipelago Koreano” [sic]. Syntypes NHMUK 1985201 (3).

Distribution. Ecuador: without specified locality (NORDSIECK, 2019).

Remarks. PFEIFFER (1856 [1854-1860]: 79) already cast doubt upon the type locality by stating “in China?”. SOWERBY II (1877(?) [1875-1877]: pl. 7 fig. 63) mentioned “Central America”. DUNKER (1882: 380) was the first to report it from Colombia (“prope Pasto”); see also LINARES & VERA (2012: 151). SYKES (1896: 57) reported the species also from Venezuela.

Genus *Incania* Poliński, 1922

Nenia (Incania) Poliński, 1922, *Bull. Acad. Polon. Sci.*, B (1922): 125. Type species by original designation *Clausilia chacaensis* Lubomirski, 1880.

Incania anoecia Ehrmann, 1949 (Fig. 259D-F)

Incania anoecia Ehrmann in Zilch, 1949, *Archiv für Moll.*, 78: 87, pl. 5 figs 15-16. “Unbekannt [Unknown]”. Holotype SMF 62023; paratype SMF 62024 (1).

Distribution. Ecuador: Only known from an unspecified locality.

Remarks. Although the type material was labelled without further specification of locality data, there is a sample (UF 210213, without precise locality) which reveals this as an Ecuadorian species (H. Nordsieck, pers. commun.).

Incania auriculina (Jousseume, 1900) (Fig. 260A-B)

Nenia auriculina Jousseume, 1900, *Bull. Soc. Philom. Paris*, (9) 2: 22, pl. 1 fig. 11. “Equateur”. Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2484 (1).

Figure 259. A-C: *Cyclonena cyclostoma* (L. Pfeiffer, 1850), Ecuador, syntype NHMUK 1985201 (H 20.5 mm); D-F: *Incania anoecia* Ehrmann, 1949, Ecuador, holotype SMF 62023 (H 18.7 mm). Figure 260. A, B: *Incania auriculina* (Jousseume, 1900), Ecuador, syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2484 (H 19.4 mm); C-E: *Incania bourcierii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854), Tungurahua, unknown locality, syntypes NHMUK 1998121 (H 16.6 mm).

Figura 259. A-C: *Cyclonena cyclostoma* (L. Pfeiffer, 1850), Ecuador, sintipo NHMUK 1985201 (H 20,5 mm); D-F: *Incania anoecia* Ehrmann, 1949, Ecuador, holotipo SMF 62023 (H 18,7 mm). *Figura 260.* A, B: *Incania auriculina* (Jousseume, 1900), Ecuador, sintipo MNHN-IM-2000-2484 (H 19,4 mm); C-E: *Incania bourcierii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854), Tungurahua, localidad desconocida, sintipos NHMUK 1998121 (H 16,6 mm).

Distribution. Ecuador: Only known from an unspecified locality.

Incania bourcierii (L. Pfeiffer, 1854) (Fig. 260C-E)

Clausilia bourcierii Pfeiffer 1854, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 20: 152. "Tunguragua, reipublicae Aequatoris". Syntypes NHMUK 1998121 (3).

Distribution. Tungurahua: without precise locality (TL).

Incania crossei (Hidalgo, 1869) (Figs. 261, 256)

Clausilia crossei Hidalgo, 1869, *J. de Conchyl.*, 17: 413. "Baeza, Equateur". Type material not located.

Distribution. Napo: Baeza (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. The original figure from Hidalgo (1870, *J. de Conchyl.*, 18: 66, pl. 6 fig. 9) is herein reproduced.

Genus *Neniptyx* H. Nordsieck, 2007

Neniptyx Nordsieck, 2007, *Worldwide door snails*: 150. Type species by original designation *Clausilia buckleyi* Higgins, 1872.

Neniptyx buckleyi (Higgins, 1872) (Figs. 262A-C, 256)

Clausilia (*Nenia*) *buckleyi* Higgins, 1872, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 40: 686, pl. 46 fig. 4. "Macas". Syntype NHMUK 1880.12.3.3 (1)

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Macas (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Genus *Neniops* Pilsbry, 1926

Neniops Pilsbry, 1926, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 78: 9. Type species by original designation *Clausilia magistra* G.B. Sowerby III, 1892.

Neniops archidona (Jousseau, 1900) (Figs. 262D-E, 256)

Nenia archidona Jousseau, 1900, *Bull. Soc. Philom. Paris*, (9) 2: 15, pl. 1 fig. 1. "Archidona, Equateur". Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2483 (1).

Distribution. Napo: Archidona (TL).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Family LIMACIDAE Batsch, 1789

Remarks. This family consists of slugs of variable size, body elongate-cylindrical, fusiform when contracted. Mantle ovate, disposed at anterior part of body, usually about 1/3 body length. Pneumostome in majority of genera postmedially or nearly so. Transversal grooves on sole straight. Shell plate-like, with slightly elevated (sub)medial nucleus (SCHILEYKO, 2003b: 1489). This family is autochthonous in the Palearctic region, introduced in the Neotropics.

Genus *Limacus* Lehmann, 1864

Limacus Lehmann, 1864, *Malak. Bl.*, 11: 145. Type species by monotypy *Limacus breckworthianus* Lehmann, 1864.

261

262

Figure 261. *Incania crossei* (Hidalgo, 1869). Napo: Baeza. Original figure in HIDALGO (1870): pl. 6 fig. 9 (H 24 mm). Figure 262. A-C: *Neniptyx buckleyi* (Higgins, 1872), Morona-Santiago, Macas, syntype NHMUK 1880.12.3.3 (H 41.2 mm); D, E: *Neniops archidona* (Jousseume, 1900), Napo, Archidona, syntype MNHN-IM-2000-2483 (H 30.7 mm).

Figura 261. *Incania crossei* (Hidalgo, 1869). Napo: Baeza. Figura original en HIDALGO (1870): pl. 6 fig. 9 (H 24 mm). Figura 262. A-C: *Neniptyx buckleyi* (Higgins, 1872), Morona-Santiago, Macas, sintipo NHMUK 1880.12.3.3 (H 41,2 mm); D, E: *Neniops archidona* (Jousseume, 1900), Napo, Archidona, sintipo MNHN-IM-2000-2483 (H 30,7 mm).

Remarks. Keel short, vague. Colour pattern of numerous small dark spots not arranged in longitudinal rows or series of larger spots. Anatomical details in SCHILEYKO (2003b) and ROWSON *ET AL.* (2014).

❖ *Limacus flavus* (Linnaeus, 1758) / *Limacus maculatus* (Kaleniczenko, 1851)

Limax flavus Linnaeus, 1758, *Systema Naturae*, ed.10, 1: 652. [Sweden].

Krynickillus maculatus Kaleniczenko, 1851, *Bull. Soc. Imp. Natur. Moscou*, 24: 226, pl. 6 fig. 2.

“*Tauriam meridionalem*. Prope pagum Kuczukoij”.

Remarks. On the iNaturalist website a number of observations are identified as *Limacus flavus* (Linnaeus, 1758). However, this species can be easily mistaken for *L. maculatus* (Kaleniczenko, 1851). The only way to be sure of an identification is either by dissection or by molecular research (B. Rowson, pers. comm. 11 November 2020). We therefore refrain from giving distributional data. See ROWSON *ET AL.* (2014) for anatomical details.

Family AGRIOLIMACIDAE H. Wagner, 1935

Remarks. This family consists of slugs of small or medium size. Mantle occupies anterior part of body. Pneumostome situated postmedially or nearly medially. Part of mantle around pneumostome elevated and thickened a little to form a slight swelling. Peripheral part of sole covered irregularly with transverse grooves, which passing on central part, curved in form of 'V' towards posterior end of body. Shell with excentric nucleus (WIKTOR, 1999; SCHILEYKO, 2003b: 1502). This family is autochthonous in the Palearctic region, introduced in the Neotropics.

Genus *Deroceras* Rafinesque, 1820

Deroceras Rafinesque, 1820, *Annals of Nature*, 1: 10. Type species by monotypy *Limax gracilis* Rafinesque, 1820.

Remarks. Slugs with rather slim body having spindle-shaped appearance at contraction. Keel as a light angulosity at posterior end of body, visible at contraction of animal. Between mantle slit and middle line of back there are 12-14, rarely 10-16 rows of wrinkles. Body length up to 60 mm, usually up to 45 mm. Colouration uniform or with dark pattern of small spots, which sometimes integrate into a net-like pattern, never forming regular bands (SCHILEYKO, 2003b: 1502).

❖ *Deroceras reticulatum* (O.F. Müller, 1774) / *Deroceras laeve* (O.F. Müller, 1774)
Deroceras invadens Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011

Limax reticulatus Muller, 1774, *Vermium terr. fluv.*, 2: 10. "In horto Regensburgensi & Friedrichdalensi".

Limax laevis Müller, 1774, *Vermium terr. fluv.*, 2: 1. Not given.

Deroceras invadens Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011, *Folia Malacologica*, 19 (4): 220, figs 3a-b. "Nork Park, Banstead, Surrey, U.K.". SMNG p16551.

Remarks. In iNaturalist a number of observations are identified as *Deroceras reticulatum* (Muller, 1774). However, this species can be easily mistaken for *D. invadens* Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011 or *D. laeve* (Müller, 1774). The only way to be sure of an identification is either by dissection or by molecular research (B. Rowson, pers. comm. 11 November 2020). We therefore refrain from giving distributional data. See ROWSON *ET AL.* (2014) for anatomical details.

Family GASTRODONTIDAE Tryon, 1866

Remarks. This family is widely distributed in the Palearctic region, as well as in North and Central America (SCHILEYKO, 2003a). Introductions in the Neotropics have

been reported by *e.g.* SCARABINO (2003), SIMONE (2006), SALAS OROÑO *ET AL.* (2007), MIQUEL & HERRERA (2014).

Genus *Zonitoides* Lehmann, 1862

Zonitoides Lehmann, 1862, *Malak. Bl.*, 9: 111. Type species by monotypy *Helix nitida* O.F. Müller, 1774.

❖ *Zonitoides (Zonitoides) arboreus* (Say, 1818) (263, 269)

Helix arboreus Say, 1818, *Amer. ed. Nicholson's Brit. encycl.*: [no. 2], pl. 4 fig. 4. No type locality given. Type material not located.

Distribution. Napo: Baeza (EC00004); 13.9 km west of Pifo (■ UF 37403); Pichincha: Chiriboga (■ FMNH 216363)

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Also reported from the Galápagos: San Cristóbal Island (MIQUEL & HERRERA, 2014). Further reported from the Nearctic region and Central America (BARKER, 1999); anthropogenic distribution: America, Australia, Europe, Hawaii, Hong Kong, Israel, Japan, Kenya, Madagascar, New Zealand, South Africa (PILSBRY, 1946; BARKER, 1999).

Family OXYCHILIDAE Hesse, 1927 (1879)

Remarks. An introduced *Oxychilus* species, *O. alliarius* (J.S. Miller, 1822), is mentioned by DARRIGRAN *ET AL.* (2020) in their Supplementary Material, without further data or reference to a voucher.

Family PRISTILOMATIDAE Cockerell, 1891

Remarks. A family mainly occurring in the Nearctic and Palearctic regions. For endemic species on the Galápagos see MIQUEL & HERRERA (2014).

Genus *Hawaiiia* Gude, 1911

Hawaiiia Gude, 1911, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 9: 272. Type species by original designation *Helix kawaiensis* Reeve, 1854 [corrected by the author in an erratum to '*Helix hawaiiensis* Ancey' (= *Vitrea hawaiiensis* Ancey, 1904); see <https://biodiversitylibrary.org/page/30825120> and WOOD & GALLICHAN, 2008: 50].

❖ *Hawaiiia minuscula* (A. Binney, 1840) (Figs. 264, 269)

Helix minuscula A. Binney, 1840, *Boston J. Nat. Hist.*, 3: 435, pl. 22 fig. 4. [U.S.A.] "in Ohio,in Vermont".

Distribution. Tungurahua: Baños (WEYRAUCH, 1967a: 345).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. The species has also been recorded in South America from different localities in Argentina (VIRGILLITO & MIQUEL, 2013).

Family EUCONULIDAE H.B. Baker, 1928

Remarks. A diverse circumglobally family, represented in the Neotropics by a few genera (SCHILEYKO, 2002); this author also summarises anatomical information. Phylogenetic data *e.g.* in HYMAN *ET AL.* (2007), HORSÁKOVÁ *ET AL.* (2019). For occurrences in South America see SIMONE (2006), MASSEMIN *ET AL.* (2009), LINARES & VERA (2012).

Genus *Guppya* Mörch, 1867

Guppya Mörch, 1867, *J. de Conchyl.*, 15: 256. Type species by monotypy *Conulus vacans* Guppy, 1866.

Guppya wolfii (K. Miller, 1879)

Hyalina wolfii Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 117. "Guayaquil". Type material not located.

Distribution. Guayas: Guayaquil (TL).

Remarks. The historical locality "Guayaquil" is likely a proxy for a sampled locality elsewhere and should be considered with some caution. Since Miller's type material could not be found, we consider this a *nomen dubium*.

Guppya sp.

Distribution. Pichincha: Without specific locality (CORREOSO, 2008).

Remarks. There are no official records of Euconulidae from Ecuador, but CORREOSO (2008: 85, fig. 44) figured a living *Guppya* identified as a *Guestieria* or *Happia* sp. (Scolodontidae). Based on the picture available, it cannot be identified to species level.

Comments on the family. From yet unidentified material as well as from several iNaturalist observations we suspect that some other genera from this family are also present in Ecuador. A paper on this topic is in preparation.

Family SPIRAXIDAE H.B. Baker, 1939

Remarks. A very diverse Neotropical family, which SCHILEYKO (2000b) split into Spiraxidae and Oleacinidae. Monographed by Pilsbry (1907-1908). South American occurrences see *e.g.* MASSEMIN *ET AL.* (2009), LINARES & VERA (2012).

Genus *Euglandina* Crosse & P. Fischer, 1870

Euglandina Crosse & Fischer 1870 in Fischer & Crosse, 1870-1878, *Mission au Mexique*, 7 (1): 84, 97. Type species by subsequent designation (PILSBRY, 1907 [1907-1908]: 175) *Achatina lignaria* Reeve, 1849.

Euglandina aequatoria (S.I. da Costa, 1900) (Figs. 265, 269)

Glandina aequatoria da Costa, 1900, *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 4: 67, pl. 7 fig. 4. "Peramba, Ecuador". NHMUK 1907.11.21.107

263

264

Figure 263. *Zonitoides (Zonitoides) arboreus* (Say, 1816). U.K.: Northwich, NHMUK 20200307 (D 4.5 mm). Figure 264. *Hawaiia minuscula* (A. Binney, 1840). U.S.A., Ohio: Cincinnati, NHMUK 1843.9.29.59 (D 2.3 mm).

Figura 263. *Zonitoides (Zonitoides) arboreus* (Say, 1816). *Reino Unido:* Northwich, NHMUK 20200307 (D 4,5 mm). *Figura 264.* *Hawaiia minuscula* (A. Binney, 1840). *Estados Unidos, Ohio:* Cincinnati, NHMUK 1843.9.29.59 (D 2,3 mm).

Distribution. Ecuador: “Peramba” (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. PILSBRY (1907 [1907-1908]): 181) remarked that “this form needs comparison with *E. ecuadoriana* (Miller), which, from the description, must be very similar”. The locality given by da Costa could not be found with modern gazetteers; it might be a misspelling for Paramba, a Hacienda near Ibarra in Prov. Imbabura.

Euglandina ecuadoriana (K. Miller, 1878) (Figs. 266, 269)

Glandina ecuadoriana Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 159, pl. 7 fig. 1. “Val de Pilaton”.

Distribution. Pichincha: Rio Pilatón valley (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Figure 265. *Euglandina aequatoria* (S.I. da Costa, 1900). Ecuador: “Peramba”. Holotype NHMUK 1907.11.21.107 (H 59 mm).

Figura 265. *Euglandina aequatoria* (S.I. da Costa, 1900). Ecuador: “Peramba”. Holotipo NHMUK 1907.11.21.107 (H 59 mm).

Euglandina saccata (L. Pfeiffer, 1861) (Fig. 267, 269)

Oleacina saccata Pfeiffer, 1861, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 29: 26. “Respublica [sic] Aequatoris”. Syntypes NHMUK 20190601 (2)

Distribution. Recorded by COUSIN (1887: 5) between “Balsapaniba et Tamboloma” [the latter is in Prov. Loja], and at “Quinzacarpí, versant occidental du Pichincha” [western slopes of (mountain) Pichincha].

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. The latter locality could not be found with modern gazetteers.

Euglandina striata (O.F. Müller, 1774) (Figs. 268, 269)

Buccinum striatum Müller, 1774, *Vermium terr. fluv.*, 2: 149. No type locality. Type material not located.

Achatina dactylus Broderip in Broderip & Sowerby I, 1832, *Proc. Comm. Corr. Zool. Soc. London*, 2: 32. [Colombia] “in Insulâ Tumaco”. Type material not located.

Figure 266. *Euglandina ecuadoriana* (K. Miller, 1878). Pichincha: Río Pilatón valley. Original figure in MILLER (1878): pl. 7 fig. 1 (H 62 mm). Figure 267. *Euglandina saccata* (L. Pfeiffer, 1861). Ecuador. Syntype NHMUK 20190601 (H 41.2 mm). Figure 268. *Euglandina striata* (O.F. Müller, 1774). A: Ecuador, Guayas, Cabo San Lorenzo, ANSP 180251 (H 67 mm); B: Pichincha, Puerto Quito, living specimen (photo: Adrián González Guillén).

Figura 266. *Euglandina ecuadoriana* (K. Miller, 1878). Pichincha: Valle del Río Pilatón. Figura original en MILLER (1878): pl. 7 fig. 1 (H 62 mm). Figura 267. *Euglandina saccata* (L. Pfeiffer, 1861). Ecuador. Sintipo NHMUK 20190601 (H 41,2 mm). Figura 268. *Euglandina striata* (O.F. Müller, 1774). A: Ecuador, Guayas, Cabo San Lorenzo, ANSP 180251 (H 67 mm); B: Pichincha, Puerto Quito, ejemplar vivo (foto: Adrián González Guillén).

Distribution. ?Chimborazo: Bucay (■ANSP 186541); Chanchan valley, Huigra (■ANSP 186540); Guayas: near Colonche (ANSP 168057); Julio Moreno (■MCZ 144521) [Simon Bolívar]; Manabí: Cabo San Lorenzo (ANSP 180251); S of Santa Ana (■MCZ 144522); Pichincha: valley Río Pilatón; San Nicolas (both COUSIN, 1887); Río El Cinto, 1300 m (MARTENS, 1885a); Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Santo Domingo de los Colorados (GERMAIN, 1907). **Ecoregion.** Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145], Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214]. **Remarks.** COUSIN (1887) wrote “San-Nicolas (établissement de MM. Gachet et Martin) près la R. Napo”; this is evidently an estate, which could not be located in modern gazetteers. Some of the ANSP localities are tentatively referred to the province men-

Figure 269. Distribution of Gastrodontiidae, Pristilomatidae, and Spiraxidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 269. Distribución de Gastrodontiidae, Pristilomatidae y Spiraxidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

tioned, as more than one locality with that name exists in Ecuador. The species is also recorded from Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Guyana, Suriname, Panama, and Peru (RAMÍREZ ET AL., 2003; SIMONE, 2006; THOMPSON, 2011).

Family SOLAROPSIDAE H. Nordsieck, 1986

Remarks. This family is distributed in Central and South America and was considered as a subfamily of Pleurodontiidae by SCHILEYKO (2006). Anatomical data was presented by him and in SIMONE (2010), CUEZZO ET AL. (2018); the latter authors also give a distribution of *Solaropsis* within South America. For molecular data see WADE ET AL. (2006, 2007), SEI ET AL. (2017), and CALCUTT ET AL. (2020).

Genus *Solaropsis* H. Beck, 1837

Helix (Solaropsis) Beck, 1837, *Index moll.*: 27. Type species by subsequent designation (HERRMANNSEN, 1848: 467) *Helix pellisserpentis* Gmelin, 1791.

Helix (Psadara) K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 162. Type species by subsequent designation (PILSBRY, 1926: 9) *Helix selenostoma* L. Pfeiffer, 1852.

Remarks. CALCUTT ET AL. (2020) placed *Psadara* K. Miller, 1878 in the synonymy of *Solaropsis* Beck, 1837.

Solaropsis boetzkessi (K. Miller, 1878) (Figs. 270, 279)

Helix (Psadara) boetzkessi Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 163, pl. 7 fig. 4. Type locality: “in valli Pilatonseni”. Type material not located.

Figure 270. *Solaropsis boetzkessi* (K. Miller, 1878). Pichincha: Río Pilatón valley. Original figure in MILLER (1878): pl. 7 fig. 4 (D 20 mm). Figure 271. *Solaropsis cousini* Jousseume, 1887. Ecuador. Syntype RBINS MT.3851 (D 84.6 mm).

Figura 270. *Solaropsis boetzkessi* (K. Miller, 1878). Pichincha: Valle del Río Pilatón. Figura original en MILLER (1878): pl. 7 fig. 4 (D 20 mm). Figura 271. *Solaropsis cousini* Jousseume, 1887. Ecuador. Sintipo RBINS MT.3851 (D 84,6 mm).

Distribution. Pichincha: Río Pilatón valley (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Solaropsis cousini Jousseume, 1887 (Fig. 271)

Solaropsis cousini Jousseume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 177. "le bassin du Napo, Équateur". Syntypes RBINS MT.3851 (4).

Distribution. Ecuador: without accurate localities.

Solaropsis gibboni (L. Pfeiffer, 1846) (Figs. 272, 279)

Helix magnifica I. Lea, 1838, *Trans. Amer. Philos. Soc.*, (n.s.) 6: 89, pl. 23 fig. 88. "New Granada". Holotype USNM 105367.

Helix gibboni Pfeiffer, 1846, *Symb. Helic.*, 3: 37. New name for *Helix magnifica* I. Lea, 1838 not A. Férussac, 1821.

Helix amori Hidalgo, 1867, *J. de Conchyl.*, 15: 71, pl. 1 fig. 3. "Tena Republican Aequatoris". Syntypes MNCN 15.05/3166 (2), MNCN 15.05/3168 (2).

Distribution. Napo: Tena (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Pastaza: Puyo (■ANSP 411023; Goldberg & Einsohn 1983); Río Bobonaza (CORREOSO, 2008).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. This species is also known from Colombia (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 260).

Figure 272. *Solaropsis gibboni* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846). “New Granada”. Holotype of *Helix magnifica* Lea, 1838, USNM 105367 (D 27 mm). Figure 273. *Solaropsis iris* (K. Miller, 1878). Pichincha: Río Pilatón valley. Original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 7 fig. 3 (D up to 25 mm).
Figura 272. *Solaropsis gibboni* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846). “Nueva Granada”. Holotipo de *Helix magnifica* Lea, 1838, USNM 105367 (D 27 mm). *Figura 273.* *Solaropsis iris* (K. Miller, 1878). Pichincha: Valle del Río Pilatón. *Figura original en MILLER (1879): pl. 7 fig. 3 (D hasta 25 mm).*

Solaropsis iris (K. Miller, 1878) (Fig. 273)

Helix (Psadara) iris Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 163, pl. 7 fig. 3. Type locality: “in valli Pilatonensi, 100 m”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Pichincha: Río Pilatón valley (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. We know of no further records for this species.

Solaropsis monile (Broderip, 1832) (Figs. 274, 279)

Helix monile Broderip in Broderip & G.B. Sowerby I, 1832, *Proc. Comm. Corr. Zool. Soc. London*, 2: 29. “in Columbia (Salango)”. Possible syntype MNHN-IM-2000-1951 (1).

Figure 274. *Solaropsis monile* (Broderip, 1832). Manabí: Salango. Possible syntype MNHN-IM-2000-1951 (H 10.6 mm). Figure 275. *Solaropsis napensis* (Crosse, 1871). Ecuador: on the way from Quito to Napo. Syntype MCZ 156671 (D 36 mm). Figure 276. *Solaropsis quadrivittata* (Hidalgo, 1869). Napo: Baeza. Syntype MNCN 15.05/3193 (D 20 mm).

Figura 274. *Solaropsis monile* (Broderip, 1832). Manabí: Salango. Posible sintipo MNHN-IM-2000-1951 (H 10,6 mm). Figura 275. *Solaropsis napensis* (Crosse, 1871). Ecuador: camino de Quito a Napo. Sintipo MCZ 156671 (D 36 mm). Figura 276. *Solaropsis quadrivittata* (Hidalgo, 1869). Napo: Baeza. Sintipo MNCN 15.05/3193 (D 20 mm).

Distribution. Manabí: Mountains around Puerto López (EC00002); Salango (TL).

Ecoregion. Ecuadorian dry forests [NT0214].

Remarks. This species is also known from Colombia and Peru (LINARES & VERA, 2012: 261), but not listed by RAMÍREZ *ET AL.* (2003). The original locality as stated by Broderip may have misled Linares & Vera in their assignment of this species to the Colombian malacofauna.

277

278

Figures 277, 278. *Solaropsis selenostoma* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854). 277: Pichincha, Gualea, syntype NHMUK1966593 (D 24.8 mm); 278: Bolívar, San Luis de Pambil (photo: Adrián González Guillén).
Figuras 277, 278. *Solaropsis selenostoma* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854). 277: Pichincha, Gualea, sintipo NHMUK1966593 (D 24,8 mm); 278: Bolívar, San Luis de Pambil (foto: Adrián González Guillén).

Solaropsis napensis (Crosse, 1871) (Fig. 275)

Helix napensis Crosse, 1871, *J. de Conchyl.*, 19: 228. "cum praecedente" [Republica Aequatoris: in via e Quito a Napo]. Syntypes MCZ 156671 (1), MNHN-IM-2000-2009 (1).

Distribution. Ecuador: Unspecified locality.

Remarks. Crosse based his description on material collected and loaned by Orton. However, we do not know his itinerary, therefore the type locality is imprecise. FISCHER-PIETTE (1950: 77) listed the MNHN material as "Un specimen 28 mm (Holo-type brisé ?)", which is here not regarded as a lectotype designation.

Figure 279. Distribution of Solaropsidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.
 Figura 279. Distribución de Solaropsidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Solaropsis quadrivittata (Hidalgo, 1869) (Figs. 276, 279)

Helix quadrivittata Hidalgo, 1869, *J. de Conchyl.*, 17: 410. “Baeza, reipublicae Aequatoris”. Syntypes MNCN 15.05/3193 (1), MNCN 15.05/3194 (1).

Distribution. Napo: Baeza (TL).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Solaropsis selenostoma (L. Pfeiffer, 1854) (Figs. 277, 278, 279)

Helix selenostoma Pfeiffer, 1854, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 20: 152. “prope Gualea, reipublicae Aequatoris”. Syntypes NHMUK 1966593 (3).

Distribution. Pichincha: Gualea (TL); Los Puentes (COUSIN, 1887); San Tadeo (GERMAIN, 1907).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. This species has also been listed from Peru (RAMÍREZ *ET AL.*, 2003) and Colombia (as *Solararopsis selenostoma*; LINARES & VERA, 2012: 262).

Comments on the family. In the literature the following species related to this family have also been mentioned as occurring in Ecuador:

- *Helix catenifera* L. Pfeiffer, 1854 (*Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 20: 152), described “from the Andes of New Granada” was mentioned by LINARES & VERA (2012: 259) as “*Solaropsis catenifera* (Pfeiffer, 1852). Localidad tipo. Sin localidad definida. Tipo. Holotipo MCZ 222360?” and said to be described from Ecuador. There are several errors in this statement: 1) The publication date is 27 June 1854 (NEUBERT *ET AL.*, 2020: 91), 2) the type locality was given as mentioned above, and 3) the MCZ specimen is a syntype and not the holotype as Pfeiffer did not mention he had seen only one specimen; besides, there are two syntypes NHMUK 1966591 *ex Cuming ex Bourcier* (Fig. 280). As far as we are aware, this species has not been found in Ecuador.

Figure 280. *Solaropsis catenifera* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854). “from the Andes of New Granada”. Syntype NHMUK 1966591 (D 24.4 mm).

Figura 280. *Solaropsis catenifera* (L. Pfeiffer, 1854). “de los Andes de Nueva Granada”. Sintipo NHMUK 1966591 (D 24,4 mm).

Family HELICIDAE Rafinesque, 1815

Remarks. This highly diverse family is concentrated in Europe east to Caucasus and south to northern Africa, with some species introduced to many countries outside this area (SCHILEYKO, 2006). South American records in HAUSDORF (2002), SCARABINO (2003), SIMONE (2006), GUILLER *ET AL.* (2012), GAITÁN-ESPITIA *ET AL.* (2013), ARAYA (2015).

Genus *Cornu* Born, 1778

Cornu Born, 1778, *Index Musei Vindobonensis*, 1: 371. Type species by monotypy *Cornu copiae* Born, 1778.

❖ *Cornu aspersum* (O.F. Müller, 1774) (Fig. 281)

Helix aspersa O.F. Müller, 1774, *Vermium terr. fluv.*, 2: 59. “Italia”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Chimborazo: “The base of Chimborazo” (TAYLOR, 1914: 273). Pichincha: Quito (obs. iNaturalist 66891295, 2020; 66599554, 2020, and many others)

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121]. To be confirmed from others.

Remarks. Taylor based his record on “Férussac”, but a voucher is not known. The reference to Férussac may be based on material that was possibly collected by Humboldt and Bonpland during their expedition to Ecuador (WULF, 2016). In iNaturalist there are several observations from this species in and around Quito, and hitherto less frequent in Imbabura, and Napo provinces. As this species is associated with human habitation and movement, its distribution may be expected to extend further. It may be confused with other species, *e.g.* some *Solaropsis* species.

Figure 281. *Cornu aspersum* (O.F. Müller, 1774). Ecuador, Pichincha: Quito (iNaturalist 66891295 and 66599554, fotos: Isabella Endara and Empozo). Figure 282. *Isomeria aequatoria* (L. Pfeiffer, 1860). Ecuador. Syntypes NHMUK 20190602 (D 37,7 mm).

Figura 281. *Cornu aspersum* (O.F. Müller, 1774). Ecuador, Pichincha: Quito (iNaturalist 66891295 y 66599554, fotos: Isabella Endara and Empozo). Figura 282. *Isomeria aequatoria* (L. Pfeiffer, 1860). Ecuador. Sintipos NHMUK 20190602 (D 37,7 mm).

Family LABYRINTHIDAE Borrero, Sei, Robinson & Rosenberg, 2017

Remarks. This recently established Neotropical family, comprising 60-70 species, is distributed mostly in northwestern South America, extending east to northeastern Brazil and north to Costa Rica (SEI *ET AL.*, 2017). See SOLEM (1966) for a monograph. Anatomical data can be found in CUEZZO (2006), molecular data are given in SEI *ET AL.* (2017).

Genus *Isomeria* Albers, 1850

Helix (Isomeria) Albers, 1850, *Die Heliceen*: 126. Type species by monotypy *Helix oreas* Koch, 1844.

Isomeria aequatoria (L. Pfeiffer, 1860) (Fig. 282)

Helix aequatoria Pfeiffer, 1860, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 28: 133, pl. 50 fig. 6. "Ecuador". Syntypes NHMUK 20190602 (3).

Distribution. ?Chimborazo: Huigra; ?: Cayanded (SOLEM, 1966).

Remarks. Both localities are based on historical collections; one ("Cayanded") could not be found with modern gazetteers, the other ("Huigra") is tentatively referred to Chimborazo province as more than one such name exists in Ecuador.

Isomeria aequatoriana (Hidalgo, 1867) (Figs. 283, 301)

Helix aequatoriana Hidalgo, 1867, *J. de Conchyl.*, 17: 307, pl. 8 fig. 2. "Republica Aequatoris". Syntypes MNCN 15.05/3170 (1), MNCN 15.05/3171 (1).

Helix (Isomeria) wolfi T. Reibisch, 1896, *Abh. naturw. Ges. Isis*, 7: 56. "Machai [Macas]".

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Méndez; Chiquaza; Napo: 30 miles E Baños; Nachiyacu; Orellana: Loreto; Pastaza: Abitagua, Rio Pastaza; Mera; Puyo; Tungurahua: Topo (all SOLEM, 1966); Ecuador: imprecise locality "Quito" (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Napo moist forests [NT0142], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Isomeria alagoana Jousseume, 1887 (Figs. 284, 301)

Isomeria alagoana Jousseume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 179, pl. 3 figs 6-7. "le du chemin qui conduit de Aloag à Rio-Toachi, canton de Mégia, province de Pichincha". Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-1815 (3).

Distribution. Pichincha: near Alóag (TL).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. "Probably (...) in the upper Pilatón or Quitasol valleys" (SOLEM, 1966).

Isomeria bituberculata (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) (Figs. 285, 301)

Helix bituberculata Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 242. "prope Tunguragua reipublicae Aequatoris". Syntypes NHMUK 20160369 (3).

Helix (Dentellaria) tridentula K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 165, pl. 7 fig. 5a-5c. "Otavalo, Nanegal, Val de Pilaton". Type material not located.

Helix (Dentellaria) latidentata K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 166, pl. 8 figs 1a-1c. "Nanegal". Type material not located.

Distribution. Chimborazo: without accurate locality; Imbabura: Ibarra; Pastaza: Mera; Puyo (all SOLEM, 1966); Pichincha: Mindo (SOLEM, 1966); Nanegal (MILLER, 1878, SOLEM, 1966); San Antonio (COUSIN, 1887); Tungurahua: without accurate locality (TL); Baños; San Fernando; Topo; Cerro Tungurahua (all SOLEM, 1966).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Figure 283. *Isomeria aequatoriana* (Hidalgo, 1867). Syntype MNCN 15.05/3170 (D 71,1 mm).
Figure 284. *Isomeria alagoana* Jousseauime, 1887. Pichincha: near Alóag. Sintipo MNHN-IM-2000-1815 (D 38 mm). Figure 285. *Isomeria bituberculata* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Tungurahua: unknown locality. Syntype NHMUK 20160369 (D 36,4 mm).

Figura 283. *Isomeria aequatoriana* (Hidalgo, 1867). Sintipo MNCN 15.05/3170 (D 71,1 mm).
Figura 284. *Isomeria alagoana* Jousseauime, 1887. Pichincha: cerca de Alóag. Sintipo MNHN-IM-2000-1815 (D 38 mm). Figura 285. *Isomeria bituberculata* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Tungurahua: localidad desconocida. Sintipo NHMUK 20160369 (D 36,4 mm).

Remarks. SOLEM (1966) gave the range as “Central Ecuador, rather widely distributed in the Upper Río Esmeraldas drainage on the Pacific slope and the Río Napo and Río Pastaza on the Amazonian slopes. The few reported elevations are between 3,900-13,000 feet [c. 1,200-3,950 m]”.

Isomeria bourcierii (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) (Figs. 286, 301)

Helix bourcierii Pfeiffer, 1853, *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 3: 209. “Otoralo [*sic*, Otovalo] reipublicae Aequatoris”. Syntypes NHMUK 20160370 (3).

Distribution. Cotopaxi: Sigchos (SOLEM, 1966); Imbabura: Otovalo (TL); Napo: Cerro Antisana; Pastaza: Mera; Puyo; Pichincha: Milpe, Mindo; Cerro Pichincha; Tandayapa (all SOLEM, 1966); Nanegal (MARTENS, 1885a); Guayllabamba (SALVADOR ET AL., 2021).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Remarks. Also recorded from southern Colombia by LINARES & VERA (2012: 246).

Isomeria cymatodes (L. Pfeiffer, 1852) (Figs. 287, 301)

Helix cymatodes Pfeiffer, 1852, *Z. Malak.*, 9: 92. “...?”. Type material not located.

Helix (Isomeria) parietidentata K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 169; Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: pl. 5 figs 3a-3c. “in valli Pilatonensi”.

Distribution. Napo: without precise localities (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Pichincha: Pilatón valley (MILLER, 1878); Between Alóag and Chones (COUSIN, 1887); Rio El Cinto, 1300 m (MARTENS, 1885a).

Ecoregion. Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Isomeria gealei (E.A. Smith, 1877) (Figs. 288, 301)

Helix (Isomeria) gealei Smith, 1877, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 45: 361, pl. 39 figs 9a-9b. “Malacatos, South Ecuador”. Syntypes NHMUK 1877.3.28.1 (2).

Distribution. Loja: Malacatos; ?: “Toza” (SOLEM, 1966).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. The record for “Toza” is based on material collected by Wallis in 1877; we do not know his itinerary and the locality could not be found with modern gazetteers.

Isomeria globosa (Broderip, 1832) (Figs. 289, 301)

Carocolla globosa Broderip in Broderip & Sowerby I, 1832, *Proc. Comm. Corr. Zool. Soc. London*, 2: 30. [Colombia] “Insulae Tumaco, Columbiae Occidentalis”. Type material not located.

Helix subcastanea L. Pfeiffer, 1842, *Symb. Helic.*, 2: 103. New name for *Carocolla globosa* Broderip not *Helix globosa* G.B. Sowerby I, 1818 (unnecessary replacement name).

Isomeria subcastanea var. *kobeltiana* Gude, 1900, *J. Malac.*, 7: 144, figs 1-2. “Ecuador”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Chimborazo: Chambo; below Huigra; Cotopaxi: Sigchos (all SOLEM, 1966); Esmeraldas: 21 km NNW Lida (■UF 194618); Guayas: Bucay; Cerro Masvale;

Figure 286. *Isomeria bourcierii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Imbabura: Otovalo. Syntype NHMUK 20160370 (D 21.8 mm). Figure 287. *Isomeria cymatodes* (L. Pfeiffer, 1852). Pichincha: Río Pilatón valley. Original figure of *Helix (Isomeria) parietidentata* in MILLER (1879): pl. 5 fig. 3 (D 46 mm).
 Figura 286. *Isomeria bourcierii* (L. Pfeiffer, 1853). Imbabura: Otovalo. Sintipo NHMUK 20160370 (D 21,8 mm).
 Figura 287. *Isomeria cymatodes* (L. Pfeiffer, 1852). Pichincha: Valle del Río Pilatón. Figura original de *Helix (Isomeria) parietidentata* en MILLER (1879): pl. 5 fig. 3 (D 46 mm).

Imbabura: Ibarra; Paramba; Los Ríos: near Quevedo; Napo: without precise locality (all SOLEM, 1966); Pastaza: Mera (SALVADOR *ET AL.*, 2021); Pichincha: road from Alóag to Chones (COUSIN, 1887); Milpe; Mindo; Río Pilatón valley; San José de Minas (all SOLEM, 1966); Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Santo Domingo de los Colorados (COUSIN, 1887); Tungurahua: Topo; ?: between Manglaralto and Naute; Río Macima, Río Marone; lowlands of Guayas and Manabí (SOLEM, 1966); “Ecuador” (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017).

Figure 288. *Isomeria gealei* (E.A. Smith, 1877). Loja: Malacatos. Syntypes NHMUK 1877.3.28.1 (D 34 mm). Figure 289. *Isomeria globosa* (Broderip, 1832). Ecuador. MNCN 15.05/58516 (D 37.1 mm).
Figura 288. Isomeria gealei (E.A. Smith, 1877). Loja: Malacatos. Sintipos NHMUK 1877.3.28.1 (D 34 mm). *Figura 289. Isomeria globosa* (Broderip, 1832). Ecuador. MNCN 15.05/58516 (D 37,1 mm).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145], Western Ecuador moist forests [NT0178], South American Pacific mangroves [NT1405].

Remarks. Note that some of the localities given by SOLEM (1966), and based on historical collections, could not be traced with modern gazetteers. Also recorded from southern Colombia by LINARES & VERA (2012: 246).

Isomeria hartwegi (L. Pfeiffer, 1846) (Figs. 290, 301)

Helix hartwegi Pfeiffer, 1846, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 13: 126. "El Catamajia, near Loxa, Ecuador".
Syntypes NHMUK 1966598 (3).

Helix (Isomeria) loxensis K. Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 118, pl. 12 fig. 1. "in provincia Loja in valli Catamayo circa 3000' supra mare". Type material not located.

Distribution. Azuay: Catamayo, Loja (TL); Cuenca; Guayas: La Galia, Yaguachi Nuevo; ?: Toza (all SOLEM, 1966).

Figure 290. *Isomeria hartwegi* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846). Azuay: Catamayo. Syntype NHMUK 1966598 (D 23.6 mm). Figure 291. *Isomeria jacksoni* Solem, 1966. Ecuador: “Puntophaya”. Syntype NHMUK 20160372 (D 42.3 mm).

Figura 290. *Isomeria hartwegi* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846). Azuay: Catamayo. Sintipo NHMUK 1966598 (D 23,6 mm). *Figura 291.* *Isomeria jacksoni* Solem, 1966. Ecuador: “Puntophaya”. Sintipo NHMUK 20160372 (D 42,3 mm).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. The record for “Toza” is based on material collected by Wallis in 1877; the locality could not be found with modern gazetteers and his itinerary is unknown.

Isomeria jacksoni Solem, 1966 (Figs. 291, 301)

Helix atrata Pfeiffer, 1854, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 20: 153. “Puntophaya, reipublicae Aequatoris”. Syntypes NHMUK 20160372 (3).

Isomeria jacksoni Solem, 1966, *Fieldiana, Zool.*, 50: 178. New name for *Helix atrata* Pfeiffer, 1854 not Reeve, 1852.

Distribution. Cotopaxi: Sigchos; Imbabura: Ibarra; Morona-Santiago: Macas; Napo: without accurate locality (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Pastaza: Mera; Puyo; Pichincha: near Nanegal; Río El Cinto, 1300-1400 m (MARTENS, 1885a); Tungurahua: Topo (all SOLEM, 1966 except mentioned otherwise).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. The locality “Puntophaya” mentioned by Pfeiffer could be a misspelling and refer to Los Ríos, Puntaplaya near Babahoyo. However, this species has never been reported from the western side of the Cordillera.

Isomeria juno (L. Pfeiffer, 1850) (Figs. 292, 301)

Helix juno Pfeiffer, 1850, *Z. Malak.*, 7: 66. [Colombia] “Andibus Columbiae”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Napo: Baeza; Ecuador: “Quito” (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. Also recorded from southern Colombia by LINARES & VERA (2012: 247).

Isomeria kolbergi (K. Miller, 1878) (Figs. 293, 294, 301)

Helix (Isomeria) kolbergi Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 167, pl. 8 fig. 2a-2b. “Val de Pilaton”. Type material not located.

Helix (Isomeria) granulatissima K. Miller, 1878, *Malak. Bl.*, 25: 168, pl. 8 fig. 3. “Nanegal”. Type material not located.

Helix (Isomeria) faunus var. *ritchieana* Pilsbry, 1894 [1893-1895], *Man. Conch.*, (2) 9: 94. “Pichincha, N.-W. Ecuador”. Lectotype (BAKER, 1963: 247) ANSP 61696.

Distribution. Chimborazo: Cerro Chimborazo; Napo: Nachiyacu; Pastaza: Mera; Puyo (all SOLEM, 1966); Pichincha: Río Pilatón valley (TL); Gualea; Milpe; Mindo; Nanegal; Lloa (CORREOSO, 2008); Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Santo Domingo de los Colorados; Tungurahua: Topo (all SOLEM, 1966 except mentioned otherwise).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Northwestern Andean montane forests [NT0145].

Isomeria meyeri (Kobelt, 1894) (Fig. 295)

Helix (Isomeria) meyeri Kobelt 1894 in Pfeiffer et al. 1877-1897, *Syst. Conch.-Cab.*, (1) 12 (4): 693, pl. 198 figs 3-4 (ex Strubell ms.). “Östlichen Cordillera von Ecuador”. Type material not located.

Distribution. Ecuador: No precise locality known (SOLEM, 1966).

Remarks. This species was attributed by SOLEM (1966) to Strubell, but following the current ICZN rules Kobelt should be regarded as author.

Isomeria morula (Hidalgo, 1870) (Fig. 296)

Helix martinii Bernardi, 1858, *J. de Conchyl.*, 7: 93, pl. 1 fig. 3. “Quito, République de l'Équateur”. Lectotype (BARRERO & ARAUJO, 2012: 146) MNCN 15.05/60012.

Helix morula Hidalgo, 1870, *J. de Conchyl.*, 18: 32. New name for *Helix martinii* Bernardi, 1858 not L. Pfeiffer, 1854.

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality (TL).

Figure 292. *Isomeria juno* (L. Pfeiffer, 1850). Napo: Baeza, MNCN 15.05/13984 (D 37 mm).
 Figures 293, 294. *Isomeria kolbergi* (K. Miller, 1878). 293: Pichincha, río Pilatón valley, original figure in MILLER (1878): pl. 8 fig. 2 (D 53 mm); 294: Pichincha, unknown locality, lectotype of *Helix (Isomeria) faunus* var. *ritchieana* Pilsbry, 1894, ANSP 61696 (D 52.5 mm).

Figura 292. *Isomeria juno* (L. Pfeiffer, 1850). Napo: Baeza, MNCN 15.05/13984 (D 37 mm).
 Figuras 293, 294. *Isomeria kolbergi* (K. Miller, 1878). 293: Pichincha, valle del río Pilatón, figura original en MILLER (1878): pl. 8 fig. 2 (D 53 mm); 294: Pichincha, localidad desconocida, lectotipo de *Helix (Isomeria) faunus* var. *ritchieana* Pilsbry, 1894, ANSP 61696 (D 52,5 mm).

Isomeria triodonta (d'Orbigny, 1835) (Fig. 297)

Helix triodonta d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 3. "Guayaquil (republica Colombiana)".
 Holotype NHMUK 1854.12.4.82.

Helix atrata Reeve 1852 [1852-1854], *Conch. Icon.*, 7: pl. 99 fig. 549. "Puntophaya". Type material not located.

Isomeria mauritii Jousseaume, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 180. New name for *Helix atrata* Reeve, 1852 not L. Pfeiffer, 1854.

Isomeria mauricei - Cousin, 1887, *Bull. Soc. Zool. France*, 12: 256. Incorrect subsequent spelling for *Isomeria mauritii* Jousseaume, 1887.

Figure 295. *Isomeria meyeri* (Kobelt, 1894). Ecuador: eastern Cordillera. Original figure in PFEIFFER ET AL. (1894): pl. 198 figs 3-4 (D 36 mm). Figure 296. *Isomeria morula* (Hidalgo, 1870). Ecuador. Lectotype MNCN 15.05/60012 (D 34.2 mm).

Figura 295. *Isomeria meyeri* (Kobelt, 1894). Ecuador: Cordillera oriental. Figura original en PFEIFFER ET AL. (1894): pl. 198 figs. 3-4 (D 36 mm). Figura 296. *Isomeria morula* (Hidalgo, 1870). Ecuador. Lectotipo MNCN 15.05/60012 (D 34,2 mm).

Distribution. Ecuador: “Unknown, since the only reported locality, Puná Island, near Guayaquil, is merely the place where the type was purchased” (SOLEM, 1966: 175). The locality “Puntophaya” mentioned by Reeve could be a misspelling and refer to Los Ríos, Puntaplaya near Babahoyo.

Comments on the genus. The following species are likely associated with Ecuador in error:

- *Helix basidens* Mousson, 1873 (incorrectly listed as *Isomeria basibens* (Mousson, 1873) by LINARES & VERA, 2012: 245) is a Colombian species for which we have not seen verified records from Ecuador despite the assertion by Linares & Vera.
- *Helix neogranadensis* L. Pfeiffer, 1845 is also a Colombian species which LINARES & VERA (2012: 248) mentioned from Ecuador without further evidence.

Genus *Labyrinthus* H. Beck, 1837

Helix (*Labyrinthus*) Beck, 1837, *Index moll.*: 33. Type species by tautonymy *Helix labyrinthus* Lamarck, 1792.

□ *Labyrinthus bifurcatus* (Deshayes, 1838) (Fig. 298)

Helix bifurcata Deshayes, 1838, *Magas. Zool.*, 8: pl. 111 fig. 2. Type locality not stated. Lectotype (TILLIER, 1980: 150) MNHN-IM-2000-1834.

Figure 297. *Isomeria triodonta* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Ecuador: unknown locality. Holotype NHMUK 1854.12.4.82 (D 38.2 mm). Figure 298. *Labyrinthus bifurcatus* (Deshayes, 1838). French Guiana: Cayenne. Lectotype MNHN-IM-2000-1834 (D 31 mm).

Figura 297. Isomeria triodonta (d'Orbigny, 1835). Ecuador: localidad desconocida. Holotipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.82 (D 38,2 mm). Figura 298. Labyrinthus bifurcatus (Deshayes, 1838). Guayana Francesa: Cayenne. Lectotipo MNHN-IM-2000-1834 (D 31 mm).

Distribution. Ecuador: “No accurately localized specimens were seen” (SOLEM, 1966).

Remarks. The lectotype is from Cayenne, French Guiana (TILLIER, 1980: 150; MASSEMIN *ET AL.*, 2009: 428, pl. 13 fig. D-D'). TILLIER (1980) noted “un autre [= apart from lectotype] exemplaire d’auteur, venant de Quito, se trouve également au MNHN”. Also recorded from Venezuela, Colombia and Peru (RAMÍREZ *ET AL.*, 2003; LINARES & VERA, 2012).

Figure 299. *Labyrinthus manueli* Higgins, 1872. Morona-Santiago: Macas. Syntype NMW 1955.158.01192 (D 23.5 mm). Figure 300. *Labyrinthus raimondii* (Philippi, 1867). Pastaza: Mera. MNZW M.305789 (D 44 mm).

Figura 299. *Labyrinthus manueli* Higgins, 1872. Morona-Santiago: Macas. Syntype NMW 1955.158.01192 (D 23,5 mm). Figura 300. *Labyrinthus raimondii* (Philippi, 1867). Pastaza: Mera. MNZW M.305789 (H 44 mm).

Labyrinthus manueli Higgins, 1872 (Fig. 299, 301)

Helix quadridentata Broderip; Hidalgo, 1870, *J. de Conchyl.*, 18: 33. Not *Caracolla quadridentata* Broderip, 1832.

Labyrinthus manueli Higgins, 1872, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 40: 686, pl. 56 fig. 5a. "Macas, Ecuador". Syntype NMW 1955.158.01192 (1).

Helix manoeli (Higgins); Pfeiffer, 1875 [1875-1876], *Monogr. Helic. viv.*, 7: 462 (incorrect subsequent spelling).

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Macas (TL HIGGINS, 1872); Napo: without accurate locality (BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Pastaza: Abitagua (■MCZ 90941); Mera (SALVADOR ET AL., 2021; ■ANSP 306749); Tungurahua: Baños (■MCZ 65725).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121], Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Labyrinthus raimondii (Philippi, 1867) (Figs. 300, 301)

Helix raimondii Philippi, 1867, *Malak. Bl.*, 14: 65. [Peru] "provincia Loreto inter S[anta]. Catalina et Yanayaco". Type material not located.

Figure 301. Distribution of Labyrinthidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.
 Figura 301. Distribución de Labyrinthidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Cusuimi (■ FMNH 170619, 170621); Napo: without precise localities (COUSIN, 1887; BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017); Rio Jatunyacu (■ MCZ 64956); Pastaza: Mera (SALVADOR *ET AL.*, 2021).

Ecoregion. Napo moist forests [NT0142].

Remarks. Originally reported from Peru (see SOLEM, 1966); also recorded from French Guiana (MASSEMIN *ET AL.*, 2009: 429).

Comments on the family. The following species are likely associated with Ecuador in error:

- *Helix creveauxianus* Ancey, 1890 was mentioned from Ecuador by LINARES & VERA (2012: 251), but SOLEM (1966: 102) regarded it as a Colombian species.
- *Helix furcillatus* Hupé, 1853 is a Peruvian species with one, probably erroneous, record without precise locality mentioned in SOLEM (1966: 87). This record has been copied by LINARES & VERA (2012: 252) without comments.
- *Caracolla subplanata* Petit de la Saussaye, 1843 is a species occurring in Panama and Colombia (SOLEM, 1966: 113-122) for which one (doubtful) record from “Ecuador” was listed. This record has been copied by LINARES & VERA (2012: 256) without comments.
- *Helix tarapotoensis* J. Moricand, 1858 is a Peruvian species which was mentioned by LINARES & VERA (2012: 258) without further evidence. There is one record from “12 km SW of Santo Domingo de los Colorados” (FMNH 475535), which is likely a misidentification.

Family EPIPHRAGOMOPHORIDAE Hoffman, 1928

Remarks. There are approximately 40-50 valid species in this Neotropical family, most of which occur in the Andean region of Argentina, Bolivia and Peru. See SCHILEYKO (2004), CUEZZO (2006).

Figure 302. *Epiphragmophora macasi* (Higgins, 1872). Morona-Santiago: Macas. Original figure en HIGGINS (1872): pl. 56 fig. 6-6a (D 35 mm).

Figura 302. Epiphragmophora macasi (Higgins, 1872). Morona-Santiago: Macas. *Figura original en HIGGINS (1872): pl. 56 fig. 6-6a (D 35 mm).*

Genus *Epiphragmophora* Döring, 1875

Helix (*Epiphragmophora*) Döring, 1875, *Bol. Acad. Nac. Cienc. Exact. Córdoba*, 1: 446. Type species by subsequent designation (Pilsbry 1895 [1893-1895]: 196): *Epiphragmophora hieronymi* Döring, 1875.

Epiphragmophora macasi (Higgins, 1872) (Fig. 302)

Helix (*Aglaiia*) *macasi* Higgins, 1872, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 40: 686, pl. 56 fig. 6-6a. Type material not located.

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Macas (TL HIGGINS, 1872).

Ecoregion. Eastern Cordillera real montane forests [NT0121].

Remarks. This species has not been recorded after the original description.

Class BIVALVIA Linnaeus, 1758

Family MYCETOPODIDAE J.E. Gray, 1840

Remarks. This Neotropical family is restricted to South America and 53 species are known (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2019c). See this reference for discussion on the available phylogenetic data, distributional data and conservation status.

Genus *Anodontites* Bruguière, 1792

Anodontites Bruguière, 1792, *J. Hist. Nat.*, 1: 134. Type species by monotypy *Anodontites crispata* Bruguière, 1792.

Figure 303. *Anodontites carinata* (Dunker, 1858). “Rio Choco, Neu Granada”. Syntype ZMB 108725 (L 65 mm). Figure 304. *Anodontites crispata* (Bruguière, 1792). “Rio Napo, Ecuador”. Holotype of *Anodonta napoensis* I. Lea, 1868, USNM 25429 (L 70 mm).

Figura 303. *Anodontites carinata* (Dunker, 1858). “Rio Choco, Neu Granada”. Syntype ZMB 108725 (largo 65 mm). Figura 304. *Anodontites crispata* (Bruguière, 1792). “Rio Napo, Ecuador”. Holotipo de *Anodonta napoensis* I. Lea, 1868, USNM 25429 (L 70 mm).

□ *Anodontites carinata* (Dunker, 1858) (Fig. 303)

Anodonta carinata Dunker, 1858, *Malak. Bl.*, 5: 225. “Rio Choco, Neu Granada”. Syntype ZMB 108725 (1).

Distribution. Colombia, Venezuela (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Remarks. Mentioned from Ecuador by PEREIRA *ET AL.* (2014) without further data.

Anodontites crispata (Bruguière, 1792) (Figs. 304, 314)

Anodontites crispata Bruguière, 1792, *J. Hist. Nat.*, 1: 135, pl. 8 figs 6-7. “la Guyanne”.

Anodonta napoensis I. Lea, 1868, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 20: 162. “Rio Napo, Ecuador”. Holotype USNM 25429.

Distribution. Guayas: Rio Bodegas (SMF 11955) [Rio Babahoyo]; Rio Guyayaquil (MNHN Mp-0658; NHMUK 1876.6.21.2) [Rio Guayas]; Upper Daule, tributary of Rio Guayaquil (ANSP 366273, 366274; UMMZ 112391); Morona-Santiago: Rio Cushuimi (FMNH 173059, 179994); Orellana: Rio Napo (SMF 11957; USNM 25429, 86608); Rio Unuyacu (MNHN Mp-0354; SMF 11959); Ecuador: without specific locality “Ecuador” (RBINS Mp-0946; UMMZ 112386, 112390; USNM 126997; ZMB 50835, Mp-0159).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301], Amazonas Lowlands [316].

Remarks. Also reported from Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, French Guiana (TL), Peru, Venezuela (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Figure 305. *Anodontites elongata* (W. Swainson, 1823). Ecuador. Possible syntypes of *Anodonta hidalgoi* Germain, 1908, MNHN Mp-0401 (L 22 mm). Figure 306. *Anodontites tenebricosa* (I. Lea, 1834). “Rio la Plata”. Holotype USNM 86761 (L 85.9 mm).

Figura 305. *Anodontites elongata* (W. Swainson, 1823). Ecuador. Posibles sintipos de *Anodonta hidalgoi* Germain, 1908, MNHN Mp-0401 (L 22 mm). Figura 306. *Anodontites tenebricosa* (I. Lea, 1834). “Rio la Plata”. Holotipo USNM 86761 (L 85,9 mm).

Anodontites elongata (W. Swainson, 1823) (Fig. 305)

Anodon elongatus Swainson, 1823 [1822-1823], *Zool. Illustr.*, 3: pl. 176. “South American rivers”.

Type material not located.

Anodonta (*Glabaris*) *hidalgoi* Germain, 1908, *Bull. Mus. Nat. Hist. Nat.*, 14: 64. “Équateur”. Possible syntypes MNHN uncatalogued (2); as “Mp-0401” in GRAF & CUMMINGS (2020).

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality (TL *hidalgoi*).

Remarks. Also reported from Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Paraguay, Peru (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Anodontites tenebricosa (I. Lea, 1834) (Figs. 306, 314)

Anodonta tenebricosa Lea, 1834, *Trans. Amer. Philos. Soc.*, (n.s.) 5: 78, pl. 12 fig. 36. “Rio la Plata”. Holotype USNM 86761.

Figure 307. *Anodontites tortilis* (I. Lea, 1852). Colombia: Cartagena. Holotype USNM 86405 (L 37.3 mm).

Figura 307. *Anodontites tortilis* (I. Lea, 1852). Colombia: Cartagena. Holotipo USNM 86405 (L 37,3 mm).

Anodonta pastasana Clessin in Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 173, pl. 11 fig. 1. "Rio Pastasa".
Type material not located.

Distribution. Pastaza: Río Pastaza (TL *pastasana*).

Ecoregion. Western Amazon Piedmont [313].

Remarks. Also distributed in Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Paraguay, Uruguay (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2019c).

□ *Anodontites tortilis* (I. Lea, 1852) (Fig. 307)

Anodonta tortilis Lea, 1852, *Trans. Amer. Philos. Soc.*, (n.s.) 10: 291, pl. 28 fig. 54. "Cartagena".
Holotype USNM 86405.

Distribution. Colombia, Costa Rica, Panama (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Remarks. Mentioned from Ecuador by PEREIRA *ET AL.* (2014) without further data.

Anodontites trapesialis (Lamarck, 1819) (Figs. 308, 314)

Anodonta trapesialis Lamarck, 1819, *Hist. Nat. Animaux s. Vert.*, 6 (1): 87. "des eaux douces étrangères à celles de l'Europe?" Syntypes MHNG-MOLL-50581 (2).

Distribution. Orellana: Laguna de Samona, near Coca (RBINS Mp-0918); Rio Napo (DMNH 50514, 186551; FMNH 63398, 89820; MCZ 92310, 293522); Pastaza: Sarayacu (MNHN Mp-0657); Sucumbios: Lago Limoncocha (CM MP-103); Putumayo (ZMB

Figure 308. *Anodontites trapesialis* (Lamarck, 1819). Unknown locality. Syntype MHNG-MOLL-50581 (L 140 mm).

Figura 308. *Anodontites trapesialis* (Lamarck, 1819). Localidad desconocida. Syntype MHNG-MOLL-50581 (L 140 mm).

50833); Ecuador: without specific locality (NHMUK 1872.5.22.30, Mp-316; SMF 12142; UMMZ 22925).

Ecoregion. Western Amazon Piedmont [313], Amazonas Lowlands [316].

Remarks. Also reported from Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Honduras, Nicaragua, Mexico, Paraguay, Peru, Uruguay, Venezuela (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Anodontites trigona (Spix, 1827) (Figs. 309, 314)

Anodon trigona Spix in J.A. Wagner, 1827, *Test. fluv. Brasil.*: 29, pl. 22 fig. 2. "in fluminibus Provinciae Rio Negro".

Distribution. Orellana: Laguna de Samona, near Coca (RBINS Mp-0906); Rio Napo (ANSP 125432; FMNH 21480; RBINS Mp-0950); Pastaza: Sarayacu (MNHN Mp-0355); Sucumbios: Putumayo (ZMB 50834). Ecuador: without specific locality (DMNH 173915; RBINS Mp-0917; UMMZ 112411; USNM 127201; ZMB Mp-0179).

Ecoregion. Western Amazon Piedmont [313], Amazonas Lowlands [316].

Remarks. Distributed also in Guatemala, Honduras, Costa Rica, Panama, Colombia, Peru, Bolivia, Argentina, Paraguay, Brazil, Venezuela (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Genus *Diplodontites* W.B. Marshall, 1922

Diplodontites Marshall, 1922, *Proc. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 61 (2437): 1. Type species by original designation *Diplodontites cookei* W.B. Marshall, 1922.

Figure 309. *Anodontites trigona* (Spix, 1827). Ecuador: Rio Napo, FMNH 21480 (L 44.5 mm).
Figure 310. *Diplodontites cookei* W.B. Marshall, 1922. Colombia: Santander. Holotype USNM 341473 (L 53 mm).

Figura 309. *Anodontites trigona* (Spix, 1827). Ecuador: Río Napo, FMNH 21480 (L 44,5 mm). Figura 310. *Diplodontites cookei* W.B. Marshall, 1922. Colombia: Santander. Holotipo USNM 341473 (L 53 mm).

Diplodontites cookei W.B. Marshall, 1922 (Figs. 310, 314)

Diplodontites cookei Marshall, 1922, *Proc. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 61 (2437): 2, pl. 1 figs 1, 3, 7-8, 10, pl. 3 fig. 4. "Dept. Santander, Colombia". Holotype USNM 341473.

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Rio Cushuimi (FMNH 173058, 179992, 179993).

Ecoregion. Amazonas Lowlands [316].

Remarks. Also reported from Colombia, Peru (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Genus *Lamproscapha* W. Swainson, 1840

Lamproscapha Swainson, 1840, *Treatise malac.*: 286. Type species by subsequent designation (HERRMANNSEN, 1847 [1846-1847]: 574) *Anodon ensiformis* Spix in J.A. Wagner, 1827.

Lamproscapha ensiformis (Spix, 1827) (Figs. 311, 314)

Anodon ensiformis Spix in J.A. Wager, 1827, *Test. fluv. Brasil.*: 31, pl. 24 figs 1-2. No type locality given. Type material not located.

Distribution. Sucumbios: Putumayo (ZMB 50836).

Ecoregion. Amazonas Lowlands [316].

Remarks. Also reported from Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Guyana, Suriname, Peru, Venezuela (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Genus *Mycetopoda* d'Orbigny, 1835

Mycetopoda d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 41. Type species by subsequent designation *Mycetopoda soleniformis* d'Orbigny, 1835.

Mycetopoda siliquosa (Spix, 1827) (Figs. 312, 314)

Anodon siliquosus Spix in J.A. Wagner, 1827, *Test. fluv. Brasil.*: 30, pl. 23 fig. 2. "in flumine Perua-guaçú, ad molendinum sacchari Engenho da Ponte, in Provincia Bahiensi". Syntypes MNHN-IM-2000-317 (1).

Mycetopus occidentalis Clessin in Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 174, pl. 11 figs 2-3. "Rio Pastaza".

Distribution. Orellana: Río Unuyacu (HAAS, 1916); Pastaza: Río Pastaza (TL *occidentalis*).

Ecoregion. Western Amazon Piedmont [313].

Remarks. This species has been mentioned as *Mycetopus subsinuatus* Sowerby [a junior synonym] by HIGGINS (1872: 687) from 'Ecuador' without specific locality. See GRAF & CUMMINGS (2020) for a complete synonymy and distributional records.

Genus *Mycetopodella* W.B. Marshall, 1927

Mycetopodella Marshall, 1927, *Proc. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 71 (2678): 1. Type species by original designation *Mycetopus falcatus* Higgins, 1868.

Mycetopodella falcata (Higgins, 1868) (Figs. 313, 314)

Mycetopus falcatus Higgins, 1868, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 36: 179, pl. 14 fig. 6. "near Chyavetas, Upper Amazon". Syntype NHMUK 1868.4.3.6 (1).

Mycetopoda bolivari Haas, 1916, *Trab. Mus. Nac. Cienc. Nat, Zool.*, 25: 36, pl. 2 fig. 2. "Río Unuyacu, affluente del Napo (Ecuador)". Holotype MNCN 15.07/1.

Distribution. Orellana: Río Unuyacu (TL of *bolivari*).

Ecoregion. Amazonas Lowlands [316].

Remarks. Also recorded from Colombia, Peru and Brazil (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Figure 311. *Lamproscapha ensiformis* (Spix, 1827). Sucumbios: Putumayo, ZMB 50836 (L 110 mm). Figure 312. *Mycetopoda siliquosa* (Spix, 1827). “Rio Pastaza”. Original figure de *Mycetopus occidentalis* in MILLER (1879): pl. 11 figs 2-3 (L 96 mm). Figure 313. *Mycetopodella falcata* (Higgins, 1868). “near Chyavetas, Upper Amazon”. Syntype NHMUK 1868.4.3.6 (L 112 mm).
 Figura 311. *Lamproscapha ensiformis* (Spix, 1827). Sucumbios: Putumayo, ZMB 50836 (L 110 mm).
 Figura 312. *Mycetopoda siliquosa* (Spix, 1827). “Rio Pastaza”. Figura original de *Mycetopus occidentalis* en MILLER (1879): pl. 11 figs. 2-3 (L 96 mm).
 Figura 313. *Mycetopodella falcata* (Higgins, 1868). “Cerca de Chyavetas, Alto Amazonas”. Syntype NHMUK 1868.4.3.6 (largo 112 mm).

Comments on the family. The following species is likely in error associated with Ecuador:

- *Anodonta soleniformis* d’Orbigny, 1835 (*Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 41) is mentioned in LINARES & VERA (2012: 267; as *Mycetopoda soleniformis*) as distributed in Ecuador. However, GRAF & CUMMINGS (2020) do not mention any confirmed records for this species from this country.

Family ETHERIIDAE Deshayes 1832

Remarks. This family is “the least species rich of all six freshwater mussel families with only four species. However, these species have a widely disjunct, Gondwanan distribution in Afrotropica, Neotropica and Indotropica” (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020). Further discussion on the available phylogenetic data, distributional data and conservation status in GRAF & CUMMINGS (2019b).

Figure 314. Distribution of Mycetopodidae. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.
 Figura 314. Distribución de Mycetopodidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecorregiones.

Genus *Bartlettia* H. Adams, 1867

Bartlettia H. Adams, 1867, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 34: 444. Type species by monotypy *Etheria stefanensis* J. Moricand, 1856.

Bartlettia stefanensis (J. Moricand, 1856) (Figs. 315, 327)

Etheria stefanensis J. Moricand, 1856, *J. de Conchyl.*, 5: 178, pl. 7 fig. 10. "Haut Amazone". Syntypes MHNG-MOLL-91327 (1), SMF 4302 (1).

Distribution. Morona-Santiago: Rio Cushuimi (FMNH 173045); Orellana: Rio Napo (ANSP 125400).

Ecoregion. Amazonas Lowlands [316].

Remarks. The label from the SMF specimen has "Amazonas-Mündung, Porte S." which differs from the locality of the MHNG material; the specimen was received in 1930 and is ex-Coll. Moricand. This species is "widespread in the Amazon Basin, from Brazil west to Ecuador and Peru, as well as the Rio Paraguay" (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Comments on the family. The following species are associated with Ecuador in error: - *Acostaea rivolii* (Deshayes, 1827) (*Diction. Class. Hist. Nat.*, 11: 297). This Colombian species is given a wide distribution in LINARES & VERA (2012: 264) but restricted to the Rio Magdalena valley by GRAF & CUMMINGS (2020).

Family HYRIIDAE W. Swainson, 1840

Remarks. This family "has a widely disjunct distribution in Australasia and Neotropica" (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020), who revised the classification based on phylogenetic work. Further discussion on the available phylogenetic data, distributional data and conservation status in GRAF & CUMMINGS (2019a).

Figure 315. *Bartlettia stefanensis* (J. Moricand, 1856). “Haut Amazone”. Syntypes MHNG-MOLL-91327 (L 75.7 mm).

Figura 315. *Bartlettia stefanensis* (J. Moricand, 1856). “Haut Amazone”. Syntypes MHNG-MOLL-91327 (L 75,7 mm).

Genus *Castalia* Lamarck, 1819

Castalia Lamarck, 1819, *Hist. Nat. Animaux s. Vert.*, 6 (1): 66. Type species by monotypy *Castalia ambigua* Lamarck, 1819.

Castalia ambigua Lamarck, 1819 (Fig. 316)

Castalia ambigua Lamarck, 1819, *Hist. nat. animaux s. vert.*, 6 (1): 67. “Amérique du Sud”. Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-27235.

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality (SMF 11523, 11525).

Remarks. Also reported from Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Guyana, Paraguay, Peru, Uruguay (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Castalia crosseana Hidalgo, 1865 (Fig. 317)

Castalia crosseana Hidalgo, 1865, *J. de Conchyl.*, 13: 316. “Imbabura, Reipublicæ Æquatorianæ”. Lectotype (FISCHER-PIETTE 1950: 66) MNHN-IM-2000-35847, paralectotypes MNCN 15.07/707 + 15.07/1421 (4), RBINS MT.3889 (1), SMF 3791 (1).

Distribution. Ecuador: unnamed river or stream in Prov. Imbabura (TL); without specific locality (MNHN Mp-0876; ZMB Mp-0234).

Remarks. Also reported from Peru (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

□ *Castalia ecarinata* Mousson, 1869 (Fig. 318)

Castalia ecarinata Mousson, 1869, *Malak. Bl.*, 16: 185. “aus den Landseen von Puerto-nuovo (Magdalena)” [Colombia]. Syntypes ZMUZ.

Figure 316. *Castalia ambigua* Lamarck, 1819. "Amérique du Sud". Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-27235 (L 41 mm). Figure 317. *Castalia crosseana* Hidalgo, 1865. Imbabura: unknown locality. Paralectotype SMF 3791 (L 20 mm).

Figura 316. *Castalia ambigua* Lamarck, 1819. "Amérique du Sud". Syntype MNHN-IM-2000-27235 (L 41 mm). Figura 317. *Castalia crosseana* Hidalgo, 1865. Imbabura: localidad desconocida. Paralectotipo SMF 3791 (L 20 mm).

Tetraplon linki W.B. Marshall, 1926, *Proc. U.S. Nat. Mus.*, 69 (2638): 6, pl. 1 figs 6-7, pl. 3 fig. 2. "Sinu River at Loricata, Province of Bolivar, United States of Colombia". Holotype USNM 362860.

Distribution. Colombia (TL; GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Remarks. Mentioned from Ecuador by PEREIRA ET AL. (2014) without further data.

Genus *Diplodon* Spix, 1827

Unio (*Diplodon*) Spix in J.A. Wagner, 1827, *Test. fluo. Brasil.*: 33. Type species by subsequent designation (HAAS 1969: 510) *Unio* (*Diplodon*) *ellipticum* Spix in J.A. Wagner, 1827.

Figure 318. *Castalia ecarinata* Mousson, 1869. Colombia: Loricata. Holotype (*Tetraplon linki*) USNM 362860 (L 25.6 mm). Figure 319. *Diplodon guaranianus* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Argentina: Río Paraná. Lectotype NHMUK 1854.12.4.841 (L 21.3 mm).

Figura 318. *Castalia ecarinata* Mousson, 1869. Colombia: Loricata. Holotipo (*Tetraplon linki*) USNM 362860 (L 25,6 mm). Figura 319. *Diplodon guaranianus* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Argentina: Río Paraná. Lectotipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.841 (L 21,3 mm).

Figure 320. *Diplodon hylaeus* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Bolivia. Lectotype NHMUK 1854.12.4.843 (L 43.5 mm).

Figura 320. *Diplodon hylaeus* (d'Orbigny, 1835). Bolivia. Lectotipo NHMUK 1854.12.4.843 (L 43,5 mm).

Diplodon guaranianus (d'Orbigny, 1835) (Fig. 319)

Unio guaraniana d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 37. "Rio Parana, provincia Corrientesensi (republica Argentina)". Lectotype (JOHNSON, 1971: 85) NHMUK 1854.12.4.841.

Castalia pazi Hidalgo, 1868, *J. de Conchyl.*, 16: 353, pl. 13 fig. 6. "Imbabura, Reipublicae Aequatoriana". Syntypes MNCN 15.07/1045 (1), SMF 3892 (1).

Distribution. Imbabura: unspecified stream or river (TL *pazi*).

Remarks. Also distributed in Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Paraguay, Uruguay (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2019c).

□ *Diplodon hylaeus* (d'Orbigny, 1835) (Fig. 320)

Unio hylaea d'Orbigny, 1835, *Magas. Zool.*, 5 (61): 36. "provincia Chiquitensi (republica Boliviana)". Syntype NHMUK 1854.12.4.843 (1).

Distribution. Ecuador: without further data (PEREIRA ET AL., 2014).

Remarks. Distributed in Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Paraguay, Uruguay (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2019c); see this reference also for the full list of synonyms.

Figure 321. *Prisodon obliquus* Schumacher, 1817. Ecuador: Río Napo. Holotype of *Unio ortonii* I. Lea, 1868, USNM 703563 (L 136 mm). Figure 322. *Triplodon corrugatus* (Lamarck, 1819). Unknown locality. Holotype MHNG-MOLL-50578 (L 72 mm).

Figura 321. *Prisodon obliquus* Schumacher, 1817. Ecuador: Río Napo. Holotipo de *Unio ortonii* I. Lea, 1868, USNM 703563 (L 136 mm). Figura 322. *Triplodon corrugatus* (Lamarck, 1819). Localidad desconocida. Holotipo MHNG-MOLL-50578 (L 72 mm).

Genus *Prisodon* Schumacher, 1817

Prisodon Schumacher, 1817, *Essai nouveau syst.*: 46. Type species by subsequent designation (SIMPSON, 1896: 315) *Prisodon obliquus* Schumacher, 1817.

Prisodon obliquus Schumacher, 1817 (Figs. 321, 327)

Prisodon obliquus Schumacher, 1817, *Essai nouveau syst.*: 139, pl. 11 fig. 2. Not given. Type material not located.

Unio ortonii I. Lea, 1868, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 20: 161. "River Napo, Equador, S. Am.". Holotype USNM 703563.

Distribution. Orellana: Rio Napo (TL *ortonii*, USNM 703563; NHMUK 1888.12.4.2015). **Ecoregion.** Amazonas Lowlands [316].

Remarks. Also reported from Brazil, Colombia, Guayana, Peru, Venezuela (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020); see this reference also for the full list of synonyms.

Genus *Triplodon* Spix, 1827

Triplodon Spix in J.A. Wagner, 1827, *Test. fluv. Brasil.*: 35. Type species by monotypy *Hyria corrugata* Lamarck, 1819.

Triplodon corrugatus (Lamarck, 1819) (Fig. 322)

Hyria corrugata Lamarck, 1819, *Hist. Nat. Animaux s. Vert.*, 6 (1): 82. Holotype MHNG-MOLL-50578.

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020: MNHN Mp-0796).

Remarks. Also reported from Brazil, Colombia, Guyana, Peru, Venezuela (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020); see this reference also for the full list of synonyms.

Comments on the family. The following species are associated with Ecuador in error:
- *Diplodon losadae* F. Haas, 1966 was mentioned by LINARES & VERA (2012: 277) as distributed in Ecuador. GRAF & CUMMINGS (2020) restrict this species to the Orinoco basin in Colombia and Venezuela.

Family CYRENIDAE J.E. Gray, 1840

Remarks. A circumglobally distributed family of brackish- and freshwater clams. South American records in SIMONE (2006), LINARES & VERA (2012), CONDE & SOLIS-COELHO (2017), CLAVIJO & CARRANZA (2018). Phylogenetic data in GRAF (2013). The species from brackish water are excluded herein (see GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Genus *Corbicula* Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1811

Corbicula Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1811, *Magaz. Entd. Ges. Natur. Fr. Berlin*, 5: 56. Type species by monotypy *Tellina fluminalis* O.F. Müller, 1774.

❖ *Corbicula fluminea* (O.F. Müller, 1774) (Figs. 323, 327)

Tellina fluminea Müller, 1774, *Vermium terr. fluv.*, 2: 206. "In arena fluviali Chinae". Type material not located.

Figure 323. *Corbicula fluminea* (O.F. Müller, 1774). China: Guang-Xi, coll. A.D.P. van Peursen (L 23 mm). Figure 324. *Mytilopsis trautwineana* (Tryon, 1866). “River San Juan, New Granada”. Syntype ANSP 55454 (L 36.5 mm).

Figura 323. *Corbicula fluminea* (O.F. Müller, 1774). China: Guang-Xi, col. A.D.P. van Peursen (largo 23 mm). Figura 324. *Mytilopsis trautwineana* (Tryon, 1866). “Río San Juan, Nueva Granada”. Sintipe ANSP 55454 (largo 36,5 mm).

Distribution. Esmeraldas: Río Esmeraldas; Guayas: Isla Mocoli; Río Taura; Los Ríos: Río Baba basin; Pastaza: Río Pastaza; Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas: Río Búa (all from CONDE & SOLÍS-COELHO, 2017: table 1 and literature cited therein).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Río Atrato [301], Western Amazon Piedmont [313].

Family DREISSENIDAE J.E. Gray, 1840

Remarks. Freshwater zebra mussels occur in the Neotropics, Nearctic, Palearctic, and Afrotropics. See LINARES & VERA (2012) for South American records. Phylogenetic data in GEDA *ET AL.* (2018).

Genus *Mytilopsis* Conrad, 1857

Mytilopsis Conrad, 1857, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.*, 9: 167. Type species by monotypy: *Mytilus leucophaetus* Conrad, 1831.

Mytilopsis trautwineana (Tryon, 1866) (Fig. 324)

Septifer trautwineana Tryon, 1866, *Amer. J. Conch.*, 2: 302, pl. 20 fig. 8. “River San Juan, New Granada”. Syntype ANSP 55454.

Distribution. Ecuador: Without specific locality (GRAF & CUMMINGS, 2020).

Remarks. This species is said to be native to western Colombia and Ecuador by GRAF & CUMMINGS (2020), but no specimens from the latter country are known to us.

Family SPHAERIIDAE Deshayes, 1855

Remarks. This family has a cosmopolitan distribution and are the smallest freshwater bivalves, rarely exceeding 25 mm (LEE, 2019). Recent phylogenetic studies suggest two subfamilies with a limited number of genera. For further information, also on taxonomy and biology, and relevant literature, see LEE (2019).

Genus *Pisidium* C. Pfeiffer, 1821

Pisidium C. Pfeiffer, 1821 [1821-1828], *Naturges. Land-Süssw. Moll.*, 1: 17. Type species by subsequent designation (GRAY, 1847: 185) *Tellina amnica* O.F. Müller, 1774.

□ *Pisidium boliviense* Sturany, 1900 (Fig. 325)

Pisidium boliviense Sturany in von Bayern, 1900, *Nachr. Deutsch. Malak. Ges.*, 32: 57, pl. 1. "Tümpel auf der Puna bei Machacamac, zwischen Chililaya und La Paz". Type material not located.

Distribution. Ecuador: without specific locality (PEREIRA ET AL., 2014).

Remarks. Also reported from Bolivia (TL), Brazil, Peru (PEREIRA ET AL., 2014). These authors did not mention vouchers for their Ecuadorian record.

Pisidium wolfii Clessin, 1879 (Figs. 326A, 327)

Pisidium wolfi Clessin in Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 178, pl. 11 figs 7-9. "Rio Pedro (val de Chillo)". Type material not located.

Distribution. Pichincha: Rio San Pedro (TL).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Genus *Sphaerium* Scopoli, 1777

Sphaerium Scopoli, 1777, *Intr. hist. natur.*: 397. Type species by monotypy *Tellina cornea* Linnaeus, 1758.

Sphaerium aequatoriale Clessin, 1879 (Figs. 326B, 327)

Sphaerium aequatoriale Clessin in Miller, 1879, *Malak. Bl.*, (N.F.) 1: 176, pl. 11 figs 4-6. "Rio Pedro (Val de Chillo)". Type material not located.

Distribution. Pichincha: Rio San Pedro (TL).

Ecoregion. North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato [301].

Species excluded from the Ecuadorian malacofauna

Additional to taxa mentioned earlier, the following ones, described or recorded from Ecuador, are no longer considered to be part of its malacofauna:

Figure 325. *Pisidium boliviense* Sturany, 1900. Bolivia: “Tümpel auf der Puna bei Machacamac, zwischen Chililaya und La Paz”. Original figure in VON BAYERN (1900): pl. 1 (L up to 7.8 mm).
 Figure 326. A: *Pisidium wolfii* Clessin, 1879, Pichincha, Río San Pedro, original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 11 figs 7-9 (L 5 mm); B: *Sphaerium aequatoriale* Clessin, 1879, Pichincha, Río San Pedro, original figure in MILLER (1879): pl. 11 figs 4-6 (L 9 mm).
 Figura 325. *Pisidium boliviense* Sturany, 1900. Bolivia: “Tümpel auf der Puna bei Machacamac, zwischen Chililaya und La Paz”. Figura original en VON BAYERN (1900): pl. 1 (L hasta 7,8 mm).
 Figura 326. A: *Pisidium wolfii* Clessin, 1879, Pichincha, Río San Pedro, figura original en MILLER (1879): pl. 11 figs. 7-9 (L 5 mm); B: *Sphaerium aequatoriale* Clessin, 1879, Pichincha, Río San Pedro, figura original en MILLER (1879): pl. 11 figs. 4-6 (L 9 mm).

- *Cylindrella aequatoria* Morelet (1873, *J. de Conchyl.*, 21: 124, pl. 5 fig. 1; described from “environs de Quito”); mislabelled locality data and recognised as a Cuban species (see TOMLIN, 1912: 323), currently *Arangia sowerbyana* (L. Pfeiffer, 1846) [Urocoptidae].
- *Cyclostoma aspratile* Morelet (1873, *J. de Conchyl.*, 21: 125, pl. 5 fig 2; described from “environs de Quito”); mislabelled locality data. SOLEM (1960: 422) erroneously attributed Tomlin’s paper quoted above to this taxon. WATTERS (2006: 150) recognised it as *Diplopoma (Diplopoma) lachneri* (L. Pfeiffer, 1862) [Urocoptidae].
- *Cyclostoma bifasciatum* G.B. Sowerby II (1850, *Thesaur. conch.*: 167*, pl. 31B figs 322-323; described from “Guayaquil”); see SOLEM (1960: 422), who argued it must have mislabelled locality data [Urocoptidae].
- *Bulimus maracaibensis* L. Pfeiffer (1856, *Malak. Bl.* 3: 186) was listed by BREURE & BORRERO (2008). This was based on an unconfirmed record by MARTENS (1893 [1890-1901]) and is well outside the range of this species, as explained by BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2016: 84) [Orthalicidae].

Figure 327. Distribution of Etheriidae, Hyriidae, Cyrenidae and Sphaeriida. See Appendix 1 for explanation of ecoregions.

Figura 327. Distribución de Etheriidae, Hyriidae, Cyrenidae y Sphaeriidae. Véase Apéndice 1 para explicación de las ecoregiones.

- *Orthalicus obductus* Shuttleworth (1856, *Noticiae malac.*, 1: 61, pl. 3 figs 1-3) was described from northern Colombia. The Ecuadorian record is likely a misidentification (BREURE & MOGOLLÓN, 2016: 84) [Orthalicidae].

- *Bulimus inaequalis* Pfeiffer (1857, *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 24: 330) was described from “Banks of the Maranhon” and was listed as *Drymaeus (Drymaeus) inaequalis* (Pfeiffer, 1857) by BREURE & BORRERO (2008). This was based on an unconfirmed record in ANSP which, after consultation and re-identification, is now listed under *D. (D.) andai* Jousseau [Bulimulidae].

- *Thaumastus (Atahualpa) brunneus* Strebel (1910, *Abh. Naturw. Ver. Hamb.*, 19 (3): 19, pl. 2 fig. 25) described from “Ecuador”, now considered a synonym of the Bolivian *Thaumastus (Thaumastus) inca* (d’Orbigny, 1835), was excluded by BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2016: 86) [Megaspiridae].

- *Helix equestrata* J. Moricand (1858, *J. de Conchyl.*, 7: 449, pl. 13 fig. 1), mentioned by GERMAIN (1907: 53), is a Peruvian species [Labyrinthidae].

- *Helix oreas* Koch in Philippi (1844, *Abb. Beschr. Conch.*, 1: 151, *Helix* pl. 5 fig. 2) is a Colombian species, and was erroneously mentioned by GERMAIN (1907: 53) from Ecuador; see SOLEM (1966: 168) [Labyrinthidae].

CITIZEN SCIENCE AS A PROMISING TOOL

Worldwide citizen volunteers with an interest in nature are increasingly photographing animals in their natural environment, contributing to community-based monitoring and “crowd-sourcing” data collection (CONRAD & HILCHEY, 2011;

DICKINSON *ET AL.*, 2012). Our study has included several observations made by citizen scientists and included on the iNaturalist website. However, this potentially useful data can only be used to advance our knowledge if the datasets are of high

Figure 328. Way a shell can be photographed to allow expert identification (photos: Marijn Roosen).

Figura 328. Forma en que se puede fotografiar una concha para permitir la identificación de un experto (fotos: Marijn Roosen).

quality (KOSMALA *ET AL.*, 2016). And although several observations on iNaturalist are qualified as ‘research quality’, the snails photographed do not allow for a verified identification in the majority of cases. While pictures of living specimens can be very useful, especially if they are taken by good photographers, these pictures can often be identified only at the genus level; it remains crucial for a specific identification to take at least an apertural view as shown in this study, preferably with some measure of length. Few species show characteristics that makes them identifiable at first sight. As the results of VAN HORN *ET AL.* (2018) showed, current computer vision software leads to poor results especially for groups with small numbers of training examples, of which non-marine molluscs are a typical example. And although the illustrations herein could possibly be used as training pictures for computer vision, it is recommended that citizen scientists take their pictures in a way that allows identification by experts (Fig. 328). If this would be done in the coming years, the contribution of citizen scientists to our knowledge of the malacofauna of Ecuador could improve the distributional data presented herein.

DISCUSSION

The data presented in this study allows for an overall analysis of occurrences and distribution, taking into

account that for a number of species no precise localities are known. For *Bivalvia* generally only the river is known, and each river is counted as one locality record in Table II.

This overview of 331 species comprises a mixture of groups that are relatively well-known due to recent revisionary work (*e.g.*, Galápagos *Bulimulidae*), and groups that were last monographed about a century ago. Together with the poor distributional data, the taxonomic redundancy will differ among the families but is difficult to estimate; for Mollusca as a whole this has been estimated at 20-40% (BOSS, 1971; BOUCHET, 1997). BREURE & MOGOLLÓN (2010) have published about the species-area relationship of land snails for a selected number of Neotropical countries. At that time only provisional data for the Orthalicoidea of Ecuador were available, while for most other countries data on the total number of land snails could be used. From the total number of species, 26 are indicated as introduced. While there may still be some discussion about the native area for some of these species, the present study does not allow for a detailed discussion about the impact assessment of these species in Ecuador. For a recent assessment in Indonesia and a discussion of alternative assessment schemes, see NURINSIYAH & HAUSDORF (2019).

While our data shows that the Ecuadorian mainland malacofauna is highly

Table II. Number of species, and records used in this study.
 Tabla II. Número de especies y registros utilizados en este estudio.

Total number of species	331
- Gastropoda	307
- Bivalvia	24
Number of species with unspecified or imprecise localities	60
Number of species doubtfully recorded for Ecuador	15
Number of species unconfirmed for Ecuador	8
Number of introduced species	26
Number of endemic species (excluding to be confirmed)	179
Number of species without modern records	169
Total number of locality records and observations	946

biodiverse with 331 species, we consider the distributional data to be relatively poor. For many species no vouchered recent records are available, and in many cases species have not been recorded after their initial description. The geographical distribution of sampled localities shows a bias for populated areas and areas with relatively easy access are clearly well-represented. Many historical collections were made this way (see e.g. ORTON, 1871 and BREURE & ARAUJO, 2017 with references therein). It is striking that of no less than 169 species (i.e. ~ 51% of the current total) no 'modern' (last 50 years) records could be found. Two factors might explain this (a) until relatively recently, since the end of the 19th century there has not really been a local knowledge-base, and collecting has mainly been done haphazardly or not reported in full within the literature; (b) the increase of human activities have led to habitat destruction, fragmentation or degradation. This is especially worrying as the predicted future loss of habitat is greatest in tropical areas, particularly forests, grasslands and savannas (e.g., BROOKS ET AL., 2002; GROOM ET AL., 2004; WATSON ET AL., 2010; KNOWLTON & GRAHAM, 2011; MANTYKA-PRINGLE ET AL., 2011; DURÃES ET AL., 2013; MENÉNDEZ-GUERRERO & GRAHAM, 2013; CUESTA ET AL., 2017). Although all specific studies are related to plants and vertebrate species, it is likely that invertebrates (*in casu* molluscs) are affected in a similar way.

We know of one extinct species, but it is worrying that the combination of taxa being endemic to Ecuador and lacking modern records applies for 130 species (~40%), and it cannot be excluded that several are already extinct due to ongoing habitat destruction. Recently the study of ROY ET AL. (2018) has indicated that the acceleration in mining activities constitute a serious threat to protected areas and habitats where land molluscs in Ecuador do occur. As OVANDO ET AL. (2019) have shown, a database of occurrences for a relatively well-sampled group can yield priority areas for molluscan conservation. This gives the firm impression that the need for a systematic survey of the mainland malacofauna through targeted field work is highly urgent. The number of species in the table above with imprecise or unspecified localities (~ 18%) is also an indication that more field research is needed to ascertain the existence of these species. However, we urge malacologists working with the regional fauna to make their results of field work public (through databases or publications) in order to increase our knowledge of occurrences of species in different habitats.

In Table III, for each family the total number of species (including doubtful, unconfirmed, or introduced) and the number of endemic species is given, as well as the number of precise localities recorded so far. It should be stressed that this is only a proxy for the actual

Table III. Number of species, endemics and localities per family.
 Tabla III. Número de especies, endémicas y localidades por familia.

	species	endemic	localities		species	endemic	localities
Helicinidae	11	3	23	Pupillidae	1	0	4
Proserpinellidae	2	2	3	Gastrocoptidae	3	1	0
Neritidae	1	0	4	Valloniidae	2	0	3
Ampullariidae	17	7	4	Vertiginidae	1	0	1
Neocyclotidae	34	26	41	Clausiliidae	11	10	7
Hemisinidae	4	2	3	Limacidae	2	0	0
Thiaridae	1	0	4	Agriolimacidae	3	0	0
Cochliopidae	7	4	5	Gastrodontiidae	1	0	3
Lymnaeidae	5	2	8	Oxychilidae	1	0	0
Physidae	3	0	6	Pristilomatidae	1	0	1
Acroloxidae	1	1	1	Euconulidae	2	1	0
Planorbidae	11	4	16	Spiraxidae	4	3	13
Veronicellidae	9	3	42	Solaropsidae	8	5	10
Achatinidae	24	11	288	Helicidae	1	0	1
Streptaxidae	1	1	1	Labyrinthidae	18	13	82
Scolodontidae	18	12	34	Epiphragmophoridae	1	1	1
Succineidae	4	2	11	Mycetopodidae	11	0	19
Strophocheilidae	2	1	11	Ethiriidae	1	0	2
Orthalicidae	21	13	102	Hyriidae	7	0	1
Amphibulimidae	16	10	58	Cyrenidae	1	0	5
Bulimulidae	46	34	116	Dreissenidae	1	0	0
Megaspiridae	7	4	8	Sphaeriidae	3	2	2
Simpulopsidae	2	1	2	Total	331	179	946

distribution, especially of the land molluscs, as not all observations which can be found on the internet could be checked with certainty.

As this shows the number of endemics is relatively high proportion (~53%) of the current total of species. Even if we take into account that the number of valid species may turn out to be a bit lower, this remains a relatively high percentage. The number of precise localities is, however, very unevenly distributed and mainly concentrated in some of the more well-known families consisting of larger-sized species.

Large areas of Ecuador are recognized as belonging to the main biodiversity hotspots of the world (MYERS *ET AL.*, 2000), and its Andean region stands out as its 'hottest' part (BRUMMITT & LUGHADHA, 2003). According to MESTANZARAMÓN *ET AL.* (2020) the National

System of Protected Areas (Fig. 329) is the most effective in-situ conservation instrument in place at the country level. Nonetheless CUESTA *ET AL.* (2017) have shown that, although Ecuador's efforts to preserve its natural heritage are noteworthy, the current system of national protected areas could be improved considerably. It may be noted that their study was limited to vascular plants, mammals, birds, amphibians and reptiles, and freshwater fishes. As shown in the introduction above, the conservation status of molluscs in Ecuador is poorly known, and partly based on incorrect classification. THOMSON *ET AL.* (2018) have argued that taxonomy based on solid science is necessary for global conservation. But besides a correct classification, good records are also needed of the distribution of species to enable conservation policies and actions. An overlay

Figure 329. Protected areas in Ecuador. Parque Nacional, 1: Cajas; 2: Cotopaxi; 3: Llanganates; 4: Podocarpus; 5: Sangay; 6: Yasuni; 7: Cayambe Coca; 8: Yacuri; 9: Machalilla; 10: Sumaco Napo-Galeras; 11: Galápagos. Reservas Biológicas, 12: Limoncocha; 13: E; Cónдор; 14: El Quimi; 15: Cerro Plateado; 16: Colonso Chalupas. Reserva Geobotánica, 17: Pululahua. Reservas Ecológicas, 18: Antisana; 19: Arenillas; 20: El Ángel; 21: Manglares Cayapas Mataje; 22: Cofan Bermejo; 23: Cotacachi Cayapas; 24: Mache Chindul; 25: Los Ilinizas; 26: Manglares Churute. Reservas Marinas, 27: Galera San Francisco; 28: El Pelado; 29: Cantagallo-Machalilla; 30: Galápagos. Áreas Nacionales de Recreación, 31: El Boliche; 32: Playas de Villamil; 33: Quimsacocha; 34: Parque Lago; 35: Isla Santay; 36: Los Samanes. Reservas de Producción de Fauna, 37: Chimborazo; 38: Cuyabeno; 39: Puntilla de Santa Elena; 40: Manglares El Salado. Refugios de Vida Silvestre, 41: Manglares Estuario del Río Muisne; 42: Paschocha; 43: Islas Corazón y Fragatas; 44: Isla Santa Clara; 45: La Chiquita; 46: El Zarza; 47: Manglares Estuario del Río Esmeraldas; 48: El Pambilar; 49: Manglares El Morro; 50: Pacoche. Área Ecológica de Conservación, 51: Siete Iglesias. Source: <<https://www.nationalparks-worldwide.com/ecuador.htm>>.

Figura 329. Áreas protegidas en Ecuador. Parque Nacional, 1: Cajas; 2: Cotopaxi; 3: Llanganates; 4: Podocarpus; 5: Sangay; 6: Yasuni; 7: Cayambe Coca; 8: Yacuri; 9: Machalilla; 10: Sumaco Napo-Galeras; 11: Galápagos. Reservas Biológicas, 12: Limoncocha; 13: E; Cónдор; 14: El Quimi; 15: Cerro Plateado; 16: Colonso Chalupas. Reserva Geobotánica, 17: Pululahua; Reservas Ecológicas, 18: Antisana; 19: Arenillas; 20: El Ángel; 21: Manglares Cayapas Mataje; 22: Cofan Bermejo; 23: Cotacachi Cayapas; 24: Mache Chindul; 25: Los Ilinizas; 26: Manglares Churute. Reservas Marinas, 27: Galera San Francisco; 28: El Pelado; 29: Cantagallo-Machalilla; 30: Galápagos. Áreas Nacionales de Recreación, 31: El Boliche; 32: Playas de Villamil; 33: Quimsacocha; 34: Parque Lago; 35: Isla Santay; 36: Los Samanes. Reservas de Producción de Fauna, 37: Chimborazo; 38: Cuyabeno; 39: Puntilla de Santa Elena; 40: Manglares El Salado. Refugios de Vida Silvestre, 41: Manglares Estuario del Río Muisne; 42: Paschocha; 43: Islas Corazón y Fragatas; 44: Isla Santa Clara; 45: La Chiquita; 46: El Zarza; 47: Manglares Estuario del Río Esmeraldas; 48: El Pambilar; 49: Manglares El Morro; 50: Pacoche. Área Ecológica de Conservación, 51: Siete Iglesias. Fuente: <<https://www.nationalparks-worldwide.com/ecuador.htm>>.

Figure 330. Projection of recorded localities from terrestrial species (open circles) on the map with protected areas on the mainland. See also legend of previous figure.

Figura 330. Proyección de localidades registradas de especies terrestres (círculos abiertos) en el mapa con áreas protegidas en tierra firme. Véase también la leyenda de la figura anterior.

of all recorded localities of terrestrial species on the map of protected areas (Fig. 330) reveals that most of the protected areas are virtually unknown as far as their malacofauna is concerned. It is clear to us that without good (published) inventories, impactful conservation actions will be difficult or, with ongoing habitat changes, will be shown to have become futile in the future.

The 'known unknown' status of many of Ecuador's non-marine molluscs, combined with the ongoing biodiversity threats and climate change, makes an increased effort to make inventories in a systemic way (by ecoregion or habitat type) very necessary. Hopefully this checklist can serve as a baseline document for further malacological work in this biodiversity hotspot.

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APPENDIX 1. ECOREGIONS**1. Terrestrial ecoregions**

The following terrestrial ecoregions (see Fig. 3A) have been defined by the World Wildlife Fund (WWF 2015) as occurring in Ecuador. Those used by BREURE & BORRERO (2008) have been partly re-defined or re-named. Please note the following caveats (OLSON *ET AL.*, 2004): First, no single biogeographic framework is optimal for all taxa. Ecoregions reflect the best compromise for as many taxa as possible. Second, ecoregion boundaries rarely form abrupt edges; rather, ecotones and mosaic habitats bound them. Third, most ecoregions contain habitats that differ from their assigned biome (*e.g.*, for example, rainforest ecoregions in Amazonia often contain small edaphic savannas). With these caveats in mind, ecoregions can form useful units for biological analysis and for conservation planning and action.

The numbers used in Fig. 3A are given between brackets; between square brackets the corresponding WWF codes are given referring to descriptions in WWF (2015).

Tropical and subtropical moist broadleaf forests

- Eastern Cordillera real montane forests (7) [NT0121]
- Napo moist forests (8) [NT0142]
- Northwestern Andean montane forests (5) [NT0145]
- Western Ecuador moist forests (1) [NT0178]

Tropical and subtropical broadleaf forests

- Ecuadorian dry forests (2) [NT0214]
- Tumbes-Piura dry forests (9) [NT0232]

Flooded grassland and savannas

- Guayaquil flooded grasslands (4) [NT0905]

Montane grassland and shrublands

- Cordillera Central páramo (10) [NT1004]
- Northern Andean páramo (6) [NT1006]

Mangroves

- South American Pacific mangroves (3) [NT1405]

2. Freshwater ecoregions

The freshwater ecoregions (Fig. 3B) are based on ABELL *ET AL.* (2008), the numbers used in the figure are behind each ecoregion below, and further information is available on the WWF site Freshwater Ecoregions Of the World (FEOW, 2019). In Ecuador the following occur:

Tropical and subtropical coastal rivers

- North Andean Pacific Slopes - Rio Atrato (11) [301]

Montane freshwaters

- Amazonas High Andes (12) [312]
- Western Amazon Piedmont (13) [313]

Tropical and subtropical floodplain rivers and wetland complexes

- Amazonas Lowlands (14) [316]

The occurrences of species in the ecoregions are summarised in Table IV. This may allow for further studies in ecological communities or biogeography (but see MUNGUÍA-ORTEGA *ET AL.*, 2021).

Table IV. Ecuadorian species and their occurrences in ecoregions.

Tabla IV. Especies ecuatorianas y su presencia en ecorregiones.

	TERRESTRIAL										FRESHWATER		
	moist forest				dry forest		grassland	páramo	mangrove	coast	montane		lowland
	NT0121	NT0142	NT0145	NT0178	NT0214	NT0232	NT0905	NT1006	NT1405	301	312	313	316
<i>Bourciera fraseri</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1859)	x												
<i>Bourciera helicinaeformis</i> L. Pfeiffer, 1852			x										
<i>Bourciera striatula</i> K. Miller, 1879			x										
<i>Bourciera viridissima</i> K. Miller, 1879			x										
<i>Bourciera</i> sp.													
<i>Helicina</i> (?) cf. <i>bourguignatiana</i> Ancey, 1892	x												
<i>Helicina</i> (?) <i>ecuadoriana</i> K. Miller, 1879			x										
<i>Helicina</i> (?) <i>laus</i> A.J. Wagner, 1905 ‡		x											
<i>Helicina</i> (?) <i>rhynchostoma</i> L. Pfeiffer, 1865													
<i>Helicina</i> (?) <i>unizonata</i> F. Haas, 1966 ‡		x											
<i>Lindiella cinnanomea</i> (Sykes, 1900)	x												
<i>Archecharax cousini</i> (Jousseau, 1887)			x										
<i>Clypeolum latissimum</i> (Broderip, 1833)									x				
<i>Asolene crassa</i> (Swainson, 1823)													
<i>Pomacea (Effusa) expansa</i> (K. Miller, 1879)									x				
<i>Pomacea (Effusa) quinindensis</i> (K. Miller, 1879)									x				
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) aldersoni</i> (Pain, 1946)													
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) bulla</i> (Reeve, 1856)													
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) canaliculata</i> (Lamarck, 1822)													
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) columellaris</i> (A.A. Gould, 1848)													
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) cousini</i> (Jousseau, 1887)													
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) cumingii</i> (King & Broderip, 1831)													
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) martinezi</i> (Hidalgo, 1866)									x				
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) modesta</i> (Busch, 1859)													
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) pealiana</i> (I. Lea, 1838)													
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) puntaplaya</i> (Cousin, 1887)													
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) reyrei</i> (Cousin, 1887)													
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) tenuissima</i> (Jousseau, 1894)													
<i>Pomacea (Pomacea) urceus</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)													x
<i>Daronia bicincta</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)													
<i>Daronia martinezi</i> (Hidalgo, 1866)	x												
<i>Calaperostoma bourcierii</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1854)			x										
<i>Calaperostoma cousini</i> (Jousseau, 1884) *			x										
<i>Calaperostoma</i> cf. <i>cumingii</i> (G.B. Sowerby I, 1832)			x										
<i>Calaperostoma esmeraldense</i> (K. Miller, 1879)			x	x									
<i>Calaperostoma guayaquilense</i> (G.B. Sowerby II, 1850)				x									
<i>Calaperostoma hidalgoi</i> (Crosse, 1866) *													
<i>Calaperostoma nigrofasciatum</i> (K. Miller, 1879)	x		x										
<i>Calaperostoma purum</i> (Forbes, 1850)													
<i>Calaperostoma rosenbergi</i> (S.I. daCosta, 1898)				x									
<i>Incidostoma chokolatum</i> J.P.E. Morrison, 1955								x					

	TERRESTRIAL									FRESHWATER			
	moist forest				dry forest		grassland	paramo	mangrove	coast	montane		lowland
	NT0121	NT0142	NT0145	NT0178	NT0214	NT0232	NT0905	NT1006	NT1405	301	312	313	316
<i>Incidostoma diminutum</i> J.P.E. Morrison, 1955									x				
<i>Incidostoma dunkeri</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1857)													
<i>Incidostoma ecuadorensis</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)													
<i>Incidostoma giganteum</i> (Reeve, 1842)	x	x											
<i>Incidostoma hitomi</i> Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942													
<i>Incidostoma jacksoni</i> J.P.E. Morrison, 1955	x												
<i>Incidostoma manabensis</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)				x									
<i>Incidostoma masvensis</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)					x								
<i>Incidostoma pailaense</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)													
<i>Incidostoma pazi</i> (Crosse, 1866)	x							x					
<i>Incidostoma perezii</i> (Hidalgo, 1866)	x												
<i>Incidostoma pichinchense</i> Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942	x												
<i>Incidostoma popayanum</i> (I. Lea, 1838)								x					
<i>Incidostoma quitense</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1852)	x		x										
<i>Incidostoma salangoense</i> (Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942)					x								
<i>Incidostoma stirlingi</i> Bartsch & J.P.E. Morrison, 1942	x												
<i>Incidostoma subcingulatum</i> (Kobelt, 1912)													
<i>Lagocyclus antonii</i> (Cousin, 1887)													
<i>Lagocyclus crosseanus</i> (Hidalgo, 1866)		x											
<i>Lagocyclus haematomma</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1863)													
<i>Lagocyclus vasconesi</i> (Jousseau, 1897)		x											
<i>Neocyclotus granulatum</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1863)													
<i>Hemisinus flammeus</i> (F.C. Baker, 1914)												x	
<i>Hemisinus guayaquilensis</i> (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853)										x			
<i>Hemisinus maculatus</i> (I. Lea, 1834)										x			
<i>Hemisinus simplex</i> (Tryon, 1866)													
<i>Melanoides tuberculata</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)										x			
<i>Andesipyrghus sketi</i> Hershler & Velkovrh, 1993											x		
<i>Araopyrgus colombiensis</i> Malek & Little, 1971													x
? <i>Cochliopina boetzkessi</i> (K. Miller, 1879)													
? <i>Cochliopina ecuadoriana</i> (K. Miller, 1879)													
<i>Lithococcus multicarinatus</i> (K. Miller, 1879)										x			
<i>Littoridina gaudichaudi</i> Souleyet, 1852 †													
<i>Pyrgophorus pedrinus</i> (K. Miller, 1879)										x			
<i>Galba cousini</i> (Jousseau, 1887)										x			
<i>Galba nitidella</i> (E. von Martens, 1885)											x		
? <i>Galba raphaelis</i> (Jousseau, 1887)											x		
<i>Galba schirazensis</i> (Küster, 1862)										x			
<i>Pseudosuccinea columella</i> (Say, 1817)										x			
<i>Haitia acuta</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)										x			
<i>Mayabina carolita</i> (Jousseau, 1887)										x			
<i>Mexinauta peruviana</i> (J.E. Gray, 1828)										x			
<i>Acroloxus culicoides</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)										x			
<i>Biomphalaria cousini</i> Paraense, 1966										x			
<i>Biomphalaria equatoria</i> (Cousin, 1887)										x			
<i>Biomphalaria peregrina</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)										x			

	TERRESTRIAL										FRESHWATER		
	moist forest				dry forest		grassland	piramo	mangrove	coast	montane		lowland
	NT0121	NT0142	NT0145	NT0178	NT0214	NT0232	NT0905	NT1006	NT1405	301	312	313	316
<i>Biomphalaria sericea</i> (Dunker, 1848)													
<i>Drepanotrema anatinum</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)													X
<i>Drepanotrema kermatoides</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)													X
<i>Drepanotrema lucidum</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1839)													X
<i>Drepanotrema surinamense</i> (Clessin, 1884)													X
<i>Gyraulus hindsianus</i> (Dunker, 1848)													X
<i>Helisoma trivalvis</i> (Say, 1818)													X
<i>Planorbella clevei</i> Jousseume, 1887													
<i>Belocaulus boetzkesi</i> (K. Miller, 1879)													
<i>Colosius confusus</i> Gomes, Robinson, Zimmerman, Obregón & Barr, 2013	X		X						X				
<i>Colosius festae</i> (Colosi, 1921)									X				
<i>Colosius propinquus</i> (Colosi, 1921)									X				
<i>Colosius pulcher</i> (Colosi, 1921)	X		X						X				
<i>Diploselenodes occidentalis</i> (Guilding, 1825)													
<i>Diploselenodes olivaceus</i> (Stearns, 1871)			X	X			X						
<i>Sarasinula plebeia</i> (P. Fischer, 1868)				X									
<i>Sarasinula linguaeformis</i> (C.G. Semper, 1885)	X		X										
<i>Achatina (Lissachatina) fulica</i> Bowdich, 1822	X	X	X	X	X	X							
<i>Allopeas gracile</i> (Hutton, 1834)					X								
<i>Allopeas micra</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)	X		X										
<i>Beckianum beckianum</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)	X				X		X						
<i>Leptinaria aequatoria</i> (K. Miller, 1879)				X									
<i>Leptinaria eyerdami</i> F. Haas, 1951	X												
<i>Leptinaria funcki</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)													
<i>Leptinaria unilamellata</i> (d'Orbigny, 1838)	X	X		X									
<i>Opeas hannense</i> (Rang, 1831)				X									
<i>Opeas rarum</i> K. Miller, 1879				X									
<i>Protobeliscus fairmaireanus</i> (Petit de la Saussaye, 1853)	X		X										
<i>Protobeliscus haplostylus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)	X												
<i>Protobeliscus jousseumei</i> (Cousin, 1887)	X		X										
<i>Protobeliscus major</i> (K. Miller, 1878)			X										
<i>Protobeliscus pairensis</i> (Higgins, 1872)													
<i>Protobeliscus riparius</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1854)				X									
? <i>Pseudopeas viviparum</i> (K. Miller, 1878) *			X										
<i>Rhodea aequatoria</i> S.I. daCosta, 1899			X										
<i>Rhodea cousini</i> Jousseume, 1900			X										
<i>Subulina octona</i> (Bruguière, 1789)		X		X	X								
<i>Synapterpes auratus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)	X		X										
<i>Synapterpes visendus</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)	X		X										
<i>Zoniferella albobalteata</i> (Dunker, 1882)	X		X										
<i>Zoniferella bizonalis</i> (Germain, 1907)			X										
<i>Martinella martinella</i> Jousseume, 1887 *			X										
<i>Drepanostomella exisa</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1855)			X										
<i>Drepanostomella lyzarzaburui</i> (Jousseume, 1887)			X										
<i>Guesteria locardi</i> Jousseume, 1887	X		X										

	TERRESTRIAL									FRESHWATER				
	moist forest				dry forest		grassland	paramo	mangrove	coast	montane		lowland	
	NT0121	NT0142	NT0145	NT0178	NT0214	NT0232	NT0905	NT1006	NT1405		301	312		313
<i>Guesteria martinida</i> Jousseume, 1887				x										
<i>Guesteria powisiana</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)									x					
<i>Happia baezensis</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)	x		x											
<i>Happia cyclina</i> (Cousin, 1887)				x										
<i>Happia flora</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1852)	x		x											
? <i>Scolodonta guayaquilensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1854)	x		x											
<i>Systrophia entodonta</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1859)	x													
<i>Systrophia helicycloides</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)	x													
<i>Systrophia heligmoida</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)	x		x											
<i>Systrophia insignis</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)	x													
<i>Systrophia ortoni</i> (Crosse, 1871)			x											
<i>Systrophia reyrei</i> (Souverbie, 1858)						x								
<i>Systrophia stenostrepta</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1857)														
<i>Zilchistrophia hiliaryae</i> Páll-Gergely, 2014			x											
<i>Zilchistrophia shiwarorum</i> Páll-Gergely, 2014			x											
<i>Omalonyx geayi</i> Tillier, 1980			x											
<i>Succinea aequinoctialis</i> d'Orbigny, 1838					x	x								
<i>Succinea marianita</i> (Cousin, 1887)				x										
<i>Succinea martini</i> (Jousseume, 1887)				x										
<i>Megalobulimus garciamoreni</i> (K. Miller, 1878)				x	x									
<i>Megalobulimus papelairianus</i> (Nyst, 1845)	x	x												
<i>Clathrothalicus corydon</i> (Crosse, 1869)				x										
<i>Clathrothalicus magnificus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)														
<i>Clathrothalicus phoebus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1863)														
<i>Corona pfeifferi</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)	x	x												
<i>Corona regalis</i> (Hupé, 1857)	x													
<i>Kara indentata</i> (S.I. daCosta, 1901)														
<i>Kara thompsonii</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1845)	x													
<i>Orthalicus bensoni</i> (Reeve, 1849)			x											
<i>Orthalicus bifulguratus</i> (Reeve, 1849)	x			x										
<i>Orthalicus mars</i> L. Pfeiffer, 1861														
<i>Porphyrobaphe (Oxyorthalicus) irrorata</i> (Reeve, 1849)	x		x											
<i>Porphyrobaphe (Oxyorthalicus) subirrorata</i> (S.I. daCosta, 1898)	x		x											
<i>Porphyrobaphe (Porphyrobaphe) iostoma</i> (G.B. Sowerby I, 1824)					x	x	x			x				
<i>Porphyrobaphe (Porphyrobaphe) saturnus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1860)	x		x											
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) atramentaria</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1855)	x													
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) augusti</i> (Jousseume, 1887)	x													
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) deburghiae</i> (Reeve, 1859)	x		x											
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) fraseri</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1858)	x													
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) kelleitii</i> (Reeve, 1850)	x													
<i>Sultana (Metorthalicus) yatesi galactostoma</i> (Ancey, 1890)														
<i>Sultana (Sultana) sultana</i> (Dillwyn, 1817)	x	x		x	x									
<i>Plekocheilus (Aeropictus) tenuissimus</i> Weyrauch, 1967				x								x		
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) aristaceus</i> (Crosse, 1869)				x										
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) aureonitens</i> (K. Miller, 1878)				x										
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) cardinalis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x		x											

	TERRESTRIAL										FRESHWATER			
	moist forest				dry forest		grassland	piramo	mangrove	coast	montane		lowland	
	NT0121	NT0142	NT0145	NT0178	NT0214	NT0232	NT0905	NT1006	NT1405		301	312	313	316
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) dolianus</i> (S.I. daCosta, 1898)			x											
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) eros</i> (Angas, 1878)	x													
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) floccosus</i> (Spix, 1827)	x													
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) jimenezi</i> (Hidalgo, 1872)	x													
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) lynceus</i> (Deville & Hupé, 1850)	x	x												
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) nocturnus</i> Pilsbry, 1939	x		x											
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) oligostylus</i> Pilsbry, 1939	x													
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) piperitus mcgintyi</i> 'Pilsbry' H.B. Baker, 1963			x											
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) roseolabrum</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x													
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) taylorianus</i> (Reeve, 1849)	x		x											
<i>Plekocheilus (Eurytus) tricolor</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x		x											
<i>Plekocheilus (Plekocheilus) cecepeus</i> Breure & Araujo, 2015														
<i>Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) aequatoria</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x													
<i>Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) anthisanensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)									x					
<i>Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) caliginosa</i> (Reeve, 1849)									x					
<i>Bocourtia (Kuschelenia) cotopaxiensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)			x						x					
<i>Bostryx alausiensis</i> (Cousin, 1887)									x					
<i>Bostryx bilineatus</i> (G.B. Sowerby I, 1833)				x	x		x							
<i>Bostryx juana</i> (Cousin, 1887)	x													
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) aequatorianus</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)			x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) albolabiatus</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x													
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) ambustus</i> (Reeve, 1849)	x		x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) andai</i> Jousseau, 1898	x													
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) baezensis</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)	x													
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) bourcierii</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x													
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) chimborasensis</i> (Reeve, 1848)									x					
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) chrysomelas</i> (Martens, 1867)														
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) expansus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)	x	x												
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) fallax</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x		x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) fucatus</i> (Reeve, 1849)			x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) hidalgoi</i> (S.I. daCosta, 1898)	x													
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) joubini</i> Germain, 1907														
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) membrielinus</i> (Crosse, 1867)			x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) nystianus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)			x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) ochrocheilus</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x													
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) orthostoma</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)														
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) peelii</i> (Reeve, 1859)			x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) petasites</i> (K. Miller, 1878)			x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) planibasis</i> Pilsbry, 1932			x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) quadrifasciatus</i> (Angas, 1878)	x													
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rabuti</i> (Jousseau, 1898)			x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rhoadii</i> Pilsbry, 1932			x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) rubrovariegatus</i> (Higgins, 1868)	x													
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) sachsei</i> (Albers, 1854)	x		x											
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) strigatus</i> (G.B. Sowerby I, 1833)	x													

	TERRESTRIAL										FRESHWATER		
	moist forest				dry forest		grassland	paramo	mangrove	coast	montane	lowland	
	NT0121	NT0142	NT0145	NT0178	NT0214	NT0232	NT0905	NT1006	NT1405	301	312	313	316
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) tigrinus</i> (S.I. daCosta, 1898)													
<i>Drymaeus (Drymaeus) valsus</i> Fulton, 1907													
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) cactivorus</i> (Broderip, 1832)					x		x						
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) flavidulus</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x												
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) loxanus</i> (Higgins, 1872)													
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) loxensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)	x												
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) subpellucidus</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)													
<i>Drymaeus (Mesembrinus) wintlei</i> Finch, 1929													
<i>Naesiotus florschuetzi</i> Breure, 1978					x	x							
<i>Naesiotus fontainii</i> (d'Orbigny, 1838)				x									
<i>Naesiotus quitensis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)	x		x					x					
<i>Stenostylus colmeiroi</i> (Hidalgo, 1872)	x												
<i>Suniellus adriani</i> Breure, 2011								x					
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) buckleyi</i> (Higgins, 1872)	x												
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) flori</i> (Jousseume, 1897)	x												
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) hartwegi</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)													
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) integer</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1855)													
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) loxostomus</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)													
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) orcesi</i> Weyrauch, 1967				x									
<i>Thaumastus (Thaumastus) tatutor</i> (Jousseume, 1887)													
? <i>Leiostracus webberi</i> Pilsbry, 1939													
<i>Simpulopsis (Eudioputus) citrinovitrea</i> (S. Moricand, 1836)			x										
<i>Pupoides paredesii</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)													
<i>Gastrocapta pazi</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)				x									
<i>Gastrocapta strangei</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1854)					x								
<i>Gastrocapta wolfii</i> (K. Miller, 1879)			x										
<i>Pupisoma (Ptychopatulula) dioscoricolum</i> (C.B. Adams, 1845)	x												
<i>Pupisoma (Pupisoma?) macneilli</i> (Clapp, 1918)	x												
<i>Sterkia (Metasterkia) bakeri</i> Pilsbry, 1921					x								
<i>Columbinia (Columbinia) cocaensis</i> (Jousseume, 1900)		x											
<i>Columbinia (Columbinia) perezii</i> (Jousseume, 1887)			x										
<i>Columbinia (Steatonenia) cousini</i> (Jousseume, 1900)													
<i>Columbinia (Steatonenia) reyrei</i> (Jousseume, 1887)			x										
<i>Cyclonena cyclostoma</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1850)													
<i>Incania anoecia</i> Ehrmann, 1949													
<i>Incania auriculina</i> (Jousseume, 1900)													
<i>Incania bourcierii</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1854)													
<i>Incania crosseii</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)	x												
<i>Neniaptyx buckleyi</i> (Higgins, 1872)	x												
<i>Neniops archidona</i> (Jousseume, 1900)		x											
<i>Limacus flavus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)													
<i>Limacus maculatus</i> (Kaleniczenko, 1851)													
<i>Deroceras reticulatum</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)													
<i>Deroceras laeve</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)													
<i>Deroceras invadens</i> Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011													
<i>Zonitoides (Zonitoides) arboreus</i> (Say, 1816)	x		x										

	TERRESTRIAL										FRESHWATER			
	moist forest				dry forest		grassland	piramo	mangrove	coast	montane		lowland	
	NT0121	NT0142	NT0145	NT0178	NT0214	NT0232	NT0905	NT1006	NT1405	301	312	313	316	
<i>Hawaia minuscula</i> (A. Binney, 1840)	x													
<i>Guppya wolfii</i> (K. Miller, 1879) *														
<i>Guppya</i> sp.														
<i>Euglandina aequatoria</i> (S.I. daCosta, 1900)			x											
<i>Euglandina ecuadoriana</i> (K. Miller, 1878)			x											
<i>Euglandina saccata</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1861)	x													
<i>Euglandina striata</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)			x		x									
<i>Solaropsis boetzkesi</i> (K. Miller, 1878)			x											
<i>Solaropsis cousini</i> Jousseaume, 1887														
<i>Solaropsis gibboni</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)	x		x											
<i>Solaropsis iris</i> (K. Miller, 1878)			x											
<i>Solaropsis monile</i> (Broderip, 1832)					x									
<i>Solaropsis napensis</i> (Crosse, 1871)														
<i>Solaropsis quadrivittata</i> (Hidalgo, 1869)	x													
<i>Solaropsis selenostoma</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1854)			x											
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	x													
<i>Isomeria aequatoria</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1860)														
<i>Isomeria aequatoriana</i> (Hidalgo, 1867)	x	x	x											
<i>Isomeria alagoana</i> Jousseaume, 1887			x											
<i>Isomeria bituberculata</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x		x											
<i>Isomeria bourcierii</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853)	x		x											
<i>Isomeria cymatodes</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1852)			x											
<i>Isomeria gealei</i> (E.A. Smith, 1877)	x													
<i>Isomeria globosa</i> (Broderip, 1832)	x		x	x				x						
<i>Isomeria hartwegi</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1846)	x													
<i>Isomeria jacksoni</i> Solem, 1966	x													
<i>Isomeria juno</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1850)	x													
<i>Isomeria kalbergi</i> (K. Miller, 1878)	x		x											
<i>Isomeria meyeri</i> (Kobelt, 1894)														
<i>Isomeria morula</i> (Hidalgo, 1870)														
<i>Isomeria triodonta</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)														
<i>Labyrinthus bifurcatus</i> (Deshayes, 1838)														
<i>Labyrinthus manueli</i> Higgins, 1872	x	x												
<i>Labyrinthus raimondii</i> (Philippi, 1867)		x												
<i>Epiphyragmaphora macasi</i> (Higgins, 1872)	x													
<i>Anodontites carinata</i> (Dunker, 1858)														
<i>Anodontites crispata</i> (Bruguière, 1792)									x			x		
<i>Anodontites elongata</i> (W. Swainson, 1823)														
<i>Anodontites tenebricosa</i> (I. Lea, 1834)											x			
<i>Anodontites tortilis</i> (I. Lea, 1852)														
<i>Anodontites trapesialis</i> (Lamarck, 1819)											x	x		
<i>Anodontites trigona</i> (Spix, 1827)											x	x		
<i>Diplodontites cookei</i> W.B. Marshall, 1922													x	
<i>Lamproscapha ensiformis</i> (Spix, 1827)													x	
<i>Mycetopoda siliquosa</i> (Spix, 1827)											x	x		
<i>Mycetopodella facata</i> (Higgins, 1868)													x	

	TERRESTRIAL									FRESHWATER			
	moist forest				dry forest		grassland	paramo	mangrove	coast	montane		lowland
	NT0121	NT0142	NT0145	NT0178	NT0214	NT0232	NT0905	NT1006	NT1405	301	312	313	316
<i>Bartlettia stefanensis</i> (J. Moricand, 1856)													X
<i>Castalia ambigua</i> Lamarck, 1819													
<i>Castalia crosseana</i> Hidalgo, 1865													
<i>Castalia ecarinata</i> Mousson, 1869													
<i>Diplodon guaranianus</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)													
<i>Diplodon hylaeus</i> (d'Orbigny, 1835)													
<i>Prisodon obliquus</i> Schumacher, 1817													X
<i>Tripodon corrugatus</i> (Lamarck, 1819)													
<i>Corbicula fluminea</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)										X		X	
<i>Mytilopsis trautwineana</i> (Tryon, 1866)													
<i>Pisidium boliviense</i> Sturany, 1900													
<i>Pisidium wolfi</i> Clessin, 1879										X			
<i>Sphaerium aequatortiale</i> Clessin, 1879										X			

APPENDIX 2. LOCALITY DATA

Table V. Localities, coordinates and altitude in meters above sea level.
 Tabla V. Localidades, coordenadas y altura en metros sobre el nivel del mar.

Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)
Abitagua	-1.42348	-78.15052	2900	Chanduy	-2.40179	-80.67965	11
Achupallas	-2.28279	-78.76929	3333	Chaupi	-1.16667	-78.61667	2900
Agoyan	-1.38333	-78.31667	2290	Chical	1.01232	-78.24334	971
Agua Blanca	-1.53267	-80.73785	111	Chillogallo	-0.27541	-78.55577	2882
Aguarico	-0.28333	-75.86667	227	Chimborazo (Cerro)	-1.48217	-78.78114	4535
Alaspungo	-0.01224	-78.6062	3075	Chimborazo (Prov.)	-1.91667	-78.75	
Alausi	-2.20329	-78.84714	2345	Chiquaza	-1.93333	-77.83333	790
Alchipichi	0.04221	-78.40272	2084	Chiriboga	-0.22631	-78.7664	1845
Alóag	-0.46786	-78.58445	2880	Chongon	-2.23596	-80.0784	43
Altar (Cerro)	-1.67307	-78.44477	3859	Chota	0.47233	-78.06162	1553
Ambato	-1.24908	-78.61675	2597	Chuintsa	-2.014850	-76.681083	244
Andoas	-2.56667	-76.63333	251	Chunchi	-2.29026	-78.91994	2260
Antisana (Azuay)	-2.95	-79.01667	2700	Colonche	-2.02148	-80.66924	10
Antisana (Cerro)	-0.49573	-78.18787	4292	Cosanga	-0.57763	-77.86886	1940
Archidona	-0.9095	-77.80772	576	Cotacachi	0.30107	-78.26428	2442
Ashuara	-2.75	-77.5	245	Cotopaxi (Cerro)	-0.68517	-78.47603	4188
Atacames	0.87012	-79.84821	10	Cuenca	-2.9	-78.98333	2543
Atacames (9 km SW)	0.76667	-79.83333	67	Cuenca (11 mi W)	-2.870414	-79.204382	3700
Ayampe	-1.66667	-80.81667	5	Cuenca-Paute	-2.85253	-78.82655	2560
Ayapamba-Santa Rosa	-3.574843	-79.772496	1128	Cumbaya	-0.2007	-78.43133	2361
Azogues	-2.73969	-78.8486	2500	Cushuimi	-2.52083	-77.72944	297
Baeza	-0.45	-77.88333	1916	Cusuimi	-2.72491	-77.67824	226
Baeza Colonial	-0.46314	-77.89375	1898	Cuyabeno	-0.25911	-75.89398	223
Bahia de Caraquez	-0.59792	-80.42367	8	Cuyabeno (R.F.)	-0.01667	-76.18333	221
Ballenita	-2.20528	-80.87305	17	Cuyuja	-0.42306	-78.06515	3600
Balsas	-3.76085	-79.82404	660	Durán	-2.17579	-79.85519	3
Balzar	-1.36501	-79.90494	36	El Chaco	-0.33822	-77.81018	1600
Baños	-1.39699	-78.42289	1805	El Goaltal	0.801339	-78.209513	1530
Boliche	-0.45	-78.7	2836	El Laurel	0.83175	-78.0525	2480
Bucay (Chimborazo)	-2.166667	-79.1	880	El Pailón	0.997769	-78.26241	1267
Bucay (Guayas)	-2.68333	-79.66667	21	El Pun	0.66667	-77.61667	3125
Cabo San Lorenzo	-1.05875	-80.91257	14	El Troje	-0.33333	-78.51667	3055
Cajabamba	-1.69592	-78.75823	3200	Esmeraldas	0.9667	-79.65	10
Canande Reserve	0.5263889	-79.21278	343	Francisco de Orrelana	-0.46645	-76.98719	255
Cañar	-2.56062	-78.9394	3120	Gonzanama	-4.05972	-79.3706	1195
Canelos	-1.58941	-77.7576	472	Gualaceo	-2.89264	-78.77814	2235
Caranqui	0.32287	-78.12173	2297	Gualaceo-Azogues	-2.854461	-78.811333	2360
Carmela	-1.71667	-80.0	12	Gualaquiza	-3.403333	-78.581667	850
Cascol (8 km NNW)	-1.566667	-80.483333	370	Gualea	0.11667	-78.74761	1342
Casitagua	-0.03901	-78.51029	3578	Guarumos	-0.06667	-78.63333	2892
Catamayo	-3.98652	-79.35912	1268	Guayaquil	-2.250813	-79.872980	3
Cayambe	0.04084	-78.14524	2815	Guayaquil (near)	-2.42586	-80.0762	2
Cerros de Abitagua	-1.42348	-75.15052	2035	Guayllabamba	-0.05795	-78.3411	2172
Cerros de Masvale	-2.393	-79.67541	572	Huigra	-2.28902	-78.98329	1267
Chacras	-3.53064	-80.1654	76	Ibarra	0.37702	-78.11812	2198
Chaguarpamba	-3.87776	-79.64455	1768	Ibarra (35 km N)	0.593754	-77.960493	2900
Chambo	-1.73055	-78.59595	2751	Ibarra (9.4 km N)	0.445354	-78.117712	1770
Chanchalahuá	-1.58333	-78.73333	3175	Iliniza Sur	-0.67872	-78.72763	4094

BREURE *ET AL.*: Land and freshwater molluscs of mainland Ecuador

Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)
Imbabura (Cerro)	0.275128	-78.178175	3700	Nuevo Rocafuerte	-0.92624	-75.40243	190
Isla de Puna	-2.73879	-79.90881	17	Olmedo	0.14711	-78.0709	3115
Isla la Plata	-1.27252	-81.06906	83	Otavalo	0.23457	-78.26248	2532
Jama	-0.166667	-80.25	59	Otongo	-0.392	-79.19483	593
Jipijapa	-1.34872	-80.57875	287	Oyacachi	-0.21485	-78.07154	3253
Jipijapa (11 km WSW)	-1.383333	-80.616667	250	Pacayacu	-2.04699	-76.9657	289
Jipijapa (6 km SSE)	-1.4	-80.583333	320	Pachijal valley	0.0159	-78.72775	1725
Julio Moreno	-2.18471	-80.35916	121	Pacto	0.15	-78.75	1100
La Selva Lodge	0.266667	-77.416667	605	Pajan (9 km WSW)	-1.583333	-80.483333	178
Lago Agrio	0.079685	-77.010065	320	Palenque Science Center	-0.58656	-79.36472	148
Lago Limoncacha	-0.41068	-76.62378	249	Pallatanga	-2.01392	-78.92697	2115
Lago San Pablo	0.209167	-78.224167	2665	Palmar	-1.88333	-79.46667	5
Laguna de Samona	-0.46645	-76.98719	253	Palmar (4 km N)	-1.95	-80.716667	75
Las Cruces	-1.616667	-79.96667	21	Palmar (5 km N)	-1.966667	-80.716667	65
Latacunga	-0.93521	-78.61554	2770	Papallacta	-0.3716	-78.13927	3473
Le Chontal	0.30107	-78.26428	2444	Paramba	0.816667	-78.35	702
Lida (21 km NNW)	0.918333	-78.545	760	Paramo de Sighos	-0.7	-78.883333	2770
Lita	0.87475	-78.46781	675	Paschoa	-0.43333	-78.48333	4200
Llao	-0.24994	-78.58379	3052	Pascales	-2.07368	-79.92889	19
Loja	-3.99313	-79.20422	2060	Paschoa (Cerro)	-0.499743	-78.455043	3410
Loja (Prov.)	-4.16667	-79.5		Pastocalle	-0.61372	-78.62725	3371
Loreto	-0.633333	-77.316667	491	Patate	-1.31215	-78.508	2176
Los Puentes	0.04604	-78.67427	1589	Patuca	-2.7559	-78.26231	539
Macas	-2.30868	-78.11135	914	Patuca (59 km SE)	-3.250555	-78.117222	1870
Machachi	-0.51011	-78.56712	2933	Paute	-2.77928	-78.76213	2189
Machai	-2.98942	-79.07142	2725	Pedro Carbo	-1.81563	-80.23309	55
Machala	-3.26667	-79.95	28	Penipe-Puela	-1.58083	-78.53726	2523
Machala (59 km W)	-0.368311	-78.834228	1250	Pichincha (Cerro)	-0.171	-78.598	4500
Machalilla	-1.47341	-80.76439	20	Pifo (14 km W)	-0.22831	-78.34316	2590
Malacatos	-4.233333	-79.23333	1765	Pilatón valley	-0.31604	-78.95475	819
Manduriacu	0.293889	-78.86389	1015	Pinas	-3.68107	-79.68083	1010
Manglaralto	-1.84942	-80.74505	7	Pinas (9 km W)	-3.65663	-79.75360	859
Manta	-0.96212	-80.71271	23	Pintag	-0.366667	-78.38333	2793
Mapasingue	-2.15	-79.9		Pisagua	-1.08333	-79.4	83
Mataje	1.06667	-78.58333		Pomasqui	-0.0542	-78.45382	2457
Mendez	-2.73233	-78.30995	446	Parvenir	-1.61311	-75.73327	200
Mera	-1.46667	-78.13333	2764	Progreso	-1.77454	-79.7153	8
Miasal	-2.59578	-77.77803	277	Progreso (11 km W)	-2.383333	-80.466667	62
Milagro	-2.13404	-79.59415	5	Progreso (17 km WNW)	-2.366667	-80.55	180
Milpe	0.02969	-78.95	900	Progreso (5 km NNE)	-2.366667	-80.483333	69
Mindo	-0.04933	-78.77269	1270	Providencia	-0.472253	-76.45913	230
Mirador	-0.01667	-78.51667	2750	Pucayacu	-0.71507	-79.1177	668
Mocha	-1.41939	-78.66207	3261	Puerto Lopez	-1.55917	-80.80957	12
Montalvo	-2.04934	-77.00856	316	Puerto Napo	-1.04304	-77.79422	436
Monteverde	-2.05501	-80.73367	7	Pujili	-0.95759	-78.69636	2944
Monteverde (4 km N)	-1.983333	-80.716667	25	Pululuhua	0.03805	-78.48794	2514
Nabón	-3.33933	-79.06549	2864	Puñapi	-1.38743	-78.47588	2031
Nachiyacu	-0.833333	-77.783333	762	Punta Blanca	-1.6875	-80.80833	86
Nanegal	0.14031	-78.67566	1233	Puyo (Pastaza)	-1.483333	-77.983333	924
Nobol	-1.91667	-80.01667	6	Quevedo	-1.02863	-79.46352	61
Nono	-0.06737	-78.57653	2743	Quevedo (35 mi E)	-1.022849	-78.975367	3200
Nuevo Corrientes	-1.997791	-76.766108	253	Quininde	0.3166667	-79.483333	80

Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)
Quito	-0.22985	-78.52495	2854	San Lorenzo	1.27538	-78.79829	12
Quito (120 km SE)	-1.037778	-77.8025	489	San Lucas	-3.737509	-79.260164	2500
Quito (15 km N)	0.070236	-78.423715	1930	San Miguel (Bolivar)	-1.70884	-79.04311	2444
Quito-Nanegalito (km 52)	-0.016039	-78.680877	2240	San Miguel de los Bancos	-0.023128	-78.767792	1647
rio Atacames	0.87085	-79.85078	8	San Nicolas (Carchi)	0.80919	-77.80649	3000
rio Ayampe	-1.672315	-80.81361	3	San Nicolas (Pichincha)	-0.31667	-78.45	2485
rio Baba	-1.85687	-79.67418	9	San Pablo	-3.15	-79.3	3352
rio Babahoyo	-2.18603	-79.86673	5	San Tadeo	0.01667	-78.8	1338
rio Bobonaza	-2.58999	-76.63318	233	Santa Ana	-1.20726	-80.37132	61
rio Bua	-0.02055	-79.60055	148	Santa Elena	-2.22622	-80.805873	40
rio Cachabi	1.05598	-78.81814	15	Santa Lucia	-2.18333	-80.0	9
rio Cayapas	0.86679	-78.95642	14	Santa Rosa	-3.43333	-79.96667	39
rio Cushuimi	-2.80582	-77.64483	208	Santa Rosa (31 mi N)	-3.106911	-79.765822	21
rio Daule	-1.64077	-80.02325	11	Santiago Playa de Oro	0.87628	-78.79458	66
rio El Cinto	-0.02626	-78.81989	1040	Santo Domingo	-0.25305	-79.17536	554
rio Esmeraldas	0.92097	-79.65918	8	Sarayacu	-1.73651	-77.48477	369
rio Guayas	-2.65136	-79.90905	2	Shushufindi	-0.438192	-76.278984	230
rio Jatunyacu	-1.047557	-77.80716	464	Sigchos	-0.70221	-78.88652	2849
rio Mira valley	1.07202	-78.894	11	Sigsig	-3.101805	-78.817995	3275
rio Napo	-0.778733	-75.535872	200	Sucua	-2.45866	-78.17171	830
rio Pastaza	-2.12078	-77.43022	365	Tamboloma	-3.81667	-79.26667	2548
rio Putumayo	0.04863	-75.6411	200	Tandayapa	-0.01667	-78.76667	1657
rio Quijos	-0.333333	-77.75	2030	Tena	-0.9938	-77.81286	504
rio Quininde	0.33798	-79.46822	74	Tiguino	-1.25	-77.21667	310
rio San Pedro	-0.17721	-78.41328	2190	Tiputini	-0.7858	-75.52918	187
rio Taura	-2.51859	-79.75386	2	Topo	-1.416667	-78.16667	1213
rio Unuyacu	-0.93839	-75.88261	200	Tumbaco	-0.214	-78.40489	2336
rio Verde	1.07202	-79.41974	1	Tungurahua	-1.45269	-78.44166	3920
Riobamba	-1.67098	-78.64712	2758	Turin (near)	-0.5	-76.033333	223
Salango	-1.59288	-80.80425	8	Vinces	-1.55611	-79.75191	17
Samana	0.119152	-76.975165	315	Yaguachi Nuevo	-2.0968	-79.69485	12
San Antonio (Pichincha)	-0.00662	-78.44668	2421	Yantzaza	-3.749942	-78.631212	874
San Antonio (Tungurahua)	-1.15	-78.46667	3658	Yaruqui	-0.19172	-78.29968	2955
San Bartolome	-3.00866	-78.84719	2798	Yasuni (P.N.)	-1.09479	-75.80669	192
San Fernando	-1.26625	-78.74579	3245	Yungilla	-1.39598	-78.34972	1600
San Francisco	-2.9	-78.76667	2258	Yunguilla - Huasibaico	-2.767095	-79.334708	2900
San Gabriel	0.57261	-77.82071	2785	Zapotal	-2.31693	-80.56263	23
San José	-1.68345	-79.02586	2465	Zapotal (3 km E)	-2.316667	-80.55	25
San Jose de Minas	0.18916	-78.49053	2373	Zaruma	-3.69132	-79.61174	1200
San José de Suno	-0.533333	-77.416667	948				

INDEX

A

<i>acarus</i> , Pupa	186	<i>antillensis</i> , <i>Sterkia</i>	191
<i>Achatina</i>	87	<i>antisana</i> , <i>Naesiotus</i>	176
<i>achatina</i> , <i>Bulla</i>	87	<i>antoni</i> , <i>Lagocyclus</i>	54
<i>aciculæforme</i> , <i>Opeas</i>	92	<i>Aperostoma</i>	
<i>Acroloxus</i>	72	<i>arboreus</i> , <i>Zonitoides</i>	199
<i>acuta</i> , <i>Haitia</i>	70	<i>Archecharax</i>	24
<i>acutius</i> , <i>Opeas</i>	88	<i>archidona</i> , <i>Neniops</i>	196
<i>adriani</i> , <i>Suniellus</i>	177	<i>arcuata</i> , <i>Veronicella</i>	84
<i>aequatoria</i> , <i>Bocourtia</i>	145	<i>aristaceus</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	137
<i>aequatoria</i> , <i>Cylindrella</i>	241	<i>Aroapyrgus</i>	66
<i>aequatoria</i> , <i>Euglandina</i>	200	<i>Asolene</i>	27
<i>aequatoria</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	212	<i>aspersum</i> , <i>Cornu</i>	210
<i>aequatoria</i> , <i>Leptinaria</i>	90	<i>aspratile</i> , <i>Cyclostoma</i>	241
<i>aequatoria</i> , <i>Rhodea</i>	97	<i>atramentaria</i> , <i>Sultana</i>	130
<i>aequatorialis</i> , <i>Vaginula</i>	85	<i>atrata</i> , <i>Helix</i>	217, 219
<i>aequatoriana</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	212	<i>atropunctata</i> , <i>Veronicella</i>	84
<i>aequatorianus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	150	<i>augusti</i> , <i>Sultana</i>	130
<i>aequatoriensis</i> , <i>Veronicella</i>	84	<i>auratus</i> , <i>Synapterpes</i>	99
<i>aequatortiale</i> , <i>Sphaerium</i>	240	<i>aureonitens</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	137
<i>aequinoctialis</i> , <i>Succinea</i>	115	<i>auriculina</i> , <i>Incania</i>	194
<i>Aeropictus</i>	136	<i>Austrocyclotus</i>	58
<i>alagoana</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	212	<i>Aylacostoma</i>	60
<i>alausiensis</i> , <i>Bostryx</i>	148		
<i>alausiensis</i> , <i>Veronicella</i>	84	B	
<i>albolabiatea</i> , <i>Zoniferella</i>	100	<i>baezensis</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	152
<i>albolabiatu</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	150, 160	<i>baezensis</i> , <i>Happia</i>	106
<i>albus</i> , <i>Planorbis</i>	77	<i>bakeri</i> , <i>Sterkia</i>	191
<i>Alcadia</i>	23	<i>Bartlettia</i>	232
<i>aldersoni</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	28	<i>basidens</i> , <i>Helix</i>	220
<i>alliaris</i> , <i>Oxychilus</i>	199	<i>Beckianum</i>	88
<i>Allopeas</i>	88	<i>beckianum</i> , <i>Beckianum</i>	89
<i>ambatensis</i> , <i>Naesiotus</i>	176	<i>Belocaulus</i>	80, 84
<i>ambigua</i> , <i>Castalia</i>	233	<i>benoni</i> , <i>Orthalicus</i>	124
<i>ambustus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	152	<i>bicarinatus</i> , <i>Planorbis</i>	78
<i>americanum</i> , <i>Pupisoma</i>	188	<i>bicineta</i> , <i>Daronia</i>	38
<i>ammoniformis</i> , <i>Helix</i>	102	<i>bicingulatus</i> , <i>Synapterpes</i>	100
<i>Ammonoceras</i>	104	<i>bielenbergi</i> , <i>Vaginulus</i>	84
<i>ammonoceras</i> , <i>Helix</i>	104	<i>bifasciatum</i> , <i>Cyclostoma</i>	241
<i>amnica</i> , <i>Tellina</i>	240	<i>bifulguratus</i> , <i>Orthalicus</i>	125
<i>amori</i> , <i>Helix</i>	205	<i>bifurcatus</i> , <i>Labyrinthus</i>	220
<i>anatinum</i> , <i>Drepanotrema</i>	74	<i>bilineatus</i> , <i>Bostryx</i>	148
<i>andai</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	152, 242	<i>Biomphalaria</i>	73
<i>andensis</i> , <i>Veronicella</i>	84	<i>bituberculata</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	212
<i>Andesipyrgus</i>	65	<i>bizonalis</i> , <i>Zoniferella</i>	100
<i>angustior</i> , <i>Orthalicus</i>	133	<i>Bocourtia</i>	145
<i>angustipes</i> , <i>Vaginula</i>	80	<i>boetzkesi</i> , <i>Belocaulus</i>	80
<i>Anodontites</i>	224	<i>boetzkesi</i> , <i>Cochliopina</i>	66
<i>anoecia</i> , <i>Incania</i>	194	<i>boetzkesi</i> , <i>Planorbis</i>	77
<i>anomala</i> , <i>Leptinaria</i>	92	<i>boetzkesi</i> , <i>Solaropsis</i>	204
<i>anthisanensis</i> , <i>Bocourtia</i>	146	<i>bolivari</i> , <i>Mycetopoda</i>	230
<i>Antidrymaeus</i>	158	<i>boliviense</i> , <i>Pisidium</i>	240

<i>Bostryx</i>	148	<i>colmeiroi</i> , <i>Stenostylus</i>	176
<i>Bourciera</i>	19	<i>colombiensis</i> , <i>Aroapyrgus</i>	66
<i>bourcierii</i> , <i>Calaperostoma</i>	38	<i>Colosius</i>	80
<i>bourcierii</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	152	<i>columbiana</i> , <i>Nenia</i>	192
<i>bourcierii</i> , <i>Incania</i>	195	<i>columbiensis</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	37
<i>bourcierii</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	214	<i>Columbinia</i>	192
<i>bourguignatiana</i> , <i>Helicina</i>	21	<i>columella</i> , <i>Pseudosuccinea</i>	70
<i>boussingaultii</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	130	<i>columellaris</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	31
<i>breckworthianus</i> , <i>Limacus</i>	196	<i>comicolense</i> , <i>Pupisoma</i>	189
<i>brevispira</i> , <i>Orthalicus</i>	132	<i>complanata</i> , <i>Veronicella</i>	80
<i>brunneus</i> , <i>Thaumastus</i>	242	<i>concentrica</i> , <i>Achatina</i>	92
<i>buckleyi</i> , <i>Neniptyx</i>	196	<i>confusus</i> , <i>Colosius</i>	80
<i>buckleyi</i> , <i>Thaumastus</i>	179	<i>conspicuus</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	180
<i>Buckleyia</i>	38	<i>cookei</i> , <i>Diplodontites</i>	228, 229
<i>bullata</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	29	<i>copiae</i> , <i>Cornu</i>	210
C		<i>Corbicula</i>	238
<i>cactivorus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	170	<i>cornea</i> , <i>Tellina</i>	240
<i>caeca</i> , <i>Helix</i>	188	<i>Cornu</i>	210
<i>calamitosa</i> , <i>Pupa</i>	191	<i>Corona</i>	122
<i>Calaperostoma</i>	38	<i>corrugatus</i> , <i>Triplodon</i>	238
<i>californica</i> , <i>Achatina</i>	97	<i>corydon</i> , <i>Clathrothalicus</i>	120
<i>caliginosa</i> , <i>Bocourtia</i>	148	<i>cotopaxiensis</i> , <i>Bocourtia</i>	148
<i>caliginosus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	175	<i>cotopaxiensis</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	148
<i>campanulatus</i> , <i>Planorbis</i>	80	<i>cousini</i> , <i>Archecharax</i>	24
<i>canaliculata</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	29	<i>cousini</i> , <i>Biomphalaria</i>	73
<i>canonicus</i> , <i>Planorbis</i>	74	<i>cousini</i> , <i>Calaperostoma</i>	38
<i>cardinalis</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	138	<i>cousini</i> , <i>Columbinia</i>	192
<i>carinata</i> , <i>Anodontites</i>	225	<i>cousini</i> , <i>Galba</i>	69
<i>carolita</i> , <i>Mayabina</i>	72	<i>cousini</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	31
<i>Castalia</i>	233	<i>cousini</i> , <i>Rhodea</i>	98
<i>catamayensis</i> , <i>Otostomus</i>	168	<i>cousini</i> , <i>Solaropsis</i>	205
<i>catenifera</i> , <i>Solaropsis</i>	209	<i>crassa</i> , <i>Asolene</i>	28
<i>catlowiae</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	175	<i>creveauxianus</i> , <i>Helix</i>	223
<i>cecepeus</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	144	<i>crispata</i> , <i>Anodontites</i>	224
<i>cephalophora</i> , <i>Veronicella</i>	84	<i>croseana</i> , <i>Castalia</i>	233
<i>cerasum</i> , <i>Ampullaria</i>	37	<i>croseanus</i> , <i>Lagocyclus</i>	66
<i>cereonitens</i> , <i>Systrophia</i>	113	<i>croseii</i> , <i>Incania</i>	196
<i>chacaensis</i> , <i>Clausilia</i>	194	<i>cubensis</i> , <i>Physa</i>	72
<i>chamaeleon</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	152	<i>cuencanus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	88
<i>chemnitzii</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	37	<i>culicoides</i> , <i>Acroloxus</i>	73
<i>chillu</i> , <i>Scutalus</i>	176	<i>cumingii</i> , <i>Calaperostoma</i>	40
<i>chimborasensis</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	155	<i>cumingii</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	32
<i>chocolatum</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	44	<i>cuneus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	93
<i>chrysomelas</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	155	<i>cuzcana</i> , <i>Happia</i>	106
<i>cincta</i> , <i>Corona</i>	122	<i>Cyane</i>	24
<i>cinnanomea</i> , <i>Linidiella</i>	24	<i>cyclina</i> , <i>Happia</i>	106
<i>citrinovitrea</i> , <i>Simpulopsis</i>	185	<i>Cyclonena</i>	194
<i>Clathrothalicus</i>	120	<i>cyclostoma</i> , <i>Cyclonena</i>	194
<i>clevei</i> , <i>Planorbella</i>	80	<i>cymatodes</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	214
<i>Clypeolum</i>	26	D	
<i>cocaensis</i> , <i>Columbinia</i>	192	<i>dactylus</i> , <i>Achatina</i>	202
<i>Cochliopina</i>	66	<i>Daronia</i>	37
<i>cocki</i> , <i>Nenia</i>	192	<i>deburghiae</i> , <i>Sultana</i>	130

<i>delphinulus</i> , <i>Cyclophorus</i>	58	<i>fairmaireanus</i> , <i>Protobeliscus</i>	93
<i>Deroceras</i>	198	<i>falcata</i> , <i>Mycetopodella</i>	230
<i>deyrollei</i> , <i>Clausilia</i>	192	<i>fallax</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	158, 173
<i>diminutum</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	44	<i>fasciata</i> , <i>Melanoides</i>	64
<i>dioscoricolum</i> , <i>Pupisoma</i>	188	<i>faunus</i> , <i>Helix</i>	218
<i>Diplodon</i>	234	<i>felix</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	174
<i>Diplodontites</i>	228	<i>femurina</i> , <i>Nenia</i>	192
<i>Diploselenodes</i>	84	<i>festae</i> , <i>Colosius</i>	81
<i>doliarius</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	138	<i>Filocyclus</i>	58
<i>Drepanostomella</i>	102	<i>fischeri</i> , <i>Cyclotus</i>	46
<i>Drepanotrema</i>	74	<i>flammeus</i> , <i>Hemisinus</i>	61
<i>dresseli</i> , <i>Opeas</i>	88	<i>flavidulus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	170
<i>Drymaeus</i>	150, 173	<i>flavus</i> , <i>Limacus</i>	197
<i>dunkeri</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	45	<i>floccosus</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	138
<i>duryi</i> , <i>Helisoma</i>	79	<i>flora</i> , <i>Happia</i>	107
<i>dysoni</i> , <i>Cyclostoma</i>	58	<i>flori</i> , <i>Thaumastus</i>	179
E		<i>florschuetzi</i> , <i>Naesiotus</i>	174
<i>ecarinata</i> , <i>Castalia</i>	233	<i>fluminalis</i> , <i>Tellina</i>	238
<i>ecuadorensis</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	46	<i>fluminea</i> , <i>Corbicula</i>	238
<i>ecuadoriana</i> , <i>Cochliopina</i>	66	<i>fontainei</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	148
<i>ecuadoriana</i> , <i>Euglandina</i>	201	<i>fontainii</i> , <i>Naesiotus</i>	174
<i>ecuadoriana</i> , <i>Helicina</i>	21	<i>fordii</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	161
<i>Effusa</i>	28	<i>fraseri</i> , <i>Bourciera</i>	19
<i>elata</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	150	<i>fraseri</i> , <i>Sultana</i>	132
<i>elegans</i> , <i>Physa</i>	70	<i>fucatus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	158
<i>elegantissimus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	174	<i>fulgur</i> , <i>Zebra</i>	125
<i>elizabethae</i> , <i>Sultana</i>	134	<i>fulguratus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	185
<i>ellipticum</i> , <i>Unio</i>	234	<i>fulica</i> , <i>Achatina</i>	87
<i>elongata</i> , <i>Dryptus</i>	126	<i>funcki</i> , <i>Leptinaria</i>	90
<i>elongatus</i> , <i>Anodontites</i>	226	<i>fungairinoi</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	132
<i>elongatus</i> , <i>Hemisinus</i>	62	<i>furcillatus</i> , <i>Helix</i>	223
<i>elongatus</i> , <i>Orthalicus</i>	130	G	
<i>ensiformis</i> , <i>Lamproscapha</i>	230	<i>galactostoma</i> , <i>Sultana</i>	132
<i>entodonta</i> , <i>Systrophia</i>	109	<i>galapagorum</i> , <i>Pupisoma</i>	189
<i>Epiphragmophora</i>	224	<i>Galba</i>	68
<i>equatorensis</i> , <i>Rhodea</i>	97	<i>garciamoreni</i> , <i>Megalobulimus</i>	116
<i>equatoria</i> , <i>Biomphalaria</i>	74	<i>Gastrocopta</i>	186
<i>equestrata</i> , <i>Helix</i>	242	<i>gaudichaudi</i> , <i>Littoridina</i>	67
<i>ernesti</i> , <i>Helicina</i>	22	<i>gealei</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	214
<i>eros</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	138	<i>geayi</i> , <i>Omalonyx</i>	114
<i>esilicaulis</i> , <i>Vaginula</i>	84	<i>gibboni</i> , <i>Solaropsis</i>	205
<i>esmeraldense</i> , <i>Calaperostoma</i>	40	<i>gibbonius</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	138
<i>Eudioptus</i>	185	<i>giganteum</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	46
<i>Euglandina</i>	200	<i>globosa</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	214
<i>Eurytus</i>	137	<i>gloriosus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	130
<i>excisa</i> , <i>Drepanostomella</i>	103	<i>goodalli</i> , <i>Helix</i>	92
<i>expansa</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	28	<i>goodalli</i> , <i>Opeas</i>	92
<i>expansus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	155	<i>gracile</i> , <i>Allopeas</i>	88
<i>eyerdami</i> , <i>Lamellaxis</i>		<i>gracilis</i> , <i>Limax</i>	198
<i>eyerdami</i> , <i>Leptinaria</i>	90	<i>granulatissima</i> , <i>Helix</i>	218
F		<i>granulatus</i> , <i>Neocyclotus</i>	58
<i>fabrefactus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	173	<i>grevillei</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	128
		<i>gualbertoi</i> , <i>Aplecta</i>	72

<i>guaranius</i> , <i>Diplodon</i>	236	<i>Isomeria</i>	212
<i>guatemalensis</i> , <i>Opeas</i>	101	J	
<i>guayaquilense</i> , <i>Calaperostoma</i>	40	<i>jacksoni</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	48
<i>guayaquilensis</i> , <i>Aylacostoma</i>	62	<i>jacksoni</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	217
<i>guayaquilensis</i> , <i>Hemisinus</i>	62	<i>jacksoni</i> , <i>Naesiotus</i>	175
<i>guayaquilensis</i> , <i>Scolodonta</i>	108	<i>jacksoni</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	139
<i>guayaquilensis</i> , <i>Subulina</i>	98	<i>jatesi</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	132
<i>Guestieria</i>	104	<i>jimenezi</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	138
<i>Guppya</i>	200	<i>joubini</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	158
<i>Gyraulus</i>	77	<i>jousseamei</i> , <i>Protobeliscus</i>	93
H		<i>juana</i> , <i>Bostryx</i>	149
<i>haematomma</i> , <i>Lagocyclus</i>	58	<i>juno</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	218
<i>Haitia</i>	70	K	
<i>hanleyi</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	99	<i>Kara</i>	123
<i>hannense</i> , <i>Opeas</i>	92	<i>kawaiensis</i> , <i>Helix</i>	199
<i>haplostylus</i> , <i>Protobeliscus</i>	93	<i>kellestii</i> , <i>Sultana</i>	132
<i>Happia</i>	104	<i>kermatoides</i> , <i>Drepanotrema</i>	75
<i>hartwegi</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	216	<i>knorri</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	172
<i>hartwegi</i> , <i>Thaumastus</i>	180	<i>kobeltiana</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	214
<i>Hawaiiia</i>	199	<i>kolbergi</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	218
<i>hawaiiensis</i> , <i>Vitrea</i>	199	<i>Kuschelenia</i>	145
<i>Helicina</i>	21	L	
<i>helicinaeformis</i> , <i>Bourciera</i>	19	<i>Labyrinthus</i>	220
<i>helicycloides</i> , <i>Systrophia</i>	110	<i>labyrinthus</i> , <i>Helix</i>	220
<i>heligmoida</i> , <i>Systrophia</i>	110	<i>lachneri</i> , <i>Diplopoma</i>	241
<i>Helisoma</i>	78	<i>lacustris</i> , <i>Patella</i>	72
<i>Hemibulimus</i>	119	<i>laeve</i> , <i>Deroceras</i>	198
<i>Hemisinus</i>	60	<i>Lagocyclus</i>	54
<i>hidalgoi</i> , <i>Anodonta</i>	226	<i>lamellata</i> , <i>Achatina</i>	90
<i>hidalgoi</i> , <i>Calaperostoma</i>	41	<i>Lamproscapha</i>	230
<i>hidalgoi</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	158	<i>latidentata</i> , <i>Helix</i>	212
<i>hieronymi</i> , <i>Epiphragmophora</i>	224	<i>latissimum</i> , <i>Clypeolum</i>	26
<i>hiliaryae</i> , <i>Zilchistrophia</i>	112	<i>laus</i> , <i>Helicina</i>	22
<i>hindsianus</i> , <i>Gyraulus</i>	77	<i>lautus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	172
<i>hitomi</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	48	<i>Leiostracus</i>	183
<i>hygrohyla</i> , <i>Helix</i>	150	<i>Leptinaria</i>	90
<i>hyla</i> , <i>Diplodon</i>		<i>leucophaetus</i> , <i>Mytilus</i>	239
I		<i>lignaria</i> , <i>Achatina</i>	200
<i>inaequalis</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	152, 174, 242	<i>lignicola</i> , <i>Pupa</i>	188
<i>inca</i> , <i>Thaumastus</i>	242	<i>Limacus</i>	196
<i>Incania</i>	194	<i>lineolatus</i> , <i>Strombus</i>	60
<i>Incidostoma</i>	44	<i>linguaeformis</i> , <i>Sarasinula</i>	86
<i>indentata</i> , <i>Kara</i>	124	<i>Linidiella</i>	24
<i>insignis</i> , <i>Systrophia</i>	110	<i>linki</i> , <i>Tetraplon</i>	234
<i>integer</i> , <i>Thaumastus</i>	181	<i>Lissachatina</i>	87
<i>invadens</i> , <i>Deroceras</i>	198	<i>Lithococcus</i>	66
<i>iodes</i> , <i>Orthalicus</i>	130	<i>Littoridina</i>	67
<i>iostoma</i> , <i>Porphyrobaphe</i>	128	<i>locardi</i> , <i>Guestieria</i>	104
<i>iris</i> , <i>Solaropsis</i>	206	<i>loroisianus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	122
<i>irregularis</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	174	<i>losadae</i> , <i>Diplodon</i>	238
<i>irrorata</i> , <i>Porphyrobaphe</i>	126	<i>loxanus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	171
<i>isabellinus</i> , <i>Orthalicus</i>	124		

<i>loxensis, Drymaeus</i>	172	<i>minima, Neritina</i>	26
<i>loxensis, Helix</i>	216	<i>minor, Bulimus</i>	152
<i>loxensis, Zebra</i>	180	<i>minor, Dryptus</i>	128
<i>loxostomus, Thaumastus</i>	182	<i>minor, Eurytus</i>	143
<i>lucidum, Drepanotrema</i>	76	<i>minor, Obeliscus</i>	93
<i>lugubris, Vaginula</i>	80,82	<i>minuscula, Hawaiaia</i>	199
<i>lutea, Orphnus</i>	124	<i>modesta, Pomacea</i>	33
<i>lutea, Thaumastus</i>	160	<i>monile, Solaropsis</i>	206
<i>luteostoma, Ampullaria</i>	28	<i>montezumi, Aperostoma</i>	38
<i>lymnaeiformis, Bocourtia</i>	145	<i>moreletiana, Helicina</i>	22
<i>lynciculus, Plekocheilus</i>	139	<i>morula, Isomeria</i>	218
<i>lyzarzaburui, Drepanostomella</i>	103	<i>multicarinatus, Lithococcus</i>	66
M		<i>murrinus, Bulimus</i>	173
<i>macasi, Epiphragmophora</i>	224	<i>Mycetopoda</i>	230
<i>macneilli, Pupisoma</i>	188	<i>Mycetopodella</i>	230
<i>maculata, Pomacea</i>	28	<i>Mytilopsis</i>	239
<i>maculatus, Hemisinus</i>	62	N	
<i>maculatus, Limacus</i>	197	<i>Naesiotus</i>	149, 174
<i>magistra, Clausilia</i>	196	<i>napensis, Solaropsis</i>	208
<i>magnifica, Achatina</i>	119	<i>napo, Bulimus</i>	164
<i>magnifica, Helix</i>	205	<i>napoensis, Anodonta</i>	225
<i>magnificus, Clathrothalicus</i>	121	<i>Neniaptyx</i>	196
<i>major, Hamadryas</i>	158	<i>Neniops</i>	196
<i>major, Helicina</i>	23	<i>Neocyclotus</i>	58
<i>major, Protobeliscus</i>	94	<i>neogranadensis, Helix</i>	220
<i>malleatum, Incidostoma</i>	44	<i>neritella, Helicina</i>	21
<i>manabense, Incidostoma</i>	48	<i>nigricans, Orphnus</i>	124
<i>manueli, Labyrinthus</i>	222	<i>nigricans, Thaumastus</i>	160
<i>maracaibensis, Bulimus</i>	134	<i>nigrofasciatum, Calaperostoma</i>	42
<i>marianita, Succinea</i>	115	<i>nigrolimbatus, Bulimus</i>	176
<i>marianita, Veronicella</i>	86	<i>nitens, Physa</i>	72
<i>mars, Orthalicus</i>	126	<i>nitida, Helix</i>	199
<i>Martinella</i>	101	<i>nitidella, Galba</i>	69
<i>martinella, Martinella</i>	101, 102	<i>nitidens, Bulimus</i>	186
<i>martinezi, Daronia</i>	38	<i>nocturnus, Plekocheilus</i>	140
<i>martinezi, Pomacea</i>	32	<i>nux, Bulinus</i>	174
<i>martini, Succinea</i>	116	<i>nux, Naesiotus</i>	145, 174
<i>martinida, Guestieria</i>	104	<i>nystianus, Drymaeus</i>	160
<i>martinidella, Aplecta</i>	72	O	
<i>martinii, Helix</i>	218	<i>obductus, Orthalicus</i>	134, 212
<i>masvense, Incidostoma</i>	48	<i>obliquus, Prisdodon</i>	237, 238
<i>mauritii, Isomeria</i>	219	<i>occidentalis, Diploselenodes</i>	84
<i>Mayabina</i>	72	<i>occidentalis, Mycetopus</i>	230
<i>mcgintyi, Plekocheilus</i>	141	<i>occidentalis, Otostomus</i>	170
<i>Megalobulimus</i>	116	<i>ochrocheilus, Drymaeus</i>	160
<i>Melanoides</i>	64	<i>octona, Subulina</i>	98
<i>membielinus, Drymaeus</i>	158	<i>oligostylus, Plekocheilus</i>	140
<i>Mesembrinus</i>	170	<i>olivaceum, Aperostoma</i>	54
<i>Metasterkia</i>	191	<i>olivaceus, Diploselenodes</i>	84
<i>Metorthalicus</i>	130	<i>olivaceus, Orphnus</i>	124
<i>Mexinauta</i>	72	<i>Omalyonyx</i>	114
<i>meyeri, Isomeria</i>	218	<i>Opeas</i>	92
<i>micra, Allopeas</i>	88		

<i>orbicula</i> , <i>Systrophia</i>	113	<i>Pseudopeas</i>	96
<i>orcei</i> , <i>Mesembrinus</i>	155	<i>Pseudosuccinea</i>	70
<i>orcei</i> , <i>Thaumastus</i>	182	<i>pseudosuccinea</i> , <i>Helix</i>	185
<i>oreas</i> , <i>Helix</i>	212, 242	<i>Ptychopatula</i>	188
<i>orinus</i> , <i>Naesiotus</i>	176	<i>pulchellum</i> , <i>Pseudopeas</i>	
<i>Orthalicus</i>	124	<i>pulcher</i> , <i>Belocaulus</i>	84
<i>orthostoma</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	152, 160	<i>pulcher</i> , <i>Colosius</i>	82
<i>ortoni</i> , <i>Systrophia</i>	110	<i>pulcher</i> , <i>Hemisinus</i>	62
<i>ortonii</i> , <i>Unio</i>	238	<i>pumilus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	92
<i>osculati</i> , <i>Melania</i>	62	<i>puntaplaya</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	34
<i>Oxyorthalicus</i>	126	<i>Pupisoma</i>	188
		<i>Pupoides</i>	186
P		<i>purum</i> , <i>Calaperostoma</i>	43
<i>pailaense</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	48	<i>putris</i> , <i>Helix</i>	115
<i>pairensis</i> , <i>Protobeliscus</i>	95	<i>Pyrgophorus</i>	67
<i>paredesii</i> , <i>Pupoides</i>	186	Q	
<i>parietidentata</i> , <i>Helix</i>	214	<i>quadridentata</i> , <i>Helix</i>	222
<i>pastasana</i> , <i>Anodonta</i>	227	<i>quadrifasciatus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	164
<i>pazi</i> , <i>Castalia</i>	236	<i>quadrioittata</i> , <i>Solaropsis</i>	209
<i>pazi</i> , <i>Gastrocopta</i>	186, 188	<i>quadrocularis</i> , <i>Veronicella</i>	84
<i>pazi</i> , <i>Hemisinus</i>	62	<i>quinindensis</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	28
<i>pazi</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	50	<i>quitense</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	54
<i>pealiana</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	34	<i>quitensis</i> , <i>Ampullaria</i>	32
<i>pedrinus</i> , <i>Pyrgophorus</i>	67	<i>quitensis</i> , <i>Naesiotus</i>	174
<i>peelii</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	161		
<i>pellisserpentis</i> , <i>Helix</i>	204	R	
<i>pentadina</i> , <i>Helix</i>	136	<i>rabuti</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	166
<i>peregrina</i> , <i>Biomphalaria</i>	74	<i>raimondii</i> , <i>Labyrinthus</i>	222
<i>perezi</i> , <i>Columbinia</i>	192	<i>raphaelis</i> , <i>Galba</i>	69
<i>perezi</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	52	<i>rarum</i> , <i>Opeas</i>	92
<i>peruviana</i> , <i>Mexinauta</i>	72	<i>regalis</i> , <i>Corona</i>	122
<i>petasites</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	164	<i>regina</i> , <i>Helix</i>	122
<i>pfeifferi</i> , <i>Corona</i>	122	<i>reticulatum</i> , <i>Deroceras</i>	198
<i>phasianella</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	128	<i>reyrei</i> , <i>Columbinia</i>	194
<i>phoebus</i> , <i>Clathrothalicus</i>	122	<i>reyrei</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	36
<i>pichinchense</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	52	<i>reyrei</i> , <i>Systrophia</i>	112
<i>pilsbryi</i> , <i>Neritina</i>	26	<i>rhoatsi</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	166
<i>piperitus</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	141	<i>Rhodea</i>	97
<i>Pisidium</i>	240	<i>rhynchostoma</i> , <i>Helicina</i>	22
<i>planibasis</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	164	<i>riograndensis</i> , <i>Cochliopa</i>	66
<i>Planorbella</i>	80	<i>riparius</i> , <i>Protobeliscus</i>	96
<i>platae</i> , <i>Helix</i>	27	<i>ritchieana</i> , <i>Helix</i>	218
<i>plebeia</i> , <i>Sarasinula</i>	85, 86	<i>riveti</i> , <i>Veronicella</i>	84
<i>Plekocheilus</i>	136	<i>riveti</i> , <i>Zoniferella</i>	100
<i>Pomacea</i>	28	<i>rioolii</i> , <i>Acostaea</i>	232
<i>popayanum</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	52	<i>rosenbergi</i> , <i>Calaperostoma</i>	44
<i>popelairianus</i> , <i>Megalobulimus</i>	118	<i>roseolabrum</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	142
<i>Porphyrobaphe</i>	126	<i>rubrovariegatus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	167
<i>powisiana</i> , <i>Guestieria</i>	104	<i>rufescens</i> , <i>Potamojanuarius</i>	80
<i>Prisodon</i>	237		
<i>propinquus</i> , <i>Colosius</i>	81	S	
<i>Protobeliscus</i>	93	<i>saccata</i> , <i>Euglandina</i>	202
<i>Psadara</i>	204	<i>sachsei</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	168
<i>pseudoiostomus</i> , <i>Pachytholus</i>	182		

<i>saladensis</i> , <i>Hemisinus</i>	62	<i>surinamense</i> , <i>Drepanotrema</i>	76
<i>salengoense</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	54	<i>swifti</i> , <i>Proserpina</i>	24
<i>Sarasinula</i>	85	<i>swifti</i> , <i>Proserpina</i>	24
<i>Sarasinula</i>	85	<i>Synapterpes</i>	99
<i>saturnus</i> , <i>Porphyrobaphe</i>	128	<i>systropha</i> , <i>Helix</i>	109
<i>schirazensis</i> , <i>Galba</i>	70	<i>Systrophia</i>	109
<i>Scolodonta</i>	108, 110		
<i>selenostoma</i> , <i>Helix</i>	204	T	
<i>selenostoma</i> , <i>Solaropsis</i>	209	<i>tamsiana</i> , <i>Helicina</i>	22
<i>semiclausus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	172	<i>tarapotoensis</i> , <i>Helix</i>	223
<i>semipictus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	143	<i>Tatutor</i>	183
<i>semperi</i> , <i>Streptaxis</i>	108	<i>tatutor</i> , <i>Thaumastus</i>	183
<i>sericea</i> , <i>Biomphalaria</i>	74	<i>taylorianus</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	143
<i>shirviarorum</i> , <i>Zilchistrophia</i>	112	<i>tenebricosa</i> , <i>Anodontites</i>	226
<i>siliquosa</i> , <i>Mycetopoda</i>	230	<i>tenuissima</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	36
<i>simplex</i> , <i>Hemisinus</i>	62	<i>tenuissimus</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	136
<i>Simpulopsis</i>	185	<i>teres</i> , <i>Veronicella</i>	84
<i>simulans</i> , <i>Kuschelenia</i>	145	<i>thammianus</i> , <i>Megalobulimus</i>	116
<i>sketi</i> , <i>Andesipyrigus</i>	65	<i>Thaumastus</i>	179
<i>smithii</i> , <i>Biomphalaria</i>	73	<i>thompsonii</i> , <i>Kara</i>	124
<i>Solaropsis</i>	204	<i>thompsonoides</i> , <i>Thaumastus</i>	124
<i>soleniformis</i> , <i>Anodonta</i>	231	<i>tigrinus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	168
<i>soleniformis</i> , <i>Mycetopoda</i>	230	<i>tortilis</i> , <i>Anodontites</i>	227
<i>solida</i> , <i>Ampullaria</i>	28	<i>trapesialis</i> , <i>Anodontites</i>	227
<i>solutus</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	148	<i>trautwineana</i> , <i>Mytilopsis</i>	239
<i>sowerbyana</i> , <i>Arangia</i>	241	<i>tricolor</i> , <i>Plekocheilus</i>	143
<i>Sphaerium</i>	240	<i>tridentata</i> , <i>Zilchistrophia</i>	112
<i>spinosus</i> , <i>Pyrgulopsis</i>	67	<i>tridentula</i> , <i>Helix</i>	212
<i>spirula</i> , <i>Cyclostrema</i>	37	<i>trigona</i> , <i>Anodontites</i>	228
<i>Steatonenia</i>	192	<i>triodonta</i> , <i>Isomeria</i>	219
<i>stefanensis</i> , <i>Bartlettia</i>	232	<i>Triplodon</i>	238
<i>stenostrepta</i> , <i>Systrophia</i>	112	<i>trivolvus</i> , <i>Helisoma</i>	79
<i>Stenostylus</i>	176	<i>trullisatus</i> , <i>Orthalicus</i>	133
<i>Sterkia</i>	191	<i>truncatula</i> , <i>Galba</i>	70
<i>stirlingi</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	54	<i>truncatulum</i> , <i>Buccinum</i>	68
<i>stramineum</i> , <i>Cyclostoma</i>	58	<i>tuberculata</i> , <i>Melanoides</i>	64
<i>strangeana</i> , <i>Gastrocopta</i>	187		
<i>strangei</i> , <i>Pupa</i>	187	U	
<i>striata</i> , <i>Euglandina</i>	202	<i>undulata</i> , <i>Caprella</i>	136
<i>striatula</i> , <i>Bourciera</i>	20	<i>unguis</i> , <i>Helix</i>	114
<i>strigatus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	168	<i>unilamellata</i> , <i>Helix</i>	90
<i>stuhlmanni</i> , <i>Meisenheimeria</i>	85	<i>unilamellata</i> , <i>Leptinaria</i>	90
<i>subcastanea</i> , <i>Helix</i>	214	<i>unizonata</i> , <i>Helicina</i>	22
<i>subcingulatum</i> , <i>Incidostoma</i>	54	<i>urceus</i> , <i>Pomacea</i>	36
<i>subirrorata</i> , <i>Porphyrobaphe</i>	128		
<i>subpellucidus</i> , <i>Drymaeus</i>	172	V	
<i>subplanata</i> , <i>Caracolla</i>	223	<i>vacans</i> , <i>Conulus</i>	200
<i>subsiniuatus</i> , <i>Mycetopus</i>	230	<i>valenciennesii</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	118
<i>Subulina</i>	98	<i>valenzuela</i> , <i>Leptinaria</i>	92
<i>Succinea</i>	115	<i>varians</i> , <i>Vaginula</i>	80
<i>sulculosa</i> , <i>Helix</i>	185	<i>vasconesi</i> , <i>Lagocyclus</i>	58
<i>Sultana</i>	130	<i>Velletia</i>	73
<i>sultana</i> , <i>Sultana</i>	133	<i>veranyi</i> , <i>Bulimus</i>	136
<i>Suniellus</i>	176	<i>vermiculatus</i> , <i>Naesiotus</i>	176

<i>vesperus, Mesembrinus</i>	100	<i>wolffi, Helix</i>	212
<i>virgulata, Helix</i>	170	<i>wolffi, Pisidium</i>	240
<i>viridissima, Bourciera</i>	21	<i>wolffii, Gastrocopta</i>	188
<i>visendus, Synapterpes</i>	100	<i>wolffii, Guppya</i>	200
<i>vittatus, Bulimus</i>	183	Y	
<i>vivens, Potamopyrgus</i>	66	<i>yatesi, Sultana</i>	132
<i>viviparum, Pseudopeas</i>	96	<i>yzabalensis, Planorbis</i>	74
<i>volsus, Drymaeus</i>	169	Z	
W		<i>zebra, Buccinum</i>	124
<i>wallisi, Orthalicus</i>	120	<i>zebra, Orphnus</i>	124
<i>Wayampia</i>	110	<i>Zilchistrophia</i>	112
<i>webberi, Leiostracus</i>	184	<i>Zoniferella</i>	100
<i>willineri, Paracochlea</i>	185	<i>Zonitoides</i>	199
<i>wintlei, Drymaeus</i>	172		

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- La revista *Iberus* publica artículos, notas y monografías que versen sobre cualquiera de los aspectos relacionados con la Malacología. Se entiende por artículo un trabajo de investigación de al menos 6 páginas de texto, incluidas láminas, gráficos y tablas. Las notas son trabajos de menor extensión. Las monografías son trabajos sobre un tema único, de extensión superior a las 50 páginas impresas y que serán publicadas, si procede, como un suplemento de *Iberus*. Los autores interesados en publicar monografías deberán ponerse previamente en contacto con el Editor de Publicaciones. Se entiende que el contenido de los manuscritos no ha sido publicado, ni enviado simultáneamente a otra revista para su consideración.

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Artículo: Ros J. 1976. Catálogo provisional de los Opisthobranquios (Gastropoda: Euthyneura) de las costas ibéricas. *Miscelánea Zoológica*, 3 (5): 21-51.

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Figura 1. *Neodoris carvi*. A: animal desplazándose; B: detalle de un rinóforo; C: branquia.

Figure 1. *Neodoris carvi*. A: animal crawling; B: detail of a rhinophore; C: gill.

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- Manuscripts may be written in Spanish, English, Italian, French or Portuguese.

- Manuscripts submitted for publishing must be initially sent as a single Word file, which must include all tables and figures. When a paper has joint authorship, one author must accept responsibility for all correspondence, and all authors must declare their consent for publication. The authors must include a list of at least 4 possible referees; the Editor can choose any others if appropriate.

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Following pages. These include the rest of the paper, divided into sections under short headings. Whenever possible the text should be arranged as follows: Introduction, Material and methods, Results, Discussion, Conclusions, Acknowledgements and References. Unusual abbreviations used in the text must be grouped in one alphabetic sequence after the Material and methods section.

- Notes should follow the same layout, without the abstract.

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Book: Fretter V. and Graham A. 1962. *British Prosobranch Molluscs*. Ray Society, London, 765 pp.

Chapter of a book: Ponder W.F. 1988. The Truncatelloidean (= Rissoocean) radiation - a preliminary phylogeny. In Ponder W.F. (Ed.): *Prosobranch Phylogeny. Malacological Review*, suppl. 4: 129-166.

Paper: Ros J. 1976. Catálogo provisional de los Opisthobranchios (Gastropoda: Euthyneura) de las costas ibéricas. *Miscelánea Zoológica*, 3 (5): 21-51.

Web site: WoRMS Editorial Board. 2020). World Register of Marine Species. Available at <<http://www.marinespecies.org>>, accessed December 9, 2020.

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Figure 1. *Neodoris carvi*. A: animal crawling; B: detail of a rhinophore; C: gill.

Figura 1. Neodoris carvi. A: animal desplazándose; B: detalle de un rinóforo; C: bránquia.

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Fundado por Ilídio Félix Alves em 1986, o Instituto Português de Malacologia (IPM) é uma associação sem fins lucrativos, com objectivos científicos tais como: estimular a investigação científica em Malacologia, promover o intercâmbio de informações entre malacologistas, centralizar e difundir informações sobre Malacologia, estabelecer contactos, convénios e acordos de cooperação com organismos afins, nacionais e estrangeiros, promover reuniões, conferências, congressos, expedições e quaisquer outras actividades científicas ligadas à Malacologia. Mais informação em www.ipmalac.pt

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ÍNDICE

Iberus

40 (1) 2022

BREURE A.S.H., ROOSEN M.T. & ABLETT J.D. Land and freshwater molluscs of mainland Ecuador: an illustrated checklist

Moluscos terrestres y dulceacuícolas de Ecuador continental: un listado ilustrado 1-290

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